

INTERLINEAR TRANSLATION

ACROSS THE MUSLIM WORLD

A Comparative Perspective

Themed Section

edited by

Ronit RICCI and Fadhli LUKMAN

Cover page: The penultimate page of a late 17th century Qur'ān from the island of Manipa in Maluku, Indonesia. Arabic with interlinear translation in Malay and notes in Dutch.
Leiden University Library, Special Collections, MS Orient 1945.

A special thanks to Ernst-Jan Munnik for his assistance and to Genie Yoo for bringing the manuscript to our attention.

Contents

FADHLI LUKMAN and RONIT RICCI	
Introduction.....	5
A.C.S. PEACOCK	
Medieval Eastern Turkish Interlinear Translation: Their Manuscripts, Audience, and Persian Background.....	19
AGLAIA IANKOVSKAIA	
A World of Words and Words for the World: Encyclopaedism and Language Learning in a 19 th -century Arabic-Malay Vocabulary.....	51
RAPHAEL MICHAELI	
Interlinear Translation in Textual Performance: The Usage of Swahili in Arabic Mawlid Readings from East Africa.....	73
FADHLI LUKMAN	
Surau Texts Translated: Translation in Form, Textual Analysis in Substance.....	103
MIDORI KAWASHIMA	
Ingenuity Between the Lines: Interlinear Translation from Arabic to Malay to Vernacular in Mindanao.....	123
MUHAMMAD DLUHA LUTHFILLAH	
Not the <i>Utawi</i> You Think You Know: Some Preliminary Notes on Early Javanese Interlinear Translations.....	175
RONIT RICCI	
Interlinear Texts from Indonesia: Preliminary Thoughts on Their Study.....	197
Notes on Contributors.....	221

Interlinear Translation Across the Muslim World: A Comparative Perspective

Introduction

FADHLI LUKMAN and RONIT RICCI¹

The articles that make up this special issue are based on papers first presented at the international workshop, “Interlinear Translation Across the Muslim World: A Comparative Perspective,” held at The Hebrew University of Jerusalem on November 18–20, 2024. The workshop took place within the ongoing inquiries of the ERC-funded research project Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies, that focuses on interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world between the 16th and 20th centuries.² Within this research framework the interlinear text is viewed as an entry point to studying interlingual and intercultural contacts and encounters, beginning at the level of single words but striving to explore wider processes of linguistic, religious and social continuities and change. From the perspective of translation studies, such texts offer us an opportunity to examine one end of the “translation continuum” where the translator’s choices vis à vis the original text are visible on the page.

The workshop aimed to share some of the insights gained through individual and collaborative work within Textual Microcosms and to expand the scope of inquiry of Islamic interlinear translation to additional regions, languages and cultures, allowing for a comparative perspective. More specifically, we aspired to explore interlinear translations in their local, particular contexts, and as a phenomenon shared across disparate parts of a global Muslim civilization. In this workshop the Arabic source text was posited both as a “baseline”

1 We thank all participants in the workshop, including the authors of this issue’s articles as well as those who ultimately did not contribute an article: Oman Fathurahman, Tobias Sick, Zacky Khairul Umam, Dror Weil and Mykhaylo Yakubovych. We also offer our gratitude to the Israel Science Foundation (grant number 3125/24) and the European Research Council Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant agreement No. CoG 101001731) for generously funding the workshop, and to our project coordinators Noor Salaymeh and Hiba Dawas for all the time and work they invested in making the event possible.

2 For more on Textual Microcosms please see: <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/>

that allows a comparison of diverse interlinear translations of the same texts across languages and cultures, and as itself a “shifting terrain” that invites scrutiny due to mistakes, mis-translation, a range of doctrinal agendas, and ideas about untranslatability as they were shaped and sustained across time and place, pointing to the always-tentative nature of both original and translation and the ongoing dynamics that shape and re-shape them both.

In this introduction we offer a literature review of prior scholarship on interlinear translation in the Muslim world, followed by suggestions for further research directions and a brief outline of the issue’s contents.

The review that follows is by no means exhaustive. Nevertheless, brief as it may be, it spans a wide geographical and historical range in considering interlinear translation, covering much of the Islamic world, from Persia, Turkey and Islamic Spain, to Africa, China, South Asia, and Southeast Asia, and tracing interlinear translation practices from as early as the tenth century to the twentieth century. While the question of Qur’an translation has dominated much of the discussion (as elaborated below), other genres and areas of knowledge such as law, theology, sufism, grammar, poetry, and cosmology have also played important roles in the development of interlinear translation patterns and vice versa, interlinear translation has contributed to shaping their transmission across cultures and space. Although often overlooked in earlier scholarship, interlinear translation is now receiving renewed attention—including in this special issue—not only for its pedagogical and exegetical functions but also as a significant textual practice with visual, technical, and sociolinguistic implications.

The Study of Muslim Interlinear Translation: the Qur’an as a Starting Point

There is no doubt that the prominent area in which scholars have engaged with interlinear translation in the Muslim world has been in relation to Qur’an translation. Until only a few decades ago, the dominant academic assumption held that Muslims historically avoided translating the Qur’an, with such practices emerging only in the modern period. A brief yet influential essay by A. L. Tibawi is often cited as providing a comprehensive overview of juridical opinions within the Islamic intellectual tradition concerning the (un)translatability of the Qur’an, while also addressing its historical, theological, and rhetorical dimensions. He contends that, up to the fifth century of Islam, the prevailing stance was to maintain the Qur’an’s untranslatability, and that little of significance occurred in this discourse thereafter.³ In a recorded conversation uploaded to YouTube, Travis Zadeh—whose work will be discussed below—recalled that even a scholar of Shahab Ahmad’s calibre made a dismissive remark, suggesting that there was nothing more to explore on the subject of Qur’an translation, as it had already been done, referring to Tibawi’s essay.⁴

3 A. L. Tibawi, “Is the Qur’ān Translatable?: Early Muslim Opinion,” *The Muslim World* 52, no. 1 (1962), <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1478-1913.1962.tb02588.x>.

4 Travis Zadeh, “Can the Qur’an be Translated? Debates in Early Islam and Today”, interview by Gabriel Said Reynolds, January 12, 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F519Pc9tJK0&t=2463s>.

Bruce Lawrence, in his book *The Koran in English* (2017), also engages with this assumption. He explains that, according to the orthodox view, the Qur'an must remain in Arabic and should not be translated. The use of the Anglicized term “the *Koran*,” he argues, “is itself a choice of history over orthodoxy.” That the Qur'an could become the *Koran*—in other words, that it could be translated—was a view that had prevailed earlier among a European non-Muslims milieu but emerged only at the dawn of the twentieth century in the Muslim world.⁵ Riddell upholds this dominant assumption, identifying three key reasons for Muslim reluctance to translate the Qur'an: the doctrine of its inimitability (*i'jāz*), the alleged corruption (*tahrīf*) of earlier scriptures, and the fear of foreign influence if the Qur'an were rendered into another language.⁶ Furthermore, Hartmut Bobzin, in his entry for the *Encyclopaedia of the Qur'an*, points to an indirect indication from al-Zamakhsharī's interpretation of Q. 14:4 as a clue to the possibility of Qur'anic translation in early Islam. He fills the historical silence by highlighting annotations in Qur'anic commentaries in Persian and early Turkish. While the term “translation” is used only vaguely in these instances, Bobzin applies it more explicitly when referring to the Aljamiado (an old Spanish dialect) translation of the Qur'an in seventeenth-century Islamic Spain and the translation by Shāh Walī Allāh Dihlawī in eighteenth-century India.⁷

Of course, many other scholars besides Tibawi, Lawrence, Riddell, and Bobzin have studied Qur'an translation. However, it is worth noting—especially in light of our current focus—that these scholars paid little attention to interlinear translation in their work. It seems that they had a clear idea of what constitutes translation, and the long history of interlinear glosses, annotations, insertions, or other forms of textual intervention—however one chooses to label them—was excluded from being recognized or positioned within the framework of translation. Likewise, those who study the history of Qur'anic texts containing interlinear materials rarely frame their sources as translations, or at best, make only a vague connection to the concept of translation.⁸

More recently, the Qur'an with interlinear materials has been incorporated into the grand history of Qur'an translation. In *The Vernacular Qur'an: Translation and the Rise of Persian Exegesis*, Travis Zadeh placed interlinear translation at the center of discussions on the (un)translatability of the Qur'an, both in theoretical and historical terms. Through an investigation of the history of interlinear Qur'an translation into Persian from as early as the fourth/tenth century, Zadeh offers a comprehensive challenge to the prevailing scholarly near-consensus on Muslims' reluctance to translate the Qur'an. He contends that the widespread assumption that Muslims refrained from translating the Qur'an is contradicted by the historical record, which reveals that numerous translations were produced within the structured context of religious education. While not entirely dismissing the reluctance to

5 Bruce B. Lawrence, *The Koran in English: A Biography* (Princeton University Press, 2017), xi–xviii.

6 Peter G. Riddell, “Translating the Qur'an into Indonesian Languages,” *Al-Bayān – Journal of Qur'ān and Hadīth Studies* 12, no. 1 (2014): 2, <https://doi.org/10.1163/22321969-12340001>.

7 Hartmut Bobzin, “Translation of the Qur'an,” in *Encyclopaedia of the Qur'ān*, ed. Jane Dammen McAuliffe (Brill, 2006), 5:341.

8 For example: Dmitry Bondarev, “The Language of the Glosses in the Bornu Quranic Manuscripts,” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London* 69, no. 1 (2006): 113–40.

translate, Zadeh argues that the theological position within the Islamic intellectual tradition is far more nuanced than the notion that Muslims have held a consistently reluctant attitude toward Qur'an translation throughout history. He contends that this assumption was shaped by Orientalist conceptions of Islam and the Qur'an, and that it has, in turn, influenced modern-reformist Muslim views on translation. Furthermore, Zadeh demonstrates how the Persian tradition of interlinear Qur'an translation aimed to preserve the sanctity of the Arabic text while simultaneously legitimizing Persian as a language of religious scholarship and cultural expression.⁹

Zadeh's contribution is particularly significant in that it has prompted scholars to incorporate interlinear Qur'an translations into the broader historiography of Qur'an translation. As a result, the long-standing narrative—that Muslims did not translate the Qur'an until the modern period has found a strong antithesis, driving a shift of perspective. This shift is evident in several recent overviews of Qur'an translation history, including Brett Wilson's chapter in *The Oxford Handbook of Qur'anic Studies* and Johanna Pink's contribution to *The Routledge Companion to the Qur'an*.¹⁰ While the earlier edition of the *Encyclopaedia of the Qur'an* gave little attention to interlinear translation, the more recent supplementary entry by Johanna Pink et al. (including Zadeh) has finally incorporated the rich textual tradition of interlinear Qur'an translation across the Muslim world, including examples dating as far back as tenth-century Persia and extending to twentieth-century Indonesia.¹¹

Perhaps an even more consequential contribution of Zadeh's scholarship, particularly for our current interest, lies in its theoretical intervention. His argument extends beyond merely rejecting the claim that Muslims did not translate the Qur'an; it critically interrogates the very notion of the Qur'an's untranslatability. At the core of this interrogation is a challenge to prescriptive models of translation, which tend to assume that a proper or accurate translation supplants the original. The scholarship that works with these models of translation generally excludes interlinear translation from the historiography of Qur'anic translation. In contrast, Zadeh contends that the interlinear format of early Persian Qur'anic translation "moves translation into the realm of commentary and interpretation, supplementing, expanding, and opening up the Arabic text, but not replacing it."¹²

This perspective has introduced a significant new scholarly approach to the theoretical discourse on Qur'an translation. Johanna Pink observes that the existence of interlinear,

9 Travis Zadeh, *The Vernacular Qur'an: Translation and the Rise of Persian Exegesis* (Oxford University Press, 2012), 16.

10 M. Brett Wilson, "Translations of the Qur'an: Islamicate Languages," in *The Oxford Handbook of Qur'anic Studies*, ed. Mustafa Shah and M. A. S. Abdel Haleem (Oxford University Press, 2020), 552–564; Johanna Pink, "Translation," in *The Routledge Companion to the Qur'an*, 1st ed., by George Archer et al. (Routledge, 2021), 364–376. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315885360-36>.

11 Johanna Pink et al., "Translations of the Qur'an [2025]," in *Encyclopaedia of Qur'an Online* (Brill), accessed July 6, 2025, <https://referenceworks.brill.com/display/entries/EQO/EQCOM-063375.xml>.

12 Travis Zadeh, "The Fātiḥa of Salmān Al-Fārisī and the Modern Controversy over Translating the Qur'an," in *The Meaning of the Word: Lexicology and Qur'anic Exegesis*, ed. S.R. Burge, Qur'anic Studies Series 13 (Oxford University Press in association with The Institute of Ismaili Studies, 2015), 398.

word-for-word translations suggests that the doctrinal prohibition against translating the Qur'an was largely theoretical in nature.¹³ She further argues that interlinear translations blur the line between translation and vernacular exegesis, particularly as they are often accompanied by commentaries.¹⁴ Moreover, while modern Qur'an translation modelled after Biblical translation tends to regard the presence of the translator's voice as a marker of lower quality, Pink's study of Javanese interlinear Qur'an translation contends that the translator's voice can, in fact, serve as a crucial element in establishing the translation's authority.¹⁵

In the same vein, Simon Leese notes that Shāh Walī Allāh produced his translation of the Qur'an *taht al-khaṭṭ* (beneath the lines), in a manner that closely mirrored the structure of the Qur'anic Arabic, thereby signaling that the translation was not intended to replace the original text. His translation of the Qur'an, along with other Arabic texts circulating during his time—such as sufi *dhikr*—“served to mediate the sounds and structure of Arabic while enabling wider groups in society to access their meaning.”¹⁶ Leese's perspective demonstrates how incorporating interlinear translation into the broader landscape of Qur'an translation and embracing Zadeh's call to broaden the concept of translation allows for a more empathetic understanding of the position frequently adopted by modern Qur'an translators: that their work does not constitute the Qur'an itself, nor is it a substitute for the original.¹⁷

An illuminating influence of Zadeh's theoretical perspective can be seen in Oğuzhan Tan's distinction between modern Qur'an translation and interlinear translation. He argues that interlinear translations are not translations in the modern sense but rather function as “study books” for readers who can access the original Arabic and seek to deepen their understanding by examining the correspondence between individual words or phrases and their meanings. However, he does not define what he means by modern Qur'an translation, referring to it merely as “textual translation”—perhaps assuming the concept to be self-evident. Although Tan follows the common assumption that Muslims were reluctant to translate the Qur'an until the modern period, he views the history of interlinear translation in the Persian context and its extension into Turkish as a form of permissible translation within Islamic and Turkic traditions.¹⁸

Another challenge to Muslim reluctance towards Qur'an translation is presented by Taufiq Hanafi in his recent study of an interlinear Qur'an translation in Sundanese, the

13 Johanna Pink, “Translation,” in *The Routledge Companion to the Qur'an*, by George Archer, Maria M. Dakake, and Daniel A. Madigan, 1st ed. (New York: Routledge, 2021), 365, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315885360-36>.

14 Pink, “Translation,” 366.

15 Johanna Pink, “The ‘Kyai’'s Voice and the Arabic Qur'an; Translation, Orality, and Print in Modern Java,” *Wacana* 21, no. 3 (December 30, 2020): 329–59, <https://doi.org/10.17510/wacana.v21i3.948>.

16 Simon Leese, “Arabic Utterances in a Multilingual World: Shāh Walī-Allāh and Qur'anic Translatability in North India,” *Translation Studies* 14, no. 2 (May 4, 2021): 242–61, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14781700.2021.1919192>.

17 Consuelo López-Morillas, *El Corán de Toledo: Edición y Estudio Del Manuscrito 235 de La Biblioteca de Castilla-La Mancha* (Ediciones Trea, 2011).

18 Oğuzhan Tan, “Translating The Sacred: Islamic Law, Ottoman Readership, and Two Examples of a Transitional Genre,” *Ilahiyat Studies* 15, no. 2 (2024): 201–31, <https://doi.org/10.12730/is.1458921>.

regional language of West Java, Indonesia. He opens his article by discussing the controversy sur-rounding efforts to translate the Qur'an—both through his personal encounters and the historical debates in early 20th-century Indonesia. His focus is on the intersection of theological hesitation and the linguistic register of Sundanese, posing the question: what happens when divine speech is translated into low colloquial Sundanese? He argues that such a translation not only enhances the legibility of the Qur'an but also fosters a direct and intimate connection between readers and their faith.¹⁹

Challenging the earlier scholarly assumption that Muslims did not translate the Qur'an, as Zadeh did, is not the only avenue through which interlinear translation has prompted a rethinking of the history of Qur'an translation. Arif Maftuhin, while largely adhering to the assumption of Muslim's general hesitation regarding Qur'an translation, views translation as a necessary but not inherently desirable practice within Muslim communities. Examining the history of pre-modern interlinear translations of the commentary *al-Jalālayn* in Indonesia, he argues that such translations represent a pragmatic response to the enduring tension between the doctrinal prohibition against translating the Qur'an and the community's need to comprehend its meaning.²⁰

Interlinear Translation and Textual Practice

Debates on theoretical perspectives on the Qur'an's translation and its historiography represent an important development, particularly where the inclusion of interlinear translation has enriched the field. Beyond these debates, numerous studies on Islamic interlinear translation have drawn attention to a wide range of subjects. Some remain focused on Qur'anic texts, but certainly not exclusively; others engage with textual legacies from diverse fields, including Islamic jurisprudence, history, rhetoric, cosmology, and more. Mahmood Kooria examines how the translation of Shāfi'ite jurisprudential texts—circulating across the Indian Ocean, including in interlinear form—played a crucial role in the transmission of Shāfi'ism in these regions. Beyond the Qur'an and jurisprudence, Azyumardi Azra observed that the legacy of interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world also includes theology and sufism, while Dror Weil, in the context of Chinese Islamic history, points to its use in fields as diverse as jurisprudence, theology, and linguistics, as well as Qur'anic commentary, cosmology, mysticism, rhetoric, astronomy, history, and poetry.²¹

19 Taufiq Hanafi, "Contemporary Sundanese Quran; A Departure or Divine Proximity?," *Wacana* 26, no. 2 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.17510/wacana.v26i2.1758>.

20 Arif Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable: The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice," *Indonesia and the Malay World*, January 4, 2024, 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2264672>.

21 Azyumardi Azra, "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia," in *Sadur Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia Dan Malaysia*, ed. Henri Chambert-Loir (KPG, École française d'Extrême-Orient, Forum Jakarta-Paris, Pusat Bahasa, dan Universitas Padjadjaran, 2009), 435–443; Dror Weil, "Islamicated China: China's Participation in the Islamicate Book Culture during the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries," *Intellectual History of the Islamicate World* 4, nos. 1–2 (2016): 49, <https://doi.org/10.1163/2212943X-00401005>.

Multilingualism is one of the salient features of manuscripts with interlinear translation. The production of such multilingual manuscripts demands particular attention to their visual form, technical execution, contextual functions, and patterns of use and readership—all of which have been examined in a number of studies. The visual representation of the interlinear format plays a central role in Simon Leese’s interpretation of Shāh Walī Allāh’s Persian Qur’an translation in the aforementioned article. Leese prefers the term *subliner* rather than *interlinear*, to more accurately reflect the concept of *taht al-khaṭṭ* (beneath the line), as opposed to between the lines. Terminological preferences aside, Ünver Rüstem’s study of the visual dimension of the *muṣḥaf* featuring interlinear translation in Persian and Turkish highlights the subordinate position of the translation within the textual hierarchy on the page. He notes that “the smaller, usually disjointed glosses only compel the reader-viewer to better perceive the Arabic’s elegance and cohesiveness.”²²

Consuelo López-Morillas surveys Qur’anic manuscripts from the Iberian Peninsula that contain both Arabic and monolingual texts. While most bilingual copies alternate blocks of Arabic and Aljamiado text, a few examples exhibit interlinear translation. In these cases, although dedicated space is provided between the Arabic lines, it is often insufficient—resulting in the translation being cramped into double lines or extending into the margins.²³ It is for this reason that Ünver Rüstem suggests interlinear translation is visually ill-suited for recitation or literary appreciation and instead appears intended primarily to aid comprehension.²⁴

In her descriptive study of Qur’anic manuscripts—tracing the transformation of oral revelation into written form and the evolution of manuscript formats in response to the changing needs of Muslim communities—Sheila S. Blair observes that bilingual, interlinear Qur’anic manuscripts, particularly those in Arabic and Persian or Eastern Turkish and dating to as early as the fourth/tenth century, were likely used for proselytisation and conversion.²⁵

Beyond the visual, technical, and contextual dimensions of manuscripts with an interlinear format, Dmitry Bondarev examines the multilingual character of the Qur’an’s interlinear translation into Old Kanembu—a language once spoken in the sultanates of Kanem and Bornu in West Africa—as a means of linguistic reconstruction of this long-forgotten language (though he does not explicitly use the term *interlinear*).²⁶ His study stands as a testament to the considerable scholarly significance of such manuscripts.

In addition, Bondarev highlights the nature of the Islamic intellectual and pedagogical tradition in the region, shaped by the interlinguistic encounter between Arabic and the local vernacular. He notes that the interlinear format was used to comment on the Qur’an at a highly detailed level, firmly grounded in Arabic grammatical structures. Combined with linguistic features specific to Old Kanembu, this practice enabled the language to become “a

22 Ünver Rüstem, “Rendering the Word of God: The Art of Qur’ans with Interlinear Persian and Turkish Translations,” *Res: Anthropology and Aesthetics* 81–82 (December 2024): 141–62, <https://doi.org/10.1086/730515>.

23 López-Morillas, *El Corán de Toledo*.

24 Rüstem, “Rendering the Word of God.”

25 Sheila S. Blair, *Glorifying God’s Word: Manuscripts of the Qur’an* (Oxford University Press, 2014), 228.

26 Bondarev, “The Language of the Glosses in the Bornu Quranic Manuscripts.”

medium used in excelling at delivery of the meaning of the Qur'an to the public." Bondarev characterizes this exegetical use of the interlinear format as a paradox: the interpretation of the Qur'an in an incomprehensible language. By "incomprehensible language," he means that, because the practice was so closely tied to Arabic structures, the exegetical technique was accessible only to a learned circle of scholars and students, while remaining entirely unintelligible to untrained speakers.²⁷

Looking far back to the early years of Islamic intellectual tradition, Asma Hilali invites us to consider the gradual emergence of interlinear translation as a "textual practice" in the Islamic intellectual tradition. In her study of seventh- and eighth-century Qur'anic manuscripts that feature occasional and fragmentary marginal or interlinear annotations, she observes that the use of both the margins and interlinear space was limited during this early period. When such interventions do appear, they tend to be personal, subjective, and unsystematic—markedly different from the more structured and deliberate features found in manuscripts produced during the later scholastic tradition, beginning in the tenth century. In this light, these early emendations, she suggests, may be understood as tentative precursors to the formalized scholastic transmission practices that would eventually take shape.²⁸

A number of other studies move us forward to the Islamic learning and intellectual traditions of later centuries, extending across a wider global context. Dror Weil, whose work focuses extensively on Arabo-Persian Islamic texts, book culture, and their interactions with Chinese literary traditions, identifies interlinear glossing and marginal commentary as important models of scholarly practice.²⁹ Beginning with the Mongol conquest of China—which initiated China's participation in Islamicate book culture in the thirteenth century—extant manuscripts exhibit multiple systems of annotation and glossing. These include interlinear Persian or Arabic glosses, often comprising word-for-word or phrase-by-phrase translations, interlinear glossing and interpretation in Chinese written in modified Arabic script, grammatical markings, marginal commentaries, and glosses or interpretations in Chinese characters.³⁰ One significant development noted by Weil is the emergence of Chinese-Muslim scholarly networks, particularly those established by Hu Dengzhou (1522–1597), a Muslim scholar from Shaanxi. The primary interest of this network was on detailed grammatical analysis and literal glossing of Arabic and Persian texts, followed by close

27 Dmitry Bondarev, "Qur'anic Exegesis in Old Kanembu: Linguistic Precision for Better Interpretation," *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 15, no. 3 (2013): 56–83, <https://doi.org/10.3366/jqs.2013.0114>.

28 Asma Hilali, "Writing the Qur'ān Between the Lines: Marginal and Interlinear Notes in Selected Qur'ān Fragments from the Museum of Islamic Art, Qatar," in *From Scrolls to Scrolling*, ed. Bradford A. Anderson (De Gruyter, 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110634440-004>.

29 Weil, "Islamicated China"; Dror Weil, "Unveiling Nature: Liu Zhi's Translation of Arabo-Persian Physiology in Early Modern China," *Osiris* 37 (June 2022): 47–66, <https://doi.org/10.1086/719220>; Dror Weil, "Collation and Articulation of Arabo-Persian Scientific Texts in Early Modern China," in *Routledge Handbook on the Sciences in Islamicate Societies*, 1st ed., by Sonja Brentjes et al. (Routledge, 2023), 696–704. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315170718-62>; Dror Weil, "Crossing Boundaries: Reading *Mirṣād al-'Ibad* in Early Modern China (Redrawing and Straddling Borders)," *International Journal of Asian Studies*, January 10, 2024, 1–13, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1479591423000475>.

30 Weil, "Islamicated China," 55.

examination of their rhetorical and logical structures as well as their content.³¹ Weil further suggests that interlinear translation functioned as a tool for acquiring literacy in Arabic and Persian and served as an aid in reading and interpreting other Arabo-Persian texts.³²

Weil's observation on the pedagogical function of interlinear translation is arguably one of its most striking features and strongly resonates with experiences in the Indonesian and Malay world. As noted, Maftuhin in his work highlights the pedagogical use of *Tafsīr al-Jalālayn* in West Sumatra and Java.³³ This observation is further corroborated by Aglaia Iankovskaia, who, in her study of a didactic poem on how to be a good student, argues that the interlinear translation format allows the manuscript to present Arabic didactic verse alongside its explanatory Malay translation on the same page—constituting an effort to integrate moral instruction with the teaching of the Qur'an's language.³⁴ Furthermore, drawing on the same text, she was able to reconstruct its performative dimension and mode of transmission. The pedagogical practice likely took place in a classroom setting, where both the Arabic source text and its Malay translation were read aloud in a structured and ritualized manner: the teacher would recite the *matn* (main text) at the front of the class, the students would repeat it orally in unison, and the translation would be written interlinearly in their individual copies of the text.³⁵

Directions for Further Research

Beyond the variegated research reviewed, the questions it has posed and the case studies it has explored, there are further dimensions of interlinear translation that remain understudied and invite further research. One such area is the *system* of translation itself. In Java, the practice of *terjemahan gandul* (hanging translation) is well known, and comparable models can also be found in the Malay world. These interlinear translations employ formulaic terms to render specific elements of the Arabic source text—particularly its grammatical components—into local languages. The contribution by Lutfillah in this issue examines such a system in the Javanese context, and Bondarev's aforementioned study, which pays close attention to the linguistic minutiae of Old Kanembu, offers a strong foundation for further research in this area.

Interlinear translations are often written in scripts derived from Arabic, a feature known across regions, and thus script-use is another dimension of these translations that invites comparison. Another underexamined aspect is the influence of interlinear translation on the languages into which Arabic texts were rendered. While such inquiries exist for the Malay context, most notably in the works of Van Ronkel, Peter G. Riddell, and Ronit Ricci, and for

31 Weil, "Unveiling Nature," 51.

32 Weil, "Islamicated China," 49.

33 Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable."

34 Aglaia Iankovskaia, "Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje," *Archipel* 106 (2023): 89–124, <https://doi.org/10.4000/11wu6>.

35 Aglaia Iankovskaia, "On 'Hanging Meaning' and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh," *Archipel* 107 (2024): 119–35, <https://doi.org/10.4000/12fv1>.

West Africa in the works of Bondarev, greater attention should also be given to other languages shaped by the practice of interlinear translation.³⁶

Furthermore, as a separate line of inquiry deserving its own dedicated study, interlinear translation was not limited to Muslim contexts or solely intended for Muslim audiences. A few studies have begun to explore its appropriation by Orientalist and Western scholars. Zahra Kazani, for example, discusses a Qur’anic manuscript held at the British Museum that features Persian interlinear translation accompanied by English annotations, forming a three-tiered textual structure. She argues that this manuscript functioned as a tool for language acquisition and knowledge extraction within the broader framework of Orientalist efforts to classify and systematise Indian knowledge.³⁷ Similarly, Roberto Tottoli, in his analysis of a seventeenth-century Latin interlinear translation of the Qur’an, interprets such works as part of a larger Orientalist intellectual project.³⁸ These examples remind us that interlinear translation has served multiple audiences and purposes—religious, pedagogical, political, and epistemological—across centuries and cultures, and its full complexity is only beginning to be appreciated in scholarship today.

Keeping the comparative angle in mind we might also ask what genres and particular texts were particularly “prone” to being translated between the lines across regions, and why. Studies might explore the histories of interlinear translation within particular Muslim communities, schools of thought, or regions; forms of continuity and change in practices of interlinear translation; pedagogical contexts of interlinear translation; visual and sonic aspects of interlinear translations, i.e., what does shifting the focus from content to visual dimensions of the interlinear page reveal, and what does a consideration of the sounding out of two languages entail?³⁹ The performative elements of interlinear translation have also received minimal attention to date and could offer a rich site of investigation.⁴⁰

36 Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalam Arab Terhadap Tatakalam Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528; Peter G. Riddell, “Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay,” *Studia Islamika* 9, no. 2 (2002): 1–28, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/sdi.v9i1.672>; Ronit Ricci, “Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation,” *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80, <https://doi.org/10.1163/24056480-00101008>.

37 Zahra Kazani, “Between the Foreign and the Familiar: A Qur’an Manuscript and Its Later English Annotations at the East India Company,” *Journal of Islamic Manuscripts* 11, no. 3 (2020): 373–409, <https://doi.org/10.1163/1878464X-01103004>.

38 Roberto Tottoli, “The Latin Translation of the Qur’ān by Johann Zechendorff (1580–1662) Discovered in Cairo Dār al-Kutub,” *Oriente Moderno* 95, nos. 1–2 (2015): 5–31, <https://doi.org/10.1163/22138617-12340081>.

39 For a preliminary study on visual dimensions of interlinear manuscripts see Ronit Ricci, “Implicit Comparisons: Visuality and the Interlinear Manuscript Page,” *History and Theory*, published online 16 September 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1111/hith.70002>.

40 On performative aspects of interlinear translation see Michaeli’s article in this issue; Ronit Ricci, “Sound Across Languages,” *Philological Encounters* 5, no. 2 (2020): 97–111; Omri Ganchrow, “Weaving Voices: Translation and Identity in Balinese *Pepaosan* Performances of the *Bhagavad Gītā*.” (M.A Thesis, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 2025).

Before moving on to a brief outline of this issue's content, a note on transliteration and spelling is warranted. Multiple orthographic systems, especially when Arabic or Arabic-derived words are concerned, across places and time periods during which orthographic variation was the norm and spelling reforms took place repeatedly, make spelling in an issue such as this one challenging. Therefore, we did not strive for consistency and authors made their own decisions (e.g., how to spell Indonesian or Turkish words derived from Arabic), while when citing we used the original spelling rather than impose more recent conventions.

Brief Overview of the Articles

The articles in the following pages cover a wide range of sites and traditions of interlinear translation produced within Muslim communities and institutions, from The Philippines to Kenya and from Turkey to Indonesia. Taken together, they point to the geographical, chronological and cultural range of this translation paradigm and to its flourishing as both a form of shared practice and one that possessed distinct characteristics and significance in particular local contexts.

Andrew Peacock's article opens the issue with a discussion of interlinear translations in Middle Turkic/Medieval Eastern Turkish. He surveys the extant interlinear Qur'anic translations that have come down to us and argues these are closely connected with a slightly earlier Persian tradition. The article discusses the evidence for the context of production and circulation of these texts, and concludes by adducing some evidence for later non-Qur'anic interlinear translations in Khwarazmian and Chaghatay. Peacock also argues that the interlinear manuscripts he discusses represent an elite form of cultural production. In doing so, the article not only illuminates a relatively underexplored corpus but also provides an important point of departure for broader reflections on the role of interlinear translation in the intellectual history of Central Asia.

Aglaia Iankovskaia in her article explores two manuscripts containing copies of a thematic Arabic-Malay vocabulary titled *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-ʿArab* (A list in Arabic speech) from West Sumatra, Indonesia. The vocabulary contains a list of Arabic words arranged in thematic sections (e.g., God's names, animals, items of clothing) and provided with Malay equivalents below the line. The article discusses the encyclopaedic nature of such an arrangement and addresses the pedagogical functions of this thematic dictionary as a tool for teaching and learning Arabic as a foreign language. Juxtaposing two versions of the same text, Iankovskaia questions the modes of its transmission and reasons for employing an interlinear model of translation in a dictionary. By bringing to light this little-known textual tradition, the article enriches our understanding of the creative strategies through which Arabic was taught and transmitted in the Malay world.

Raphael Michaeli discusses *mawlid* recitations from East Africa that feature a fluid interchange between Arabic and Swahili. He asks whether the use of Swahili verses interwoven into recitations of Arabic *mawlid* texts can be understood as a form of oral interlinear translation. By doing so his article suggests employing the paradigm of interlinear translation in performative contexts in which a written text is replaced by oral presentation, drumming and movement, expanding the purview of how we consider interlinearity across context and media.

Fadhli Lukman investigates the translation tradition of *surau* communities in the Minangkabau world. Focusing on the manuscript collection of Surau Simaung in Sijunjung, West Sumatra, he explores the nature of translation practices in the surau, where, as he has found, occasional interlinear translation predominates. He argues that translation in the surau was not primarily about finding lexical equivalents to Arabic in Malay but was fundamentally an exercise in textual analysis: it served as a vernacular expression of the post-classical Islamic intellectual project, in which surau scholars pursued rigorous grammatical engagement with Arabic texts, transforming translation into a tool of learning and inquiry.

Midori Kawashima turns our attention to the southern Philippines, examining the long-standing use of interlinear translation among Muslims in Mindanao. She draws attention both to the broader Southeast Asian tradition of Arabic–Malay translation within which Mindanao translators were operating and to forms of local innovation. Focusing on four works from the Lanao region—three manuscripts and a lithographed book produced between the late eighteenth and the mid-twentieth century—the study analyses translations of Arabic hadith texts into Malay and Maranao. It demonstrates that while Mindanao scholars followed familiar interlinear conventions, they also adapted and expanded them, adding explanatory glosses, clarifying pronouns, and eventually creating interlinear translations in their own vernacular language, Maranao. In doing so, they not only facilitated Arabic learning but also contributed to the Islamic reform movement, which sought to make religious texts accessible to the wider population. The article sheds new light on the intellectual creativity of Maranao scholars and underscores the significance of interlinear translation in the development of Islamic literary culture in the southern Philippines.

Muhammad Dluha Lutfillah examines the systematic practice of interlinear translation in Javanese Islamic texts, in which certain Javanese words within the translation served as grammatical and discursive markers to guide readers through the Arabic. Central to the study is the trajectory of the word *utawi*, traced in manuscripts from the sixteenth to the nineteenth centuries. The article shows how *utawi*'s role shifted from rendering the Arabic conjunction *wāw al-isti'nāf* to functioning primarily as a marker of the *mubtada'* (subject in a nominal sentence). This micro-level analysis highlights pedagogical and linguistic transformations in Islamic Java and enriches our understanding of textual transmission and local hermeneutics.

Finally, Ronit Ricci engages with scholarship on Muslims' practices of interlinear translation in Indonesia, where such translations were known since at least the late 16th century and have circulated widely since. She asks whether this textual abundance was matched by the range of scholarly writings produced about the interlinear phenomenon, focusing on the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Rather than offering an exhaustive survey the article raises questions about how interlinear translations were perceived and points to possible trends that have helped shape the scholarly context for current research on interlinear translation from the Indonesian-Malay world.

References

- AZRA, Azyumardi. "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia." In *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, edited by Henri Chambert-Loir. KPG, École française d'Extrême-Orient, Forum Jakarta-Paris, Pusat Bahasa, dan Universitas Padjadjaran, 2009, 435–443.
- BLAIR, Sheila S. *Glorifying God's Word: Manuscripts of the Qur'an*. Oxford University Press, 2014.
- BOBZIN, Hartmut. "Translation of the Qur'an." In *Encyclopaedia of the Qur'ān*, edited by Jane Dammen McAuliffe, vol. 5. Brill, 2006.
- BONDAREV, Dmitry. "Qur'anic Exegesis in Old Kanembu: Linguistic Precision for Better Interpretation." *Journal of Qur'anic Studies* 15, no. 3 (2013): 56–83. <https://doi.org/10.3366/jqs.2013.0114>.
- . "The Language of the Glosses in the Bornu Quranic Manuscripts." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 69, no. 1 (2006): 113–40.
- GANCHROW, Omri. "Weaving Voices: Translation and Identity in Balinese *Pepaosan* Performances of the *Bhagavad Gītā*." (M.A Thesis, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 2025).
- HANAFI, Taufiq. "Contemporary Sundanese Quran; A Departure or Divine Proximity?" *Wacana* 26, no. 2 (2025): 212–235. <https://doi.org/10.17510/wacana.v26i2.1758>.
- HILALI, Asma. "Writing the Qur'ān Between the Lines: Marginal and Interlinear Notes in Selected Qur'ān Fragments from the Museum of Islamic Art, Qatar." In *From Scrolls to Scrolling*, edited by Bradford A. Anderson. De Gruyter, 2020, 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110634440-004>.
- IANKOVSKAIA, Aglaia. "Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje." *Archipel* 106 (2023): 89–124. <https://doi.org/10.4000/11wu6>.
- . "On 'Hanging Meaning' and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh." *Archipel* 107 (2024): 119–35. <https://doi.org/10.4000/12fv1>.
- KAZANI, Zahra. "Between the Foreign and the Familiar: A Qur'an Manuscript and Its Later English Annotations at the East India Company." *Journal of Islamic Manuscripts* 11, no. 3 (2020): 373–409. <https://doi.org/10.1163/1878464X-01103004>.
- LAWRENCE, Bruce B. *The Koran in English: A Biography*. Princeton University Press, 2017.
- LÓPEZ-MORILLAS, Consuelo. *El Corán de Toledo: Edición y Estudio Del Manuscrito 235 de La Biblioteca de Castilla-La Mancha*. Ediciones Trea, 2011.
- MAFTUHIN, Arif. "Translating the Untranslatable: The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice." *Indonesia and the Malay World*, January 4, 2024, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2264672>.
- PINK, Johanna. "The 'Kyai's' Voice and the Arabic Qur'an; Translation, Orality, and Print in Modern Java." *Wacana* 21, no. 3 (2020): 329–59. <https://doi.org/10.17510/wacana.v21i3.948>.
- . "Translation." In *The Routledge Companion to the Qur'an*, 1st ed., by George Archer, Maria M. Dakake, and Daniel A. Madigan. Routledge, 2021, 364–376. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315885360-36>.
- , Travis ZADEH, Mohsen FEYZBAKHSH, et al. "Translations of the Qur'ān [2025]." In *Encyclopaedia of Qur'an Online*. Brill. Accessed July 6, 2025. <https://referenceworks.brill.com/display/entries/EQO/EQCOM-063375.xml>.
- RICCI, Ronit. "Implicit Comparisons: Visuality and the Interlinear Manuscript Page." *History and Theory*, published online on 16 September 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hith.70002>.
- . "Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation." *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80. <https://doi.org/10.1163/24056480-00101008>.
- . "Sound Across Languages." *Philological Encounters* 5, no. 2 (2020): 97–111.

<https://doi.org/10.1163/24519197-BJA10002>.

- RIDDELL, Peter G. "Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay." *Studia Islamika* 9, no. 2 (2002): 1–28. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/sdi.v9i1.672>.
- . "Translating the Qur'ān into Indonesian Languages." *Al-Bayān – Journal of Qur'ān and Hadīth Studies* 12, no. 1 (2014): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22321969-12340001>.
- RONKEL, Ph. S. van. *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalam Arab Terhadap Tatakalam Melayu*, trans-lated by A. Ikram. Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as "Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische," *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528
- RÜSTEM, Ünver. "Rendering the Word of God: The Art of Qur'ans with Interlinear Persian and Turkish Translations." *Res: Anthropology and Aesthetics* 81–82 (December 2024): 141–62. <https://doi.org/10.1086/730515>.
- TAN, Oğuzhan. "Translating The Sacred: Islamic Law, Ottoman Readership, and Two Examples of a Transitional Genre." *Ilahiyat Studies* 15, no. 2 (2024): 201–31. <https://doi.org/10.12730/is.1458921>.
- TIBAWI, A. L. "Is the Qur'ān Translatable?: Early Muslim Opinion." *The Muslim World* 52, no. 1 (1962): 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1478-1913.1962.tb02588.x>.
- TOTTOLI, Roberto. "The Latin Translation of the Qur'ān by Johann Zechendorff (1580–1662) Discovered in Cairo Dār al-Kutub." *Oriente Moderno* 95, nos. 1–2 (2015): 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22138617-12340081>.
- WEIL, Dror. "Collation and Articulation of Arabo-Persian Scientific Texts in Early Modern China." In *Routledge Handbook on the Sciences in Islamicate Societies*, 1st ed., by Sonja Brentjes, Peter Barker, and Rana Brentjes. Routledge, 2023, 696–704. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315170718-62>.
- . "Crossing Boundaries: Reading *Miršād al-'Ibad* in Early Modern China (Redrawing and Straddling Borders)." *International Journal of Asian Studies*, January 10, 2024, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1479591423000475>.
- . "Islamicated China: China's Participation in the Islamicate Book Culture during the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries." *Intellectual History of the Islamicate World* 4, nos. 1–2 (2016): 36–60. <https://doi.org/10.1163/2212943X-00401005>.
- . "Unveiling Nature: Liu Zhi's Translation of Arabo-Persian Physiology in Early Modern China." *Osiris* 37 (June 2022): 47–66. <https://doi.org/10.1086/719220>.
- WILSON, M. Brett. "Translations of the Qur'an: Islamicate Languages." In *The Oxford Handbook of Qur'anic Studies*, edited by Mustafa Shah and M. A. S. Abdel Haleem. Oxford University Press, 2020, 552–564.
- ZADEH, Travis. "The Fātiḥa of Salmān Al-Fārisī and the Modern Controversy over Translating the Qur'an." In *The Meaning of the Word: Lexicology and Qur'anic Exegesis*, edited by S.R. Burge. Qur'anic Studies Series 13. Oxford University Press in association with The Institute of Ismaili Studies, 2015, 375–420.
- . *The Vernacular Qur'an: Translation and the Rise of Persian Exegesis*. Oxford University Press, 2012.

© Fadhli Lukman, UIN Sunan Kalijaga, Yogyakarta
◀ fadhli.lukman@uin-suka.ac.id ▶

© Ronit Ricci, Hebrew University of
Jerusalem & Australian National
University
◀ Ronit.Ricci@mail.huji.ac.il ▶

Medieval Eastern Turkish Interlinear Translations: *Their Manuscripts, Audience and Persian Background*

A.C.S. PEACOCK (University of St Andrews)¹

Abstract

This article discusses interlinear translations in Middle Turkic/Medieval Eastern Turkish (also known as Qarakhanid and Khwarazmian Turkish). The article surveys the extant interlinear Qur'anic translations that have come down to us, and argues these are closely connected with a slightly earlier Persian tradition, exemplified by the Samanid-era translation of al-Ṭabarī's *Tafsīr*. The article discusses the evidence for the context of production and circulation of these texts, and concludes by adducing some evidence for later non-Qur'anic interlinear translations in Khwarazmian and Chaghatay. It argues that these interlinear manuscripts represent an elite form of cultural production.

Keywords: Qarakhanid, Khwarazmian, Middle Turkic, Qur'an, translation

Introduction

The practice of interlinear translation in the Islamic world is first attested in Central Asia in the tenth to eleventh centuries, and interlinear Qur'ans represent one of the earliest forms of textual production in both Persian and Turkish, constituting two closely linked traditions. The appearance of this practice is unquestionably associated with the process of vernacularisation that was taking place at the same time in this region—the emergence of Persian and Turkish as literary languages of the Islamic world, for the first time offering written alternatives to Arabic for the development of Islamic literatures. Vernacularisation is usually associated with the patronage of two dynasties, the Samanids of Transoxiana (r. 892–999), under whose rule in the tenth century some of the earliest works of New Persian were first composed,² and the Turkish Qarakhanids (r. 999–1211), who are linked to the

1 I gratefully acknowledge the support of the Leverhulme Trust, which awarded me a Research Fellowship that allowed this research to be undertaken. I am indebted to Kristof D'hulster, Ronit Ricci and Fadhli Lukman for their comments on drafts of this article.

2 On this see G. Lazard, "The Rise of the New Persian Language," in *The Cambridge History of Iran*, vol. 4, *The Period from the Arab Invasion to the Saljuqs*, ed. R.N. Frye (Cambridge University Press, 1975), 595–632; A.C.S. Peacock, *Mediaeval Islamic Historiography and Political Legitimacy: Bal'amī's Tārīkhnāma* (Routledge, 2007), chapter 1.

appearance of a Turkish Islamic literature in the Kashgar region in the eleventh century.³ The two languages had rather different fates, however: while Persian was almost immediately widely adopted for administrative, literary and religious purposes throughout the eastern Islamic world, Turkish literary production remained much more limited. The early interlinear Qur'an translation into the Middle Turkic language usually described as Qarakhanid Turkish, of which the principal surviving witness is held in the John Rylands Library in Manchester, is one of only a handful of Islamic Turkish literary works that can be attributed to the pre-Mongol period with some certainty. The others are the Sufi-influenced didactic poem *Ḳutadḡu bilig* (Wisdom of Royal Glory) by Yūsuf Khāṣṣ Ḥājib, composed in Kashgar in 1069–1070 for the Qarakhanid ruler Tabghach Bughrā Khān Abū'l-Ḥasan ibn Sulaymān, the Turkish-Arabic dictionary *Dīwān lughāt al-Turk* written between approximately 1072 and 1077 by Maḥmūd al-Kāshgharī, a member of the Qarakhanid ruling family, and a didactic poem entitled the *Atabetü'l-ḥakaik* (Portal of Truths), which probably dates to the late twelfth or early thirteenth century. The interlinear Qur'an translation thus has considerable importance as one of the representatives of this very small corpus of early Turkish Islamic literature, although its principal witness is a manuscript of the late fourteenth century.

From the late thirteenth century, Turkish, in different dialect forms, started to be adopted as a literary language in Anatolia, the lands of the Golden Horde in Central Asia and the Qipchaq steppe, and Mamluk Syria and Egypt. The most closely related of these dialects to Qarakhanid Turkish was Khwarazmian, which developed in the thirteenth century and was used in the Golden Horde lands and even on occasion in Anatolia and Egypt. Indeed, the Eastern Turkish tradition of interlinear Qur'an translations represented by Qarakhanid and Khwarazmian remained influential even in areas where different dialects predominated, and manuscripts in these languages circulated in Anatolia and the Mamluk lands. Interlinear translations into Anatolian Turkish first appear around the beginning of the fifteenth century, and thus represent a slightly later tradition that space does not allow detailed consideration of here.⁴ In the same period, at least two different Turkish Qur'an translations were available in the Mamluk sultanate.⁵

3 On early Turkish literature see Robert Dankoff, "Qarakhanid Literature and the Beginnings of Turco-Islamic Culture," in Robert Dankoff, *From Mahmud Kaşgari to Evliya Çelebi Studies in Middle Turkic and Ottoman Literatures* (Isis, 2009), 11–18.

4 For examples of such Anatolian Turkish interlinear Qur'ans, see for example, British Library Or 9515, discussed by G.M. Meredith-Owens, "Notes on an Old Ottoman Translation of the Kur'ān," *Oriens* 10, no. 2 (1957): 258–276; the oldest dated example is Bursa, İnebey Yazma Eser Kütüphanesi Genel 1, dated to 804/1401, published by Murat Küçük as *Eski Anadolu Türkçesi Dönemine Ait Satır Arası İlk Kur'an Tercümesi* (TTK, 2022). Useful surveys of manuscripts of Turkish Qur'an translations in both eastern and western dialects (most of which are interlinear) include Muhammed Hamidullah, "Kur'an-ı Kerim'in Türkçe Yazma Tercümeleri," *Türkiyat Mecmuası*, no. 14 (1964): 65–80; Mehmet Kara, "Doğu ve Batı Türkçesinde Kur'an Tercüme ve Tefsirleri," *Diyanet İlmî Dergi* 29, no. 3 (1993): 25–36. On Anatolian/Ottoman interlinear Qur'ans see Eleazar Birbaum, "On Some Turkish Interlinear Translations of the Koran," *Journal of Turkish Studies/Türklük Bilgisi Araştırmaları*, no. 14 (1990): 113–138.

5 Mustafa Tokar, "Memlük Sahasında Yazılmış Kur'an-ı Kerim Tercümesi Yok Mudur?" in *Tarihî Türkçe Kur'an Tercümeleri Üzerine Araştırmalar*, ed. Ahmet Akpınar (Kriter, 2024), 29–57. On Turkish Qur'ans that can be associated with the Mamluks, see Kristof D'hulster, "Qayt Sharif's Turkic Class Notes and Tamurbāy's Arabic Scribbles: Language and Education at the Mamluk Barracks in the Light of MS

In this article I will examine interlinear Qur'an translations into Eastern Turkish (i.e., Qarakhanid and Khwarazmian). To date scholarship has tended to treat Turkish interlinear translations in isolation from the Persian texts that accompany them and rarely touches on the broader questions of why such manuscripts were produced, concentrating instead on the grammatical and lexical features of these works as linguistic evidence for the development of Middle Turkic. In contrast, this article studies the early interlinear Turkish translations of the twelfth to fourteenth century with a view to assessing the context for their consumption and production, and thus their audience, as well as their relationship to the slightly older Persian tradition of translation to which they were indebted. This has not received adequate attention, a fact exacerbated by the fact that existing publications of early Turkish interlinear translations usually omit any accompanying Persian texts, presenting the Turkish entirely divorced both the Arabic and Persian texts it was intended to accompany.

Qur'an translations constitute a major part of the interlinear corpus in both Persian and Turkish, but interlinear translation was sometimes used for other works, including on occasion literary texts. For example, one of the oldest interlinear Persian manuscripts extant is the *Badāyi' al-mulāḥ*, a collection of Arabic poetry that survives in a late twelfth century manuscript from Transoxiana furnished with a Persian interlinear translation.⁶ In the final section of this article I turn to non-Qur'anic interlinear translations and transliterations, to understand the broader context for the production of this genre. Turkish had the peculiarity that it could be written in two scripts, Arabic, and Uyghur, the latter having been inherited from the pre-Islamic traditions of Turkish literacy to which the Qarakhanids were heirs. Although Arabic was far more widely used, during the fifteenth century there was a revival of interest in the Uyghur script, especially for luxury texts produced for courtly audiences, and as a result the practice of interlinear translation seems to have given birth to a cognate one of interlinear transliteration/transcription which I consider briefly in the concluding section of this article.

Transoxiana and the Rise of Interlinear Translations

The Turkish interlinear translations are closely connected with the somewhat earlier Persian translations of the Qur'an. I will briefly review the circumstances of composition of the most influential of these Persian versions, the Samanid *Tafsīr*.

The development of Persian as a vehicle for Islam which could transcend the diverse local languages of Central Asia (Sogdian, Khwarazmian, Bactrian, to mention a handful which are attested in textual form) can be traced back to shortly after the Muslim conquest of Transoxiana in the early eighth century. According to the historian of Bukhara, Narshakhī, writing in the tenth century, "The people of Bukhara, at the beginning (of their conversion to

Ayasofya 1448," *Mamluk Studies Review* (2025) (in press). I am grateful to the author for discussing this question with me and providing a pre-publication copy of his article.

6 Abū Muḥammad Majd al-Dīn Qāsim ibn Ḥusayn ibn Muḥammad Tarā'ifi Khwārazmī, ma'rūf biḥ Ṣadr al-Afāḍil, *Badāyi' al-mulāḥ*, ed. Muṣṭafā Awliyā'i (Mīrāth-i Maktūb, 2003). The manuscript is Süleymaniye Library, Istanbul, MS Laleli 1750, dated to 592/1195.

Islam), during prayer, read the Qur'an in Persian, for they were unable to understand Arabic." Nonetheless, the somewhat alien status of Persian in this Sogdian-speaking region is reflected in the fact that Narshakhī tells us the instructions for the prostrations were given in Sogdian.⁷ Over the next century there is sporadic and partial evidence for the writing of Persian, but the development of the literary language is usually attributed to the patronage of the Samanids, who sponsored both translations and original works in Persian. One of the most significant of these Samanid projects was the great translation and interpretation of the Qur'an commissioned by the Samanid amir Maṣṣūr ibn Nūḥ (r. 961–976) ostensibly based (loosely) on the Arabic commentary of the Baghdad-based scholar al-Ṭabarī (d. 923), the *Jāmi' al-bayān fī tafsīr āyāt al-Qur'ān* (Compendium of Explanations Commenting on the Verses of the Qur'an). Around the same time, Maṣṣūr ibn Nūḥ commissioned his vizier Bal'amī to translate al-Ṭabarī's universal history, the *Ta'rīkh al-rusul wa'l-mulūk* (History of Prophets and Kings).⁸ The Persian *Tafsīr* translation itself records how it came into being:

Page | 22

This book is the great *Tafsīr* correctly translated from the version of Muḥammad ibn Jarīr al-Ṭabarī, may God have mercy on him, into the Persian language (*bi zabān-i pārsī u darī*).⁹ They brought this book from Baghdad in forty volumes. It was written in Arabic with long *isnāds*. It was brought to the victorious amīr Abū Šāliḥ Maṣṣūr ibn Nūḥ ibn Naṣr b Aḥmad ibn Ismā'īl, may God have mercy on them all. Reading this book and its expression in Arabic was difficult for him, and so he requested it be translated into Persian (*bi zabān-i pārsī*).

He gathered the ulama of Transoxiana and consulted them as to whether it would be permissible to translate this book into Persian. They said that reading and writing the *tafsīr* of the Qur'an in Persian is permissible for someone who does not know Arabic, for as God, great and glorious is He, has said, "We have not sent a Prophet save with the tongue of his people" (Q 14:4). Another reason is that in times of old, people knew Persian, from the time of Adam to the time of the Prophet Ismā'īl all the prophets and kings of the earth spoke Persian. The first to speak Arabic was the Prophet Ismā'īl, and our Prophet came from the Arabs, and this Qur'an was sent to him in Arabic. Here in this region the language is Persian (*pārsī*) and the kings of this area are Persian kings (*mulūk-i 'ajam*).

The victorious king Abū Šāliḥ ordered the ulama of Transoxiana to assemble, such as the *faqīh* Abū Bakr Aḥmad ibn Ḥāmid from Bukhara, Khalīl ibn Aḥmad al-Sijistānī, and Abū Ja'far ibn Muḥammad ibn 'Alī, and from Bab al-Hindu the *faqīh* al-Ḥasan ibn 'Alī Mandūs, and Abū al-Jahm Khālid ibn Hānī *al-mutafaqqih*, and others from Samarqand, Ispijab, Farghana, and from every town in Transoxiana. All issued written rulings that this was the correct course regarding the translation of this book.

7 Richard N. Frye, trans., *The History of Bukhara, Translated from a Persian Abridgement of the Arabic Original by Narshakhi* (The Mediaeval Academy of America, 1954), 48.

8 On this, and in general on Samanid literary patronage, see Peacock, *Mediaeval Islamic Historiography*.

9 *Darī* is used in this period to refer to the Persian literary language; for a discussion of its relationship to *pārsī*, see Gilbert Lazard, "Darī," *Encyclopaedia Iranica* Vol. VII, Fasc. 1, 34–35.

Then the Amir, the victorious king Abū Šālih (i.e., Manšūr ibn Nūh), ordered this group of ulama to choose from among themselves the most virtuous and learned to translate this book. They translated this book, and excised the long isnads and shortened the text of the reports (*akhbār*), and made it into twenty volumes.¹⁰

As with the *History*, the *Tafsīr* was very far from representing a translation of al-Ṭabarī's work.¹¹ Rather, it constituted both a radical abridgement and adaptation that exploited al-Ṭabarī's name to give authority to a project that was very different from the original. First and foremost, the *Tafsīr* translation represents an interlinear Persian translation of the Qur'an, and the exegesis in Persian that follows each section bears little relationship to al-Ṭabarī's text. Although the interlinear nature of this translation is not clear from the modern printed edition, in which the Arabic text of the Qur'an is omitted and only the Persian is presented, it is evident from early manuscripts, such as that illustrated in Fig. 1. Whereas in the *Jāmi' al-bayān* al-Ṭabarī had provided a philological exegesis, with *isnāds* for variant explanations of both individual words and grammatical questions as well as debates about the broader meaning, in the Persian *Tafsīr* the philological baggage is jettisoned entirely. In place of the variant accounts of the original, a single smooth narrative relates the verses to the historical events to which they allude. The preoccupation of the Persian text with such historical narratives is quite distinct from the grammatical, legal and theological matters that represented the main concern of not just al-Ṭabarī, but most other Arabic Qur'an commentaries.¹² Rather, it shares many interests with Bal'amī's version of al-Ṭabarī, specifically narratives of pre-Islamic history and Prophets, as well as affinities with the Iranian tradition of advice literature or "mirrors for princes."¹³

Zadeh suggests that the *Tafsīr* translation circulated particularly in courtly contexts,¹⁴ as is suggested by both the work's contents and the form of the earliest extant manuscripts, many of which, although no older than the twelfth century, are luxury products decorated with gold illumination. Indeed, it is noteworthy that the prime justification for the translation is the status of Persian as the language of kingship. The translators' audacious claim is that Persian is not simply the language of Transoxiana and its kings, but of Prophecy itself, the original language spoken by Adam. The verse "We have not sent a Prophet save with the tongue of his people" thus serves not simply to justify the translation of the Qur'an into Persian, but in fact explains why the Qur'an is not in Persian, the original language of Prophecy. The Persian *Tafsīr*'s agenda is thus not simply—or indeed not even—one of making Arabic knowledge accessible to a non-Arab audience. It is destined for a royal patron,

10 Habīb Yaghmā'ī, ed., *Tarjama-yi tafsīr-i Qur'ān* (Intishārāt-i Dānishgāh-i Tahrān, 2536/1356), 6–7; my translation differs in minor details from that in János Eckmann, "Eastern Turkic Translations of the Koran," in *Studia Turcica*, ed. L. Ligeti (Akadémiai Kiadó, 1971), 149–150; reprinted in János Eckmann, *Middle Turkic Glosses of the Rylands Interlinear Koran Translation* (Akadémiai Kiadó, 1976), 11–12

11 On the Persian version of al-Ṭabarī's *History*, see Peacock, *Mediaeval Islamic Historiography*.

12 Travis Zadeh, *The Vernacular Qur'an: Translation and the Rise of Persian Exegesis* (Oxford University Press, 2012), 313, 315.

13 Zadeh, *Vernacular Qur'an*, 321.

14 Zadeh, *Vernacular Qur'an*, 312–313.

Fig. 1 The interlinear translation (right) and commentary (left) in an early manuscript of the Samanid translation of al-Tabarī’s *Tafsīr* (circa 1200 AD). Bursa, İnebey Yazma Eser Kütüphanesi, Genel 4441, fol. 16b-17a.

and is intended to assert the status of Persian as a language of both kingship and religion, as is suggested by the text’s explicit claim of the involvement of both the ruler and the ulama in the translation project. The strictures about the ruler having found reading it in Arabic difficult should not necessarily be read literally, but rather they reflect a Samanid predilection for using language as a means of asserting both a dynastic and a regional identity. The Samanid *Tafsīr* thus differs from the other Qur’an translations which were probably circulating in the period through its proclamation of its close links to state, giving it something of an official character.

Yet there is no doubt that the practice of creating interlinear Persian translations and exegesis was already widespread by the tenth century. Numerous early but undated Qur’an translations survive, and the text of the Samanid *Tafsīr* gives evidence of interventions by a variety of copyists, indicating the genesis of the text stretched over a considerable period.¹⁵ Writing in the late eleventh century under Qarakhanid rule, at Uzgend in easternmost Transoxiana, the noted jurist al-Sarakhsī tried to justify the writing of interlinear Persian translations by claiming the authority of the Prophet’s Persian Companion Salmān al-Fārisī

15 Zadeh, *Vernacular Qur’an*, 313.

for the practice.¹⁶ Despite the acceptance amongst Hanafis—the predominant law school in Central Asia—of the permissibility of translating the Qur’anic text, this may indicate that it remained sufficiently debated that some further authority was thought desirable.

The Samanid *Tafsīr*, and the translation of the Qur’an it contained, had a major influence on the emergence of Turkish Qur’an translations. It was on the Persian translation of the Qur’an, rather than the Arabic, that the Turkish versions were largely (although not exclusively) based, while two Turkish Qur’an translation manuscripts also incorporate exegetical text based on the Samanid Persian *Tafsīr*. It is likely too that the practice of making interlinear translations was inspired by the precedent of the Samanid *Tafsīr*, for we know that in this period there were also other Qur’an translations circulating with very different methods of translating. For example, a metrical translation of parts of the Qur’an into Persian was produced in Transoxiana somewhere around the tenth to twelfth centuries, as was one into rhymed prose by the scholar Abū Ḥafṣ al-Nasafī (d. 1147).¹⁷ There were also bilingual translations versions of the Qur’an in which the translation followed the original, but was not written in interlinear fashion.¹⁸ There were, then, alternative models for translation that could have been used, and the fact that the Turkish Qur’an translation draws on the Samanid *Tafsīr* reflects not just its prestige but also, as I will argue below, its shared agenda and audience.

Early Turkish Interlinear Qur’an Translations

None of the early Turkish versions of the Qur’an are dated (although the manuscripts sometimes are), which means they can only be approximately dated on philological grounds, and none contain the information about patronage as the Samanid *Tafsīr* did. The earliest manuscripts date to the fourteenth century, by which point it seems the practice of making Qur’ans furnished with interlinear Turkish translations was well established, albeit not as prevalent as it was with Persian.¹⁹ The distinguished Turkologist János Eckmann (1905–

16 See Travis Zadeh, “The Fātiḥa of Salmān al-Fārisī and the Modern Controversy over Translating the Qur’ān,” in *The Meaning of the Word: Lexicology and Tafsīr*, ed. Stephen Burge (Institute of Ismaili Studies/Oxford University Press, 2015), 375–420; on al-Sarakhsī see N. Calder, “al-Sarakhsī,” *EP*.

17 On these see Zadeh, *The Vernacular Qur’an*, 268–290, but regarding the date and place of composition of the metrical Qur’an fragment see also Ashraf Sādiqī, “Baḥthī dar bāb-i kitāb-i *Pulī miyān-i shi’r-i hajā’ī wa ‘arūzī-yi fārsī dar dū qarn-i awwal-i hijri* az Duktur Aḥmad ‘Alī Rajāī,” in Muḥammad Ja’far Yāḥaqqī et al, *Khirad bar sar-i Jān: Nāmgāna-yi Ustād ‘Alī Rajāī Bukhārāī* (Intishārāt-i Sukhan, 1391), 349–388, who suggests it should be dated to twelfth century Transoxiana rather than tenth century.

18 See Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Supplément persan 1671, a compilation of religious texts in Persian, including partial translations of the Qur’an, probably produced in twelfth century Transoxiana.

19 In general see Gulnaz Sibgatullina, “On Translating the Qur’an into Turkic Vernaculars: Texts, Ties, and Traditions,” in *European Muslims and the Qur’an: Practices of Translation, Interpretation, and Commodification*, eds. Gulnaz Sibgatullina and Gerard Wiegers (De Gruyter, 2024), 189–218; for studies of the early Turkish Qur’ans see Abdülkadir İnan, *Kur’ān-ı Kerim Tercemelerinin Üzerine bir İnceleme* (TTK, 1961); Eckmann, “Eastern Turkic Translations of the Koran”; Hendrik Boeschoten, “Translations of the Koran: Sources for the History of Written Turkic in a Multilingual Setting,” in *Turkic-Iranian Contact Areas: Historical and Linguistic Aspects*, eds. Lars Johanson and Christiane Bulut (Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2006), 75–76

1971), whose work forms the basis for all subsequent research on the subject, was aware of five eastern Turkish interlinear Qur'an translations in Qarakhanid or Khwarazmian Turkish,²⁰ a number which today has increased to eight with the discovery of three codices in Mashhad unknown to Eckmann. The manuscripts listed below represent the earliest Eastern Turkish interlinear Qur'an translations, and in most cases constitute fragments only. Although, as is conventional, I distinguish between Qarakhanid and Khwarazmian Turkish, it should be noted that the boundaries between these are not at all hard and fast and in some cases it is debated to which dialect group a manuscript belongs (and indeed, in some cases different dialects are used in the same manuscript).²¹ Moreover, works from one dialect circulated and were copied in regions where another dialect predominated, so the dialect does not indicate clearly the place of production or consumption:

Qarakhanid Turkish (Central Asia, 11th-13th C)

John Rylands Library, University of Manchester, MSS Arabic 760–773.²² Copied in the second half of the 14th century, no later than 1400, and has been dated stylistically to c.735/1335.²³ Trilingual, with Arabic, Persian and Turkish text. 14 volumes surviving of a 30 volume set.²⁴

St Petersburg *Tafsīr* (the text is in Qarakhanid Turkish, the commentary in Khwarazmian, and is therefore later). St Petersburg, Institute of Oriental Manuscripts of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Asiatic Museum), S 197. Arabic and Turkish. The manuscript dates to seventeenth century.²⁵

20 Eckmann, "Eastern Turkic Translations of the Koran."

21 This is the case with TIEM 73, which contains text in both Khwarazmian and Qarakhanid Turkish. In general on its language see János Eckmann, "Eine ostmittel türkische interlineare Koranübersetzung," *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher*, no. 31 (1959): 72–85.

22 It should be noted that further fragments of this manuscript have been identified at the Chester Beatty Library, Dublin: János Eckmann, "Two Fragments of a Koran Manuscript with Interlinear Persian and Turkic Translations," *Central Asiatic Journal* 13, no. 4 (1969): 287–290. One further fragment, the first folio of the fourth *juz'* is held in the Los Angeles County Museum of Art, accession no M.73.5.490. I am grateful to Jake Benson for drawing my attention to this.

23 David James, *Qur'ans of the Mamluks* (Alexandria Press, 1988), 173–174, 244.

24 For the Turkish text see Aysu Ata, *Türkçe İlk Kur'an Tercümesi (Rylands Nüshası): Karahanlı Türkçesi (Giriş-Metin-Notlar-Dizin)* (TDK, 2004); for studies see, for example, János Eckmann, "Doğu Türkçesinde Bir Kuran Çevirisi (Rylands Nüshası)," *Türk Dili Araştırmaları Yıllığı-Belleten*, no. 15 (1967): 51–69, which contains a convenient summary of the contents of the surviving volumes; Eckmann, "Eastern Turkic Translations of the Koran."

25 The manuscript has been published in transcription and facsimile by İbrahim Halil Usta, *Orta Asya Kur'an Tefsiri (Metin-Tıpkıbasım)* (Poyraz, 2011). However, this has been inaccessible to me, so I have been obliged to exclude this text from most of my discussion. For an analysis of its lexicon see A.K. Borovkov, *Leksika Sredneaziatskogo Tefsira: XII-XIII vv* (Izd. Vostochnoi Literatury, 1963); Turkish translation as *Orta Asya'da Bulunmuş Kur'an Tefsirinin Söz Varlığı (XII.-XIII. Yüzyıllar)* (TDK, 2002); for a description of the manuscript, see L.V. Dimitrieva, *Katalog Tyurkskikh Rukopisei Instituta Vostokovedeniya Rossiskoi Akademii Nauk* (Vostochnaia Literatura, 2002), no 540. A reproduction of a folio of the manuscript was available to the time of writing on the Institute of Oriental Manuscript's

Türk-İslam Eser Müzesi İstanbul (TİEM) 73, copied 734/1333–1334 by Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh al-Shīrāzī. Arabic and Turkish (mixed Qarakhanid and Khwarazmian). Complete.²⁶

Khwarazmian Turkish (14th c) (Central Asia, although Khwarazmian also used in Crimea, Dasht-i Qipchaq, Anatolia, and Iran)

Süleymaniye Library, İstanbul, MS Hekimoğlu Cami 2, copied 764/1363.²⁷ Arabic and Turkish with Persian paratexts. Complete.

Tashkent, Beruniy Institute of Oriental Studies, MS 2008.²⁸ Trilingual, Arabic, Persian and Turkish, covering al-Baqara 23 to al-‘Inām 145 (with some omissions). Undated, Fourteenth century. From a linguistic point of view, the language of this text is highly mixed, and contains Qarakhanid, Khwarazmian and other elements.

Mashhad, Astan-i Quds MS 293, copied in 737/1337, containing an interlinear Turkish translation of sura 38–114, and Turkish *tafsīr* translated from the Samanid Persian *Tafsīr*.²⁹ The copyist was Muḥammad ibn Shaykh Yūsuf al-Abārī, known as Sayyid al-Khaṭṭāt.

Mashhad, Astan-i Quds MS 2229. Āl ‘Imran 92 to al-Nisa 24. Undated, but clearly 14th century. Partially trilingual.³⁰

Mashhad Astan-i Quds MS 1007. Trilingual, Unpublished fragment.³¹

website: https://www.orientalstudies.ru/rus/collections/turcologica/turk_collection_C_197.htm (last accessed 17 April 2025).

- 26 On this manuscript see Eckmann, “Eine ostmitteltürkische interlineare Koranübersetzung”; Abdullah Kök, “Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır-Arası Kur’an Tercümesi (TİEM 73 1v-235v/2): Giriş-İnceleme-Metin-Dizin” (PhD Dissertation, Ankara University, 2004); Suat Ünlü, “Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır Arası Kur’an Tercümesi TİEM 73 (TİEM 235v3-450r7), Giriş-Metin-İnceleme-Analitik Dizin” (PhD Dissertation, Hacettepe University, 2004); Suat Ünlü, *Karahanlı Türkçesi İlk Türkçe Satır-Arası Transkribeli Kur’an Tercümesi (TİEM 73)*, 7 vols (Selçuklu Belediyesi, 2018).
- 27 Gülden Sağol, *An Interlinear Translation of the Qur’an into Khwarazm Turkish: Introduction, Text, Glossary and Facsimile* (Harvard University, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, 1993).
- 28 Published in transcription and facsimile in Emek Üşenmez, *Türkçe İlk Kur’an Tercümelerinden Özbekistan Nüshası: Satır-Arası Türkçe-Farsça Tercümeli* (Akademik Kitaplar, 2013).
- 29 Yaşar Şimşek, *Harezm Türkçesi Kur’an Tercümesi (Meşhed Nüshası 293 No, Giriş-Metin-Dizin)*, 2 vols (Akçağ, 2019).
- 30 Emek Üşenmez, *Türkçe İlk Tercümelerinden Meşhed Nüshası: Satır-Arası Türkçe-Farsça Tercümeli* (İstanbul: Post, 2025).
- 31 Şimşek, *Harezm Türkçesi Kur’an Tercümesi*, vol. 1, 8.

The Origins of the Text of the Early Eastern Turkish Interlinear Qur'ans

To date, unfortunately, these Turkish Qur'an translations have not been subjected to the detailed study that they deserve, and remain incompletely published. A particular problem is that researchers have tended to focus their efforts on single manuscripts, and such comparisons that have been done between the different manuscripts are often superficial and partial. As a result, there remains a lack of consensus as to the relationship between the texts of the manuscripts.³² In places the manuscripts' texts agree almost exactly, but elsewhere there are significant differences. It has been suggested that the texts of TIEM 73 and the Tashkent manuscript are closely related, and these also seem to be linked to a manuscript in Khwarazmian Turkish, Hekimoğlu Cami 2,³³ which was copied in 762/1363, possibly in Konya or Erzincan.³⁴ The St Petersburg *Tafsîr* sometimes seems closer to TIEM 73, and sometimes to the Rylands manuscript.³⁵ Astan-i Quds MS 293, which gives multiple Turkish equivalents to the same Arabic word, seems to be quite distinct from the other manuscripts.

Despite the differences, it has been posited that the Turkish text in all these manuscripts derive ultimately from a common Ur-text that was produced somewhere between the tenth and twelfth centuries.³⁶ The earlier date was asserted by Togan,³⁷ but has no clear evidence to support it, and is highly unlikely given that all the other evidence points to Turkish first emerging as a language of Islam in the eleventh century. Fuad Köprülü and Abdülkadir İnan suggested that the earliest translation dated to the eleventh century.³⁸ It is likely that the differences between the various manuscripts result to some degree from the adaptation of the text by copyists to the language of their own dialect, and further research is needed on this

32 For a survey of these translations and their language see Abdülkadir İnan, "Eski Türkçe Kur'an Tercemelerinin Dili Meselesi," *Türk Dili* 1, no. 7 (1952): 295–298.

33 Üşenmez, *Türkçe İlk Kur'an Tercümelerinden*, 58; see also Kök, "Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır-Arası Kur'an Tercümesi."

34 There is no place of copying; Cailah Jackson (pers. comm. 4 August 2024) suggested Konya to me, while Alison Ohta (pers. comm. 24 August 2024) suggested Erzincan. Both these suggestions are tentative, but they do confirm this Khwarazmian Qur'an was almost certainly produced somewhere in Anatolia.

35 Kök, "Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır-Arası Kur'an Tercümesi" xl-xlvi

36 Mustafa Argunşah, "Harezmi Türkçesiyle Yapılan Kur'an Çevirisinin Beş Nüshası," *Uluslararası Türkçe Edebiyat Kültür Eğitim Dergisi* 8, no. 2 (2019), 654–698; Mustafa Argunşah, *Karahanlı - Harezmi Türkçesi Kuran Çevirileri Üzerine Notlar* (Kesit, 2023). A similar view is reached by Yaşar Şimşek in "Satırarası Türkçe Kur'an Tercümelerinin Birbiri ile İlgisi ve Tasnifi Üzerine," *Gazi Türkiyat*, no. 24 (2019): 47–65, who argues that the Ur-text was transmitted in three branches (one comprising TIEM 73 and Astan-i Quds 293; one comprising Hekimoğlu Camii 2, Mashhad 1007, Astan-i Quds 293 and the Tashkent ms; and one comprising the Rylands, Astan-i Quds 2229 and Astan-i Quds 293 manuscripts). The fact that Astan-i Quds 293 is represented in all three branches illustrates the difficulty of making such divisions and further research is required. Nonetheless, at present, the consensus of scholarship points to a single Ur-text.

37 Zeki Velidi Togan, "The Earliest Translation of the Qur'an into Turkish," *İslâm Tetkikleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, no. 4 (1964): 1–19.

38 İnan, *Kur'an-ı Kerim Tercemelerinin*, 8.

question. Yet it is possible to make some preliminary observations on this process as witnessed by the changing vocabulary of the texts. TĪEM 73 contains a higher proportion of Arabic vocabulary in Turkish than the Rylands manuscript, although the amount of Persian is comparable.³⁹ Nonetheless, occasionally it does preserve older vocabulary than the Rylands text, using for example the old Turkic loanword *ajun* (common in Buddhist and Manichaean Turkic texts) for “world”, rather than the Arabic *‘alam* found in the Rylands manuscript.⁴⁰ The lexicon of the Tashkent manuscript is strongly influenced by Arabic and Persian, which comprises 27% of its vocabulary.⁴¹ In contrast, Arabic and Persian words comprise around 14% of the vocabulary of the Rylands manuscript, a percentage comparable to that in the eleventh-century Uyghur script documents from Yarkand.⁴² This is also similar to the proportion of Arabic and Persian vocabulary in the eleventh century *Ķutadġu bilig*, which has been estimated as around one sixth of the total (500 words out of 3000, or 16%).⁴³ Clearly such comparisons are rather rough and ready as the texts compared are of different genres, but given the lack of other comparanda, the relatively consistent proportion of foreign words in the Rylands manuscript and Qarakhanid era literary texts points to a similar date. It seems that TĪEM 73 and Tashkent 2008, with their higher proportion of non-Turkish words are later, and reflect an environment in which the process of Islamisation was further advanced, with Arabic and Persian words being more familiar to the audience.⁴⁴

It seems reasonable then to posit the existence of a Turkish translation of the Qur’an composed possibly as early as the eleventh century, and probably no later than the twelfth. There are, however, few clues as to where it was produced. The noted Turkish scholar and nationalist Zeki Veldi Togan was the first to demonstrate how the early Turkish Qur’ans draw on the Samanid Persian *Tafsīr*. Noting that one of the ulama who is mentioned in its preface was from the frontier city of Ispijab, part of the land of Arghu, which was a centre of Turkish literacy in the tenth century, albeit largely Manichaean, Togan argued that the first Turkish Qur’an translation in fact was undertaken by this individual alongside the Persian translation.⁴⁵ Eckmann, and following him, Aysu Ata adduced linguistic evidence for the presence of certain grammatical features in the Rylands text that are suggested to be characteristic of Ispijab.⁴⁶ Arghu and west Turkish elements have also been detected in

39 Kk, “Karahanlı Trkesi Satır-Arası Kur’an Tercmesi,” xxviii.

40 Kk, “Karahanlı Trkesi Satır-Arası Kur’an Tercmesi,” xlvii, see the translation of Q 7: 104.

41 şenmez, *Trke İlk Kur’an Tercmelerinden*, 182.

42 Ata, *Trke İlk Kur’an Tercmesi*, xxix.

43 Uwe Blsing, “Qıl Adına Namaz: Bir Gn Adının Tarihesi,” in *Doġumunun 990. Yılında Yusuf Has Hacib ve Eseri Kutadġu Bilig Bildirileri, 26–27 Ekim 2009* (TDK, 2011), 138.

44 Cf. Kristof D’hulster, “How Do You Say Qur’an in Turkic? Observations on the Islamization of the Turkic Lexicon,” in *Continuity and Change in the Realms of Islam: Studies in Honor of Professor Urbain Vermeulen*, eds. K. D’hulster and Jo van Steenbergen (Peeters, 2008), 181–205.

45 Togan, “The Earliest Translation of the Qur’an.”

46 Eckmann, “Doġu Trkesinde Bir Kur’an evirisi,” 58–59; Ata, *Trke İlk Kur’an Tercmesi*, xxvi; this argument is based on the similarity of certain verbal forms in the Rylands text and a fourteenth century Khwarazmian translation of Sa’dī’s *Gulistn* copied by an individual from Ispijab. The distance in time and the fact there is no way of knowing if these forms are a result of the intervention of the copyist make

TIEM 73.⁴⁷ Naturally, given our very limited knowledge of the nature of the Arghu dialect, for which we are almost entirely reliant on the few and problematic examples given by Maḥmūd al-Kāshgharī,⁴⁸ such conclusions are somewhat speculative. However, further evidence in support of a Transoxianan origin is provided by the Persian text in the Rylands manuscript, which has not previously been noted. While the Persian translation basically represents that provided in the Samanid *Tafsīr*, it is characterised by a particular orthography, in particular the use of the so-called “Khurasani verbs”, that is, the use of the 2nd person plural verbal ending *-īt* in place of the standard New Persian *-īd*. Khurasani verbs commonly appear in early texts from Khurasan and Transoxiana,⁴⁹ but the Rylands manuscript is highly unusual for almost invariably using the *-īt* form; usually *-īt* appears alongside the standard form (a fact which, of course, might be explained by only partially successful attempts at standardisation by later copyists, given most extant manuscripts postdate c. 1200). In fact, one of the few other texts that invariably adopts this form is the aforementioned *Badāyi‘ al-mulaḥ*, which we know to have been copied in Transoxiana in 592/1195.⁵⁰ The consistent use of such a form in the Rylands manuscript strongly suggests that its Ur-text originated in the same milieu. If it is the case that the Turkish Ur-text did originate in Transoxiana this is significant, as otherwise evidence for the literary use of Turkish in the period is largely restricted to Kashghar, Balasaghun and Khotan, i.e., to the east of the traditional centres of Islamic culture in Transoxiana that seem to have remained overwhelmingly Persophone. Further research on the language of the Persian text is required, and this remains a promising and hitherto almost entirely unexploited avenue of establishing the origins of the Ur-text.

The Circulation of the Eastern Turkish Interlinear Qur’ans

Although none of these manuscripts has a place of copying, there are certain indications of their origin. The St Petersburg *Tafsīr* was found in Qarshi in modern Uzbekistan in 1914 by Zeki Velidi Togan; the Tashkent manuscript is also likely to be Transoxianan, on the basis of grammatical features in the Persian translations, as well as its current location.⁵¹ TIEM 73 is usually attributed to Shiraz on the basis that its scribe is named Muhammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh al-Shīrāzī.⁵² Despite the traditional assumption that the manuscript was copied in Shiraz, as is suggested by his *nisba* (which can, however, often be misleading), it is much

this argument less than compelling.

47 Kōk, “Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır-Arası Kur’an Tercümesi” xxxviii.

48 Doerfer identified Arghu with modern Khalaj, see Gerhard Doerfer, “Maḥmūd al-Kāshgharī. Arghu, Chaladsch,” *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher*, no. 7 (1987): 105–114; for another view see Gürer Gülsevin, “11. Yüzyılda Hangi Oğuz Diyalektleri Vardı?,” *Bilig*, no. 76 (2016): 269–300.

49 On the so called Khurasani verbs (*af‘āl-i Khurāsānī*), see Muḥammad Ja‘far Yāḥaqqī, ed., *Guzāra-ī bakhshi az Qur‘ān-i karīm: Tafsīr-i Shanqashī* (Intishārāt-i Bunyād-i Farhang-i Īrān, 2535), *sī u dū-sī u sih*.

50 Şadr al-Afāḍil, *Badāyi‘ al-mulaḥ*, *chahārdah*.

51 Üşenmez, *Türkçe İlk Kur’an Tercümelerinden*, 35.

52 See for example İnan, *Kur‘ān-i Kerim Tercemelerinin*, 12.

more likely to have been copied in the Crimea as is discussed further below. The Rylands manuscript was endowed by its owner, the amir Aytamish, as waqf to a madrasa in Cairo, before or around 802/1400 when he died.⁵³ It is not clear whether the manuscript was itself produced in Egypt, as the presence of the Persian translation alongside the Turkish might suggest a more Persophone environment, but its existence fits well with the Mamluk taste for monuments of early Turkish literature, including those of the Qarakhanid period, such as the *Dīwān lughāt al-Turk* and the *Ḳutadġu bilig*, which both exist in Mamluk manuscripts.⁵⁴ There is no indication of where the Mashhad manuscripts were copied, although all show connections to a Persian speaking environment.⁵⁵ Moreover, the commentary sections of Astan-i Quds 293 show the clear influence of Persian texts. It is essentially a translation of the Samanid Persian version of al-Ṭabarī's *Tafsīr*, but influences from the “mirror for princes” or *Siyāsatnāma* of the Seljuk vizier Nizām al-Mulk (d.1092) have also been detected.⁵⁶ It would seem to be a reasonable assumption that these three manuscripts were copied in Khurasan.⁵⁷

While most of these manuscripts contain very little indication of ownership and audience, we can deduce some information about the circles that might have been interested in Turkish Qur'an from the activities of the copyist of TĪEM 73, Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh al-Shīrāzī, who also sometimes refers to himself with the honorific Shams al-Dīn. This individual is known as the copyist of five other manuscripts:

1. *Jung* (collection of poetry both by Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh al-Shīrāzī and contemporaries), copied in Rajab 741/December–January 1340 in Solkhat, a city in Crimea (Istanbul, Süleymaniye Library, MS Nafiz Paşa 1026).⁵⁸
2. Jalāl al-Dīn Rūmī, *Mathnawī-yi ma'navī*, copied in 744/1344 (Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Munich, Cod. pers. 35).⁵⁹

53 Frédéric Bauden was the first to notice this, and I am very grateful for him sharing this information with me. On Aytamish see al-Sakhāwī, *al-Ḍaw' al-lāmi' li-ahl al-qarn al-tāsi'*, vol. 2 (Dār al-Jīl, 1992), 324, no. 1059.

54 On the *Ḳutadġu bilig*'s manuscripts see Reşid Rahmetli Arat, *Kutadgu bilig, I: Metin* (TDK, 1991), esp. xxxviii–xxxix; for the *Dīwān lughāt al-Turk*, see Maḥmūd al-Kāşyarī, *Compendium of Turkish Dialects*, ed. and trans. Robert Dankoff (Harvard University Printing Office, 1982), I, esp. 10–11

55 Şimşek, *Harezmi Türkçesi Kur'an Tercümesi*, vol. 1, 16.

56 Şimşek, *Harezmi Türkçesi Kur'an Tercümesi*, vol. 1, 25–26.

57 Argunşah, “Harezmi Türkçesiyle Yapılan Kur'an Çevirisinin,” describes all the Mashhad manuscripts as coming from “West Turkestan” on the basis of their linguistic features, which presumably is approximately Transoxiana or Khurasan. However, given the dialect and place of copying do not necessarily correspond geographically, it would be unwise to infer too much about the origin of the manuscripts purely on the basis of linguistic analysis.

58 This manuscript has been published as Shams al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Dawlatshāh ibn Yūsuf al-Shīrāzī, *Saḡīna-yi Shams-i Ḥājjī*, ed. Mīlād 'Aẓīmī (Intishārāt-i Sukhan, 1388). See also the description by 'Aẓīmī in “Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī: bar-rasī-yi majmū'a-yi Shams-i Ḥājj Dawlatshāh-i Shīrāzī,” *Nāma-yi Bahāristān*, no. 16 (1389): 145–192.

59 Cailah Jackson, *Mevlevi Manuscripts, 1268–c. 1400: A Study of the Sources* (Palgrave, 2024), 42.

3. *Jung* (collection of poetry by other poets, including Hāfīz, Sa'dī, Mawlānā Rūmī and others), copied in Solkhat in Jumādā I 751/July 1350. This manuscript belonged to a Dr Muḥammad-Ḥusayn 'Alī Ābādī of the Faculty of Law of Tehran University, and is now apparently lost.⁶⁰
4. Abū Bakr Maḥmūd ibn 'Alī Rāwandī's Persian translation and adaptation of the *Sharaf al-Nabī*, on the virtues of the Prophet, copied in Crimea (*bi-madīnat Qirīm*) in Jumada II 755/June 1354 (Istanbul, Beyazit Devlet Kütüphanesi, Veliyüddin Efendi 888).
5. Farīd al-Dīn 'Attār's *Tadhkirat al-awliyā'*, copied in Crimea (*fī baldat Qirīm*) in 757/1356 (Istanbul, Süleymaniye Library, MS Ayasofya 3132)

Thus four of this scribe's manuscripts state they were copied in Crimea, more precisely the city of Qirīm by which modern Eski Kırım/Stariy Krym is meant, which is also referred to by the name Solkhat. This was the main political and religious centre of Crimea in the fourteenth century, where the Golden Horde ruler Uzbek (r. 1313–1341) built a mosque and madrasa.⁶¹ Further association with the Crimea is reflected in the fact that Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh al-Shīrāzī, using the pen name of Shams-i Ḥājjī, dedicated poems to Uzbek's successor Jānī Beg, which are contained in the *Jung* dated 741.⁶² Although it is of course not impossible that the scribe moved from Shiraz to Crimea in the interlude between the copying of the Qur'an and the later manuscripts, an association with the Crimea seems much more logical as this was an important centre of early Turkish literature in the Khwarazmian dialect, in which parts of the manuscript are written.⁶³ There is much more likely to have been demand for a Turkish translation of the Qur'an in predominantly Turcophone Crimea, rather than Shiraz.

Whatever the place of production, the other manuscripts copied by Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh do allow us to suggest something concrete about the sort of communities that may have been interested in a Turkish Qur'an. Three other manuscripts by this copyist are Sufi works. Rūmī's *Mathnawī* and 'Attār's *Tadhkirat al-awliyā'* are among the most important examples of Sufi literature, the first being a verse compilation of didactic Sufi tales, the latter comprising biographies of Sufi saints. While Rāwandī, the translator of the *Sharaf al-Nabī* is best known as the compiler of a history of the Seljuks, the *Rāḥat al-ṣudūr*, the author of the Arabic original of the text, Abū Sa'd 'Abd al-Malik ibn 'Uthmān al-Wā'iz, was a Sufi shaykh.⁶⁴ The *Sharaf al-Nabī* describes Muḥammad's physical and personal qualities,

60 See the description by Īraj Afshār, "Jung-i bayāzī az 'aṣr-i Hāfīz," in Īraj Afshār, *Majmū'a-yi kamīna: maqāla-hā-ī dar nuskhā-shināsī wa kitāb-shināsī* (Intishārāt-i Īrān-zamīn, 1352), 58–70, originally published in *Yaghmā* 20 (1346); see also the comments by 'Azīmī in *Safīna-yi Shams-i Ḥājjī*, 47–50; 'Azīmī, "Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī," 150–151.

61 B. Spuler, "Kırım," *EP*.

62 *Safīna-yi Shams-i Ḥājjī*, 45–47; 'Azīmī, "Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī," 149–50.

63 See for example the Turkish poem *Yusuf u Züleyha* by Kırımlı Mahmud, which probably also dates to the fourteenth century, the language of which is described as "Crimean." İsmail Hikmet Ertaylan, *Yusuf ile Züleyha* (İstanbul Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi, 1960).

64 Christiane Gruber, "Between 'Logos' and 'Kalima': Representations of the Prophet Muḥammad in

and advocates visitation of his grave (*ziyāra*), using him as an intercessor for prayers, and contemplating him in dreams and through imagination (*khiyāl*). Sufis traditionally emphasised the exemplary qualities of Muḥammad, and this text thus serves to establish this crucial link between the believer and the Prophet. Interest in Sufism was very common among members of the political elite by the fourteenth century, and we know such elites often patronised Sufi manuscripts, as has been shown by studies on manuscripts associated with the Mevlevi order.⁶⁵ With regard to the two *jungs*, both contain substantial amounts of Sufi-orientated poetry, including among the poems composed by Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh,⁶⁶ although that is perhaps less decisive given the more or less complete permeation of Persian poetic discourse by Sufism by the fourteenth century. However, it is clear that one of the owners of the 741 *jung* was a Mevlevi,⁶⁷ again suggesting the appeal of Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh's work to such a community. Thus we can say with some confidence that the Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh, the copyist of TIEM 73, was a Sufi or closely associated with Sufi communities, and was active in the court of the Golden Horde rulers of the Crimea, whom we know from other sources to have had a distinct interest in Persianate Sufism, especially Mevlevism.⁶⁸

Most of the other interlinear Qur'an manuscripts under consideration exhibit similar connections with communities that used Persian, and on occasion can be linked directly or indirectly with Sufis. As noted above, the Rylands and Tashkent manuscripts are trilingual, containing the complete Persian text alongside the Turkish and Arabic, while all of the Mashhad manuscripts also contain Persian text for some sections (regrettably as Astan-i Quds 1007 has not been published it is not possible to comment more fully on this). However, even in a case where the Qur'anic text is only given in Arabic and Turkish, as in Istanbul Hekimoğlu Cami 2, dated by colophon to the middle of Rabī' II 764/early February 1363, Persian still plays an important role. The manuscript contains frequent marginal comments in Persian in red ink which are evidently in the hand of the copyist, introducing the occasions on which each chapter can be used for practical purposes. For example, sura Wa'l-Qalam (68) is introduced by the Hadith *ruwiya 'an al-nabī innahu qāla man qara'a hādhihi al-sūra kāna lahu thawāb aḥsana allāh ta'ālā akhlāqahu* (It is related from the Prophet the he who reads this sura will receive a reward, may God perfect his morals). Much more precise though is the information given in the margin in Persian next to the chapter heading: *in sūrat-rā bāz bikḥwānad bar niyyat-i bar-āmadan-i muhimmāt* (read this sura 70 times before undertaking important tasks).⁶⁹ Such comments frequently occur. Sura Nūḥ (71), is also introduced by a short hadith, but the Persian states that the sura should be read a thousand and one times to

Islamic Painting," *Muqarnas*, no. 29 (2009): 235.

65 Jackson, *Mevlevi Manuscripts*, 104–114.

66 'Azīmī, "Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī," 148.

67 'Azīmī, "Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī," 146.

68 Devin Deweese, "Khans and Amirs in the Qalandar-Nama of Abu Bakr Rumi: Praise of the Islamizing Jochid Elite in a Persian Sufi Work From Fourteenth-Century Crimea," *Archivum Eurasiae Medii Aevi*, no. 21 (2014/15): 53–66.

69 Hekimoğlu Cami 2, fol. 528a.

defeat enemies (*īn sūrat-rā hazār yak bi-jihat-i halāk dushman bikhwānad*).⁷⁰ Occasionally the Persian instructions are more complicated. Sura Yā Sīn (36) starts with the comment, “Whoever reads this sura to dispel calamities and arrange important affairs forty one times, or according to another account seventy five times, will be satisfied, and if he writes it and hangs it on a tree in a garden, it will bear fruit and no harm will come to him.” These comments are never given a Turkish translation. After the conclusion of the Qur’anic text, a seven page appendix in Persian provides the rules for licit pauses (*waqf*) in reading the Qur’an aloud.⁷¹ Again, this is unaccompanied by any Turkish explanation. Other material is left untranslated too, such as the Arabic *asbāb al-nuzūl* and hadith that accompany the beginning of most chapters. In other words, the Turkish is concerned only with the Qur’anic text itself, not with any of the accompanying material: to understand the manuscript in full, a mastery of Persian, and a knowledge of Arabic would have been required.

Finally, all the manuscripts discussed are to some degree luxury productions, although this does not necessarily mean they were copied in ateliers in large urban centres. In his colophon to TIEM 73, Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh makes it clear that he was responsible for the illumination as well as the copying (*katabahu wa dhahhabahu*), and his copies of the *Mathnawī*, *Tadhkirat al-awliyā’* and *Sharaf al-Nabī* are also luxury productions, while the jung of 741 is simpler, but is still carefully written with some use of illumination. In other words, Muḥammad ibn al-Ḥājj Dawlatshāh specialised in luxury manuscripts, as one might indeed expect of a copyist associated with the Golden Horde court. Turning to the other interlinear Turkish Qur’ans, the copyist of Astan-i Quds 293 was known as *sayyid al-khuttāṭ* indicating he was a master calligrapher, albeit, David James notes, possibly one active in a provincial centre given this slightly infelicitous phrasing (normally the term *sayyid al-khuttāṭīn* would be used). Blair also suggests that the scribe’s name Muḥammad ibn Shaykh Yūsuf indicates his father was a Sufi shaykh.⁷² Astan-i Quds MS 2229 is also a luxury manuscript, with three text lines to the page and gold rosettes.⁷³ The Tashkent manuscript is also carefully copied in a generously spaced *thuluth* for the Arabic text,⁷⁴ with six lines per page. However, unquestionably the most magnificent is the Rylands manuscript, of which fourteen volumes survive (Fig. 2). Originally this was a thirty volume set, owned by the Mamluk amir Aytamish whose name and endowment to the madrasa he built appear on several of the extant volumes. The pages are exceptionally generously spaced, with broad margins and only three lines of Arabic text per page, and gold illuminated rosettes mark reading pauses (*waqf*). Sura headings are elaborately illuminated, with extensive use of gold (Fig. 3). The place of production of the manuscript is not clear; Anatolia is a possibility, but so is Mamluk Egypt.⁷⁵ Stylistic analysis has suggested the decorative programme of the

70 Hekimoğlu Cami 2, fol. 545a.

71 Hekimoğlu Cami 2, fol. 579b, 583a

72 James, *Qur’ans of the Mamluks*, 175-176; Sheila Blair, *Islamic Calligraphy* (Edinburgh University Press, 2006), 373.

73 See the facsimile in the publication by Üşenmez, *Türkçe İlk Tercümelelerinden Meşhed Nüshası*.

74 *Thuluth* is an elegant, large format style of calligraphy particularly used for inscriptions and luxury manuscripts. See Blair, *Islamic Calligraphy*, 336.

75 Art historical research has suggested the Rylands manuscript was produced in eastern Anatolia or

Rylands manuscript has clear affinities with a Qur'an stand (*rahla*) made for the shrine of the Sufi poet Jalāl al-Dīn Rūmī (d. 1273) in Konya, indicating the manuscript may have been used in such a context.⁷⁶

Fig. 2 Trilingual Qur'an. John Rylands Library, University of Manchester, MS Arabic 760, fol. 8a

northwestern Iran, or possibly under the Karamanid dynasty of South-central Anatolia. See James, *Qur'ans of the Mamluks*, 176–177; Blair, *Islamic Calligraphy*, 370–373. However, aspects of the decorative programme of the manuscript also contain Mamluk features, and, more significantly, artisans travelled, and there were strong links between Anatolia and Cairo, so it is very hard to locate the place of production on stylistic criteria alone.

⁷⁶ James, *Qur'ans of the Mamluks*, 177; Blair, *Islamic Calligraphy*, 373.

Fig. 3 Start of *Sūrat al-Aḥzāb* in the trilingual Qur'an. John Rylands Library, University of Manchester, MS Arabic 768, fol. 1a

Hekimoğlu 2 also has pretensions to luxury, even if its execution is less successful, the Arabic text being written in a rather poor *naskh*. Nonetheless it starts with an illuminated *shamsa* (medallion) (Fig. 4), the opening folios are heavily illuminated (Fig. 5), and gold, red and black inks are used throughout to distinguish the Qur'anic text from paratexts such as hadith and the Persian texts. As in all of these interlinear Qur'ans, the Turkish and Persian translations appear in much thinner text beneath. However, in both Hekimoğlu 2 and the Tashkent manuscript, the interlinear translation itself becomes a decorative feature, slanting diagonally to make a series of V shapes beneath the Arabic text (Fig. 6).

Fig. 4 Interlinear Qur'an translation into Khwarazmian Turkish. Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Hekimoğlu 2, fol. 1a shamsa

Fig. 5 Interlinear Qur'an translation into Khwarazmian Turkish. Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Hekimoğlu 2, fol. 2b-3a. Opening of al-Fātiha and al-Baqara.

Thus interlinear Eastern Turkish Qur'ans are aimed at an elite audience, at least as far as the extant manuscript evidence suggests. It is true this elite may have been more at home in Turkish than Persian (or Arabic), but nonetheless, these translations originate in a Persophone milieu, relying on the Samanid *Tafsīr* both for the Persian text of the interlinear translation, and for the commentary in the cases of the Mashhad and St Petersburg Turkish *Tafsīrs*. It is likely that at least some of these Qur'an translations were produced or consumed in Sufi circles, given the clear interests of the copyist of TĪEM 73 attested by the other manuscripts he is known to have copied, and the tentative indications of Sufi connections of Astan-i Quds MS 293 and the Rylands manuscript. We cannot know for sure whether this was the case when the Ur-text was composed, but it is quite likely, given the clearly Sufi associations of our two other works of Qarakhanid Turkish literature, the *Kutadgu bilig* and *'Atabetü'l-hakaik*. Moreover, Sufi ideas claimed multilingualism was a form of divine communication, and in numerous other contexts in the Islamic world Sufism played a crucial role in the development of literary vernaculars.⁷⁷ It is thus entirely credible that the first Qur'an

77 A.C.S. Peacock, *Islam, Literature and Society in Mongol Anatolia* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 160–165.

translations in Turkish emerged in a Sufi milieu, probably in Transoxiana prior to the end of the twelfth century.

Fig. 6 Interlinear Qur'an translation into Khwarazmian Turkish. Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Hekimoğlu 2, fol. 577b-578a

The Relationship of the Turkish Translations to the Arabic and Persian texts

The question of the relationship of the Turkish to the Arabic and Persian texts is complex. In the case of one trilingual Anatolian Turkish interlinear Qur'an dating to c. 1400, it is clear that the Turkish translation is entirely based on the Persian rather than the Arabic text.⁷⁸ The medieval Eastern Turkish translations are more complicated, but show similar features. As Eckmann points out with regard to the Rylands manuscript, the Turkish text most commonly follows the Persian, even when this differs in meaning from that of the Qur'an itself. However, there are a number of instances in which the Turkish follows the Arabic rather than the Persian, and some in which it differs from both. Eckmann was inclined to attribute such differences either simply to carelessness, or to the Turkish translator(s) relying on a different

78 British Library, Or 9515, and see Meredith-Owens, "Notes on an Old Ottoman Translation." My own examination of passages from this manuscript confirmed this.

text than that in the manuscript, commenting, “It is likely that other Persian and Turkic translations were available, and the copyist simply wrote the Persian and Turkic glosses under the Arabic words without caring about their correctness or incorrectness.”⁷⁹ However, the fact that, as Eckmann noted, the tendency is for the Turkish to follow the Persian suggests that this was the prime influence on the translation. One reason for basing the Turkish on the Persian rather than the Arabic may have been theological. While Hanafis had long argued that it was permissible to use Persian rather than Arabic in case of necessity, the medieval juridical literature produced in Transoxiana, despite its extensive volume, does not seem to have contemplated the use of Turkish. Translating from Persian rather than Arabic thus avoided any theological objections, as it was not in fact the Qur’anic text that was being translated.

Bodrogligeti argued that it is better to think of the Persian and Turkish texts as representing glosses on the Arabic rather than coherent translations. As Bodrogligeti puts it, “The glosses translate words or phrases mostly in isolation, irrespective of their grammatical, and often even semantic context.”⁸⁰ The aim was less translation than to provide a crutch for the reader of the Arabic text, or, it has been suggested, for a Persian or Turkish speaker wanting to learn Arabic.⁸¹ However, with the tendency in Astan-i Quds 293 to offer multiple Turkish equivalents for the Arabic, one must wonder if on occasion the function was the reverse. Moreover, given that in manuscripts such as Hekimoğlu 2 and Tashkent, as we have seen, the interlinear translation does not in fact follow the Arabic word for word on the page, but is arranged with a view to aesthetic effect, one must query whether it could simply have acted as a crib as Bodrogligeti suggests; if so, it was hardly an effective design for one.

Much more detailed study of the various Turkish translations is needed before any concrete results can be reached. Here I wish to adduce one example that suggests the relationship of the three texts in the Rylands manuscript, and indeed their nature, is considerably more complex than has been appreciated to date. Let us take the example of Qur’an Āl ‘Imrān 200:

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اصْبِرُوا وَصَابِرُوا وَرَابِطُوا وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ لَعَلَّكُمْ تُفْلِحُونَ

In Arberry’s English version this reads,

O believers, be patient, and vie you in patience; be steadfast; fear God; haply so you will prosper⁸²

The Persian translation in the Rylands manuscript reads:

79 Eckmann, “Eastern Turkic Translations,” 154.

80 A.J.E. Bodrogligeti, “Ghosts, Copulating Friends, and Pedestrian Locusts in Some Reviews of Eckmann’s *Middle Turkic Glosses*,” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 104, no. 3 (1984): 455; also A.J.E. Bodrogligeti, “The Technique of the Glossist as a Key to Understanding the Lexical Material of Early Eastern Middle Turkic Interlinear Qur’an Translations,” *Ural-Altische Jahrbücher*, no. 50 (1978): 17–25.

81 Bodrogligeti, “Ghosts,” 456; cf. Bodrogligeti, “Technique.”

82 A.J. Arberry, trans., *The Koran Interpreted* (Allen and Unwin, 1955).

ای انانک کرویدید شکیبایی کنیت شکیت در جنگ کفار و کارزار کنیت
و بترسیت از خدای و مگر شما رستکاری بایت

Here the translator inserted after *shikībūt*, the translation for *rābiṭū* (vie you in patience) the words *dar jang-i kuffār* (in war with the infidel) into the translation. Moreover the Arabic *rābiṭū* (be steadfast) is translated by a more directly military term *kārzār kunīt* (go on campaign). The Persian translation thus reads:

O believers, be patient and have patience in battling the infidel and go on campaign, and fear God; haply you will find salvation.

Although the Persian text in the Rylands manuscript usually follows the Samanid translation quite closely, here it diverges significantly. The Samanid translation reads:

ای آنکسها که بگرویدید صبر کنید و شکیبیا باشید و بیستید بر صبر و پرهیزید از
خدای تا مگر شما براهید⁸³

O believers, have patience, be patient, and wait patiently, and heed God so that haply you will be saved.

This is much closer in meaning to the Arabic, and lacks the martial interpretation of the Rylands translation. Indeed, the word *rābiṭū*, which in the environment of tenth century Transoxiana⁸⁴ one might assume would be associated with warfare, is translated with the rather mild *bīstīd bar ṣabr* (wait patiently). However, the association of the verses with war against the infidels is suggested by the Samanid commentary, which connects them to the battle of Uḥud.

In fact, a closer version to the Rylands Persian text comes in the paraphrase of the Qur'an in Persian known after its endower the *Tafsīr-i Shanqashī*, which was probably written in Khurasan or Transoxiana in the eleventh or no later than the twelfth century, and was itself an interlinear text. The *Tafsīr-i Shanqashī* includes the same elements of fighting the infidel to achieve salvation, which are not directly present in the Arabic, or in the Samanid translation:

⁸³ *Tafsīr-i Ṭabarī*, vol. 1, 268.

⁸⁴ Transoxiana in the period represented the easternmost frontier of the Islamic world and was noted for its *ribāṭs*, which constituted bases from which pious volunteers would go and wage war seasonally on unbelievers. The insertion of the references to war on infidel in the commentary seems likely to originate in such a milieu, although battles against various infidels (Turkish and Qarakhitai) continued under Qarakhanid rule. See D.G. Tor, "The Islamization of Central Asia in the Sāmānid Era and the Reshaping of the Muslim World," *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 2, no. 2 (2009): 279–299.

ای مؤمنین بحمد و قرآن! صبر کنید بر جنگ دشمن کافر و شکیبایی کنند او
شکیبایا باشید بر حرب کافر او هم خند کنید اندر مسلمانی بر عداوت کافر او بترسید
از خدای اندران کی تان فرماید تا شما برهید از خشم و عذاب آتش دوزخ⁸⁵

O believers in Muḥammad and the Qur'an. Be patient in battling the infidel enemy, be patient while they are patient in fighting the infidel, be united in Islam against the infidel enemy, and fear God, that He may order you to be saved from his anger and the pain of hellfire.

The author of the Persian text of the Rylands Qur'an was thus doubtless aware of this exegetical tradition; even if he did not actually use the text of *Tafsīr-i Shanqashī* itself, this or something like it evidently influenced him to diverge from the text of the Samanid translation. Alternatively, it is possible that he was using a text of the Samanid *Tafsīr* that already contained such divergences. Although these are not represented in the critical apparatus of Yaghmā'ī's edition of the *Tafsīr*, it is certainly possible that the text was adapted and altered, just as that of Bal'amī's history was, and further research on the transmission of the Persian *Tafsīr* is needed.

However, the Rylands Persian text's interpretation is not found in that manuscript's Turkish translation, which here sticks more closely to the Arabic in some but not all aspects:

*Ey anlar kim bittiler şabr kılıñ meniñ birle, şabr kılıñ mende adındın, köñül bağlañ, qorkuñlar Tañrıda, bolğay kim kurtulğay-sizler.*⁸⁶

While the Turkish text agrees with the Arabic in omitting direct reference to warfare with infidels, it conforms to the Persian in interpreting the final words *la'allakum tuflihūn* (haply so you will prosper) as referring to salvation "*kurtulğay-sizler*", which is only one possible meaning of the Arabic. The relationship between the three texts is thus complex, and, *pace* Eckmann, cannot simply be reduced to carelessness. Rather, the compilers of both the Persian and Turkish texts had access to a variety of exegetical texts, parts of which were incorporated and parts of which were rejected.

The translation of the Qur'an into Turkish, then, was not simply a matter of bringing a vernacular Qur'an to an audience ignorant of Arabic. It should be seen as cultural practice that deliberately imitated the precedent of Persian translation of the Qur'an, which similarly seems to have been an expression of an elite piety, as both the preface to the Samanid *Tafsīr* and the extant manuscripts of the Persian suggest. At the same time, the independence of the Turkish version was at times asserted by deliberately rejecting the text of the Persian, which most likely was comprehensible to its audience.

⁸⁵ *Guzāra-ī Bakhshī az Qur'ān-i Karīm*, 99–100.

⁸⁶ Transcription following Ata, *Türkçe İlk Kur'an Tercümesi*, 6.

Other Interlinear Translations

Compared to Persian the practice of translating the Qur'an into Turkish seems to have remained relatively limited at least until the fifteenth century, perhaps precisely because of this limited and elite audience at which it was aimed. However, interest in interlinear translations in Turkophone elite circles was not restricted to Qur'ans, although these remain by far the best known type of such translations, and probably the most common too. The subject is in need of further research, and here I simply draw attention to some examples that illustrate some of the non-Qur'anic texts which were given interlinear Turkish translations.

Given the close relationship between interlinear Turkish and Persian that has been outlined above, it is perhaps unsurprising that occasionally we find such works based entirely on a Persian original. One such text which has recently come to light is a Khwarazmian Turkish interlinear translation on the Persian text on minerals by the Ilkhanid scholar Naşir al-Dīn Tūsī (d. 1274).⁸⁷ Both on palaeographic and philological grounds the translation and manuscript must date to the late fourteenth century. The Persian original was dedicated to an unnamed Ilkhan, probably Hülegü or Möngke, and survives in very few manuscripts. Again, then, this is a work written for an elite audience, at least in its original form, and the published photographs of the unique manuscript of the interlinear Turkish version, held in al-Azhar Library in Cairo as MS 1252, indicate it is carefully written, using red ink for the translation in contrast to black for the main text, again suggesting it was composed for a patron who wanted a high-quality product.

Over the fifteenth century, Khwarazmian evolved into the language we know as Chaghatay, which was especially patronised in late Timurid Herat. Interlinear Chaghatay Qur'ans are known, but have scarcely been studied,⁸⁸ but the prime example of an interlinear text from the period is the *Chihil Hadīth* (Forty Hadith) composed in 1481–1482 by the famous Eastern Turkish litterateur Mīr 'Alī Shīr Navā'ī (1441–1501), who was attached to the prestigious court of Herat.⁸⁹ Each of the forty hadith are given in Arabic and then on the line below are followed by Turkish translations in verse, which are themselves based in 'Abd al-Rahmān Jāmī's Persian verse version. While largely ignored today in the pantheon of Navā'ī's works, in the fifteenth century and sixteenth centuries this text was copied in several luxury manuscripts (in fact no non-luxury copies of it seem to be known), reflecting the prestige of its author as much as its contents, including the Süleymaniye Library MSS Nuruosmaniye 4968, Ayasofya 3981/1, Fatih 4056/2, Topkapı Saray Müzesi Revan 328. All of these are high quality manuscripts with illumination. An especially fine example is Nuruosmaniye 4968 (Fig. 7), copied by the scribe Qāsim 'Alī (probably late fifteenth to sixteenth century) written on gold-sprinkled paper with pages of different colours and gold embossed floral patterns. The Arabic is in gold, blue or black ink, while the Turkish verse translation nestles beneath it much like a traditional interlinear translation. A similar arrangement can

⁸⁷ F. Kurtulmuş, "Harezmi Türkçesine Ait Bilinmeyen Bir Satır Arası Tercüme: *Taḥṣūkname-i İlhanī*," *Türk Dili Araştırmaları Yıllığı-Belleten*, no. 71 (2021): 31–52.

⁸⁸ Kara, "Doğu ve Batı Türkçesinde Kur'an," 29.

⁸⁹ See Marc Toutant, *Un empire des mots: Pouvoir, culture et soufisme à l'époque des derniers Timourides au miroir de la Khamsa de Mīr 'Alī Shīr Nawā'ī* (Peeters, 2016), 31, 271.

be seen in Ayasofya 3981, copied by the famous calligrapher Sultān ‘Alī Mashhadī. Again, the original of the Prophet’s words is given prominence, while the Turkish translation is placed in smaller script beneath. A rather different arrangement is found in Fatih 4056 (Fig. 8), in which the Turkish and Arabic are of equal size, but the Arabic is picked out in red. In fact, though, as the Turkish is more extensive than the Arabic, with two lines for each line of Arabic, the effect is to give greater prominence to Navā’ī’s text.

Fig. 7 ‘Alī Shīr Navā’ī, *Chihil Ḥadīth*, Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Nuruosmaniye 4968, fol. 6b-7a

A further product of the Timurid period was the emergence of interlinear transliterations. Turkish was a language with two scripts, the Arabic and the Uyghur script. In the Islamic lands the Uyghur script seems to have largely fallen out of use after the eleventh century, but it revived in the fourteenth. It is generally accepted that this revival was a result of its similarity to the Mongolian script, and it was thus used to evoke a sense of association with

Fig. 8 ‘Alī Shīr Navā’ī, *Chihil Ḥadīth*, Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Fatih 4506, fol. 3b-4a.

the Mongol imperial venture by Timur.⁹⁰ In the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries, scribes familiar with the Uyghur script probably mainly came from families in eastern Turkestan where it was still in use, and were employed at the chancelleries of Herat. A small number of largely luxury manuscripts have come down to us from this period written in Uyghur script in the Eastern Turkish literary language. Its prestige was such that even some works in this script are found far outside the Central Asian cultural sphere in Istanbul, where, however, there was little knowledge of the script, although the language could be understood with little difficulty (Navā’ī’s works, for example, were very popular in the Ottoman lands). As a result, texts in Uyghur script were provided with an interlinear Arabic script transliteration. Most of these works from the fifteenth century were copied by an immigrant scribe from Central Asia, ‘Abd al-Razzāq Bakhshī, who served at the courts of the Ottoman sultans Mehmed the Conqueror (r. 1444–1446, 1451–1481) and Beyazid II (1481–1512).⁹¹ Evidently, they found considerable favour. Among the works copied by ‘Abd al-Razzāq were a collection of classical Eastern Turkish literature, including the early moralistic work the *Atabetü’l-Hakāik*,

90 On this process see ‘Alī Tārumī, *Bakhshīyān wa Bitikchiyān: Darbāra-yi Munshīyān-i Turkī-nawīs-i ‘Aşr-i İlkhānī wa Timūrī* (Intishārāt-i Ḥakīm Nizāmī Ganja’ī, 1402).

91 Osman Fikri Sertkaya, “Abdürezzak Baḫşī,” *Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı İslam Ansiklopedisi* 1, 297–299.

and the poems of Luṭfī and Sekkākī, as well as a story—significantly about Tīmūr—which was almost certainly dedicated to Mehmet the Conqueror (Aya Sofya MS 4757) (Fig. 9). Other interlinear works with which ‘Abd al-Razzāq was associated included his own original poems, dedicated to both Mehmet and Beyazid, and a royal decree (*yarlıgh*). However, it is also perfectly clear that this use of Uyghur was a deliberate choice, as some of ‘Abd al-Razzāq’s works are written in Arabic script. The works of ‘Abd al-Razzāq Bakhshī, both original and copied, confirm the association of interlinear texts with elite audiences.

Fig. 9 Uyghur script Eastern Turkish literary anthology with interlinear transcription into Arabic script Eastern Turkish by ‘Abd al-Razzāq Bakhshī, Süleymaniye Manuscripts Library Istanbul, MS Ayasofya 4757, fol. 1b-2a.

Conclusions

It must be emphasised that the present study is very much a preliminary attempt to assess the social context of the production and circulation of these early Turkish interlinear translations, and many questions remain open, not least the vital one of whether we are actually dealing with multiple different Qur'an translations or one translation adapted into different dialects. The relationship of these translations with both the Arabic and Persian texts remain complicated. Most of these Qur'ans remain inadequately published, and it is likely that future research will bring to light fresh examples of Eastern Turkish interlinear translations, both Qur'anic and other. However, on the basis of the evidence surveyed above, I tentatively suggest the following conclusions. From the extant manuscripts, it seems that rather than evolving as a crib for believers ignorant of Arabic, Turkish interlinear translations developed as a response to, and are tightly intertwined with, the tradition of Persian translation, and in particular the influential precedent set by the Samanid Persian *Tafsīr*. Just as the Samanid *Tafsīr* had been designed for a courtly audience, the consumers of Turkish interlinear translations were not the ignorant pious, but high ranking members of the elite, like Aytamish and conceivably the Golden Horde rulers with whom we know the copyist of TĪEM 73 to have been associated. These Turkish texts were largely produced and circulated in environments where Persian was the dominant literary language, with which their audiences must frequently have been familiar. Indeed, we must note that by the time Aytamish acquired or commissioned the Rylands manuscript, its Qarakhanid Turkish would have been linguistically rather unfamiliar and in places certainly difficult for Turkish speakers of the Qipchaq and Oghuz dialects that predominated as the media for literary Turkish in Egypt. Comprehensibility was thus not simply the motive, but rather the promotion of a sort of Turcophone cultural prestige, as is also reflected in the Mamluk-era copies made of other Qarakhanid Turkish works such as the *Dīwān lughāt al-Turk* and the *Kutadgu bilig*. Such tendencies can also be found with some of the treatments of Navā'ī's hadith, in which Navā'ī's translation is given more prominence than the original. Further, the practice of interlinear translations spawned that of transliterations/transcriptions in the fifteenth century, which served an avowed purpose of promoting a certain cultural "Turkishness" associated with imperial rule.

References

- AFSHĀR, Īraj. "Jung-i bayā'ī az 'aṣr-i Hāfīz," in Īraj Afshār, *Majmū'a-yi Kamīna: Maqāla-hā-ī dar nuskhā-shināsī wa kitāb-shināsī*. Intishārāt-i Īrān-zamīn, 1352 (originally published in *Yaghmā* 20 (1346).
- ARAT, Reşid Rahmetli. *Kutadgu bilig, I: Metin*, TDK, 1991.
- ARBERRY, A.J., trans. *The Koran Interpreted*. Allen and Unwin, 1955.
- ARGUNŞAH, Mustafa. "Harezm Türkçesiyle Yapılan Kur'an Çevirisinin Beş Nüshası," *Uluslararası Türkçe Edebiyat Kültür Eğitim Dergisi* 8, no. 2 (2019): 654–698.
- . *Karahanlı - Harezm Türkçesi Kuran Çevirileri Üzerine Notlar*. Kesit, 2023.
- ATA, Aysu. *Türkçe İlk Kur'an Tercümesi (Rylands Nüshası): Karahanlı Türkçesi (Giriş-Metin-Notlar-Dizin)*. TDK, 2004.

- ‘AZĪMĪ, Mīlād. “Matn-shināsī wa jung-pazhūhī: bar-rasī-yi majmū‘a-yi Shams-i Hājj Dawlatshāh-i Shīrāzī.” *Nāma-yi Bahāristān*, no. 16 (1389): 145–192.
- BIRNBAUM, Eleazar. “On Some Turkish Interlinear Translations of the Koran,” *Journal of Turkish Studies/Türklük Bilgisi Araştırmaları*, no. 14 (1990): 113–138.
- BLAIR, Sheila. *Islamic Calligraphy*. Edinburgh University Press, 2006.
- BLÄSING, Uwe. “Qıl Adına Namaz: Bir Gün Adının Tarihçesi.” in *Doğumunun 990. Yılında Yusuf Has Hacib ve Eseri Kutadgu Bilig Bildirileri*, 26–27 Ekim 2009. TDK, 2011.
- BODROGLIGETI, A.J.E. “The Technique of the Glossist as a Key to Understanding the Lexical Material of Early Eastern Middle Turkic Interlinear Qur’an Translations.” *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher* 50 (1978): 17–25.
- . “Ghosts, Copulating Friends, and Pedestrian Locusts in Some Reviews of Eckmann’s *Middle Turkic Glosses*.” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 104, no. 3 (1984): 455–460.
- BOESCHOTEN, Hendrik. “Translations of the Koran: Sources for the History of Written Turkic in a Multilingual Setting.” In *Turkic-Iranian Contact Areas: Historical and Linguistic Aspects*, edited by Lars Johanson and Christiane Bulut. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag, 2006.
- BOROVKOV, A.K. *Leksika Sredneaziatskogo Tefsira: XII-XIII vv.* Izd. Vostochnoi Literatury, 1963; translated as *Orta Asya’da Bulunmuş Kur’an Tefsirinin Söz Varlığı* (XII.-XIII. Yüzyıllar). TDK, 2002.
- CALDER, N. “al-Sarakhsī,” *EP*.
- DANKOFF, Robert. “Qarakhanid Literature and the Beginnings of Turco-Islamic Culture.” In Robert Dankoff, *From Mahmud Kaşgari to Evliya Çelebi Studies in Middle Turkic and Ottoman Literatures*. Isis, 2009.
- DEWEESE, Devin. “Khans and Amirs in the Qalandar-Nama of Abu Bakr Rumi: Praise of the Islamizing Jochid Elite in a Persian Sufi Work From Fourteenth-Century Crimea.” *Archivum Eurasiae Medii Aevi*, no. 21 (2014/15).
- D’HULSTER, Kristof. “How Do You Say Qur’an in Turkic? Observations on the Islamization of the Turkic Lexicon.” In *Continuity and Change in the Realms of Islam: Studies in Honor of Professor Urbain Vermeulen*, edited by K. D’hulster and Jo van Steenberghe. Peeters, 2008.
- . “Qayt Sharīfī’s Turkic Class Notes and Tamurbāy’s Arabic Scribbles: Language and Education at the Mamluk Barracks in the Light of MS Ayasofya 1448.” *Mamluk Studies Review* (2025) (in press).
- DIMITRIEVA, L.V. *Katalog Tyurkskikh Rukopisei Instituta Vostokovedeniya Rossiskoi Akademii Nauk*. Vostochnaia Literatura, 2002.
- DOERFER, Gerhard. “Mahmūd al-Kāşyarī. Arıu, Chaladsch.” *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher*, no. 7 (1987): 105–114.
- ECKMANN, János. “Eine ostmitteltürkische interlineare Koranübersetzung.” *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher*, no. 31 (1959): 72–85.
- . “Doğu Türkçesinde Bir Kuran Çevirisi (Rylands Nüshası).” *Türk Dili Araştırmaları Yıllığı-Belleten*, no. 15 (1967): 51–69.
- . “Two Fragments of a Koran Manuscript with Interlinear Persian and Turkic Translations.” *Central Asiatic Journal* 13, no. 4 (1969): 287–290.
- . “Eastern Turkic Translations of the Koran.” In *Studia Turcica*, edited by L. Ligeti. Akadémiai Kiadó, 1971. Reprinted in János Eckmann. *Middle Turkic Glosses of the Rylands Interlinear Koran Translation*. Akadémiai Kiadó, 1976. 11–19.
- . *Middle Turkic Glosses of the Rylands Interlinear Koran Translation*. Akadémiai Kiadó, 1976.
- ERTAYLAN, İsmail Hikmet. *Yusuf ile Züleyha*. İstanbul Üniversitesi Edebiyat Fakültesi, 1960.

- GRUBER, Christiane. "Between 'Logos' and 'Kalima': Representations of the Prophet Muḥammad in Islamic Painting." *Muqarnas*, no. 29 (2009): 229–262.
- GÜLSEVİN, Gürer. "11.Yüzyılda Hangi Oğuz Diyalektleri Vardı?" *Bilig*, no. 76 (2016): 269–300.
- HAMİDULLAH, Muhammed, "Kur'an-ı Kerim'in Türkçe Yazma Tercümeleri." *Türkiyat Mecmuası*, no. 14 (1964): 65–80.
- İNAN, Abdülkadir. "Eski Türkçe Kur'an Tercemelerinin Dili Meselesi." *Türk Dili* 1, no. 7 (1952): 295–8. —. *Kur'an-ı Kerim Tercemelerinin Üzerine bir İnceleme*. TTK, 1961.
- JACKSON, Cailah. *Mevlevi Manuscripts, 1268–c. 1400: A Study of the Sources*. Palgrave, 2024.
- JAMES, David. *Qur'ans of the Mamluks*. Alexandria Press, 1988.
- KARA, Mehmet. "Doğu ve Batı Türkçesinde Kur'an Tercüme ve Tefsirleri." *Diyanet İlmi Dergi* 29, no. 3 (1993): 25–36.
- al-KAŞVARI, Maḥmūd. *Compendium of Turkish Dialects*. Edited and translated by Robert Dankoff. Harvard University Printing Office, 1982.
- KÖK, Abdullah. "Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır-Arası Kur'an Tercümesi (TİEM 73 1v-235v/2) Giriş-İnceleme-Metin-Dizin." PhD Dissertation, Ankara University, 2004.
- KÜÇÜK, Murat. *Eski Anadolu Türkçesi Dönemine Ait Satır Arası İlk Kur'an Tercümesi*. TTK, 2022.
- KURTULMUŞ, F. "Harezm Türkçesine Ait Bilinmeyen Bir Satır Arası Tercüme: Taşukname-i İlhanî." *Türk Dili Araştırmaları Yıllığı-Belleten*, no. 71 (2021): 31–52.
- LAZARD, Gilbert. "Darī." *Encyclopaedia Iranica*, Vol. VII, Fasc. 1, 34–35. —. "The Rise of the New Persian Language." In *The Cambridge History of Iran*, vol. 4, *The Period from the Arab Invasion to the Saljuqs*, edited by R.N. Frye. Cambridge University Press, 1975), 595–632.
- MEREDITH-OWENS, G.M. "Notes on an Old Ottoman Translation of the Kur'ān." *Oriens* 10, no. 2 (1957): 258–276.
- NARSHAKHI, *The History of Bukhara, Translated from a Persian Abridgement of the Arabic Original by Narshakhi*. Translated by Richard N. Frye. The Mediaeval Academy of America, 1954.
- PEACOCK, A.C.S. *Mediaeval Islamic Historiography and Political Legitimacy: Bal'amī's Tārīkh-nāma*. Routledge, 2007. —. *Islam, Literature and Society in Mongol Anatolia*. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- ŞADİQİ, Ashraf. "Baḥthī dar bāb-i kitāb-i Pulī miyān-i shī'r-i ḥajā'ī wa 'arūzī-yi fārsī dar dū qarn-i awwal-i hijri az Duktur Aḥmad 'Alī Rajā'ī." In Muḥammad Ja'far Yāḥaqqī et al, *Khīrad bar sar-i Jān: Nāmgāna-yi Ustād 'Alī Rajā'ī Bukhārā'ī*. Intishārāt-i Sukhan, 1391, 349–388.
- ŞADR AL-AFĀDİL, Abū Muḥammad Majd al-Dīn Qāsim ibn Ḥusayn ibn Muḥammad Tarā'ifi Khwārazmī, *Badāyī' al-Mulaḥ*, edited by Muṣṭafā Awliyā'ī. Mīrāth-i Maktūb, 2003.
- SAĞOL, Gülden. *An Interlinear Translation of the Qur'an into Khwarazm Turkish: Introduction, Text, Glossary and Facsimile*. Harvard University, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, 1993.
- al-SAKHĀWĪ, *al-Ḍaw' al-lāmi' li-ahl al-qarn al-tāsi'*. Dār al-Jīl, 1992.
- SERTKAYA, Osman Fikri. "Abdürezzak Bahşi." *Türkiye Diyanet Vakfı İslam Ansiklopedisi* 1, 297–299.
- Shams al-Dīn Muḥammad b. Dawlatshāh b. Yūsuf al-SHĪRĀZĪ, *Safīna-yi Shams-i Hājjī*, edited by Milād 'Azīmī. Intishārāt-i Sukhan, 1388.
- SİBGATULLINA, Gulnaz, "On Translating the Qur'an into Turkic Vernaculars: Texts, Ties, and Traditions." In *European Muslims and the Qur'an: Practices of Translation, Interpretation, and Commodification*, edited by Gulnaz Sibgatullina and Gerard Wiegers. De Gruyter, 2024. 189–218.

- ŞİMŞEK, Yaşar. “Satırasası Türkçe Kur’an Tercümelerinin Birbiri ile İlgisi ve Tasnifi Üzerine.” *Gazi Türkiyat*, no. 24 (2019): 47–65.
- . *Harezm Türkçesi Kur’an Tercümesi (Meşhed Nüshası 293 No, Giriş-Metin-Dizin)*. 2 vols. Akçağ, 2019.
- SPULER, B., “Kırım,” *Ef²*
- TARUMİ, ‘Alī. *Bakhshiyān wa Bitikchiyān: Darbāra-yi Munshiyān-i Turkī-nawīs-i ‘Aşr-i İlkhānī wa Tīmūrī*. Intishārāt-i Ḥakīm Nizāmī Ganja’ī, 1402.
- TOGAN, Zeki Velidi. “The Earliest Translation of the Qur’an into Turkish.” *İslām Tetkikleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, no. 4 (1964): 1–19.
- TOKER, Mustafa. “Memlûk Sahasında Yazılmış Kur’an-ı Kerim Tercümesi Yok Mudur?” in *Tarihî Türkçe Kur’an Tercümeleri Üzerine Araştırmalar*, edited by Ahmet Akpınar. Krİter, 2024, 29–57.
- TOR, D.G. “The Islamization of Central Asia in the Sāmānid Era and the Reshaping of the Muslim World.” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 2, no. 2 (2009): 279–299.
- TOUTANT, Marc. *Un empire des mots: Pouvoir, culture et soufisme à l’époque des derniers Timourides au miroir de la Khamsa de Mīr ‘Alī Shīr Nawā’ī*. Peeters, 2016.
- ÜNLÜ, Suat. “Karahanlı Türkçesi Satır Arası Kur’an Tercümesi TIEM 73 (TIEM 235v3-450r7), Giriş-Metin-İnceleme-Analitik Dizin.” PhD Dissertation, Hacettepe University, 2004.
- . *Karahanlı Türkçesi İlk Türkçe Satır-Arası Transkribeli Kur’an Tercümesi (TIEM 73)*. 7 vols. Selçuklu Belediyesi, 2018.
- ÜŞENMEZ, Emek. *Türkçe İlk Kur’an Tercümelerinden Özbekistan Nüshası: Satır-Arası Türkçe-Farsça Tercümeli*. Akademik Kitaplar, 2013.
- . *Türkçe İlk Tercümelerinden Meşhed Nüshası: Satır-Arası Türkçe-Farsça Tercümeli*. Post, 2025.
- USTA, İbrahim Halil. *Orta Asya Kur’an Tefsiri (Metin-Tıpkıbasım)*. Poyraz, 2011 (non vidi)
- YAGHMĀ’Ī, Habīb ed. *Tarjama-yi Tafsiir-i Qur’ān*. Intishārāt-i Dānishgāh-i Tihrān, 2536/1356.
- YĀHAQQĪ, Muḥammad Ja‘far, ed. *Guzāra-ī bakhshi az Qur’ān-i karīm: Tafsiir-i Shanqashī*. Intishārāt-i Bunyād-i Farhang-i Īrān, 2535.
- ZADEH, Travis. *The Vernacular Qur’an: Translation and the Rise of Persian Exegesis*. Oxford University Press, 2012.
- . “The Fātiḥa of Salmān al-Fārisī and the Modern Controversy over Translating the Qur’ān.” In *The Meaning of the Word: Lexicology and Tafsiir*, edited by Stephen Burge. Institute of Ismaili Studies/Oxford University Press, 2015, 375–420.

© A.C.S. Peacock, University of St Andrews, UK

◀ acsp@st-andrews.ac.uk ▶

A World of Words and Words for the World: *Encyclopaedism and Language Learning in a 19th-century Arabic-Malay Vocabulary*

AGLAIA IANKOVSKAIA (SOAS, London)¹

Abstract

The article looks into two manuscripts containing copies of a thematic Arabic-Malay vocabulary titled *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-ʿArab* (A list in Arabic speech). Originating in mid-19th-century West Sumatra, the manuscripts are housed in the Leiden University Library with the numbers Or. 3231(8) and 3233(2) and belong to the collection of Dutch linguist Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk (1824–1894). The vocabulary features a list of Arabic words arranged in thematic sections and provided with Malay equivalents below the line. Starting with God’s names and words describing the natural world, it proceeds to sections dealing with human society and everyday life. The article discusses the encyclopaedic nature of such an arrangement and addresses the pedagogical functions of this thematic dictionary as a tool for teaching and learning Arabic as a foreign language in the Indonesian-Malay world. Juxtaposing two versions of the same text, it questions the modes of this text’s transmission and reasons for employing an interlinear model of translation in a dictionary. Considering the divergences between the two manuscripts as well as different misspellings they contain, the article argues that the interlinear Malay translations were transmitted separately from the Arabic wordlist.

Keywords: Arabic-Malay lexicography, West Sumatra, dictionary, interlinear translation, Islamic education

Introduction

For centuries, bilingual dictionaries appear to have been an indispensable part of foreign language learning and textual translation. Some of the dictionaries listed words in alphabetical order or in order of appearance in a text (glossaries), serving as reference works for those reading and translating texts in a foreign language. Others, i.e., systematic dictionaries, or vocabularies, grouped words related to a certain field or theme and helped

¹ This research was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (project: Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies, grant agreement no. 101001731) and by the Israel Science Foundation (grant no. 2009/19). I thank Prof. Ronit Ricci, Dr Fadhli Lukman, Dr Mulaika Hijjas, Prof. Pramono, Dr Marije Plomp, Dr Edward Weech, Dr Alexandra Kasatkina, and Annechien Ten Brinke for their insights, advice, and help with translation and accessing manuscripts.

learners to build and expand their vocabulary. Surprisingly, not too long ago dictionaries of the second type were not as widely used and available as one might expect—at least, in the Indonesian-Malay world where Islam spread starting from the 13th century and Arabic was studied as the language of the Qur’an and a key to religious sciences. This article seeks to discuss a thematic Arabic-to-Malay vocabulary found in two copies from Sumatra: Leiden Or. 3231(8) and 3233(2), both belonging to the collection of Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk (1824–1894), the well-known Dutch linguist and Bible translator. Dating back to the middle of the 19th century, they represent a type of lexicographical work that is rarely found in Malay manuscript collections.

The history of Arabic-Malay lexicography has been approached by Michael Laffan² and Nico Kaptein,³ the former also touching upon the manuscripts addressed in this article. The manuscripts, i.e., Leiden Or. 3231 and 3233, are collective volumes containing several dictionaries of different types, among them alphabetical, systematic, and specialized ones. Titled *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* (A list in Arabic speech, or List of Arabic words), the dictionary to be discussed here is of the second type, as it is arranged in thematic sections, such as spices, animals, and body parts. The words *kitāb al-lughā* (dictionary, or literally language book) preceding the title are not part of it but rather indicate the type or genre of the book.⁴ Remaining true to the title, the dictionary is indeed a list—that of Arabic words, which are provided with Malay equivalents below the line.

In the Greco-Roman world, such lists of words arranged by semantic fields were known as *onomastica*.⁵ In the Arabic Middle East, the genre also gained currency; John Haywood defines it as “general classified vocabulary,” a type of lexicographical work that consisted of words classified by subject-matter under broad headings, or sometimes according to word-forms (in some cases both methods were mixed).⁶ However, in the Arabic-speaking world such vocabularies were monolingual. Bilingual Arabic-to-vernacular dictionaries came into play with the expansion of Islam to Persian- and Turkic-speaking regions, where the word *lūgat*, *lūgat*, or *lughat* (derived from the Arabic *al-lughā*, “language”) was used to designate a dictionary.⁷ In the same meaning, that is of a dictionary or vocabulary, (*kitāb*) *lughat* appears to have settled in the Malay language.⁸ Another feature making the Arabic-Malay

-
- 2 Michael Laffan, “New Charts for the Arabic Ocean: Dictionaries as Indicators of Changing Times,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 159, no. 2–3 (2003): 351–387.
 - 3 Nico J.G. Kaptein, “Some Early Contributions to Arabic-Malay Lexicography: Sayyid ‘Uthmān of Batavia (1822–1913) as a Lexicographer,” in *Malay Images*, ed. Haji Omar A. (UPSI, 2005), 120–142.
 - 4 Jan Just Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden*, vol. 4 (Ter Lugt Press, 2007), 76.
 - 5 Rolando Ferri, “The Greco-Roman World,” in *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 84, 87–88.
 - 6 John A. Haywood, *Arabic Lexicography* (Brill, 1960), 4, 111–114.
 - 7 Marek Stachowski, “The Turkic Languages and Persian to c. 1700,” in *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 223.
 - 8 Richard J. Wilkinson, *A Malay-English Dictionary* (Kelly and Walsh, 1901), 599.

vocabulary from Van der Tuuk's collection part of a wider tradition is that the words in it are written as a continuous text, which was also typical of Persian wordlists.⁹

One more wider tradition that this vocabulary appears to be part of is that of interlinear translation from Arabic into Malay or other languages of the Islamic Indonesian-Malay world. Such translations, some of them very literal and some rather interpretative, often accompany Arabic texts found in manuscripts from the region and even in later printed editions of such texts (for scholarship on the matter see works by Azyumardi Azra, Ronit Ricci, and Arif Maftuhin).¹⁰ Along with marginal annotations and commentaries, they act as paratextual elements—not being part of the main text, translations help to explain its meaning to the readers. As supplementary, optional additions, they are not always consistent and often appear occasionally throughout a text. In the manuscripts discussed in this article, however, translation is found where it appears to be unavoidable and, more than that, essential—that is, in a dictionary. A word-by-word translation, the solely possible one for a wordbook, it follows the visual pattern commonly employed by Malay translators of Arabic texts: written in a smaller script, the units of translation are placed diagonally between the lines of the source. While the genre of the text suggests that translation is indispensable, it is still visually presented as a secondary element.

Of interest from various perspectives, the vocabulary under discussion is yet to be situated in the history of Arabic-Malay lexicography. First of all, it seems to present a rare example of a handwritten Arabic-to-Malay thematic dictionary which was likely used by Malay-speaking Muslims as a learning aid in their studies of the language of Islam. Arranged in an encyclopaedic way, it provides insights into the Arabic vocabulary that was considered relevant as well as into the compilers' worldviews and mindsets. Furthermore, the two extant copies of the same dictionary allow us to look into the divergences and misspellings found in the text and discuss the modes of its transmission. And finally, the interlinear arrangement of the dictionary deserves attention, which links it with the tradition of interlinear translation in the Islamic Indonesian-Malay world and beyond. In what follows, I address the aforementioned aspects, starting with the manuscripts' provenance and description and proceeding to the structure of the vocabulary, juxtaposing the two copies, and discussing the roles of orality and interlinearity in the text's reproduction and transmission.

9 Stachowski, "The Turkic Languages and Persian," 225.

10 See Azyumardi Azra, "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia," in *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, ed. Henri Chambert-Loir (Gramedia, 2009), 435–443; Ronit Ricci, "Reading Between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation," *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80; Ronit Ricci, "Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid syaraf al-anām* across the Indonesian-Malay World," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143–164; Arif Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable. The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 151 (2024): 279–303.

Van der Tuuk's Vocabularies

Among the manuscript collection of Van der Tuuk housed in the Leiden University Library, there are three collective volumes with the subsequent numbers Or. 3231, 3232 and 3233. They contain various texts most of which deal with the Arabic language, including Arabic-Malay and Arabic-Javanese dictionaries and texts on Arabic grammar.¹¹ Leiden Or. 3232 is copied by Van der Tuuk himself, while Or. 3233 contains marginal notes by his hand. Or. 3233 comprises three Arabic-Malay dictionaries, of which two duplicate those found in Or. 3231: Or. 3233(1) is the same as Or. 3231(6), while Or. 3233(2) is another copy of Or. 3231(8). According to Petrus Voorhoeve, “both volumes were copied about the middle of the 19th century, Or. 3233 in Sumatra. This may also be the place of origin of Or. 3231.”¹²

If this is indeed the case, the manuscripts must have been acquired by Van der Tuuk sometime between 1851 and 1857 during his travels in western and northern Sumatra. Early in 1851, the linguist, who had been commissioned by the Dutch Bible Society (*Nederlands Bijbelgenootschap*, NBG) to study the Toba Batak language and ultimately translate the Bible into it, embarked on his voyage from Java and arrived at Padang, a port in the Minangkabau lands and the seat of the colonial government of Sumatra's West Coast.¹³ From there Van der Tuuk continued north to Tapanuli region, where he settled in the coastal town of Sibolga in mid-1851. In late 1851 or early 1852, he moved further north to Barus, also a coastal town, and stayed there until April 1857, when he travelled on foot all the way back to Padang and soon left West Sumatra for good. During his residence in Barus, the scholar undertook several trips into the interior of the island, i.e., to the still independent Toba Batak and Mandailing lands.¹⁴ With the help of his local informants, whom he also hired as scribes for copying manuscripts and writing down oral texts, Van der Tuuk accumulated a collection of materials that he later bequeathed to the University of Leiden.

The Arabic-Malay vocabularies were apparently among these texts, although it remains unknown where exactly the two manuscripts come from—as the scholar did not keep records

11 See Edwin P. Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts in the Library of Leiden University and Other Collections in the Netherlands*, vol. 2 (Leiden University Library, 2007), 79–83; Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts*, 75–77; also Petrus Voorhoeve, “Indonesische handschriften in de Universiteitsbibliotheek te Leiden,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 108, no. 3 (1952): 216; Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands* (Leiden University Press, 1980), 160, 417–418; Teuku Iskandar, *Catalogue of Malay, Minangkabau, and South Sumatran Manuscripts in the Netherlands*, vol. 1, (Documentatiebureau Islam-Christendom, 1999), 120–121.

12 Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts*, 418.

13 Toba Batak are an ethnic group residing in the hinterland of North Sumatra in the vicinity of Lake Toba. At the time of arrival of European Christian missionaries in the 19th century, they had not been impacted by Islamisation and retained their animistic beliefs. Minangkabau are an ethnic group inhabiting the highlands of western Sumatra. In the mid-19th century, the majority of them already professed Islam.

14 Kees Groenboer, *Een vorst onder de taalgeleerden: Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk, taalafgevaardigde voor Indië van het Nederlandsch Bijbelgenootschap 1847–1873* (KITLV, 2002), 12–15. Mandailing are a predominantly Muslim Batak ethnic group residing in South Tapanuli.

of places where he acquired his materials.¹⁵ In his last, posthumously published work Van der Tuuk mentions an incomplete Arabic-Malay dictionary, apparently Or. 3233(2), that “comes from the Padang Highlands and is here and there Minangkabau-ish.”¹⁶ Or. 3233(2) indeed contains a colophon indicating its Minangkabau origins (f. 56v), which reads as follows: “written by a person from Bayang, son of Tuanku in Jambak bearing the title Fakih Sultan at the time of building the surau in the village of Lubuk Gambir” (*Yang menyurat dia orang Bayang anak Tuanku di Jambak yang bergelar Fakih Sultan tatkala berbuat surau dalam karya Lubuk Gambir adanya*).¹⁷ Bayang is a coastal town south of Padang to the north of which a village called Lubuk Gambir can be found, while Jambak refers to a smaller unit within the village named after the Minangkabau clan that the land belonged to.¹⁸ In any case, the circumstance that the manuscript was copied in Bayang area does not imply that this was where Van der Tuuk acquired it (likely bought, as the colophon also mentions a price—two rials). Or. 3231(8) does not have a colophon, and very little can be assumed about its origins. Both manuscripts could have been acquired either during the linguist’s overland journey to Padang, in Padang, Sibolga, or in Barus, where a local chief named Tuanku Sutan Ibrahim used to lend Van der Tuuk some of the Malay and Minangkabau texts that he owned.¹⁹

Van der Tuuk’s interest in Arabic-Malay dictionaries reflects his research methods and interests as a linguist and lexicographer from different perspectives, among them his background in Arabic studies, his lifelong interest in Malay and unfulfilled plans to compile a new dictionary of this language,²⁰ and his preference of the written word over the spoken one. First and foremost, Van der Tuuk was “a lifelong collector of words, in as many Indonesian languages as he could lay his hands on.”²¹ Although his primary mission in Sumatra was to study the Toba Batak language, he also used this opportunity to broaden his knowledge of local Malay and Minangkabau. An insight into the linguist’s early engagement with the Arabic-Malay dictionaries he had collected can be found in his letter to the Bible Society, with which he maintained regular correspondence from Barus:

These languages are rich and poor, as they like to say: rich in concrete words and poor in abstract ones. Neither Malay nor Batak has a word for *animal* in general, and I have often seen a native laughing at me because I applied *bienatang* to a worm. Meanwhile, he has a name for the smallest reptile. This is the case with all peoples who are semi-

15 Marije Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited: Malay Adventure Stories: With an Annotated Edition and Translation of the Malay Story of Bahram Syah” (Ph.D. Dissertation, Leiden University, 2014), 58.

16 Herman N. van der Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken* (’s-Gravenhage: Nijhoff, 1894), 50; see also Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts*, 81–83.

17 Among the Minangkabau, Tuanku (or Tuangku) is a title of a religious leader or scholar, while *surau* is a term for Islamic school. For Islamic education and translation practice in *surau*, see Fadhli Lukman’s article in the present issue.

18 I thank Pramono for his help in identifying the place.

19 Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited,” 43.

20 See Cornelis D. Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 152, no. 3 (1996); Andries Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996): 118, 122.

21 Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer.” 113.

civilized, and it is also the reason why, when they come into contact with foreigners, they use foreign words to express abstract ideas, while when they attain without these foreigners the requisite degree of civilisation at which the expression of abstracts becomes necessary, a concrete word gets elevated to an abstract. Isn't it to be explained in this way that *dog* (in our language the name of a type of dog) means in English *a dog* in general? At the same time, *hound* in English is the name of a type of dog, while for us *hond* is the general word. The Arabic-Malay dictionaries have elevated concrete words to general ones; thus I find *bienatang* (wild animal) given as *animal* and *kara* (certain small long-tailed monkey) as the general name for *monkey*, simply because the writers did not find general words for *animal* and *monkey* in Malay. The compilers of these dictionaries were probably Malays civilized by Arabs, because the dictionaries provide very few words taken from Arabic as equivalents of the Arabic words to be explained, which would have been the case if the authors were Arab. (*Aan Bijbelgenootschap, Baroes 27-3-1854*)²²

Van der Tuuk approached these dictionaries, which he continued to consult throughout his life, primarily from the perspective of historical linguistics. His last treatise dealt with Malay lexicography, and in it the scholar addressed one of the vocabularies (Or. 3233(2), as mentioned above) as a source on Minangkabau language and its Agam dialect, also pointing to the discrepancies between Arabic words and their vernacular translations.²³ In his lexicographical studies, Van der Tuuk used handwritten dictionaries along with multiple other manuscripts that he eagerly collected. Those were texts of most diverse content, as the scholar did not see any literary value in them²⁴ but approached them as mere sources of lexical information. Although oral conversations with native speakers constituted a substantial part of his fieldwork, Van der Tuuk considered written materials the only reliable basis for describing a language. A “conviction of his, to which he adhered also in the daily practice of his lexicographical work in the field, was that words should be studied in their syntactic context and that therefore written texts were an essential tool for a lexicographer. Consequently, the hunter of words automatically became a collector of manuscripts.”²⁵

These Van der Tuuk used to either purchase or commission as copies by local scribes; sometimes he copied texts himself in his sloppy handwriting—as is the case with the Arabic-Javanese dictionary found in Leiden Or. 3232. Unlike his materials from Bali, most of the Malay manuscripts in the scholar's collection were bought rather than copied on order.²⁶ In an article written during his residence in Barus, Van der Tuuk expresses his views on the essential role of texts as recorded by the speakers of the language:

Consultation of the natives about their language is very risky and may be useful only for verifying the pronunciation; the meaning of words is better learned from an

22 Quoted in Groenboer, *Een vorst onder de taalgeleerden*, 203.

23 Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken*, 50–52.

24 Plomp, “Never-neverland Revisited,” 21.

25 Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” 130.

26 Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” 368.

assiduous application to the study of Malay writers than from speaking to people with insufficient education to understand questions about linguistic problems.²⁷

Another consideration of his was apparently an unwillingness to put himself beyond the reach of scholarly criticism, as written sources could serve as proof for his arguments.²⁸ Handwritten texts formed the basis of Van der Tuuk's dictionaries, and they have come down to us not only as the linguist's heritage and evidence of his research methodology and sources, but also as witnesses of West Sumatra's 19th-century history and cultural milieu, as well as insights into its Islamic education practices, of which teaching and learning Arabic constituted an indispensable part.

Apart from purely linguistic inquiries, many questions could be asked in respect of the Arabic-Malay vocabulary preserved in two copies by virtue of Van der Tuuk's travels and studies. Who were the compilers of this wordlist and what audiences did they aim at? Might it have been written by an autodidact for private use, or was it rather composed by a teacher for students, or by an Arab sheikh for Malay learners of Arabic?²⁹ Were the Arabic words and their vernacular translations written down by the same scribe and at the same time, copied from a written source or orally dictated? What informed the selection of words included in the vocabulary—were they considered useful for a person aspiring to *speak* Arabic (for instance, planning a journey to Mecca), or for those reading and translating Islamic texts, the words having been extracted from those very texts rather than from the author's memory? These are far from all the questions that arise. Not all of them can be answered drawing upon the two copies at our disposal, therefore in what follows I will address only some of these questions.

Naming Things, Structuring the World

In Leiden Or. 3231, *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* occupies some 80 pages (ff. 44v–4r). The collective volume also contains several other texts by different copyists that would be helpful to a learner of Arabic, i.e., three other Arabic-Malay vocabularies and two texts on Arabic grammar. Only one of the vocabularies is arranged alphabetically (Or. 3231(6)), while the other three are systematic: Or. 3231(7) and (8) list words in thematic sections, while Or. 3231(9) deals with only one topic, which is *fiqh*. Or. 3231(8) is written by a somewhat sloppy hand in black ink; unlike other manuscripts constituting the volume, it has no rubrication in red. The sections are largely untitled, mostly marked by an overlined word “section” (*faṣl*), so that the logic of the compiler can only be guessed from the contents. Vocalized Arabic words are put one after another in a line, little space being left between them, while their

27 Herman N. van der Tuuk, “lets over de Hoog-Maleische bijbelvertaling,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde* 5, no. 1 (1856): 179. Quoted in Grijns, “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay,” 358. On Van der Tuuk's methodology in this regard, see also Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer,” 121.

28 Teeuw, 116.

29 As it appears to be the case with a similar systematic vocabulary, Or. 3231(7), which is said to have been compiled by an imam for his brethren (see Wieringa, *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts*, 2007: 81; Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts*, 2007: 76).

Malay equivalents are written in smaller script diagonally below the line. The interlinear translation appears rather terse, only one translation option provided for each word.

On the first page (f. 44r, see Fig. 1), the text identifies itself as *Kitāb al-lughā al-jadwāl fī kalām al-‘Arab*, while in the colophon (f. 4v) a different title appears, that is *al-Kitāb al-lughā al-jadwāl fī bayān al-taṣrīf* (The dictionary [entitled] “A list in the clarification of morphology”). In both cases *al-jadwāl* (list) is misspelled as *al-jadwāl*, which might as well be a misspelling of the plural form *al-jadāwil*, as on f. 44r we find *al-jadwāl* after a numeral (*thalāthat al-jadwāl*), while in the next sentence the singular form *al-jadwāl* is spelled correctly three times in a row. If the latter is the case, the title should be rather translated as “Lists in Arabic speech.” The actual wordlist is preceded with a *basmala* and traditional doxology, followed by a reference to unspecified ‘*ulamā*’ who had said that “language is soil and knowledge is vegetation” (apparently referring to the hadith found on the previous page, f. 45r) as well as that “language is the key to sciences” (f. 4v). Written in Arabic, the introductory part is also provided with interlinear Malay translation.

Page | 58

From this the compiler proceeds to explain the structure of the vocabulary, which is divided into three major parts (or lists) according to a grammatical principle: particles (*jadwāl al-ḥarf*), nouns or “names” (*jadwāl al-ism*, which also includes adjectives and numerals), and verbs (*jadwāl al-fi‘l*). These larger “chapters,” just as their sub-sections, are indiscriminately called *faṣl* throughout the text. In the introduction, however, the three large sections are referred to as lists, which might indeed explain why the title of the vocabulary should be read rather as “Lists” than “A list.” By the end of the text, the handwriting seems to become more roundish and thorough—as if a different scribe has stepped in, so that the colophon appears to be written by the same hand as the wordlist entitled *al-Lughat al-fiqh* (ungrammatical Arabic for “a dictionary of juridical terms”) that follows it (Or. 3231(9)). Laffan suggests that this latter text was added by the scribe as a supplement to the preceding vocabulary, i.e., Or. 3231(8).³⁰

The second copy of the same dictionary is also part of a collective volume, that is Leiden Or. 3233, in which it is found between two other Arabic-Malay dictionaries arranged alphabetically. One of these two, Or. 3233(1), is the same text as Or. 3231(6). Two of the three texts in Or. 3233, therefore, duplicate those in Or. 3231. Unlike Or. 3231, Or. 3233 contains notes by Van der Tuuk’s hand in the margins. The systematic vocabulary Or. 3233(2) occupies 54 pages (ff. 30v-56v) and is missing the beginning—this is only evident from the fact that it commences with the words found on page 6 of Or. 3231(8) (f. 42v), as the beginning of this second copy of the dictionary is clearly marked with a *basmala* in place of a title. The incompleteness of the text, which disconcerted Van der Tuuk,³¹ thus was likely due not to missing first pages but to an incomplete source manuscript at the copyist’s disposal. No title for the text is provided, neither on the first page nor in the above mentioned colophon that attributes the copy to a Minangkabau scribe from Bayang.

The handwriting in this copy is generally finer than in Or. 3231(8); unlike in the latter, Arabic words have no diacritics added, while the sections are highlighted in red. The number

30 Laffan, “New Charts for the Arabic Ocean,” 353.

31 Tuuk, *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken*, 52.

of lines on the page is nine, as opposed to seven in Or. 3231(8). In the margins, pencil notes and marks by the hand of Van der Tuuk appear. Some of these are catchwords in Dutch indicating categories that are treated in the unnamed *faṣl*, e.g., gold, gems, tools, animals, body parts and clothes. As in the other copy, Malay translations of the Arabic words are provided below the line. In both manuscripts translations for some words are missing, while for words that seem to have been considered synonyms, they tend to be replaced with the letter *mīm*. In Or. 3233(2), the layout appears neater than in Or. 3231(8), which is arranged in a less coherent way, interlinear translations overflowing to the margins and additional words and annotations inserted here and there. Altogether, Or. 3231(8) with its messy writing, vocalized Arabic, and no rubrication leaves an impression that it was once used in a teaching and learning process. Or. 3233(2), on the other hand, appears to be a more thorough copy of a manuscript similar to Or. 3231(8), though it once served as study material too—not for a surau student but for a Dutch linguist. Hereafter I refer to Or. 3231(8) as the first copy and to Or. 3233(2) as the second copy of the vocabulary.

As has been mentioned, the vocabulary is divided into three major chapters according to a morphological principle: particles, nouns (*al-ism*), and verbs. Within the chapter on nouns, thematic arrangement is applied. It takes an encyclopaedic form, commencing with sections on names (or attributes) of God, religious, epistemological and abstract terms, and then proceeding to words describing the physical world: those for land and sky; geographical notions; inanimate phenomena and materials; spices and aromatics; food and drink; vessels and household utensils; diseases; plants and their parts; water and fish; animals and insects; body parts; categories of people; clothes and furnishings. The encyclopaedism of the wordlist appears rather intuitive, although it might have been inspired to a certain extent by post-classical Arabic cosmologies such as *‘Ajā’ib al-makhlūqāt* (The Wonders of Creation) by Zakariyā al-Qazwīnī (c. 1203–1283), which tend to zoom in from the celestial to the terrestrial. Or it could have been inspired by some treatises of the same genre, such as the systematic Persian-Arabic dictionary by al-Zamakhsharī (1075–1144) that combines grammatical and thematic arrangements and groups nouns in sections beginning with time and sky and moving on to earthly subjects.³² Commencing with God’s names and words describing the natural world and proceeding to sections dealing with human society and everyday life, *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* follows this pattern. Assembling the elusive foreign words in logically arranged sections, the compilers unwittingly describe the world around them in an encyclopaedic and largely intuitive way, one that had been likely informed by their cultural background. In this regard, the vocabulary reflects not only language learning practices at the time, but also Malay Muslims’ worldviews and mindsets.

Having listed God’s attributes, the vocabulary proceeds to the next *faṣl* which commences with *al-ḥayāt* (life) and contains words that can be vaguely described as general terms, e.g., power, desire, speech, sleep, entrance and exit, increase and decrease. This is followed by sections dealing with celestial phenomena (sun, moon, stars, clouds, rain, wind, etc.) and the cardinal points; geographical terms (e.g., mountain, plain, forest, village, town, road, house), metals and minerals; medicine and plants. The first copy (ff. 36r–34v) contains sections on flora, spices and aromatics, drinks and cups, tools, and diseases that are missing from the

32 Haywood, *Arabic Lexicography*, 118.

second copy (see f. 35v). After these come lists of words for water bodies (sea, river, spring); fish and aquatic animals; and finally land animals—this latter section commencing with the word *al-hayawān* (animal) that is translated to Malay as *segala yang hidup* (lit. everything that lives). Amidst the reptiles, a mythical creature has crept in, i.e., *tinnīn/naga* (dragon). Some of the animal species listed are found both in the Middle East and the Malay archipelago, some are not: among the latter are camels, lions, and particular species of birds.³³

Finding no equivalents to such animals' names in Malay, the translators opt for conveying them with words for similar animals. For instance, *al-hudhud* (hoopoe) is translated as *merak* (peacock)—apparently due to the feather crests on both birds' heads. This word for some reason attracted the attention of Van der Tuuk, who notes “*hudhud*” in the margin of the page (see Fig. 2).³⁴ *Al-asad* (lion) is translated as *harimau* (tiger), *al-dhi'b* (wolf) as *harimau akar* (clouded leopard), and *al-nimr* (the actual tiger) as *harimau kecil* (small tiger) in the second copy and as another *harimau akar* in the first one. The latter case also demonstrates that, unlike the Arabic words that differ between the two copies only in spelling (misspellings occur widely in both versions of the vocabulary), their Malay translations occasionally differ in content—yet most of the translation choices still overlap. Also, as was pointed out by Van der Tuuk, Arabic loanwords are barely used in the translation—although the borrowed word for lion, *asada*, for example, had been in use in literary Malay since the 17th century.³⁵

Humans find themselves at the very beginning of the fauna section where they precede cattle and are classified according to their gender, age, and social roles: men and women, free and enslaved, old and young, kings, ministers, and generals.³⁶ A section dealing with women also appears further in the vocabulary, after the lists of words for animals and human body parts. Women are divided into maids, brides, widows, prostitutes; young, middle aged, and old; married and not.³⁷ Misspellings make some of the Arabic words unrecognizable, so that only the Malay translations allow for their identification: for instance, *al-qaḥba* (“prostitute,” translated into Malay as *perempuan jahat*, “bad woman,” in both copies) is spelled as *al-fujuba* in the first copy and in the second one as *al-taḥiya*. The following section provides a variety of kinship terms, beginning with a distinction between a *al-qarīb* (“relative,” translated into Malay as *keluarga*, “family”) and *al-ajnabī* (stranger) or *al-gharīb* (foreigner). *Al-ajnabī* is translated as *orang asing* (foreigner) in the first copy and as *orang lain* (other person) in the second one, while *al-gharīb* is conveyed as *orang dagang* (trader)—a translation choice reflecting the most historically common context for encounters with foreigners in the archipelago. The second copy also provides two Arabic synonyms for “relative” that are absent from the first one, demonstrating that the latter is not always the more complete version of the vocabulary.

33 See ff. 33v–31v in the first copy and ff. 36v–38r in the second one.

34 F. 38r of the second copy.

35 Tom G. Hoogervorst, “Seventeenth-century Malay Wordlists and Their Potential for Etymological Scholarship,” *Wacana, Journal of the Humanities of Indonesia* 25, no. 3 (2024): 543.

36 See f. 33r in the first copy, f. 36v in the second.

37 Ff. 29v (copy 1) and 39v (copy 2).

The section proceeds with words related to nobility and lineage that are followed by a list of kinship terms such as father, mother, son, grandson, and so on.³⁸ In the second copy, the translator does not differentiate between maternal and paternal aunts and uncles, conveying the four Arabic words indiscriminately as *mamak lelaki/perempuan*—quite an unidiomatic phrasing for uncle/aunt, that can be literally translated as “male uncle” and “female uncle.” Also, while the word *mamak* (maternal uncle) can sometimes be used to refer to a maternal aunt, it is not known to be applied to paternal relatives.³⁹ In the first copy, the translation attempts more precision but still does not avoid confusion: *al-‘amm* (paternal uncle) is translated as *mamak saudara bapak* (*mamak* father’s sibling), *al-‘amma* (paternal aunt) as *mamak saudara ibu* (*mamak* mother’s sibling), *al-khāl* (maternal uncle) as *saudara ibu laki-laki* (mother’s brother), and *al-khāla* (maternal aunt) as *saudara ibu perempuan* (mother’s sister). This confusion around kinship terms, especially in relation to maternal and paternal uncles, the former (*mamak*) being the central figure in the Minangkabau kinship system, might testify that the compilers of the vocabulary were more likely Malay than Minangkabau. While Minangkabau only recognize maternal uncle as *mamak*, both copies of the vocabulary use the word *mamak* to translate “paternal uncle” from Arabic, and the first copy does not translate the actual *mamak*, i.e., *al-khāl*, as *mamak* at all.

The absence in Malay of different words for sister and brother, aunt and uncle, daughter and son forces the translators to add gender markers (*perempuan*, “female”/*laki-laki*, “male”) here and there, complicating for them the already challenging task of explaining the variety of Arabic kinship terms with the few Malay words at their disposal. However, as elsewhere throughout the vocabulary, the translators still tend to opt for (inaccurate) translations rather than lengthier explanations. The words for family members are followed by those describing other kinds of interpersonal relationships, e.g., lover, friend, enemy, competitor, neighbor, compatriot, and drinking companion.

From people the vocabulary moves to their everyday life, rich and poor, and the objects that play part in it. Starting from clothing, it proceeds to household textiles, furnishings, and jewelery, *al-hijāb* being placed not among veils and headscarves but among curtains and carpets (see Fig. 3 and 4).⁴⁰ Among the face and head covers the vocabulary lists *al-burqa‘*, translated as *tutup muka* (face cover); *al-niqāb*, *ikat muka* (face band); and *al-‘iṣāba* (head band, turban), translated as *ikat kepala* (head band), as well as three words for women’s veil—*al-khimār*, *al-miqna‘a*, and *al-qinā‘*—that are translated as *mahkota* (crown, headgear). Different types of textiles are also listed (taffeta, brocade, satin), for which the translators find no Malay equivalents and describe as *kain sutra* (silk cloth). The following sections of the noun chapter of the vocabulary (*jadwal al-ism*) deal with abstract nouns, colors, adjectives, numerals, and nouns related to quantity, the pattern of its arrangement gradually changing back from thematic to grammatical.

Next to nothing being known about the authors, audiences, and reasons for compiling *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab*, the vocabulary itself appears to be the only source to draw upon.

38 Ff. 29v–28r (1) and 39v–40v (2).

39 I am grateful to Fadhli Lukman for his insights regarding the matter.

40 Ff. 28r–27r (1) and 41r–41v (2).

The numerous misspellings and inaccurate translations of Arabic words seem to indicate that the wordlist was unlikely to have been written by native Arabic-speakers. As has been suggested by Van der Tuuk, albeit on other grounds, the compilers were apparently Malay (or still possibly Minangkabau?). The providing of as many synonyms as possible and the inclusion of some rather rare and infrequently used Arabic words leave an impression that this dictionary is not a pilgrim's wordbook aiming to build an active vocabulary for speaking Arabic, but rather an aid for a bookish learner of language, a reader and translator of Arabic texts. As reading and translating Islamic texts was the major method of teaching and learning Arabic in the Indonesian-Malay world at the time,⁴¹ the words constituting the dictionary might have been collected from these very texts. Grouping them thematically would facilitate memorization and shape a passive vocabulary allowing the student to recognize these words when encountered in another text of similar genre. The translators' frequent choices in favour of inaccurate single-word equivalents rather than explanatory translations apparently worked towards the same goal, as such words would be easier to insert into the resulting translated text in Malay.

Interlinear translations, which often accompany Arabic texts in manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world, tend to allow a considerable degree of exegesis: they are often rather interpretative and can be longer and more detailed than the source.⁴² In the Arabic-Malay vocabulary in question, this does not seem to be the case, its didactic encyclopaedism manifesting itself in the thematic arrangement but not in explaining the cultural and natural realities of the Middle East. This absence of cultural translation, in its modern understanding, can be alternatively described as cultural translation of a different kind: an approach that highlights not the differences between the Arabic heartlands and the Malay Archipelago but the unity and uniformity of the Islamic world. Replacing the unfamiliar with the familiar, the vocabulary brings the language of the scripture and texts written in it closer to Malay-speaking Muslims. Employing an interlinear layout for a dictionary, a work of a different genre than the narrative texts that were usually provided with translations below the line, encompasses *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-ʿArab* within the long tradition of interlinear translation from Arabic and reception of Arabic texts in the Indonesian-Malay world. The reasons why this layout was chosen might have to do with the modes of such texts' transmission—on which juxtaposing the two copies of the same vocabulary sheds some light.

Misspellings, Discrepancies, and Where They Come From

Comparing the copies of *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-ʿArab* at our disposal reveals divergences between the two—both in the Arabic and Malay parts of the text. However, these discrepancies are of a different nature: while the Arabic wordlists in the two manuscripts differ in terms of completeness and (mis)spelling, their Malay translations vary in content.

41 See Aglaia Iankovskaia, "Reading Arabic in Sumatra. Interlinear Translation in Didactic Contexts," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 52, no. 153 (2024): 221–242.

42 See Aglaia Iankovskaia, "Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje," *Archipel*, no. 106 (2023): 89–124.

Looking into the two versions of first Arabic and then Malay components of the bilingual text, that is the vocabulary, also seems to reveal that these two parts are not necessarily inseparable and they could have been transmitted at different times and in different ways.

The Arabic wordlists in the two copies mostly overlap (except for some missing sections and words); however, the spelling of words differs to a considerable extent. Both vocabularies contain misspellings, which sometimes make the Arabic words hardly recognizable. These misspellings appear to be distributed between the two manuscripts in relatively equal proportion: some words are spelled correctly in Or. 3233(2) and misspelled in Or. 3231(8), and vice versa. Indeed, the two versions of the vocabulary help a modern reader to decipher them both. Most of the misspellings appear to be of a graphical nature, e.g., letters of similar shapes are confused or dots misplaced, which apparently indicates that the manuscripts are not directly related and the wordlists in them have travelled different paths of corruption in the process of recopying. But it might have not only been recopying written texts that contributed to this corruption.

For instance, in the section dealing with clothes and textiles (see Fig. 3 and 4), there appears a confusing word spelled as *dāl-ḥā²-rā²-yā²-dād* in the first copy and *dāl-ḥā²-rā²-ṣād* in the second one, which can be read as *dahrīd* or possibly *dahrīṣ* (as the second copy provides no diacritics). Such a word does not seem to be found in dictionaries of Arabic, but its interlinear Malay translation appears to give a clue to what it might have originally been. Below the line, this word is translated as *suji baju* (shirt embroidery). Meanwhile there is an Arabic word for embroidery that could have sounded similarly to *dahrīṣ* to a non-native Arabic speaker, that is *taḥrīz*, as well as another word, *takhrīm*, that could have possibly transformed into *dahrīṣ* as a result of two stages of corruption, phonetical and graphical—the final *mīm* having been misinterpreted by a copyist as *ṣād*. If either of the two is the case, this seems to suggest that the history of reproduction of the text included both written and oral transmission, i.e., at different points in time the vocabulary might have been copied from a manuscript and written down by dictation.

In the Arabic lines of the vocabulary, such possible traces of oral transmission still appear to be rather scarce. The majority of misspellings are those a copyist could produce due to inattention or unclear handwriting in the earlier manuscript, while the scribe's relatively fine hand, especially in the second version, suggests that the wordlist was copied without much haste from a written source. This, however, does not seem to be the case for the interlinear Malay translation, which is in both cases scribbled between the lines in a less accurate manner and might have not been copied at the same time as the Arabic text. Besides the sloppiness of the handwriting, there is another feature pointing to the different life paths of the Arabic and Malay parts of the vocabulary. Although the Malay translations of the Arabic words in the two manuscripts are largely identical, they do not overlap entirely, and the differences do not seem to result from recopying. For example, the Arabic word *al-sundus* (taffeta, thin silk textile) is translated in the first version as *kain sutra yang nipis* (thin silk fabric) and in the second one as just *kain* (cloth, fabric); and *al-biṭāna* (lining) as *lapis baju* (shirt lining) and *luar baju* (outer layer of a shirt), respectively. The translation discrepancies found in sections dealing with animals and kinship terms have been already mentioned above.

Corrupted as it is, the Arabic wordlist in the vocabulary still appears to be a more stable part of the text than the Malay translations. The spelling differences between the two manuscripts seem to be unintentional and rather result from the multiple stages of thorough

but not flawless recopying by non-native Arabic speakers. The variety in translations, on the other hand, appears to be more voluntary, which might reflect the fluid character of interlinear translation as a practice and the role of an oral element in its transmission. These observations seem to correspond to the fluidity of interlinear translation as it manifests itself in other bilingual manuscripts from the Indonesian-Malay world and from Sumatra in particular.⁴³ The majority of such manuscripts contain Arabic texts that were part of traditional Islamic education in the region and used to be studied with a teacher whose oral remarks were scribbled by students between the lines of their copies. As a result of this practice, the Arabic source texts (*matn*) in these manuscripts tend to be less variable than their Malay or other interlinear translations. Providing that the Arabic-Malay vocabulary under discussion might have been once used in a similar study and transmission process, the translation differences between the two versions could result from a teacher's reinterpretation in the classroom or a student's hastiness in writing down the translations.

Page | 64

Yet the main text, i.e., the Arabic wordlist, was most likely copied from a written source before being brought to the classroom or study circle, its transmission might have also involved oral elements—to which the few phonetical misspellings in it seem to testify. Little is known about scribal practices of manuscript production and reproduction in 19th-century Sumatra, but there is some evidence scattered around the Indonesian-Malay region and across centuries. Dick van der Meij reports Merle Ricklefs' accounts of his observations in 1960s Yogyakarta, where production of a manuscript was a group activity “done with one person writing while singing the text, another (or others) singing along or singing from an original being copied, others joining in with comments and suggestions, and so on.” Checking the newly made copy also involved singing and working in pairs.⁴⁴ This latter practice of collating a copy with the original, one scribe reading the source manuscript aloud and another checking the text in the copy, is also mentioned as early as 1603 in a treatise composed in Aceh, i.e., Bukhari al-Jauhari's *Tāj al-salāṭīn*.⁴⁵

Commenting on Merle Ricklefs' observations in Java, Van der Meij notes that “this is very interesting information as it may have serious implications for the philological method. It is not that a scribe copies the text from a manuscript in front of him, and thus he or she does not necessarily use the same letters used in the exemplar. An oral layer lies between the exemplar and the copy.”⁴⁶ Such an “oral layer” could indeed explain some of the misspellings found in the two manuscripts of *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab*. Copying a manuscript was not always a group activity, but even as an individual one it could involve oral practices, e.g., the

43 See Aglaiia Iankovskaia, “On ‘Hanging Meaning’ and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh,” *Archipel*, no. 107 (2024): 119–138.

44 Dick van der Meij, *Indonesian Manuscripts from the Islands of Java, Madura, Bali and Lombok* (Brill, 2017), 22.

45 Vladimir I. Braginsky, “Malay Scribes on Their Craft and Audience (With Special Reference to the Description of the Reading Assembly by Safirin bin Usman Fadli),” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 30, no. 86 (2002): 37–38.

46 Van der Meij, *Indonesian Manuscripts from the Islands of Java*, 22.

scribe simultaneously reading the text aloud and committing it to writing: “the mouth is reading while the hand is writing.”⁴⁷

Juxtaposing the two copies of the Arabic-Malay vocabulary seems to demonstrate that they are not directly related, apparently stemming from some other copies that were circulating in the region at the time, and that they both contain traces of oral practices having been involved in their transmission. It seems also likely that the Arabic and Malay components of the text were not transmitted at the same time and in the same place—which the vocabulary’s interlinear layout might attest to. In Malay manuscript culture, interlinear translations were viewed as paratextual, optional elements rather than parts of the main text and were often added to the *matn* as a second layer. In many manuscripts, such translations are not complete and tend to end abruptly after the first few pages—as if the translator had given up the task, or rather only part of the text had been studied by a student with a teacher. Evidence of a similar treatment of lexicographical texts can be found in a manuscript of another Arabic-Malay vocabulary which Van der Tuuk cataloged in the collection of the Royal Asiatic Society after his visit to London in 1865:

An Arabic-Malay Dictionary. Under each Arabic word the corresponding Malay is written. The last seven pages are not filled up with the Malay. I possess a complete copy, and a fragment of another work of the same kind.⁴⁸

This manuscript is RAS Raffles Malay 75 (D) that is still housed in the library of the Royal Asiatic Society.⁴⁹ As has been noted both by Van der Tuuk and later catalogers,⁵⁰ its last pages are lacking Malay equivalents for the Arabic words (see Fig. 5). This possibly indicates that compilers of such vocabularies considered translation optional rather than an indispensable part of their treatises. In this light, the Arabic-Malay vocabulary discussed in this article should not be viewed as a dictionary in its usual sense, but rather as a wordlist provided with an interlinear translation. This is indeed how this text identifies itself in the title—“A *list* of Arabic words.”

Why Interlinear? In Lieu of a Conclusion

Repeatedly labeled by its European collector and later scholars and catalogers as a “dictionary” or “vocabulary,” *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* does not entirely correspond to the (relatively modern) idea of a bilingual lexicographical work comprising words in the source language and their explicit translations to the target one. Neither does it seem to be what it

47 Braginsky, “Malay Scribes on Their Craft,” 39–40.

48 Herman N. van der Tuuk, “Short Account of the Malay Manuscripts Belonging to the Royal Asiatic Society,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* 2, no. 1 (1866): 124.

49 A digital copy of this manuscript is available online at <https://royalasiaticcollections.org/raffles-malay-75-fragment-of-malay-laws/> (accessed on 4 May 2025)

50 See Merle C. Ricklefs, Petrus Voorhoeve, and Annabel T. Gallop, *Indonesian Manuscripts in Great Britain: A Catalogue of Manuscripts in Indonesian Languages in British Public Collections* (Ecole française d’Extrême-Orient, 2014), 142.

resembles to a modern reader at first sight: a personal notebook in which a student of a foreign language writes down words learned and to be learned in an endeavour to systematize their knowledge. The vocabulary in question lies in-between those familiar genres, or rather comprises a lexicographical work of its own genre inherent in the cultural milieu and historical period it comes from. Even if initially compiled by a Malay-speaking learner of Arabic for private use and without any audiences in mind, this text certainly had an afterlife as a teaching and learning aid somewhere in West Sumatra's Islamic schools and study circles. In this educational milieu, it was read, discussed, and recopied along with other Arabic texts used as teaching materials—which largely explains the misspellings and divergences found in the two manuscripts as well as why interlinear arrangement was employed for a dictionary.

Containing not an authoritative Arabic text but a list of words compiled to be learnt and translated, the vocabulary still appears to manifest a hierarchy between the two languages—the source and the target ones, Arabic and Malay—in its layout: the Arabic words are bigger, bolder, and written by finer hand, while their Malay equivalents are smaller and scribbled chaotically in the spaces remaining between the lines. Yet it seems to be not only a perceived superiority of the language of the Qur'an over a vernacular that is reflected in the vocabulary, a work otherwise striving for certain equivalence between two languages, but also a hierarchy of a different kind—that between the text and paratext, the “black lines” of the *matn* and the “white spaces,” i.e., interlinear ones, filled with translation or annotation.⁵¹ Engaged in the same practices of transmission and consumption as other texts in Arabic used in Islamic education in the Indonesian-Malay world, *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* was apparently considered to reside in the same categories as those other texts: its Arabic and Malay components were not considered equal and inseparable, but were treated as the main text and auxiliary, explanatory notes. And in accordance with this distinction, different methods of transmission seem to have been applied to each.

As I have attempted to demonstrate in this article, the history of reproduction of the two copies of the vocabulary likely included both written and oral transmission, i.e., at different points in time the text might have been copied directly from a manuscript and at others written down by dictation. Various misspellings and discrepancies found in the Leiden manuscripts stem, therefore, not only from visual misinterpretations of letters and slips of pen by the scribe, but also from the “oral layers” between a source manuscript and its copy. In the case of the Arabic wordlist, which was considered the main text and thus was likely recopied directly from written sources, such an oral layer is limited to a few misspellings resulting from writing down by ear. As for the Malay translation below the line, it fell within the category of notes written down by students following the teacher's explanations—a sort of paratext open to improvement and modification—and thus appears to have been shaped by oral transmission to a much greater extent. Despite Van der Tuuk's distrust of the spoken word, orality still found its way into the manuscripts he collected.

The Arabic-Malay vocabulary that came down to us thanks to the Dutch lexicographer's studies and travels in Sumatra offers many interesting perspectives for inquiry. This article

51 See Mulaika Hijjas, “Marks of Many Hands. Annotation in the Malay Manuscript Tradition and a Sufi Compendium from West Sumatra,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 45, no. 132 (2017): 246.

has only touched upon some of them. The two copies of the wordlist not only shed some light on the modes of such manuscripts' reproduction, but also reveal cultural and linguistic encounters within the Islamic world, i.e., between the Indonesian-Malay region and the Middle East—the encounters that unfold between the lines, in the interlinear spaces reserved for translation. Styled as a cosmography, attempting to describe the world around it in both the language of the scripture and the mother tongue, *al-Jadwal fī kalām al-‘Arab* provides an insight into the sociolinguistic microcosm of its compilers and their audiences, who likely belonged to the same Malay-speaking and Arabic-reading Islamic educational circles of 19th-century Sumatra.

References

- AZRA, Azyumardi. “Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia.” In *Sadur Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, edited by Henri Chambert-Loir. Gramedia, 2009.
- BRAGINSKY, Vladimir I. “Malay Scribes on Their Craft and Audience (With Special Reference to the Description of the Reading Assembly by Safirin bin Usman Fadli).” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 30, no. 86 (2002): 37–61.
- FERRI, Rolando. “The Greco-Roman World.” In *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography*, edited by John Considine. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- GRIJNS, Cornelis D. “Van der Tuuk and the Study of Malay.” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 152, no. 3 (1996): 353–381.
- GROENBOER, Kees. *Een vorst onder de taalgeleerden: Herman Neubronner van der Tuuk, taalafgevaardigde voor Indië van het Nederlandsch Bijbelgenootschap 1847–1873*. KITLV, 2002.
- HAYWOOD, John A. *Arabic Lexicography*. Brill, 1960.
- HIJAS, Mulaika. “Marks of Many Hands. Annotation in the Malay Manuscript Tradition and a Sufi Compendium from West Sumatra.” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 45, no. 132 (2017): 226–249.
- HOOGERVORST, Tom G. “Seventeenth-Century Malay Wordlists and Their Potential for Etymological Scholarship.” *Wacana* 25, no. 3 (2024): 531–575.
- IANKOVSKAIA, Aglaia. “Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje.” *Archipel*, no. 106 (2023): 89–124.
- . “On ‘Hanging Meaning’ and Its Transmission. Tracing a Didactic Poem from Aceh.” *Archipel*, no. 107 (2024): 119–138.
- . “Reading Arabic in Sumatra. Interlinear Translation in Didactic Contexts.” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 52, no. 153 (2024): 221–242.
- ISKANDAR, Teuku. *Catalogue of Malay, Minangkabau, and South Sumatran Manuscripts in the Netherlands*. Vol. 1. Documentatiebureau Islam-Christendom, 1999.
- KAPTEIN, Nico J.G. “Some Early Contributions to Arabic-Malay Lexicography: Sayyid ‘Uthmān of Batavia (1822-1913) as a Lexicographer.” In *Malay Images*. Edited by Asmah Haji Omar. UPSI, 2005.
- LAFFAN, Michael. “New Charts for the Arabic Ocean; Dictionaries as Indicators of Changing Times.” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 159, no. 2–3 (2003): 351–387.

- MAFTUHIN, Arif. "Translating the Untranslatable. The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice." *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 151 (2024): 279–303.
- MEIJ, Dick van der. *Indonesian Manuscripts from the Islands of Java, Madura, Bali and Lombok*. Brill, 2017.
- PLOMP, Marije. "Never-neverland Revisited: Malay Adventure Stories: With an Annotated Edition and Translation of the Malay Story of Bahram Syah." PhD Dissertation, Leiden University, 2014.
- RICCI, Ronit. "Reading Between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation." *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80.
- . "Mediating the Maulid. Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid syaraf al-anām* across the Indonesian-Malay World." *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143–164.
- RICKLEFS, Merle C., Petrus Voorhoeve, and Annabel T. Gallop. *Indonesian Manuscripts in Great Britain: A Catalogue of Manuscripts in Indonesian Languages in British Public Collections*. New edition with addenda et corrigenda. Ecole française d'Extrême-Orient, 2014.
- STACHOWSKI, Marek. "The Turkic Languages and Persian to c. 1700." In *The Cambridge World History of Lexicography*. Edited by John Considine. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- TEEUW, Andries. "Van der Tuuk as Lexicographer." *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996): 113–133.
- TUUK, Herman N. van der. "Iets over de Hoog-Maleische bijbelvertaling." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde*, no. 5 (1856): 171–83.
- . "Short Account of the Malay Manuscripts Belonging to the Royal Asiatic Society." *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* 2, no. 1 (1866): 85–135.
- . *Eene aanvulling der Maleische woordenboeken*. 's-Gravenhage: Nijhoff, 1894.
- VOORHOEVE, Petrus. "Indonesische handschriften in de Universiteitsbibliotheek te Leiden." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 108, no.3 (1952): 209–219.
- . *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands*. Leiden University Press, 1980.
- WIERINGA, Edwin P. *Catalogue of Malay and Minangkabau Manuscripts in the Library of Leiden University and Other Collections in the Netherlands*. Vol. 2. Leiden University Library, 2007.
- WILKINSON, Richard J. *A Malay-English Dictionary*. Kelly and Walsh, 1901.
- WITKAM, Jan Just. *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden*. Vol. 4. Ter Lugt Press, 2007.

Illustrations

Fig. 1 Leiden Or. 3231, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 45r-44v.

Fig. 2 Leiden Or. 3233, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 37v-38r

Fig. 3 Leiden Or. 3231, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 28r–27v.

Fig. 4 Leiden Or. 3233, Leiden University Libraries, ff. 40v–41r.

Interlinear Translation in Textual Performance: *The Usage of Swahili in Arabic Mawlid Readings from East Africa*

RAPHAEL MICHAELI (University of Bergen)

Abstract

The present article discusses oral interlinear translations from East Africa, using Arabic *mawlid* readings as a case study. Can we understand the use of Swahili interwoven into recitations of Arabic *mawlid* texts as a form of oral interlinear translation? Several different *mawlid* readings are performed in Lamu and Tana River, where my fieldwork was conducted. A common feature among all performances is dividing the reading event into parts based on the Arabic *mawlid* text and recitations of *qaṣīda* verses that do not appear in the Arabic *mawlid* narrative. This article will compare different ways Swahili is used in *mawlid* recitations and discuss whether these may be interpreted in some cases as oral interlinear translations. Furthermore, the article analyses the fluid interchange between Swahili and Arabic during these readings, emphasizing the variation between Arabic-to-Swahili translation and independent Swahili verses. The first part of the article will provide a background on the region, interlinear translations, and *mawlid* from the Swahili coast, and the second part will describe case study examples of Swahili *qaṣīda* verses and segments of Swahili translations of *mawlid* texts, which are used during the readings.

Keywords: Interlinear translations, Mawlid, Performance, Swahili, East Africa, Islam

Introduction

This article aims to contribute to the discourse on interlinear translation across the Muslim world, with a focus on the East African Islamic context. While interlinear translations commonly refer to bilingual or trilingual written texts that display a source text and its translation line by line, this article considers oral recitations as a source for analysis, viewing texts as utterances preserved for a purpose, whether written or oral.¹

Thus, in the recitations under consideration, the Arabic text and the Swahili *qaṣīda* verses (a religious rhymed poem) that are orally woven together during the readings are regarded as

¹ Karin Barber, *The Anthropology of Texts, Persons and Publics: Oral and Written Culture in Africa and Beyond* (Cambridge University Press, 2007), 2.

forming a single textual unit and viewed as a bilingual text consisting of Arabic and Swahili.² The Swahili case studies to be presented highlight overlapping themes from the Arabic written text that are accessible and understood by the local Swahili-speaking community, and can thus be seen as orally-interwoven translations. While some examples introduce a Swahili text based on its Arabic counterpart, others focus on topics and themes that appear in the mawlid text.

The sources for this article are mawlid recitations from the Kenyan coast, documented during several field trips between 2022 and 2025. These recitations are based on reading an Arabic mawlid text, divided into several sections (*fuṣūl*). Between the reading parts, Swahili *qaṣīda* verses and poems, which are not part of the text, are orally introduced. The main argument is that these Swahili textual units, absent from the written Arabic texts used in the readings, function as translations of the mawlid into Swahili, highlighting different aspects of the text. By studying these Swahili verses through an interlinear approach, we can identify the themes of the mawlid that are selected for oral translation by the groups performing.

Page | 74

Several instances of Swahili texts interwoven into Arabic-based mawlid recitations will be introduced. I suggest dividing the examples into two categories. The first category contains Swahili poems and phrases that provide translations of the meaning of the mawlid, emphasized by the performers. In this case, titles for each example will suggest the main subject addressed or engaged with through translation. The second category features Swahili translations of the mawlid language and metaphors. Some of these examples can be traced back to an Arabic source. Both categories demonstrate how Swahili is orally woven into the Arabic-based mawlid reading as a means of interpreting, commenting on, and translating the mawlid into Swahili. The article will open with an introduction to the region, and continue with depictions of the mawlid in the East African context as well as the place and role of the translator and scribe in the written Swahili textual tradition. In the second part, several examples of orally recited Swahili verses will be presented as case studies.

The Region

The Swahili Coast is a geographic region extending from Mogadishu in modern-day Somalia south to Sofala in Mozambique. Similar architectural styles, mosques, tombs, and cultural patterns dating back to the 10th century are found along this coastal area.³ The Swahili coast is part of a trade route that connected East Africa with the Middle East, the Arabian Peninsula, India, and Southeast Asia through the seasonal monsoon winds.⁴ This region served as the

2 Swahili religious poems are called *kasida* or *qaswida*, derived from the Arabic *qaṣīda*. In the Swahili context, *kasida* is a religious and devotional poem. See Abdulaziz, M. H., "The Influence of the Qasida on the Development of Swahili Rhymed and Metred Verse," in *Qasida Poetry in Islamic Asia and Africa*, ed. Stefan Sperl and Christopher Shackle (Brill, 1996), 413. In the present article the term *qaṣīda* is used, as well as poems or Swahili verses, to describe these religious textual segments.

3 Horton Mark and John Middleton, *The Swahili: The Social Landscape of a Mercantile Society* (Blackwell, 2000), 11; Horton Mark and Felix Chami, "Swahili Origins," in *The Swahili World*, ed. Stephanie Wynne-Jones and Adria LaViolette (Routledge, 2018), 135-146.

4 One of the earliest references to this geographical area as a trading centre appears in the *Periplus Maris*

cultural and economic connection of Africa to other parts of the world through the Indian Ocean to its east.⁵

In the northern part of the Swahili coast, within the current Kenyan nation-state, lies Lamu County, where most of the fieldwork for this article was conducted. It is the smallest county in Kenya, bordering Somalia to the north. Lamu is also the name of an archipelago consisting of three main islands (Lamu, Manda, and Pate) and two smaller islands (Ndau and Kiwayuu), all located very close to the Kenyan mainland. Finally, Lamu refers to one of these islands and to a town on that same island (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Lamu in the western Indian Ocean (based on data from OpenStreetMap contributors).

Historically, the Lamu archipelago was the trade and cultural center of the northern Swahili coast. Despite global changes in the region, local families in Lamu town kept a social hierarchy and structure of an elite group of patricians (Swahili: *wangwana*) and plantation owners, parallel to the involvement of officials of the Omani Zanzibar Sultanate, the Mazrui in Mombasa, and later the German and British protectorate.⁶ In the 19th century, Lamu was

Erythraeid (PME). See, Lionel Casson, *The Periplus Maris Erythraei: Text with Introduction and Commentary* (Princeton University Press, 1989).

5 Abdul Sharif, "Between Two Worlds: The Littoral Peoples of the Indian Ocean," in *The Global Worlds of the Swahili: Interfaces of Islam, Identity and Space in 19th and 20th Century East Africa*, ed. Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann (Lit Verlag, 2006), 15–30.

6 At the end of the 15th century the Portuguese entered the Indian Ocean trade and colonized the East African coast. Resistance is recorded from Pate at this time, and with the help of the Omanis the Portuguese were eventually pushed out by the end of the 17th century. Then followed the Omani Mazrui

a city-state well connected to the southern Zanzibari Sultanate and the Mombasa Mazrui. However, the northern Swahili area seemed to maintain its partial independence under foreign influence and was always an important hub for Swahili cultural and textual production.

The stratified social structures in Lamu changed at the beginning of the 20th century due to the rise of colonialism, the abolition of slavery, and the appearance of a new religious authority led by herbalist and scholar Habib Swaleh (1853–1935). Swaleh founded the Riyāḍa Mosque, which became a centre for Muslim religious and spiritual life.⁷ He was a revivalist of Islamic education who became the patron saint of Lamu. The establishment of the Riyāḍa Mosque was part of reconnecting with the Ḥadramī Bā-‘Alawī tradition as articulated by the Ḥadramī teacher ‘Alī Ḥibshī (d. 1333/1915) and the opening of Islamic education to slaves and former slaves who had previously been denied access to Islamic knowledge.⁸

South of Lamu lies the Tana River, which is also the name of a county in Kenya. Some of the mawlid readings used for analysis in this article were made in Kipini (see Fig. 2). On the riverbanks live the Pokomo, a Bantu-speaking group, which is divided into the “upper Pokomo” and “lower Pokomo” (the names correspond to the segments of the river) and is further divided into sub-areas.⁹

occupation during the 17th and 18th centuries, which was centred around Mombasa and Lamu as part of the first Omani entrance to East Africa. In 1840, the Omani Bu-sa‘idi dynasty moved their sultanate from Oman to Zanzibar. By the end of the 19th century, the British protectorate and German East Africa gained power in the region which lasted until the independence of Kenya and Tanzania. See, Randall L. Pouwels, *Horn and Crescent: Cultural Change and Traditional Islam on the East African Coast, 800–1900*, African Studies Series, no. 53 (Cambridge University Press, 1987); Patricia W. Romero, *Lamu: History, Society, and Family in an East African Port City* (Markus Wiener Publishers, 1997); Clélia Coret, “Runaway Slaves and the Aftermath of Slavery on the Swahili Coast: New Perspectives from Witu in the 19th Century,” *Journal of Global Slavery* 6 (2021): 275–313.

- 7 For the digitized manuscript collection of the mosque library see, Endangered Archives Programme. EAP466: Digitisation of Islamic Manuscripts of Kenya. British Library. <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP466>.
- 8 Pouwels, *Horn and Crescent*, 199; Romero, *Lamu: History, Society*, 168-172; Anne K. Bang, *Sufis and Scholars of the Sea: Family Networks in East Africa, 1860–1925* (Routledge Curzon, 2003), 150-151. The first Riyāḍa mosque was established by ‘Alī Ḥibshī in Say’ūn, then the Lamu Riyāḍa mosque was founded as an offshoot with a link to ‘Alī Ḥibshī’s teachings and later, in 1916 a third Riyāḍa mosque was founded in Solo, Java. In all of these mosques the same *mawlid* text, written by ‘Alī Ḥibshī, is recited until today.
- 9 Derek Nurse and Thomas J. Hinnebusch, *Swahili and Sabaki: A Linguistic History* (University of California Press, 1993), 16.

Fig. 2 The Lamu Archipelago and Kipini (based on data from OpenStreetMap contributors).

Umar Dimah (1906-2006?), who according to various informants and accounts worked in the household of Habib Swaleh, the saint and founder of the Riyāḍa mosque in Lamu, was among the teachers who introduced Islamic practices in the Tana River region at the beginning of the 20th century.¹⁰ The spread of Islam along the Tana River by Umar Dimah and his companions was not free of tension. Several accounts indicate that the introduction of Islamic principles caused conflicts with the local Pokomo practices led by the elders. Islam was introduced at the start of the 20th century along the river and challenged local norms.¹¹

Mawlid in the East African Context

Mawlid is a text and an Islamic social event that has been practiced on the coast since at least the 18th century, and likely earlier.¹² In Swahili, it is referred to as a reading (*kusoma mawliidi*), and sometimes as a religious service, and is considered part of Islamic practice in the region, distinctive from other performative traditions found on the Swahili coast.¹³

¹⁰ Robert Bunge, *Islamization Among the Upper Pokomo* (Syracuse University Press, 1979), 52; Ali Kalindi Saidi, *Challenges Facing the Madrasa Institutions in the Teaching of Islamic Religious Education: A Case Study of Galole Constituency of Tana River County* (MA Thesis, Nairobi University, 2016), 47.

¹¹ Bunge, *Islamization*, 50-57.

¹² *Mawlid* manuscripts found in Pate from the end of the 18th century clearly show that the text was used in the region. Hamburg Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures, MPRINT-LAMU-PATE-005.

¹³ Jan Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 3rd ed. (Brill, 1971), 278. The same reference to *mawlid* as a reading is also applied in Zanzibar, the Comoro and Mayotte, see Michael Lambek, “The Ludic Side of Islam in Mayotte,” in *The Global Worlds of the Swahili: Interfaces of Islam, Identity and Space in 19th*

The text describes the birth of the Prophet and is used in social gatherings where participants actively perform a panegyric to the Prophet.¹⁴ The praise performed is believed to be a positive act that brings blessings upon the one who praises, a belief based on different traditions and sayings but mainly on the Quranic verse (33:56), which is recited in every mawlid reading:

ان الله وملائكته يصلون على النبي يا أيها الذين امنوا صلوا عليه وسلموا تسليما

God and his angels bless the Prophet - so, you who believe, bless him too and give him greetings of peace¹⁵

Social gatherings where the mawlid text is recited can take place at any time but are mainly recognized for celebrating the presumed birth of the Prophet on the 12th day of *Rabīʿ al-Awwal*. Muslim scholars wrote mawlid texts, and some versions, more than others, were widely translated or inspired additional mawlid versions written in Arabic, Swahili, Persian, Urdu, Turkish, Malay, and Javanese.¹⁶

Mawlid texts describe the birth of the Prophet and the emergence of Islam, including particular “episodes” taken from Prophetic *ḥadīth* and *sīra nabawiyya* accounts, some of which are regarded as more reliable than others.¹⁷ During mawlid events in East Africa, the Quran is recited, alms are given in the form of food, the Prophet is praised, and *duʿāʾ* prayers (religious supplications) are articulated. The mawlid text draws from several Islamic textual traditions, and the event itself is rooted in various Islamic practices.

Many reading events in East Africa (but not all) end with the *qiyām*. This is the moment when the birth of the Prophet is indicated, or an alternative explanation is that it is the moment when the Prophet participates in the reading in some way, and the participants stand up to

and 20th Century East Africa, ed. Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann (Lit Verlag, 2006), 161–86; Hanni Nuotio, “The Dance That Is Not Danced, the Song That Is Not Sung: Zanzibari Women in the Maulidi Ritual,” in *The Global Worlds of the Swahili*, ed. Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann, 187–208, 198; Aīsha Schmitt, “Nyoyo Zimefurahika: Urban Qasida in Zanzibar” (PhD Dissertation, SOAS University of London, 2012).

14 Some *mawlid* texts and events also describe and commemorate the birth (or death) of other individuals and saints such as the *mawlid* of ‘Abd al-Qādir al-Jaylānī (d. 561/1166). In his pioneering study of *mawlid* in Egypt J.W. McPherson describes *mawlid* events dedicated to different saints, see Joseph Williams McPherson, *The Mawlid of Egypt: Egyptian Saints-Days*, ed. Russell McGuirk, foreword by Valerie J. Hoffman (Ginkgo Library, 2023; originally written 1941). In the present article *mawlid* is referred to in the context of *mawlid al-Nabī* (the birth of the Prophet).

15 M. A. S. Abdel Haleem, *The Qur’an: A New Translation*, Oxford World’s Classics (Oxford University Press, 2005).

16 Marion Holmes Katz, *The Birth of the Prophet Muḥammad: Devotional Piety in Sunni Islam* (Routledge, 2007); Sigrid Kleinmichel, *Die Geburt des Propheten Muhammad: Drei Dichtungen aus Mittelasien* (Reichert Verlag, 2009); Ronit Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the Maulid Sharaf al-Anām Across the Indonesian-Malay World,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143-164.

17 Katz, *The Birth of the Prophet*, 6-61.

honor him.¹⁸ The *qiyām*, as a practice of standing at a particular point during the ritual, is normally observed in East Africa.

Mawlid is a retelling of the story of the birth of the Prophet, seen as a pivotal moment of cosmic transition from darkness to light with the appearance of Islam. In this frame narrative, prayers and praises for the Prophet are extensively intertwined, creating a text that functions as a prayer manual used by a group, as a group reading through the text follows a sequence of prayers. In the East African context, mawlid was intended to strengthen the faith of the community and teach about the life of the Prophet. At the same time, it served as a call to conversion and a way to reach out to and incorporate newcomers into the community, as evidenced by the involvement of former slaves and slaves in the practice.¹⁹

Fig. 3 A group from Tana River performing mawlid. October 2022, Lamu. Photograph by the author.

Several different mawlid readings are held in Lamu and Tana River today. A common feature among all performances is the division of the oral reading event into sections based on the

¹⁸ As a result of this understanding *mawlid* practice and specifically the standing up in the moment of the *qiyām* has been a controversial issue among Muslim communities. See Nico Kaptein, “The Berdiri Mawlid Issue among Indonesian Muslims in the Period from circa 1875 to 1930,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 149, no. 1 (1993): 124–53; Marion Holmes Katz, “Women’s ‘Mawlid’ Performances in Sanaa and the Construction of Yemeni National Identity,” *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 40, no. 4 (2008): 589–614.

¹⁹ Pouwels, *Horn and Crescent*, 196.

Arabic mawlid text and recitations of *qaṣīda* poems that are not part of the Arabic mawlid sequence. These can be in Swahili and/or Arabic. As the mawlid text is divided into several sections, a *qaṣīda* is introduced orally after each one. In some readings, six or eight *qaṣīda* poems are added, and in others, twenty or more. While the mawlid texts used for this article are mostly read in Arabic, the *qaṣīda* verses in these reading events are in Swahili. In these cases Arabic and Swahili alternate during the mawlid performance, creating a bilingual mawlid reading. In a similar manner to texts written in an interlinear format, a clear relationship between the languages is also emphasized here, as Arabic is used for the text recitations and Swahili for the *qaṣīda* verses, which I will argue based on the following example act to some extent as techniques of translating the mawlid into Swahili.

Fig. 4 Stretching the skin of the matari, tambourine during mawlid. October 2022, Lamu. Photograph by the author.

Three different Arabic mawlid versions serve as a frame for different mawlid readings. Some groups use the same text in different ways. These texts are *Mawlid Daybaʿ*, written by the Yemeni scholar from Zabīd, Ibn Daybaʿ (d.944/1537); *Mawlid Barzanjī*, written by the famous Shafīʿī mufti of Medina, Jaʿfar al-Barzanjī (d.1177/1764); and *Mawlid Simṭ al-Durar*, written by ʿAlī Ḥibshī, a revivalist of Islamic studies in Ḥaḍramawt and the founder of the Riyāḍa mosque and *madrassa* in Sayʿūn. All the performances are divided into reading the Arabic text and reciting devotional poems that are not part of the original text. Percussionists accompany the recitation of the poems with several rhythms played simultaneously, and while one reciter performs the reading of the text, all participants recite the *qaṣīda* poems, reflecting the transition from listening to participating. During the *qaṣīda* recitations, participants add movements while chanting the *qaṣīda* verses.²⁰ Mawlid readings can last from about an hour and a half up to six hours.

When I first compared oral mawlid readings with the Arabic text, I did not pay much attention to the Swahili parts that were interwoven in it, as I was mainly focused on the Arabic sections. It was only later—partly thanks to the workshop on interlinear translation across the Muslim world,

²⁰ For an example of the entrance *qaṣīda* poem recited by the group from Kipini see Ramiya wetu Group, “Firka ya Tanariver Maulidi ya Rama (Kiswahili) – Kipini,” YouTube video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a6alGvciWU8>. Posted June 2, 2022. For a longer reading example, based on *Barzanjī* and also from Tana River, see “Mawlid ya Rama Yakiongozwa na wazee kutoka Tana River,” YouTube video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A4cEPiitQBs&t=4641>. Streamed live November 11, 2023.

which this special issue is based on—that I realized some of these fragments are, in fact, interesting and intriguing textual indications. After listening to the recordings I made I was able to identify some of the Swahili poems in the work of Harries, Boyd, and Knappert.²¹

The subjects of these *qaṣīda* poems within the Arabic mawlid readings vary. Some are fragments of poetry, and others are translations of the mawlid narrative from past centuries. Different textual additions are introduced into the oral reading and inserted between the Arabic text recitations, creating a new oral textual compilation that combines Arabic and Swahili. The Swahili verses offer participants a straightforward way to engage in the reading ritual and articulate complex ideas from the Arabic text.

Before presenting Swahili examples, I will address a textual interlinear mawlid, which presents an abridged Arabic mawlid sequence with a Swahili rendering. From this point, we can consider the role of the translator within the Swahili context.

Translating from Arabic to Swahili

Swahili literature from the 17th to the 19th centuries reflects the hybridization of Arabic and Swahili, and comprise the earliest Arabic/Swahili textual evidence from the region.²² Many of these texts are poems and devotional Islamic liturgical texts intended for oral recitation and communal use. The *Hamziyya*, a praise poem to the Prophet Muhammad in which each verse ends with the letter *hamza* (from here the name *Hamziyya*) exemplifies this meeting point of Swahili and Arabic and introduces one of the earliest interlinear translations from the region. The *Hamziyya* is an Arabic *qaṣīda*, also known as *Umm al-qurā* (the mother of the cities), written by al-Būṣīrī (d.696/1294). The text was translated into Swahili in an interlinear format, with the Swahili verse placed under the Arabic, and it was composed in a Swahili poetic structure and meter.²³ This is one example of how “Islamic terms, concepts, and practices were adapted, versified, and “Swahilized.”²⁴ The next example has undergone a similar translation process.

21 Lyndon Harries, *Swahili Poetry* (Clarendon Press, 1962); Alan Boyd, “To Praise the Prophet: A Processual Symbolic Analysis of ‘Mawlid’, a Muslim Ritual in Lamu, Kenya” (PhD Dissertation, Indiana University, 1980); Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*.

22 Annachiara Raia, “Swahili Palimpsests: The Muslim Stories Beneath Swahili Compositions,” *Swahili Forum* 25 (2018): 16–41; Nicholas Mainey Brown, “Swahili Poetry, Classical Tradition,” in *Encyclopedia of African Religions and Philosophy* (Springer Netherlands, 2021), 650–653.

23 It was rendered to Swahili in several different manuscript formats, see Ahmed Hussein Parker, “Manuscripts and Transmission of Knowledge in Swahili Society: A Comparative Analysis of Form and Usage of *Qaṣīda al-Hamziyya*” (PhD Dissertation, University of Hamburg, 2019), 55, 112–114.

24 Annachiara Raia, “Prayers Uttered Down on Paper: A Stylistic Analysis of Swahili Devotional Lyrics,” *Journal for Islamic Studies* 38, no. 2 (2020): 102–40, 109.

A Swahili/Arabic Interlinear Mawlid

In what follows, I will describe a written interlinear mawlid translation. As the Arabic manuscript title states, *hadhā kitāb mawlūd al-musammā al-Kawkab al-Duriyya al-mufassar bi-al-Sawāhiliyya* (this is a mawlid text titled *The Radiating Star* explained in Swahili). It is an interlinear, abridged translation of the versified mawlid composed by Zayn al-‘Ābidīn (d.1317/1899). al-‘Ābidīn composed his mawlid version based on *mawlid Barzanjī*, written by Ja‘far al-Barzanjī. The manuscript is written in both Swahili and Arabic, using Arabic script (*Ajami*), line under line. The scribe explains in the opening section how mawlid should be translated and conducted. This explanation gives us a sense of how mawlid was practiced in the late 19th century in the region and how translations were undertaken in the Swahili context.

The Journey of the Text

The manuscript under discussion was written by the renowned scholar Sharifu Mansab (d.1922) from Lamu and is dated 1891. Several references can be found for this source, which is preserved and digitized by the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin under the title *Kitabu Mauludi*.²⁵ It was translated into German by Gustav Neuhaus in 1935, into English in 1962 by Lyndon Harries, and later again in 1971 by Knappert, who used three manuscripts of the text, of which only the Mansab version is reported to have been a bilingual interlinear text.²⁶ The other two only included the Swahili version. Neuhaus translated the Arabic and the Swahili into German, creating a trilingual translation serving scholarly interest in Swahili in Germany.

Neither Neuhaus nor Harries or Knappert seemed to pay special attention to the fact that Sharifu Mansab created his mawlid text in an interlinear format. Still, Neuhaus noted the different languages that appear in the manuscript and chose to translate each part separately into German: the Arabic and the Swahili. The German translations he provided for the Swahili and Arabic differ, which means he did notice differences between the versions. Additionally, Neuhaus offered a poetic adaptation (*Umdichtung*) of the mawlid into German, making it the first (and possibly only) mawlid text rendered into German to date. Although the work of Neuhaus is very precise, his lack of addressing the interlinear dimension of the text resonates with questions raised by Ricci about the limited attention paid to the interlinear model.²⁷ In 1962, Harries, and later Knappert in 1971, focused solely on the Swahili sections of the same manuscript, ignoring the Arabic and the modality of the text.

The Radiating Star discussed here was created at the request of the German colonial explorer Gustav Denhardt (d. 1917) from Sharifu Mansab, and was made for German scholarly interest in Swahili, as it was intended to be published as part of a Swahili *Ajami* compilation translated into German.²⁸ It was probably created in its original form for the German

25 *Kitabu Mauludi*, Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, https://digital-beta.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/werkansicht?PPN=PPN78882564X&PHYSID=PHYS_0005&DMDID=.

26 Gustav Neuhaus, “Kitabu Mauludi, Buch der Geburt Muhammed’s,” *MSOS* 38 (1935): 145–201; Harries, *Swahili Poetry*, 105–118; Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 276–311.

27 Ricci in the present issue.

28 It was intended to be a part of the publication of Büttner *Suaheli Schriftstücke in Arabischer Schrift*

public so it could learn how mawlid should be properly conducted and, as will be shown below, see how the text can be organized in different layout formats.²⁹

The Role of Translator in the Swahili Context

I will translate for you into the Lamu language.³⁰

Many Swahili translations and texts based on Arabic works begin with an introduction by the scribe explaining that he is presenting the text in Swahili or the language of Amu (an old name for Lamu), as many people do not understand Arabic. This seems to be a common pattern in several mawlid translations and other texts that moved from Arabic to Swahili, offering a clear reason for the translation.³¹

The scribe in the manuscript under discussion states (in Swahili) at the beginning of the text that he will now introduce the mawlid in Swahili. The Swahili verse in transliteration is – *Sasa tutangia kufasiri ngwatu'awini*. The Swahili verb *kufasiri* is based on the Arabic term *tafsīr*.³² The same term is also used in the Arabic title of the text (*al-Mufassar bi-al-Sawāḥilī*), indicating that this text is rendered in Swahili. While Neuhaus used the term “explanation” (*Erklärung*) in his German translation from 1935, Knappert and Harries used the term “translation” in their English version.³³ It is interesting to see how, in their work, Knappert, Harries, and Neuhaus had different understandings of this term and of the work Sharifu Mansab created. But how did Swahili translators view their work and effort?

The Arabic word *tafsīr* can be translated as exegesis, interpretation, or commentary, as in *tafsīr al-Quran* (Quranic commentary) or *Tafsīr al-Jalālayn* (a Quranic commentary produced by the two Jalāl).³⁴ While *tafsīr* (commentary) can also be viewed as a type of trans-

(Swahili texts in Arabic script) published in 1892, none of which is written in an interlinear format. See Carl Gustav Büttner, *Suaheli Schriftstücke in Arabischer Schrift* (Stuttgart and Berlin: W. Spemann, 1892). The account of the journey of this manuscript can be found in Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 148, and in Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 276-77.

29 Gori discusses how manuscript collections were compiled and at times influenced by colonialism in this process. See Alessandro Gori, “Some Observations on Composite and Multiple-Text Manuscripts in the Islamic Tradition of the Horn of Africa,” in *One-Volume Libraries: Composite and Multiple-Text Manuscripts*, ed. Michael Friedrich and Cosima Schwarke (De Gruyter, 2016), 155–69.

30 Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 279.

31 Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 279, 315; Raia, “Swahili Palimpsests”, 16; Parker, *Manuscripts and Transmission of Knowledge*, 217-218. This tendency seems to have moved into early Swahili print, Annachiara Raia, “Transoceanic Print Histories: Twentieth-Century Swahili Muslim Networks in the Indian Ocean,” *Islamic Africa* 14 (2023) 55-78, 61.

32 Swahili *ajami* - سَاسٌ يُبَغِّى كُفَسِرَ غَتُّ عَوْنِ

33 Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 154, verse 14; Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 283, verse 19a; Harries, *Swahili Poetry*, 105; In another instance, Neuhaus translated the Arabic term *tawdīh*, explanation as *Erklärung*. See, Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 194, r.6. Here it is the transliteration of an Arabic sidenote from Tafel 4a.

34 The term *Jalālayn* refers to the two Egyptian authors, Jalāl al-Dīn al-Maḥallī (d.864/1459) and his student Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī (d.911/1505) who composed the famous Quranic exegesis known as *Tafsīr al-Jalālayn*.

lation, it does not mean a word-for-word translation.³⁵ In the context of Swahili poetry and literature, Raia argues that the term should be understood as a “literary relationship which is created through appropriating the Arabic source text and reformulating it into a new Swahili poetic genre and register.”³⁶ In the present case, as described by Raia, it appears that the scribe considers himself the one who explains the meaning of the mawlid and translates its content into Swahili. He is “a copyist, an adapter, a quoter, an editor and a commentator of the work.”³⁷

Reflecting on the broad role the scribe plays, Mansab opened the manuscript with two beautiful Arabic verses from the *Hamziyya* poem, accompanied by an interlinear Swahili translation. These Arabic verses depict the craft of creating poetry and translations in the eyes of the scribe (see Fig. 5).

From the craft of poetry, he wove a cloak for you / which the weavers from Sana could not weave / its verses fit together shining brighter than pearls and / neither the talented nor the untalented could create a similar harmony.³⁸

Page | 84

These verses depict the craft of writing poetry by likening it to weaving a cloak, which shines brighter than pearls. The last verse in the Swahili version is translated from Arabic as “*fikrani mbili: haziki na jenga yamo.*” It suggests a somewhat different meaning than the original Arabic, and can be translated as “two thoughts, destruction and construction, lie within it.”³⁹ It appears that Sharifu Mansab used the earlier translation of the *Hamziyya* into Swahili which also presents a similar translation of the Arabic verse.⁴⁰

With this interpretation of the Arabic, the verse receives an additional meaning, suggesting that in the process of poetry creation, an element of destruction and construction takes place. While the Arabic verse implies that no one can create a similar poem, the Swahili

35 Arif Maftuhin, “Translating the Untranslatable,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 151 (2023): 279–303.

36 Raia, “Swahili Palimpsests,” 17.

37 Raia, “Swahili Palimpsests,” 24. Related to this, Vierke questions whether Swahili poetry should be regarded as imitations or authentic creations, see Clarissa Vierke, “Poetic Links Across the Ocean: On Poetic ‘Translation’ as Mimetic Practice at the Swahili Coast,” *Comparative Studies of South Asia, Africa, and the Middle East* 37, no. 2 (2017): 321–35, 329.

38 This translation from the Arabic is mine. For the full Arabic version see Al-Būṣīrī, *al-Hamziyya*, in *Majmū‘ al-Mutun al-Kabīr* (Maṭba‘at al-Istiḳāma, 1958), 93. حاك من صنعة القريض بوردا لك / لم تحك وشيها / صنعاء / اعجز الدر نظمه فاستوت / فيه اليدان الصناع والخرقاء

39 For the German translation see “Zwei Gedanken liegen darin: *Zerstörung und Wiederaufbau.*” Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 151. Parker translated the Swahili from the *Hamziyya* as “There are two types of personality: the clever and the foolish.” Parker, *Manuscripts and Transmission of Knowledge*, 297. And Olali seems to provide a translation based on the Arabic, “...there is no single known artist who has the ability to compose such a magnificent piece of work like the *Hamziyyah.*” Tom Olali, *Performing Arts in Lamu Maulidi Festival* (LAP Lambert, 2012), 516. Parker and Olali do not seem to notice the difference meaning between the Arabic and Swahili.

40 It seems like the scribe uses here the ‘Aydārūs translation from the mid 18th century. Parker, *Manuscripts and Transmission of Knowledge*, 297.

translations suggests a different meaning and could hint at the way the scribe or translator views his role.⁴¹ It is as if in the act of translating the Swahili translator reconstructs the rhymes and structure into the Swahili format and context. In this sense, the Swahili translator creates a new poetic form through a process that also implies destruction.

A similar approach can be seen in the following verse that appears at the beginning of another version of the same mawlid translation. "...I will translate for you into the Lamu language, for those who are like me; that we may know the qualities of the Prophet, we too, non-Arabs; When the two Barzanjis achieve a crown, let me be there too."⁴² Here, the scribe sees his role as the one who unites the two mawlid versions of Barzanjī for the Swahili audience, positioning himself at the centre of the new textual production.

The Radiating Star: A Textual Description

Following the title page and the verse from the *Hamziyya*, an Arabic blessing opens the text without a translation, followed by a Swahili-versified explanation of how to begin the mawlid recitation. The scribe states that the first step is to recite the first sura of the Quran, then the ninety-nine names of Allah.⁴³ In the margin of the same opening page, the scribe notes that reciting these names prepares participants for prayer and strengthens their hearts, as transmitted by Tirmidhī *ṣaḥ*.⁴⁴

Then, the scribe introduces the ninety-nine names of God, followed by a *du‘ā’* in Arabic and an introduction to the text in versified Swahili. Here, the scribe continues explaining in Swahili how the mawlid should be observed. He mentions that Muḥaffar al-Dīn, the ruler of Erbil, popularized the mawlid while spending 300,000 dinars on the reading he conducted.⁴⁵ He continues by listing the positive effects of mawlid in this life and in the afterlife, then provides additional practical instructions.

First, choose a nice place for the reading, light a lamp for the people who join, put on your best garment, and light incense. Then, recite the *fātiḥa* for the participants, followed by the names of God. Don't forget to add *Jala jalaluhu* (Exalted is His Glory) after each name. This is how you should do it. Donate some sweets and perfume. And all this you should do with the intention of honoring the birth of the Prophet.⁴⁶

41 For the explanation of the Arabic verse see, Sidi Ibn ‘Aḥḥāba al-Ḥasanī, *al-Anwār al-Qudsiyya fī Sharḥ al-Qaṣīda al-Hamziyya* (Dār al-Kutub al-‘Ilmiyya, 2013), 424.

42 Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 279.

43 *Kitabu Mauludi*, Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, fol, 1v.

44 See *Kitabu Mauludi*, Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, fol, 1v; Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 152, tafel 1a. Tirmidhī is the name of an early *ḥadīth* collector and the term *ṣaḥ* indicates it is a reliable transmission.

45 Muḥaffar is the name associated with the earliest *mawlid* events recorded in the Sunni Muslim world which took place in Erbil in the 13th century. See Aḥmad ibn Muḥammad Ibn Khallikān, *Wafayāt al-a‘yān wa-Anbā’ Abnā’ al-Zamān*, ed. Iḥsān ‘Abbās (Dār al-Thaqāfa, n.d.), 4:117-19; Katz, *The Birth of the Prophet*, 2.

46 My translation based on the German version, see Neuhaus, *Kitabu Mauludi*, 153-154; cf. Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 279-283.

The Swahili opening verses are divided into two lines written in red and two written in black. When the Arabic abridged mawlid text begins, the Swahili verses appear beneath the Arabic. Here, the Arabic is written in red, and the Swahili in black.⁴⁷

Interestingly, the scribe alters the structure and layout of the text throughout the manuscript, seemingly introducing different writing styles for the German scholarly audience the text was initially intended for. The Arabic is first written in two straight lines; later, it shifts to one verse on the right side of the page and the other beneath on the left. Eventually, the Arabic verses are written in the middle of the page, on top of each other, followed by the Swahili translation underneath in two straight lines (see Fig. 6). The four-verse format of the text is typical of the Swahili *ukawafi* genre, a genre of poetry believed to have mystical powers.⁴⁸ The scribe modifies the format of the Arabic verses while the Swahili remains unchanged.

Fig. 5 *Kitabu Mauludi*. The opening page and Hamziyya verse, fol. 1r. Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin.

47 In some places also green and violet are used for decoration, see Fig. 5 and 7.

48 Clarissa Vierke, “Of Patience and Pity: Rewriting and Reciting the Widely Travelled Islamic Poem ‘The Hawk and the Dove’ in East Africa,” *Islamic Africa*, no. 14 (2023): 5–41, 23.

Fig. 6 *Kitabu Mauludi*. Arabic red and Swahili black. From right to left: fol. 3v., fol. 4v., fol. 5r. Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin.

The *qiyām* (the indication in the text marking the birth of the Prophet) is given a special decorated page (Fig. 7), followed by the *qaṣīda* — *Ashraqa al-badr ‘alaynā* (The full moon has risen upon us) with a Swahili translation beneath each line. After the *qaṣīda* the text continues in the latest format until the end of the mawlid. On the last page a Swahili versified ending appears, followed by an Arabic *du‘ā* with no translation.

Fig. 7 *Kitabu Mauludi*. The *qiyām*, fol. 6v. Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin.

It seems that the instructions of Mansab in the interlinear mawlid manuscript from 1891 remain relevant for performances today, even though additional changes have been made during the second half of the 20th century, such as the use of microphones, cameras, and later cell phones and livestream. The principles explained by Mansab—the preparation of the space, the alms, Quranic recitation, and the overall intention—are still applicable as they highlight the essence and purpose of the performative act. The place and role of the Swahili translator, as seen from this brief discussion, can also be observed in the mawlid readings and through the Swahili *qaṣīda*, which is orally interwoven into the text.

Oral Recitations, Swahili in between the Lines of the Mawlid

The following section is divided into two parts: the first introduces examples of Swahili usage as a tool for translating the meaning and function of the text, and the second presents various examples of Swahili verses based on the Arabic structure and metaphors, as well as translations of mawlid texts. Both parts are based on recordings made during three mawlid seasons in Lamu and Kipini in October 2022, October-November 2023, and September-October 2024.⁴⁹

Umar Dimah and the Spread of Islam to the Tana River

The first poem to be discussed is one performed by a group from Tana River dedicated to praising their teacher, Umar Dimah. According to several accounts, once Habib Swaleh, the saint and teacher from Lamu, noticed that Umar Dimah had learned Islamic principles and ethics solely by watching and listening to classes he did not directly attend and while working in the household, Habib Swaleh decided to send him back home to Tana River with books, as a qualified teacher, so he could teach there and spread Islamic knowledge among the Pokomo.⁵⁰

This anecdote and the following poem illustrate the reforms and religious revival that Habib Swaleh introduced to Lamu, showing how Islam spread south. This process aligns with the opening of Islamic education and of the Riyāḍa mosque, recognizing those whom the ruling families of Lamu marginalized during the 19th century.⁵¹

Translation:⁵²

49 All translations are mine unless stated otherwise.

50 This anecdote was narrated to me by several informants and is partly described by Bunge, *Islamization*, 53–54; and Kalindi, *Challenges Facing the Madrassa*, 47.

51 Romero, *Lamu: History, Society*, 168–172.

52 I thank Khaulah Abdulkadir, Mwanaharusi Salim and Mohamed Aidarus Noor for their help with the translation of the poem in to English. Part of the poem can be followed on YouTube. Mawlid ya Rama, Markaz Swalihina Kisauni, YouTube video, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sexKZT6RQUc>. See, (5:04:10). Streamed live October 26, 2024.

Umar Dimah – Umar Dimah / Mola amueke pema - Umar Dimah / Pamoya na wake wendani – Waliosimamia Dini / Katika jimbo la mtoni – (bwana) Umar Dimah / Kutaja hatutowata Majina Kumina sita / Dini waloifuata – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Wao ni/na vijana wao – Walofuata nyayo zao / Dini kuiendea mbio – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Wa kwanza Haji Ali – Mwenye sifa za Ali / Kwenye vita hakimbli

Umar Dimah – Umar Dimah,
 God bless him – Umar Dimah,
 Together with his companions – who spread the religion,
 In the region of Mtoni river – bwana Umar Dimah,⁵³
 We will not stop – mentioning sixteen names,
 Who followed the religion – bwana Umar Dimah,
 They and their descendants – who followed in their footsteps,
 They turned to the religion – bwana Umar Dimah,
 The first is Haji Ali – who has the qualities of Ali,
 Not evading conflict and war – bwana Umar Dimah,
 And the second is Saidi Omari – Khatib of the mosque,
 He was always content – bwana Umar Dimah,
 Mjuja is the third – Good behavior and compassion are his virtues,
 Not taking anything from others – bwana Umar Dimah,
 Galola Hamisa is number four – he called people to prayer,
 In Masikiti Masalani – bwana Umar Dimah,
 The fifth is the teacher Awadha Dololo – Who taught in Milalulu,
 Know all that – Umar Dimah,
 Number six was Hirbai Jilo – Who was sitting in Majengo,
 Promoting the religion – bwana Umar Dimah,
 Number seven was the teacher Papuya – Who promoted the religion,⁵⁴

The poem continues to praise 16 teachers who transmitted Islamic knowledge to the Tana River region. It describes how Islam spread in the nearby county along the river through these teachers, who are also depicted as heroes, as they opened *madrassa* schools in what is known as the Upper Pokomo region, including the towns of Masalani, Milalulu, Zubaki, Ndura, and Gwano. Some of the names of the teachers also refer to the towns they came from.⁵⁵

What seems to be a simple Swahili praise poem for teachers also expresses some of the core ideas and concepts introduced in the Arabic mawlid version. The *Barzanjī* version (used in the current recording and as the most common mawlid text in Tana River), and in fact any mawlid text from East Africa, celebrate the birth of the Prophet as the hero who brought Islam to humanity. It is a story of appearance, birth, and the spread of Islam. These are central

– (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Wa pili saidi Omari – Khatwibu Kwenye mimbari / Asiyekuioa na kiburi – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Mjuja ndiye wa tatu – Alonaswifa za utu / Hatumii haki ya mtu – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Galole Hamisa wa nne – Alekuwa muadini / Masikiti masalani – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / (x2) Wa tano Awadhi Dololo – kasomesha malaalulu / Mulijue jambo hilo – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Wa sita nihiribai – Majengo kaambiwa akae / Dini aisimamie – (Bwana) Umar Dimah / Wa sabaa Mwalimu Pupuya – Dini kaisimamia.

53 *Bwana* means master in Swahili.

54 *Galola* (verse 15) is a second name for today's capital, Hola. *Masalani* (verse 16) is a town located between Tana River County and Garissa and *Milalulu* (verse 17) refers to either a location or a sub-group of the Pokomo. See, Kalindi, *Challenges Facing the Madrassa*, xiv.

55 Bunge, *Islamization*, 53.

themes emphasized in the Arabic text which is recited during mawlid events. Additionally, many mawlid texts include episodes of conversion as part of the mawlid sequence.⁵⁶

The present poem directly addresses these topics: conversion and the spread of Islam. Although the mawlid conversion narrative is not translated into Swahili or told based on the Arabic text, it is nonetheless translated here as it occurred within the context of the group that performs the mawlid. In this case, the teacher Umar Dimah and his followers are the ones who brought Islam to the Tana River region and converted the local community. The poem, in this sense, serves as a translation of one of the core themes and the essence of mawlid texts, as well as the role this theme plays in the local setting. It highlights the celebration of the birth of the Prophet, the emergence of Islam, and its spread to the Tana River. The mawlid is rearticulated and “woven” into the local context through this poem.

The poem serves a dual purpose. First, it is a didactic description of how Islamic knowledge spread south from Lamu, and second, it introduces the “appearance of Islam” narrative, which is recited in Arabic in the text and in Swahili, through oral poetry. The Arabic mawlid text focuses on the birth of the Prophet, celebrating the moment Islam appeared in the world, and the poem describes the introduction of Islam to the Pokomo community. Although the poem is a simple praise of the teachers, it can be seen as a mawlid within a mawlid: the celebration of the formation of an Islamic community among the Pokomo.

O Prophet, show us the way!

The second example from the same reading, performed by the groups from Tana River, is a short verse that was repeated while standing and walking in a circle. Since the mawlid readings in Tana River last all night, with large parts recited while sitting in a demanding prayer-like position on the knees, this *qasīda* verse provides a moment of respite to stretch the legs after the long, rigid sitting. It also adds another layer of meaning to the verse as it is recited while walking.

Translation:⁵⁷

We are walking towards the Prophet, may he show us the way.

This simple, fascinating verse recited in Swahili between the Arabic reading parts of the mawlid is, similar to the previously described poem, a translation of an essential part of the mawlid. The translation may not be directly based on the Arabic text but rather on the meaning the group ascribes to it, as a way to praise the Prophet and, through this act, draw closer to him. While the earlier example addressed the spread of Islam, here the participants

⁵⁶ Conversion to Islam appears as a part of the *Dayba' mawlid* text through the account of Ka'ab al-Aḥbār, who narrates the story of how he converted to Islam from Judaism. The conversion happened after he opened a secret sealed box belonging to his father following his death. In this secret box Ka'ab al-Aḥbār found a part of the Jewish scripture which, according to Muslim tradition, indicates that a Prophet named Muhammad will come and bring Islam to the world. At the end of the *Mawlid Sharaf al-Anām* the narrative of conversion is narrated through the account of a Jewish couple. Here the woman sees the Prophet in a dream and converts to Islam. Katz, *The Birth of the Prophet*, 74–75; Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid.”

⁵⁷ *Tutakwenda kwa Mtume tunyeshenja.*

express in Swahili their desire to be close to the Prophet. They do so by praising him and physically walking, adding movement to the recitation. The Prophet is highlighted here as the figure who shows his followers the way. Both examples resonate with themes from the mawlid, articulated in Swahili and here, accompanied by additional bodily gestures.

Expanding the use of “translation” as a theoretical framework could emphasize aesthetic choices made by groups of performers, such as bodily gestures or percussion rhythms. These choices might also reveal and reflect different interpretations of the textual function. Or in other words how various groups of users perform and use the mawlid text differently. In this context, the body and the way the text is performed, can serve as an interpretative tool, offering a commentary of sort on the recited text.⁵⁸

An intriguing question, which will be further explored through other examples, is what each group chooses “to translate.” Or, put differently, which aspects of the mawlid are selected for translation? This choice of what to emphasize in Swahili also reflects how particular groups of performers understand the text. It also relates to written interlinear translation, where we can see in detail (more than in other types of translation) the choices translators make regarding how to translate specific words, idioms, and structures.⁵⁹ Although the Arabic meaning may not always be obvious and clear, the group still demonstrates a remarkable and deep interpretation of the text.

While the above two examples are used by the group from Tana River, the next Swahili poem, interwoven within the Arabic mawlid text, was recorded in both Tana River and Lamu. This indicates that although different groups focus on different aspects to highlight and “translate,” some verses are shared by both and could be seen as commonly accepted translations.

Celebrating Mawlid

The following poem deals with the legitimacy of expressing joy during mawlid recitations. The first verse is quoted from Boyd.⁶⁰

Translation:⁶¹

“If we dance it is no surprise,
The Habasha did,⁶²
The mosque of the Prophet,

58 On changes in ritual practice see, Corinne Ann Kratz, *Affecting Performance: Meaning, Movement, and Experience in Okiek Women’s Initiation* (Smithsonian Institution Press, 1994); Daren Ellsworth Ray, “Celebrating Swahili New Year: A Performative Critique of Textual Islam in Coastal Kenya,” *The Muslim World* 105, no. 4 (2015): 582-607.

59 Ronit Ricci, “Reading Between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation,” *Journal of World Literature* 1 (2016): 68–80.

60 Boyd, *To Praise the Prophet*, 39.

61 *Tukiteza sijabu / Wameteza mahabasha / Masikiti wa habib / Waterema na kushasha / Dhahiri imefunuka / Mtume wetu hakika / Ni mwezi usioshaka / Mbinguni unawirika / Mawliidi yako Jeddah / Na madina ni ziada / Lamu Meki shdida / Kumsifu Ahmada / Apingoo mulidi / Ya mtume muhmdii Marhaba / Wa juwa huyoni hasidi / Mgonjo asie (Hanan) nadawa.*

62 *Habasha* refers to Ethiopians.

It is full of joys.’⁶³

Clarity has emerged,
Our Prophet is real,
The moon that has no doubt,
Shines brightly in the heavens.

Mawliidi is performed in Jeddah,
and Madina as well,
And here in Lamu, it is so beautiful.
Give praise to Muhammad.

Those who oppose mawlid,
Oh Prophet Muhammad welcome,
They are envious,
Sick people with no cure.

The current example includes several verses combined and does not form a single, coherent poem. The opening stanza is part of a poem written in the mid-20th century by Hussein Badawy.⁶⁴ These verses address the legitimacy of the mawlid and also a significant and debated aspect of it—joy, and how and when it should be (or not be) expressed.⁶⁵ Here, the poem expresses joy while also responding to criticism that the mawlid is un-Islamic. A common example in religious discussions on this subject is the story of how the Prophet was welcomed by his supporters in Medina. They came out with drums to celebrate his return, reciting the *qaṣīda*, *ṭala‘ al-badr ‘alayna* (The full moon has risen upon us).⁶⁶

The first stanza in the present poem begins by highlighting the importance of joyfulness in mawlid celebrations and Islam, and the third and fourth stanzas continue the theme of the legitimacy of the mawlid. The poem states that mawlid is performed in Mecca and Jeddah, so why should it not be performed here in Lamu? Then, the poem describes those who oppose mawlid as sick and envious, people for whom there is no cure. The audience and participants recite the Arabic supplication *Allah hu jalla wa ‘alā* (God is great and exalted) repeatedly, between the Swahili verses.

The second verse (also recorded in mawlid readings from Zanzibar)⁶⁷ will lead us to the second category of Swahili translations, which are based on Arabic descriptions from the

63 Boyd, *To Praise the Prophet*, 39.

64 A descendent of the teacher and founder of the Riyāda mosque in Lamu, Habib Swaleh. Boyd, *To Praise the Prophet*, 39-41.

65 Schielke places the aspect of Joy in *mawlid* as his main research question in his study on *mawlid* in Cairo. See Samuli Schielke, *The Perils of Joy: Contesting Mulid Festivals in Contemporary Egypt* (Syracuse University Press, 2012).

66 Ibn Hajar al-‘Asqalani in his commentary on the *ḥadīth* collection of al-Bukhari discuss this widely recited poem while arguing it does not introduce a sound chain of transmission regarding the occasion on which it was recited. See Ibn Ḥajar al-‘Asqalani, *Fath al-Bari*, vol. 7 (Egypt: Dār al-Rayān lil-Turāth, 1986), vol 7: 307, *ḥadīth* number 3925.

67 See, Schmitt “*Nyoyo Zimefurahika*”, 327.

mawlid narrative, not necessarily from a specific text. The Swahili verses used here describe the rise and appearance of the Prophet using the moon as a metaphor, very much aligned with the Arabic mawlid text and Arabic poetry.

While some verses, such as the one using the moon metaphor and light to describe the appearance of the Prophet, seem like direct translations of the Arabic mawlid, other parts addressing the apologetics of mawlid and its legitimacy appear unrelated to the text but touch upon important themes of the mawlid and its understanding.

The examples introduced so far are linked to the spiritual and devotional themes of the mawlid, along with one example addressing debates about the mawlid event and the expression of joy. These poems, I would argue, are actually translations of what the group of performers considers essential aspects of the mawlid practice, aspects which are then rephrased and validated in Swahili throughout the mawlid recitation. In this sense, what we see when applying the “interlinear” lens is what certain groups view as the core aspects of the ritual, or, in other words, what is worth translating and highlighting.

Translating a Text, Its Metaphors and Structure

The following examples show a different type of translation, not meant to reassess interpretations of the text, but to introduce metaphors and narratives from the Arabic mawlid text into Swahili. While Raia explores how Islamic prayers are “imbued” within the lines of Swahili poetry,⁶⁸ the current examples demonstrate how Swahili verses inspired by mawlid metaphors and ideas are used within the lines of the Arabic mawlid recitation.

The Land of Islam

The following poem was recited between the lines of the Arabic *mawlid Dayb*⁶ text in Lamu and the *Barzanjī* text in Tana River, reflecting an accepted translation.

Translation:⁶⁹

We will not leave this land again,
To consume that which is haram,
I am going to Mecca and Medina,
The land of al-Sham.

O Prophet: peace.

On the day of the beloved,
We will come together,
May he intercede for us and increase our good deeds.

68 Raia, “Prayers Uttered Down on Paper”, 109.

69 *Si toketi tena (x2) Nchi hizi / kula haramu / Nendao zangu Makka (x2) na Madina / Nchi za Shamu / Ya nabi salama / Siku Habibu x2 tatuandama (takwandana) / Sote umati / Atushufaiie x2 Atuongezee na Hasanaati.*

Many elements conveyed in Arabic during the mawlid reading are emphasized and articulated in this Swahili poem. The intercession powers of the Prophet, the special day dedicated to him, and Mecca and Medina, the places where Islam originated and where most of the mawlid accounts take place. The first stanza emphasizes the fact that Islam has reached the land of the performers in East Africa, and that they will never return to their previous practices, described as sinful (*haramu*). On the one hand, Mecca, Medina, and al-Sham are depicted as Islamic centers, and on the other, the performers declare that Islam has reached their lands, and they will not revert to their former habits. Islam is portrayed as timeless and placeless, but also as originating in the Arab lands.

The second stanza, following the blessing for the Prophet, emphasizes the element of the day dedicated to the Prophet. An occasion that unites the community and bestows blessings through the Prophet's intercession. This poem exemplifies the translation of specific topics and ideas into Swahili. The eternal existence of Islam, as well as the day dedicated to the Prophet, are key aspects of the mawlid.

Ya Dura Mandhuma (Strung Pearls)

The following example, recited during the same mawlid reading from Lamu, is a Swahili poem found in *Ajami* script manuscripts and translated into English by Lyndon Harries.⁷⁰

Translation⁷¹

“Write ye, scribe, and keep steady your writing,
Preface it with the name of God,
And put the dots and vowels in place,
That the readers may not find fault with it.”⁷²

Harries explains in the introduction to his translation that this poem, of which only the first verse is recited aloud in the current recording, was composed by Sayyid ‘Umar bin Amin bin ‘Umar bin Amin bin Nadhir al-Ahdal, who was the *qadī* of Siyu in 1856. The title of the poem is *Ya Dura Mandhuma*, based on the Arabic *al-Durr al-Manzuma* (Strung Pearls), which is a poem with linked verses “like strings of pearls.”⁷³

The poem is based on the Arabic alphabet, with the opening of each verse beginning with a consecutive letter and three different vowels (a, i, u). In Arabic, the fourth verse typically ends with the letter hamza, known as *Hamziyya*, but in Swahili, it ends with the letter mim, making it a *Mimiyya*.⁷⁴ Harries discusses the poem, which is based on a manuscript written

⁷⁰ Harries, *Swahili Poetry*, 118-119.

⁷¹ *Andika mandishi Hati utunge (utunze?) / Isimu ya mola utangulize / Utie mukuta na irabuze / Wasikulaiti wenye kusema.*

⁷² The translation is taken from Lyndon Harries, *Swahili Poetry*, 119. For more on the composer of the poem see Lyndon Harries, “A Poem from Siu from the Swahili-Arabic Text,” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 13, no. 3 (1950): 759–70, 759.

⁷³ Lyndon Harries, *The Form and Content of Traditional Swahili Literature* (PhD Dissertation, University of London, 1953), 147.

⁷⁴ Ahmad Parker, “Arabic-Swahili Hamziyya Manuscripts: Observations on Two Testimonies of the Text,” in *One Text, Many Forms: A Comparative View of the Variability of Swahili Manuscripts*, ed. Ridder H.

by the renowned scribe from Lamu and a student of Sharifu Mansab, Muhammad Kijuma (d. 1945).⁷⁵

This Swahili poem belongs to the Swahili *ukawafi* genre, a type of poetry that possesses mystical powers, such as the *Kozin a Ndiwa* (The Raven and the Pigeon), mawlid, mi'rāj (the night journey), and the *kishamiya* (the story of the Prophet and his coat).⁷⁶ It is composed in a four-verse structure in the same way as the mawlid translation.

The present example has neither a direct connection to nor is it based on mawlid references. However, it is interesting to consider why this poem was recited in the context of the mawlid reading. Is it solely because, as Harries noted, the use of the mystical (*ukawafi*) meter makes it eligible for mawlid recitations? Or is it due to the authority of its composer as a religious scholar? Another possibility is that the poem in this meter fits the structure of the recitation. Examples like this, which do not appear to have a direct relation to the Arabic mawlid text, can still show which textual traditions were viewed as appropriate for the ritual and raise additional questions about forms of intertextuality and textual relations.

You are the Sun, You are the Moon: A Mawlid within a Mawlid

Another example recited during the *Dayba'* mawlid reading by the same group from Lamu is actually part of a Swahili translation of a different Arabic mawlid text. While the current reading follows the *Dayba'* text, the Swahili verse recited is part of a translation of *Mawlid 'Azab*, and the verse in the recording comes from the first part of that text.⁷⁷ According to Knappert the translation was made by Sharifu Mansab, the same scholar who wrote the aforementioned interlinear manuscript.⁷⁸

“When her pregnancy completed nine months,
His birth approached,
He who was to be sent came to us,
To reward us all with good recompense.”⁷⁹

Another stanza of the same mawlid translation is recited during the *qiyām* of each *Dayba'* reading in Lamu. This is a Swahili translation of the Arabic poem: “The full moon has arisen upon us.” It also appears in the interlinear manuscript described above, in a slightly different

Samsom and Clarissa Vierke (Hamburg Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures, 2021), 53–64.

75 No date is provided by Harries but he does indicate that most of the works of Kijuma were copied at the beginning of the 20th century. For SOAS library online access - [*al-Durr al-Manzuma*], SOAS Library, MS 53500, <https://digital.soas.ac.uk/LSMD000227/00001/1x?search=ms+%3d53500>. Accessed July 4, 2025.

76 Vierke, “Of Patience and Pity”, 23.

77 The *mawlid* was composed by Muhammad bin Muhammad al-'Azab al-Madanī (d. 1293/1876), a Shāfi'ī scholar born in Dimyāt, Egypt. He later moved to Medina. See, al-Dahlawī, *Fayḍ al-Malik al-Wahāb al-Muta'ālī bi-Anbā' Awā'il al-Qarn al-Thālith 'Ashar wa-al-Tawālī* (Maktaba al-Asadī, 2009), 1521-1522.

78 Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 322. The same verse is also used in Zanzibar. Schmitt, “*Nyoyo Zimefurahika*”, 237-238.

79 Translations taken from Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 323, verse 27: *Mimba ikitimu nyezi tisiya / Kuzaliwa kwake mekurubiya / Mwenye kutwongoa metuyiliya / Kutujazi sote majaza mema.*

version. Knappert translates the Swahili word *kemia* (written here *kimiya*), based on the Arabic *'Iksīr* (elixir), as medicine or elixir.⁸⁰ In the present translation, it is translated as “the bud of every blessedness.”

“You are indeed the sun, indeed the moon,
You are indeed the light upon light,
You are the bud of every blessedness,
You are indeed the lamp, that has a fine light.”⁸¹

These two stanzas are recited in Swahili, based on a Swahili translation of *Mawlid 'Azab*. They are recited during a *mawlid* reading which is based on the Arabic *Mawlid Dayb'*, creating an oral combination of two *mawlid* versions: one in Arabic (*Dayba'*) and the other in Swahili based on *Mawlid 'Azab*. Further research may reveal whether more of these Swahili verses are taken from other translations.

A Swahili Mawlid

The final example of Swahili usage in Arabic-based *mawlid* recitations is not a *qaṣīda* recited between the Arabic *mawlid* sections, but a chapter of the reading recited in Swahili, based on a Swahili translation from Arabic. The same translation also forms the basis for complete Swahili *mawlid* readings and, in several cases, is used only for the last part of the recitation before the *qiyām*. In these instances, three chapters are recited in Arabic, and the third part, leading to the *qiyām* and the conclusion of the oral recitation, is recited in Swahili.

The Swahili translation used in the oral readings is a recent translation created by the female scholar Zainab Amin al-Rudainy (see Fig. 8). Zainab Amin, also known as Amati Zainabu, was born in 1939 in Pate and later moved to Malindi, Kenya. She studied at the Riyāḍa mosque and school and later taught in Malindi, where she established her *madrasa*.⁸²

The *Barzanjī* translation of Amati Zainabu was written in *Ajami* script, and it is based on the prose version of *Barzanjī*, here reconstructed into Swahili verse and meter. The oral recitation of the Swahili part differs significantly from the Arabic one, as the text is translated into a Swahili meter. As a result, the recitation has a unique sound and rhythm that only applies to the Swahili reading.⁸³

80 Knappert, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 290, verse 49c.

81 Translation taken from Schmitt, “*Nyoyo Zimefurahika*”, 347. The same verse appears also in Knappert in another *mawlid* translation of his, *Swahili Islamic Poetry*, 324–325, verse 34. *Wewe ndiwe yuwa ndiwe kamari / Wewe ndiwe nuri iyu la nuri / Wewe ni kimiya kya kulla heri / Wewe ndiwe taa ya nyoyo njema.*

82 Abdallah Abdulkadir Mohamed, “An Analytical Survey on the Contribution of Women Scholars of Riyadha Mosque of Lamu in Dissemination of Islamic Knowledge on the Coastal Kenya (1922–2018)” (MA Thesis, Pwani University, 2020), 73.

83 For the Swahili reading of the present *Barzanjī* translations see, Maulid ya Kiswahili, YouTube video, uploaded by uraidhu shariff Alwy, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y_i8oqjCHM0. (20:50).

Fig. 8 The opening page of the Swahili mawlid. Image from the private collection of Annachiara Raia.

Fig. 9 The third reading part in the Swahili mawlid. Image from the private collection of Annachiara Raia.

Opening verses of chapter three in the Swahili mawlid:⁸⁴

When the pregnancy reached two months,
 According to the authentic words transmitted,
 He ('Abdallah), the father of the bringer of glad tidings,
 Completed the journey,
 To Madina, the radiant one, the city of the righteous,
 He stayed for a month,
 With his in-laws from the clan of Najariyya.
 Then an illness seized him in full force,
 He had no way to recover,
 His destiny had come to an end.

Page | 98

The present translation follows the same verse sequence as in the *Barzanjī* text, describing at the beginning of the third part (*faṣl*) the death of 'Abdallah, the father of the Prophet, in Medina. Then the mawlid sequence continues in both versions to the birth indication leading to the *qiyām*. The Swahili translation appears to closely follow the same verse structure created by Barzanjī, with each part of the text containing the same number of verses. However, in the Swahili version, the verses are arranged as a poem in two columns (see Fig. 9), suggesting a similar process of rendering the mawlid into verse as in the previous version.

The present Swahili *Barzanjī* translation is another example of the interchangeable language usage in mawlid readings. The translation introduces meter and stanza based on Swahili poetry, which is clear in the recitation practice. This last example is not recited between the Arabic reading parts but serves as an independent recitation in Swahili. Swahili is not only seen as a language for translation to aid understanding and study, but also as a language appropriate for ritual purposes.

Conclusion

The present article aimed to examine the oral use of Swahili in Arabic-based mawlid readings from East Africa within the framework of the interlinear translation model. While this model usually focuses on a written text with a translation, the current study proposes analyzing the Swahili utterances, which are not written but orally introduced during the reading, as methods for translating parts of the mawlid text, as well as its function and meaning, into Swahili. In this process the study presents several examples, some of which can be seen as translations of the function of the text within the Swahili context or among a specific group of performers, while others highlight metaphors, language structures, and translations that are also woven

84 *Yalipotimu kamili, mimba miezi miwili, kwa swahili ya kauli, maneno yalopokewa / Aliifunga Safari, hoyo babake bashiri, akanenda munawari, Madina mui wa wema / kaketi mwezi kamili, Abdillahi ilhali, kawazuru wake khali, wa bani Najjariya / Maradhi yakamshika, mwezi mzima hakika, asione kupunguka, ila ajali kukoma.*

into Arabic-based mawlid readings. Both types of examples demonstrate how performers “weave” the text into their Swahili context.

Further research on oral Swahili utterances, verses, and poetry used in Arabic-based mawlid readings may reveal which themes from the mawlid recur in Swahili. Using the Arabic mawlid text as a “baseline” helps us understand what the orally recited utterances refer to (or not). Is the utterance connected to a function of the mawlid? Or is it a metaphor? The themes highlighted in these Swahili poems reflect the subjects considered important for understanding the text.

Some of these textual variations include translations, interpretations, and independent devotional poetry, all of which carry historical and social significance and relate to the role of the translator in the Swahili context, as shown in the discussion of the interlinear manuscript created by Sharifu Mansab. What is called a mawlid reading here is actually an oral collection of diverse poetry and texts from different times that are used to praise the Prophet.

Following Swahili poetry, which is recited between the lines of the Arabic mawlid text, allows us to reflect on the interpretation of an Arabic text and its significance in a non-Arabic speaking community. It also highlights the social context in which the mawlid text is performed. Further study can explore performative elements, such as movements and rhythm, and ask whether they, too, can be conceptualized as additional layers of interlinearity.

References

Sources

- al-Būṣīrī. *al-Hamziyya*. In *Majmūʿ al-Mutun al-Kabīr*. Maṭbaʿat al-Istiqāma, 1958.
- al-Dahlawī. *Fayḍ al-Malik al-Wahhāb al-Mutaʿālī bi-anbāʾ awāʾil al-qarn al-thālith ʿashar wa-al-tawālī*. Maktabat al-Asadī, 2009.
- al-Dur al-Manzūma*. SOAS Library, MS 53500. Accessed July 4, 2025. <https://digital.soas.ac.uk/LSMD000227/00001/1x?search=ms+%3d53500>.
- Amīn al-Rudainy Zainab, *Mawlid Yā Rasūl* (Madrasat al-Nūr al-Islāmiyya, 1991). Hamburg Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures, MPRINT-LAMU-PATE-005.
- Ibn Hajar al-ʿAsqalānī. *Fath al-Bārī*. Vol. 7. Dār al-Rayān lil-Turāth, 1986.
- Ibn Khallikān, Aḥmad b. Muḥammad. *Wafayāt al-aʿyān wa-Anbāʾ Abnāʾ al-Zamān*. Edited by Iḥsān ʿAbbās. Dār al-Thaqāfa, n.d.
- Kitabu Mauludī*. Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin, MS PPN78882564X. Accessed July 4, 2025. <https://digital-beta.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/werkansicht?PPN=PPN78882564X&PHYSID=PHYS0005&DMDID=>.
- Majmūʿa min mawlid sharaf al-anām. Mawlid al-Barzanjī*. Maktabat Ishāʿat al-Islām, n.d.
- Majmūʿa min mawlid sharaf al-anām. Mawlid al-Daybaʿ*. Maktabat Ishāʿat al-Islām, n.d.
- Majmūʿa min mawlid sharaf al-anām. Mawlid Sharaf al-Anām*. Maktabat Ishāʿat al-Islām, n.d.

Studies

- ABDEL HALEEM, Muhammad A. S. *The Qur'an: A New Translation*. Oxford World's Classics. Oxford University Press, 2005.
- ABDULAZIZ, Mohamed Hassan. "The Influence of the Qasida on the Development of Swahili Rhymed and Metred Verse." In *Qasida Poetry in Islamic Asia and Africa*, edited by Stefan Sperl and Christopher Shackle. Brill, 1996.
- BANG, Anne K. *Sufis and Scholars of the Sea: Family Networks in East Africa, 1860–1925*. Routledge Curzon, 2003.
- BOYD, Alan. "To Praise the Prophet: A Processual Symbolic Analysis of 'Maulidi', a Muslim Ritual in Lamu, Kenya." PhD Dissertation, Indiana University, 1980.
- BUNGER, Robert. *Islamization Among the Upper Pokomo*. Syracuse University Press, 1979.
- BROWN, Nicholas Mainey. "Swahili Poetry, Classical Tradition." In *Encyclopedia of African Religions and Philosophy*. Springer Netherlands, 2021.
- BÜTTNER, Carl Gustav. *Suaheli Schriftstücke in Arabischer Schrift*. W. Spemann, 1892.
- CASSON, Lionel. *The Periplus Maris Erythraei: Text with Introduction and Commentary*. Princeton University Press, 1989.
- CORET, Clélia. "Runaway Slaves and the Aftermath of Slavery on the Swahili Coast: New Perspectives from Witu in the 19th Century." *Journal of Global Slavery*, no. 6 (2021).
- GORI, Alessandro. "Some Observations on Composite and Multiple-Text Manuscripts in the Islamic Tradition of the Horn of Africa." In *One-Volume Libraries: Composite and Multiple-Text Manuscripts*, edited by Michael Friedrich and Cosima Schwarke. De Gruyter, 2016.
- HARRIES, Lyndon. "A Poem from Siu from the Swahili-Arabic Text." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 13, no. 3 (1950).
- . "Strung Pearls: A Poem from the Swahili-Arabic Text." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 15, no. 1 (1953).
- . *Swahili Poetry*. Clarendon Press, 1962.
- . "The Form and Content of Traditional Swahili Literature." PhD Dissertation, University of London, 1953.
- HORTON, Mark, and Felix Chami. "Swahili Origins." In *The Swahili World*, edited by Stephanie Wynne-Jones and Adria LaViolette. Routledge, 2018.
- HORTON, Mark, and John Middleton. *The Swahili: The Social Landscape of a Mercantile Society*. Blackwell, 2000.
- KATZ, Marion Holmes. *The Birth of the Prophet Muhammad: Devotional Piety in Sunni Islam*. London: Routledge, 2007.
- . "Women's 'Mawlid' Performances in Sanaa and the Construction of Yemeni National Identity." *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 40, no. 4 (2008).
- KAPTEIN, Nico. "The Berdiri Mawlid Issue among Indonesian Muslims in the Period from circa 1875 to 1930." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 149, no. 1 (1993).
- KLEINMICHEL, Sigrid. *Die Geburt des Propheten Muhammad: Drei Dichtungen aus Mittelasien*. Reichert Verlag, 2009.
- KNAPPERT, Jan. *Swahili Islamic Poetry*. 3rd ed. Leiden: Brill, 1971.
- KRATZ, Corinne Ann. *Affecting Performance: Meaning, Movement, and Experience in Okiek Women's Initiation*. Smithsonian Institution Press, 1994.

- LAMBEK, Michael. "The Ludic Side of Islam in Mayotte." In *The Global Worlds of the Swahili: Interfaces of Islam, Identity and Space in 19th and 20th Century East Africa*, edited by Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann. Lit Verlag, 2006.
- MAFTUHIN, Arif. "Translating the Untranslatable." *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 151 (2023).
- MCPHERSON, Joseph Williams. *The Moulids of Egypt: Egyptian Saints-Days*. Edited by Russell McGuirk. Foreword by Valerie J. Hoffman. Gingko Library, 2023. Originally written 1941.
- MOHAMED, Abdallah Abdulkadir. "An Analytical Survey on the Contribution of Women Scholars of Riyadha Mosque of Lamu in Dissemination of Islamic Knowledge on the Coastal Kenya (1922–2018)." MA Thesis, Pwani University, 2020.
- NEUHAUS, Gustav. "Kitabu Mauludi, Buch der Geburt Muhammed's." *MSOS*, no. 38 (1935).
- NUOTIO, Hanni. "The Dance That Is Not Danced, the Song That Is Not Sung: Zanzibari Women in the Maulidi Ritual." In *The Global Worlds of the Swahili: Interfaces of Islam, Identity and Space in 19th and 20th Century East Africa*, edited by Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann. Lit Verlag, 2006.
- NURSE, Derek, and Thomas J. Hinnebusch. *Swahili and Sabaki: A Linguistic History*. University of California Press, 1993.
- OLALI, Tom. *Performing Arts in Lamu Maulidi Festival*. LAP Lambert, 2012.
- PARKER, Ahmad. "Arabic-Swahili Hamziyya Manuscripts: Observations on Two Testimonies of the Text." In *One Text, Many Forms: A Comparative View of the Variability of Swahili Manuscripts*, edited by Ridder H. Samsom and Clarissa Vierke. Hamburg Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures, 2021.
- PARKER, Ahmed Hussein. "Manuscripts and Transmission of Knowledge in Swahili Society: A Comparative Analysis of Form and Usage of Qaṣīda al-Hamziyya." PhD Dissertation, University of Hamburg, 2019.
- POUWELS, Randall L. *Horn and Crescent: Cultural Change and Traditional Islam on the East African Coast, 800–1900*. African Studies Series, no. 53. Cambridge University Press, 1987.
- RAIA, Annachiara. "Prayers Uttered Down on Paper: A Stylistic Analysis of Swahili Devotional Lyrics." *Journal for Islamic Studies* 38, no. 2 (2020).
- . "Swahili Palimpsests: The Muslim Stories Beneath Swahili Compositions." *Swahili Forum*, no. 25 (2018).
- RAY, Daren Ellsworth. "Celebrating Swahili New Year: A Performative Critique of Textual Islam in Coastal Kenya." *The Muslim World* 105, no. 4 (2015): 582-607.
- RICCI, Ronit. "Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the Maulid Sharaf al-Anām Across the Indonesian-Malay World." *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023).
- . "Reading Between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation." *Journal of World Literature*, no. 1 (2016).
- ROMERO, Patricia W. *Lamu: History, Society, and Family in an East African Port City*. Markus Wiener Publishers, 1997.
- SAIDI, Ali Kalindi. "Challenges Facing the Madrassa Institutions in the Teaching of Islamic Religious Education: A Case Study of Galole Constituency of Tana River County." MA Thesis, Nairobi University, 2016.
- SCHIELKE, Samuli. *The Perils of Joy: Contesting Mulid Festivals in Contemporary Egypt*. Syracuse University Press, 2012.

- SHARIF, Abdul. "Between Two Worlds: The Littoral Peoples of the Indian Ocean." In *The Global Worlds of the Swahili: Interfaces of Islam, Identity and Space in 19th and 20th-Century East Africa*, edited by Roman Loimeier and Rüdiger Seesemann. LIT Verlag, 2006.
- SCHMITT, Aïsha. "Nyoyo Zimefurahika: Urban Qasida in Zanzibar." PhD Dissertation, SOAS University of London, 2012.
- VIERKE, Clarissa. "Of Patience and Pity: Rewriting and Reciting the Widely Travelled Islamic Poem 'The Hawk and the Dove' in East Africa." *Islamic Africa*, no. 14 (2023).
- . "Poetic Links Across the Ocean: On Poetic 'Translation' as Mimetic Practice at the Swahili Coast." *Comparative Studies of South Asia, Africa, and the Middle East* 37, no. 2 (2017).

© Raphael Michaeli, University of Bergen, Norway

◀ raphael.michaeli@uib.no ▶

Surau Texts Translated: *Translation in Form, Textual Analysis in Substance*

FADHLI LUKMAN (UIN Sunan Kalijaga, Yogyakarta)¹

Abstract

This article investigates the translation tradition of *surau* communities in the Minangkabau world, with a focus on interlinear translation. With its prominent role in the Islamization of the region, the *surau* held an important historical function as a vital centre for the production, teaching, learning, and preservation of Islamic manuscripts—mostly composed in Arabic, while those written in Malay are filled with rich Arabic concepts, vocabulary, and technical expressions. As such, translation emerges as an integral aspect of engagement with the manuscripts, supporting both comprehension and instruction. Focusing on the manuscript collection of Surau Simaung in Sijunjung, West Sumatra, the study explores two central questions: first, the role and positioning of Arabic and Malay within the translation practices of *surau* manuscripts; and second, the origins of grammatical literalism, a feature often associated with interlinear translation in the *surau* tradition. This study shows that translation practices in the *surau* were diverse, encompassing holistic, running-sequential, and interlinear paradigms. Among these, occasional interlinear translation predominates, revealing a distinctive form of grammatical literalism rooted in the Arabic linguistic structure, reflective of post-classical scholarly practices. Rather than producing idiomatic Malay renderings, *surau* scholars pursued rigorous grammatical engagement with Arabic texts, transforming translation into a tool of learning and inquiry. Translation was not primarily about finding lexical equivalents in Malay but was fundamentally an exercise in textual analysis. It served as a vernacular expression of the post-classical Islamic intellectual project—*translation in form, textual analysis in substance*.

Keywords: Surau, Minangkabau, translation, literalism, textual analysis

¹ This research was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (project *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*, grant agreement no. 101001731). I am deeply grateful to Ronit Ricci and all members of the *Textual Microcosms* research group for their invaluable support, guidance, and feedback throughout the research and writing of this article. I also extend my sincere appreciation to Yulfira Riza, Ahmad Taufik Hidayat, Rahmi Yunita, Shafwatul Bary, Apria Putra, Nofel Nofriadri, and Novizal Wendri for their kind assistance and insightful discussions during the research.

Introduction

This article examines the tradition of translating Arabic texts into Malay within the Minangkabau world (*Alam Minangkabau*). The Minangkabau are an ethnic group inhabiting the central region of the island of Sumatra. They refer to their homeland as *Alam Minangkabau*, which encompasses the highland heartland villages in the Bukit Barisan mountain range—known as *Darek*—as well as the expanding coastal regions to the east and west, referred to as *Rantau*.² Although the Minangkabau are today commonly associated with the province of West Sumatra, this association is “arbitrary and a shadow of colonial partitioning.”³ The language spoken in

Fig. 1 The Province of West Sumatra in Indonesia, which is currently strongly associated with the Minangkabau region.

this region is Minangkabau, a variety or dialect of Malay. It is predominantly oral in character, with a strong cultural emphasis on oral eloquence and a rich oral literary tradition.⁴ While the Minangkabau language has distinctive features of its own, the shared use of Arabic script in the writing system of both Minangkabau and Malay prior to the dominance of the Roman script further blurred the boundaries between the two.⁵

There is a record of Islamization of one of the Minangkabau kings through marriage with a sister of Sultan Mansur Syah of Melaka (1459–1477),⁶ yet it seems that

- 2 M Yusuf, ed., *Katalogus Manuskrip dan Skriptorium Minangkabau* (C-DATS-TUFS, 2006), 1; Jeffrey Hadler, *Muslims and Matriarchs: Cultural Resilience in Indonesia through Jihad and Colonialism* (Cornell University Press, 2008), 3, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7591/j.ctt7zc7n>.
- 3 Hadler, *Muslims and Matriarchs*, 4.
- 4 Khaidir Anwar, “Minangkabau, Background of the Main Pioneers of Modern Standard Malay in Indonesia,” *Archipel* 12, no. 1 (1976): 83, <https://doi.org/10.3406/arch.1976.1296>.
- 5 P Voorhoeve, *Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Sumatra*, Bibliographical Series 1 (Netherlands: 1955), 16.
- 6 Jane Drakard, “A Kingdom of Words: Minangkabau Sovereignty in Sumatran History” (Ph.D.

surau, a traditional Islamic learning institution in the region, is more responsible for the Islamization of the region than politics. The reason is that, on the one hand, the loyalty of the Minangkabau community was more closely aligned with the *nagari* (villages) than with the central authority of the kingdom; and on the other hand, most *surau* were rooted in the *nagari* and local market networks.⁷ This suggests that the spread of Islam in Minangkabau was shaped more by grassroots religious education and local sociocultural structures than by top-down political initiatives.

Integral to the *surau*'s role in the Islamization of the region is their historical function as vital centres for the production, teaching, learning, and preservation of Islamic manuscripts.⁸ Functioning as scriptoria, *surau* not only stored manuscripts but also fostered vibrant intellectual activity through live oral instruction.⁹ The digital collections of Minangkabau manuscripts preserved across several platforms—such as the Leiden Digital Collection, the Endangered Archives Programme of the British Library, and the DREAMSEA Project—stand as testament to the unparalleled importance of the *surau* in the Minangkabau manuscript tradition. Local accounts and catalogues also document private collections, yet these manuscripts are typically inherited from *surau* or from the leaders of a *ṭarīqa* associated with a particular *surau*.¹⁰

The majority of *surau* manuscripts bear strong pedagogical characteristics, often taking the form of personal or instructional notes.¹¹ As such, the *surau* manuscripts stand as written monuments to the dynamic oral teaching practices that animated these institutions. These manuscripts are mostly composed in Arabic, while those written in Malay are heavily laden with Arabic concepts, vocabulary, and technical expressions. Translation emerges as an integral aspect of engagement with the manuscripts, indispensable both for understanding the content and for facilitating the teaching process. Grasping the modes of translation employed within the *surau* tradition thus offers critical insights into the mechanisms of education and knowledge transmission in these institutions.

This article investigates the translation tradition of *surau* communities in the Minangkabau world, with a focus on interlinear translation. However, I argue that the existing *surau* corpus suggests that interlinear translation cannot be studied in isolation from the broader manuscript culture of the *surau*. Accordingly, this study examines interlinear translation in close connection with other translation practices also found within the *surau* tradition. In doing so, it draws on the manuscript collection of *Surau Simaung* in Sijunjung,

Dissertation, The Australian National University, 1993), 35.

7 Drakard, "A Kingdom of Words," 1–15; Christine Dobbin, *Kebangkitan Islam dalam Ekonomi Petani yang Sedang Berubah, Sumatra Tengah, 1784–1847*, trans. Lillian D. Tedjasudana (INIS, 1992), 144; Anwar, "Minangkabau," 80.

8 Azyumardi Azra, *Surau: Pendidikan Islam Tradisi dalam Transisi dan Modernisasi* (PT. Logos Wacana Ilmu, 2003); Oman Fathurahman, "Naskah dan Rekonstruksi Sejarah Lokal Islam; Contoh Kasus dari Minangkabau," *Wacana* 7, no. 2 (2005).

9 Pramono, *Khazanah Naskah Minangkabau* (Penerbit Erka, 2018), 7.

10 Yusuf, *Katalogus Manuskrip*; Pramono, *Khazanah Naskah Minangkabau*.

11 Arif Maftuhin, "Translating the Untranslatable: The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice," *Indonesia and the Malay World*, January 4, 2024, 1–25, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2264672>.

West Sumatra, which houses eighty-eight manuscripts encompassing 209 texts across a wide range of Islamic disciplines, including *taṣawwuf*, *kalām*, Qur'an and *tafsīr*, hadith, *fiqh*, history, *falak*, and Arabic linguistics.¹² The majority of these texts are Arabic with Malay translations and annotations, and even original Malay compositions frequently contain Arabic expressions—whether Qur'anic verses, prophetic traditions, or technical terminology—most of which are accompanied by translations. Although many of the texts are undated, those with dates predominantly originate from the late eighteenth to early nineteenth centuries. Earlier materials—or at least copies of texts from the earlier period—are also present, including works attributed to earlier Malay authors, such as 'Abd al-Ra'ūf al-Sinkilī (d. 1693), Shams al-Dīn al-Sumatrānī (d. 1630), and 'Abd al-Ṣamad al-Falimbānī (d. c. 1789). In light of its breadth and diversity, the Surau Simaung collection may be considered representative of the broader surau textual tradition.

To uncover the translation tradition of the surau manuscript culture, this study is guided by two central questions: first, the role and positioning of Arabic and Malay within the translation practices of surau manuscripts; and second, the origins of grammatical literalism, a feature often associated with interlinear translation in the surau tradition. Both questions reveal important aspects of surau manuscript culture, in which the majority of texts take the form of occasional interlinear translations, with Arabic functioning as the primary language of discourse and Malay serving a secondary, supportive role. This suggests that the Surau Simaung collection represents the apex of the surau textual tradition, where engagement with Arabic had become institutionalized. Moreover, the meticulous attention to fine-grained Arabic grammar evident in the collection indicates that, for surau communities, translation was not merely a matter of rendering Arabic into Malay, but a deeper intellectual endeavour aimed at mastering the Islamic sciences through post-classical engagement with Arabic texts.

The Surau Manuscript Tradition: Between Arabic and Malay

Ronit Ricci has identified three distinct paradigms to the translation of Islamic manuscripts in Malay and Javanese literary traditions. The first paradigm, which she terms “holistic translation,” involves rendering and adapting entire works from Arabic or Persian into Malay or Javanese. These translations often preserve overarching storylines, dialogic structures, or theological themes, but also display considerable flexibility, as translators reshape the texts to suit local literary tastes and their own agendas in disseminating Islamic knowledge. The second paradigm transpires at the sentence level, in which Arabic phrases are immediately followed on the page by their Malay or Javanese counterparts. These renderings range from highly literal to paraphrastic or interpretive, where the bilingual layout often invites readers or listeners to move back and forth between languages. The third paradigm is interlinear

¹² The current caretaker himself notes that the digital copies made available through the DREAMSEA Project does not represent the entirety of his holdings. All sources consulted in this study are drawn from the digital copies of the DREAMSEA Project, under the collection code DS 0043. (<https://www.hmmcloud.org/dreamsea/manuscripts.php?country=&tags=&city=&author=&library=Surau+Si+maung&language=&projnum=&writingSupport=&title=&script=&searchType=1>)

translation, in which Malay or Javanese words are inserted between the lines of Arabic text in a near word-for-word fashion. This mode lays bare the mechanics of translation, revealing how translators grappled with the linguistic structure of Arabic while attempting to maintain clarity in the target language. Among the three, it is the most linguistically meticulous and closely tied to the grammatical features of the source text.¹³

With a minor adjustment, Ricci's categorization proves particularly useful for examining the tradition of Arabic translation within the Minangkabau surau context, as all three paradigms are represented in the surau manuscript collection. Within the Surau Simaung collection, texts belonging to the first paradigm, holistic translation, are largely derivative of certain more popular works. The most prominent examples are texts concerning the *Sifat dua puluh* (the twenty attributes of God), which are derived from the textual traditions of al-Sanūsī and Tilimsānī.¹⁴ One narrative text, *Hikayat Puti Bilqis* (The Tale of Princess Bilqis) also appears to follow this paradigm, although further investigation is required to determine the original Arabic source from which it was translated.¹⁵ Texts following this first paradigm are, in principle, monolingual. However, given that the whole collection of Surau Simaung largely consists of Islamic works, it is unsurprising that Arabic words and quotations frequently appear within the texts of this translation paradigm.

For the second paradigm, while Ricci refers to this as sentence-level translation, this article adopts the term *running-sequential translation*, as the same format may also apply to smaller units, such as phrases, rather than complete sentences. This adjustment more accurately captures the granularity of translation practices in the surau tradition. This translation paradigm is characterized by a bilingual layout in which the Arabic source text appears first, followed directly by its Malay translation. The Arabic segments may range from a single phrase to sentences of several lines, sometimes extending to half of, or an entire page. The Malay translation continues along the same horizontal line or textual flow, resulting in a unified manuscript in which source and translation are read as part of a continuous sequence. A variation of this format involves texts primarily composed in Malay but interspersed with Arabic expressions—drawn from the Qur'an, hadith, Islamic treatises, or technical terminology—each followed by a corresponding Malay explanation.

These texts are written in *Jawi*, a modified Arabic script adapted to represent Malay phonemes absent in Arabic. To visually distinguish between the two languages, scribes commonly used red ink for Arabic and black for Malay. In some cases, verbal cues such as *artinya* (its meaning is) are also employed to signal transitions. In the absence of colour differentiation or verbal markers, however, the visual uniformity of the script and layout can

13 Ronit Ricci, "Story, Sentence, Single Word: Translation Paradigms in Javanese and Malay Islamic Literature," in *A Companion to Translation Studies*, by Sandra Bermann and Catherine Porter, Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 86 (West Sussex: Wiley Blackwell, 2014), 543–56; For interlinear translation, see also: Ronit Ricci, "Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation," *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80, <https://doi.org/10.1163/24056480-00101008>.

14 Philipp Bruckmayr, "The Šarḥ/Hāšiya Phenomenon in Southeast Asia: From al-Sanūsī's Umm al-Barāhīn to Malay Sifat Dua Puluh Literature," *MIDÉO. Mélanges de l'Institut Dominicain d'études Orientales*, no. 32 (May 15, 2017): 27–52.

15 DS 0043 00007.

obscure the bilingual structure, making the presence of translation less readily apparent to untrained readers.

Examples 1 and 2 below are excerpts from *Murād al-‘ishq* (the desire of love) of Shams al-Dīn al-Sumatrānī (d. 1039/1630).¹⁶ This text is written entirely in black ink. As such, the visual aspect alone does not indicate that it contains an Arabic text accompanied by a Malay translation. The two samples illustrate how Arabic words are translated sequentially into Malay within a sentence, with the translation often presented in an appositive phrase or clause, resulting in a multilayered sentence structure. I have provided a literal English translation for both examples, along with visual markers to aid understanding. Words in **bold** represent Arabic terms or expressions, those that are underlined are their translations, and *italicized* words are verbal cues that connect the two. The integration between translation and source text makes this format challenging to read, but it reveals how the practice of translation facilitated the encounter with, and introduction of Arabic terminology to a Malay audience.

Page | 108

1. Maka inilah kitab yang menghimpun pada menyatakan tauhid dan hati ta’līf shaikh Shamsy al-Dīn ma’nānya daripada **kitab tasawwuf** artinya perkataan pada ilmu **sūfi** artinya orang tahqīq yang suci i’tiqādnya, karangan Shaikh Muḥy al-Dīn ibn ‘Arabī **qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu** artinya dipersuci Allah ta’ālā rahasianya.

This is the book that gathers explanations of tawḥīd and the (spiritual) heart, composed by Shaykh Shams al-Dīn; which means it is a **book of taṣawwuf**—that is, a work on sūfi knowledge—referring to people of realization (tahqīq), whose faith is pure, authored by Shaykh Muḥy al-Dīn ibn ‘Arabī, **qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu**—meaning, may Allah Most High sanctify his inner reality.¹⁷

2. Maka hati ‘arif yang **nūrānī itu** artinya hati yang Cahaya itu amat besar lagi amat luas daripada segala alam, sehingga daripada ‘arash pun amat luas, maka daripada pihak amat besarnya dan amat luas dan amat **latifnya** artinya halus maka ia menerima tajallī dhāt Allah ta’ālā ...

So the heart of the ‘arif that is **luminous (nūrānī)**—that means the heart that is Light—is extremely vast and exceedingly expansive beyond all the worlds, even more expansive than the Throne (‘arsh). So, from the aspect of its immensity, vastness, and **latif**—that is, its fineness—it receives the tajallī (divine manifestation) of the Essence (dhāt) of Allah, the Exalted...

Not all translations that belong to this category are as complex as the two examples above. *Zahrāt al-murīd fī bayān kalimat al-tawḥīd* (the flower of the seeker in elucidating the word of Divine unity), attributed to ‘Abd al-Ṣamad al-Falimbānī,¹⁸ and an untitled treatise by ‘Abd

¹⁶ DS 0043 00018, 41v-42v

¹⁷ I intentionally set aside stylistic conventions concerning bolding or italicization in this and similar sentences in order to more clearly distinguish between the original terms, their translations, and the verbal cues that serve as bridges between the two.

¹⁸ DS 0043 00008

Fig. 2 *Sharḥ umm al-barāhīn* or *Tilimsānī* by ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad ibn ‘Umar ibn Ibrāhīm al-Tilimsānī (d. 897/1492), The DREAMSEA Project, DS 0043 00087, illustrating the typical pattern of occasional interlinear translation found in the surau manuscript tradition

al-Raʿūf al-Singkīlī¹⁹ consisting of seven theological questions and their answers, present translations whose format makes for a more readable text. In these texts, not only are the Arabic and Malay sections distinguished by colour—red for Arabic and black for Malay—but the layout also ensures that the Arabic text completes a sentence or a short section before the Malay translation follows. Rather than interweaving Arabic phrases with their translations, these works place the Arabic and Malay components in distinct positions, each forming a coherent unit on its own, albeit arranged along a sequential, continuous line.

The third translation paradigm observed in Surau Simaung manuscript collections is interlinear translation. Interlinear translation is characterized by its format, in which the translation is written between lines that are spaced out to allow each translated word to appear directly beneath its corresponding word in the source text. This layout enables the translator to pursue a word-for-word rendering and to attend to even the smallest linguistic features of the original, wherever possible. Ricci notes that while interlinear translation does not challenge the notion that a “perfect” translation is ultimately unattainable, it nonetheless comes closer to that ideal than other translation models. This is because interlinear translation seeks “to find equivalents for even small grammatical particles like prepositions or suffixes—an attempt that can go so far in trying to replicate the original text’s syntax that the translated sentence compromises its semantic meaning.”²⁰

A broad overview of the manuscript collection at Surau Simaung reveals two important observations. First, that interlinear translation is typically applied on an occasional basis as the available translation of the original Arabic text does not constitute a complete or meaningful sentence in itself. Second, Malay translation is not the only material appearing beneath the lines; the interlinear material is more diverse than translation.

In general, there are three types of interlinear material in the manuscript tradition of Surau Simaung. The first two are verbal: Malay translations and Arabic glosses. The Malay translations provide equivalents of the Arabic source text and are predominantly rendered in either a literal or paraphrastic style. Arabic glosses, on the other hand, consist of brief explanatory notes attached to specific Arabic words or phrases. These glosses can be broadly categorized into three types:

(1) cultural glosses, such as the insertion of *ism al-balad* (the name of the country) when a city is mentioned;

(2) grammatical glosses, including clarifications of an implicit subject following a verb—e.g., identifying *Allāh*, *Muhammad*, or another figure after *qāla* (he said)—or the use of words to indicate grammatical positions such as *mafʿūl bih* (object), and *ḥāl* (adverbial accusative) beneath the relevant words; and

(3) technical glosses, which offer citations from other sources or define key concepts. In didactic-linguistic texts covering subjects such as *naḥw*, *ṣarf*, and *maʿānī*, a common form of technical gloss is the insertion of sample sentences to illustrate specific linguistic unit or

19 DS 0043 00019, 290v. – 299r.

20 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 69.

function. In texts on *ṣarf*, basic verb-inflection patterns are often provided.²¹ Texts on *tajwīd*, which concerns the proper recitation of the Qur'an, may include examinations of recitation rules, as exemplified in treatments of sura al-Fātiḥa.²²

The third type of interlinear material commonly found in the manuscript tradition of Surau Simaung is non-verbal, consisting of visual marks that serve as reading aids. These marks often reflect personal patterns of use, as the style and function of such annotations may vary from one manuscript to another. Nevertheless, several recurring practices can be identified. One frequently observed function is itemization: when a text lists multiple elements within a category, each item is marked in an identical way—sometimes simply with a red upper line—to indicate that they belong to the same conceptual group. Another common function is grammatical clarification, where marks are used to connect pronouns with their referents or verbs with their corresponding subjects. Less frequently, these non-verbal marks serve a punctuation-like role, signalling specific points within the texts or marking the closure of a discourse unit. Furthermore, in manuscripts that include marginal notes, the connecting marks linking words in the main text to their explanations in the margins are often inscribed beneath the lines as well.

There is a fundamental distinction between the first two translation paradigms—holistic and running-sequential translation—and interlinear translation within the Surau Simaung manuscript collection. In the former, Malay functions as the primary language of discourse, while in the latter, Arabic occupies that dominant position, with Malay serving a supporting role.

To clarify this point, let us revisit the examples previously cited for holistic and running-sequential translation. Three texts were discussed in relation to the running-sequential paradigm: *Murād al-‘ishq*, *Zahrat al-murīd*, and an untitled treatise by ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf. *Murād al-‘ishq* is essentially a Malay prose composition enriched with Arabic vocabulary and conceptual elements, in which Arabic terms are immediately followed by their Malay translations. In this respect, the text shares a defining feature with works in the holistic translation category, *Hikayat Puti Bilqis* and *Sifat dua puluh*, in that they are essentially Malay texts.

Zahrat al-murīd and the untitled work of ‘Abd al-Ra’ūf present a different case. Both authors state in their respective introductions that the original compositions were written in Arabic, and that the translations were produced in response to specific requests. This suggests the existence of an earlier monolingual Arabic version—now likely lost—and a later bilingual version, complemented with Malay translation, which survives as part of the Surau Simaung collection. Because many Arabic theological and philosophical terms in the original could not be adequately conveyed through literal translation alone, extended elaboration became necessary in the translated version. This format corresponds to what Mahmood Kooria terms *intermittent translation*, a sub-category of commentarial translation, in which the Arabic text is accompanied by extensive explanations provided by the author or translator. In this context, brief Arabic statements are frequently followed by lengthy Malay commentaries—at times extending over several pages. Arabic functions here as a marker of scholarly authority, while the Malay translation and explanation serves the pedagogical needs of a local audience. Considering this

21 DS 0043 00045, 20r

22 DS 0043 00008, 70r

production history, it can be argued that it is the Malay explanatory content, rather than the Arabic original, that constitutes the *raison d'être* of both texts.

Interlinear translation, by contrast, reflects a more sustained and institutionalized practice of close reading and engagement with Arabic texts. While the previously discussed texts suggest that direct interaction with Arabic was primarily undertaken by translators—typically established scholars—who produced Malay translations for general readers, interlinear texts indicate a broader context of engagement of Arabic. In these works, rather than simply providing ready-made Malay translations, scholars taught the Arabic texts directly to students, employing the various interlinear materials described above. This approach embedded the practice of engaging with Arabic more deeply within educational settings.

In other words, these texts, within the surau educational setting, were intended to be read and understood in their Arabic form, with the Malay translation occupying a secondary, supportive role. The diverse interlinear materials described above reinforce this point. The second type of Arabic gloss—namely, grammatical glosses—suggests that the texts were first approached with a conscious awareness of Arabic linguistic structures. In the interlinear Malay translations, this linguistic orientation often shaped the Malay renderings, which frequently make more sense when interpreted through the lens of Arabic grammar (a point to which we will return in the following sub-section). Moreover, the technical glosses—consisting of partial citations drawn from other sources—also tend to refer to Arabic-language references. As a result, the proportion of Malay content in many of these texts is significantly lower than that of the Arabic. This indicates that Arabic defines the identity of these texts, with the Malay translation serving as one of several comprehension aids, alongside Arabic glosses and non-verbal interlinear elements such as the marks mentioned earlier.

Texts with full line-by-line interlinear Malay translation are, of course, also available. In a text of this kind the Malay translation plays a more prominent role compared to other kinds of interlinear intervention. This kind of translation is most likely intended for beginners, as evidenced by the introductory level of the texts' content. In the Surau Simaung collection, the texts that fall into this category are *Ādāb al-muta'allim* (the etiquette of the student),²³ *Bayān al-sirr al-ghayb wa al-shahāda min al-kashf wa al-sirar al-rububiyya* (elucidation of the secret of the unseen and the visible realms through unveiling and the mysteries of Divine lordship),²⁴ an untitled treatise on *tajwīd* (DS 0043 00008, p. 80v), and two texts on Arabic morphology (DS 0043 00045; DS 0043 00034). In these texts, the words of the translation are organized into a coherent sentence that can be comprehended on its own. Even without the original text, the translated version, although it may not sound entirely natural and idiomatic to modern readers, is still understandable. In these texts the Malay translation plays a particularly important role, and given that they are elementary in nature, it is acceptable that other forms of interlinear materials are largely sidelined.

23 DS 0043 00014

24 DS 0043 00005 p. 101v

Behind Grammatical Literalism

In his pioneering 1899 article, the Dutch scholar Ph. S. van Ronkel demonstrated the apparent influence of Arabic syntactic structure on Malay language through works of translation.²⁵ Peter G. Riddell similarly observed this tendency in a Malay rendering of a Qur'an commentary—a phenomenon he terms *translationese*.²⁶ In another study, Ricci further illustrates how interlinear translation reflects shifts in word order, subject–verb position, tense, and emphasis, resulting from the practice of word-for-word translation. In a particularly striking formulation, she characterizes this phenomenon as one in which Arabic grammar “glues together” Malay vocabulary in the interlinear rendering. She concludes her observations with an open question: how and why did such models come into being?²⁷

The phenomenon of Malay vocabulary being structured according to Arabic grammatical rules is referred to in this article as *grammatical literalism*. While literal translation is conventionally understood as a word-for-word rendering from one language to another, the grammatical disparities between Arabic and Malay—such as those involving tense, number, and gender—mean that many features explicit in Arabic remain unexpressed in Malay. This discrepancy prompts translators to accommodate these differences, often at the expense of the natural grammatical structure of Malay as the target language. This section explores such issues of grammatical literalism in the surau manuscript tradition, demonstrating that its translation practices are consistent with the observations made by the aforementioned scholars. It will also consider a possible answer to the question Ricci has raised regarding the origins of such translation models.

The preceding section has demonstrated that translation constitutes only one among several forms of interlinear intervention within the surau manuscript tradition. It has also been shown that the majority of surau manuscript collections containing translation feature interlinear translation applied on an occasional basis. In view of this, to what extent can such interlinear intervention be meaningfully associated with literalism, given that the translation appears only in truncated or fragmentary form?

We are fortunate that, although limited in number, the surau manuscript tradition preserves texts containing line-by-line interlinear translation, as previously noted. These texts enable a more sustained engagement with the question of grammatical literalism in translation practices within the surau manuscript tradition, and thus serve as important points of reference in discussions of other, more occasional interlinear texts. The following example offers a compelling illustration of the tendency towards literalism in interlinear translation:

25 Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat Arab Terhadap Tatakalimat Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528.

26 Peter G. Riddell, “Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay,” *Studia Islamika* 9, no. 2 (2002): 23, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/sdi.v9i1.672>.

27 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 76.

3. *I'lam anna al-fi'l 'alā ayy binā' kāna lā yakhlū min an yakūna ṣaḥīḥan aw muḍā'afan ... (Know that the verb, in whatever pattern it may be, is not devoid of being either ṣaḥīḥ or muḍā'af ...)*²⁸

Ketahui olehmu bahwasanya segala fi'l atas barang bina ada iya tiada sunyi daripada bahwa keadaannya bina ṣaḥīḥ atau bina muḍā'af ... (Know by you that every fi'l upon whatever bina it may be, its state is not devoid of being (either) bina ṣaḥīḥ or bina muḍā'af...)

The original Arabic sentence in this example is relatively straightforward; nonetheless, the translator appears to have attempted to render each word individually, maintaining a strict one-to-one correspondence between source text and translation. The phrase *olehmu* (by you) is used to translate an unexpressed pronoun functioning as the object of the imperative verb *i'lam* (know). The semantic subtlety conveyed by the definite article *al-* in *al-fi'l*, which implies *shumūl* (wholeness), is also translated, resulting in *al-fi'l* being rendered as *segala fi'l* (every *fi'l*). The term *fi'l* itself is left untranslated, as it functions here as a technical linguistic concept. The appositive phrase *'alā ayy binā' kāna* (in whatever pattern it may be) is rendered word for word, producing an unnatural formulation: *atas barang bina ada iya* (upon whatever bina it may be). A similarly literal rendering of *min an yakūna* (being either) likewise results in an awkward construction. The unnatural nature of the translation of *kāna* and *yakūna* (both mean “[to] be” in the different declensions) in this example is entirely consistent with Van Ronkel’s observation of the same issue.²⁹ In such cases, Riddell’s observation seems particularly apt: even Malay readers “probably had even greater headaches trying to understand” *atas barang bina dia*.³⁰ It is only by referring back to the Arabic sentence that one can make proper sense of the intended meaning.

It has been noted that the primary distinction between line-by-line interlinear translation and occasional translation lies in the fact that the former yields a complete sentence in translation, while the latter provides only individual words or particles without forming a coherent or meaningful expression. Based on the way grammatical literalism is explained above, one way to identify literalism in occasional interlinear translation is to assume that close attention to linguistic details—such as gender, number, and tense—may serve as an indicator of a grammatically literal rendering. This assumption rests on the understanding that occasional translation essentially constitutes a written record of oral translation practices that took place in didactic settings. If such details as gender and number inflection, or other subtle features, are inscribed in occasional interlinear form, this suggests that they were also observed during the oral translation process. It was not uncommon for oral translation to be accompanied by extended explanatory remarks. However, the full extent of the oral translator’s elaboration was not necessarily transcribed onto the written page, thereby resulting in the fragmentary form of occasional interlinear translation preserved in the manuscript.

²⁸ DS 0043 00045, 8r.

²⁹ Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat*, 17.

³⁰ Riddell, “Literal Translation,” 23.

From this perspective, it becomes evident that manuscripts containing occasional inter-linear translation demonstrate a clear tendency towards literal translation. This is due to the fact that such manuscripts reflect the translator’s or reader’s attentiveness to fine-grained linguistic details, even when the translation is not exhaustive. The manifestations of this attentiveness are varied. Figs 3, 4, and 5 illustrate how occasional interlinear translation reveals the translator’s deep grammatical sensibilities. In Fig. 3, for instance, the word *al-jumal* (sentences) is translated with *segala* (all). Here, *segala* does not represent a full lexical translation of *al-jumal* but rather reflects a partial rendering—specifically, the semantic import of the definite article *al-* which semantically signifies *shumūl* (wholeness). The noun *jumal* itself is left untranslated.

In Fig. 4, the word *shahāda* (a testimony) is translated as *sempurna* (perfect). As with the previous example, this translation does not reflect the entire lexical content of the Arabic word but instead captures its semantic connotation, its being grammatically a *maf’ūl muṭlaq* (cognate accusative). That is, the translator chooses to convey the emphatic or intensifying function of the word rather than translate the noun *shahāda* directly. Also in Fig. 5, only a single word is translated across two visible lines—namely, *al-salāṭīn* (kings), which is rendered as *raja2* (the numeral indicating reduplication, hence “raja-raja” or “kings,” to denote plurality). This translation highlights the plural form of the Arabic original. This choice underscores the translator’s attention to number inflection—an important grammatical detail that might otherwise be lost in an occasional interlinear context.

These examples collectively demonstrate that occasional translation, while fragmentary on the surface, is in fact highly attentive to the structural and semantic details of the Arabic text. It reflects a deep engagement with the linguistic substance of the source, despite not offering a full linear rendering. Though it may appear random or haphazard, a closer examination of texts featuring such translation reveals that most basic verb inflections and grammatical features are, in fact, accommodated within the translation. This way, the occasional written interventions between the lines function not merely as translations but as interpretive cues or prompts that facilitate oral reading, teaching, and comprehension of the source text as well as reinforcement of Arabic grammatical knowledge.

Fig. 3 *Qaṭr al-nadā*’ by Abū ‘Abdullāh Jamāl al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf ibn Hishām al-Anṣārī (d. 761/1360), DS 0043 00006, 1v

Fig. 4 *al-Sanūsī* by Abū ‘Abdillāh Abū Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf al-Sanūsī al-Ḥusaynī (d. 895/1490), DS 0043 00019, 178r

Fig. 5 *Tanbīh al-māshī* by ‘Abd al-Ra’uf al-Sinkīlī al-Jāwī (d. 1693), DS 0043 00018, 12v

However, the Surau Simaung collections show that such literalism is not the exclusive property of interlinear translation. Running-sequential translation also follows the same tendency. Note that the source consulted by Riddell in his aforementioned study for the argument of *translationese* is not an interlinear translation. Just like the case with Ricci’s source in the Sri Lankan Malay manuscript, example 4 follows the original Arabic that commences the clause with a verb-subject order, something that is not conventional for Malay.³¹

4. *qaddasa-llāhu sirrahu* artinya dipersucikan Allah ta‘ālā rahasianya ([may] sanctified Allah his secret which means sanctified [by] Allah may He be Exalted his secret)³²

³¹ Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 72.

³² In this and the following example, the underlined English corresponds to the underlined Arabic sentence.

5. ... *wa ja'ala al-jannata maskanahu wa mathwāhu* dan yang menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan akan dia kediamannya (...and He made Paradise his dwelling and his abode and that which makes Paradise a dwelling of a believer and it his abode)

Example 5 provides a more compelling illustration of how Arabic syntax, even outside an interlinear format, structurally binds Malay vocabulary to the original. This includes elements that are not explicitly present in the Arabic text but are syntactically implied. Each word in the Malay translation is anchored to an Arabic counterpart: *wa* (and) becomes *dan* (and), *ja'ala* (he made) becomes *menjadikan* (makes), *al-jannata* (the garden) becomes *surga* (paradise), and *maskanahu* (his dwelling) is rendered as *tempat mukmin* (a dwelling of a believer). In this last case, the pronoun *-hu* in *maskanahu* is resolved by referring back to *mu'min*, a noun mentioned earlier in the text. Notably, the word *yang* (that/which) in *dan yang menjadikan* (that which makes) has no direct lexical counterpart in the Arabic, but its presence is informed by the syntactic role of *wa* (and) at the beginning of the expression. This conjunction links *ja'ala* (he made) to a preceding verb, *ḥafīza* (he protected), which itself follows *alladhī* (those), a relative pronoun typically translated as *yang* in Malay. Thus, the translator's insertion of *yang* signals an awareness of the underlying conjunctive structure of the Arabic.

The phrase *dan akan dia kediamannya* (and it his abode) for *wa mathwāhu* (and his abode) reflects an impressive syntactic sensitivity. Here, *dan* (and) corresponds to *wa* (and), functioning as a conjunction linking *maskanahu* (his dwelling) and *mathwāhu* (his abode). A straightforward translation might have rendered the passage as *menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan kediamannya* ([to] make Paradise a dwelling of a believer and his abode). However, the translator chooses *menjadikan surga akan tempat mukmin dan akan dia kediamannya* (makes Paradise a dwelling of a believer and [make] it his abode), revealing a distinct grammatical interpretation. Rather than viewing *wa* as connecting *maskanahu* and *mathwāhu* directly, the translator appears to interpret *wa* as linking two complete predicates: *al-jannata maskanahu* and (*hiya*) *mathwāhu*. The subject *hiya* is not textually present but is understood through *ellipsis* (*muqaddara*), a common feature in Arabic whereby syntactic elements are omitted yet implied. It refers back to *al-jannata* (the garden), a feminine noun. Accordingly, the phrase *akan dia kediamannya* reflects this: *akan* indicates the object, *dia* realizes the elided pronoun *hiya*, and *kediamannya* renders *mathwāhu*, with the possessive *-nya* (his) pointing back to *mu'min*.

In his study, Riddell argues that the tendency towards *translationese* is inherited from the literal scriptural translation that was observed by 'Abd al-Ra'ūf al-Sinkīlī, the author of *Tarjumān al-mustafīd* that he consulted, while the *Tarjumān* author was in the Middle East.³³ This argument situates the Qur'anic text and its translation at the core of a literal impulse. Van Ronkel in his study also emphasized the role of the Qur'an in this respect alongside *fiqh*.³⁴ The manuscripts from Surau Simaung, however, suggest that this technique of translation may not directly related to scriptural translation, nor is it exclusive to *fiqh*

33 Riddell, "Literal Translation," 10.

34 Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat*, 37.

literature. Rather, it derives from the prevailing approach to studying Islamic texts within the tradition of post-classical scholasticism.

Commentary and gloss constituted the dominant modes of intellectual composition in post-classical Islam, spanning the sixteenth to nineteenth centuries.³⁵ Significantly, the majority of texts in the surau collection fall within this category. Texts featuring running-sequential translation, although original compositions by Malay authors, are deeply rooted in Arabic Islamic scholastic works. They function primarily as commentaries on selected passages extracted from these Arabic source texts as well as their own texts.³⁶ Likewise, texts with interlinear translation are rarely devoid of glosses and marginal annotations. Another key feature of the post-classical intellectual tradition was its sustained preoccupation with the lexical, rhetorical, and logical dimensions of the commented-upon texts. Within this approach, substantial portions of the commentary are often devoted to lexicographical treatment of individual words.³⁷ The surau texts strongly resonate with this mode of inquiry, and this orientation is clearly reflected in their translation practices.

Page | 118

Arabic language texts occupy a prominent place in the Surau Simaung collection. The most illustrative examples in this context are works belonging to the genres of *tarkīb* (structure; composition) and *i'rāb* (the system of declension). These are derivative, commentarial genres that focus on the linguistic analysis of a base text. It remains a subject of inquiry whether *tarkīb* and *i'rāb* represent distinct genres or are essentially the same with different names. The evidence from Surau Simaung, however, indicates that *i'rāb* tends to involve a more detailed analysis than *tarkīb*. In the collection, we find three different copies of *Tarkīb al-ʿawāmil*, one copy of *Tarkīb al-Ājurrūmiyya*, and one of *I'rāb matan al-kāfiya*.

The *tarkīb/i'rāb* genre demonstrates that such linguistic analysis was not merely applied as a method of examining texts, but also gave rise to a distinct genre of intellectual endeavour in its own right. Each of these texts investigates the linguistic features of individual words within their respective base texts—namely, *al-ʿAwāmil*, *Ājurrūmiyya*, and *Matan al-kāfiya*. They explore the types of words or particles mentioned, their syntactic positions, grammatical inflection (*i'rāb*), and morphological patterns, number, semantic connotation, and other relevant linguistic features. Fig. 6 illustrates how *tarkīb* functions. The text in red represents the base text, while the black text—breaking down the base text, largely into individual words—constitutes a linguistic analysis of each word or phrase from the Arabic source. This particular page offers only minimal commentary for most of the words, although it is not uncommon to find pages containing more elaborate explanations. This analysis extends beyond the level of individual words, encompassing phrases and clauses as well.

35 Ahmed El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition* (Princeton University Press, 2020), 9; 31.

36 Mahmood Kooria, *Islamic Law in Circulation: Shāfiʿī Texts across the Indian Ocean and the Mediterranean*, Cambridge Studies in Islamic Civilization (Cambridge University Press, 2022), 327.

37 El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics*, 35.

Fig. 6 *Tarkīb al-‘awāmil*, DS 0043 00004

The concept of ellipsis (*muqaddara*) is integral to understanding the practice of Malay translation. In Arabic grammar, the principle is that a sentence must complete all the basic structural elements, whether it is a nominal or verbal sentence. When a structural element is missing, it is the reader’s duty to analyse the construction and supply the implied component.

Fig. 6 illustrates how the *basmala* formula is linguistically analysed in the *tarkīb* genre. The full *basmala* phrase—*bi-smi-‘l-lāh al-raḥmān al-raḥīm*—is divided into four segments, each written in red ink. Interspersed between these segments is the grammatical explanation, written in black ink. The first segment, *bi-smi* (in the name [of]), is analysed beginning with the identification of *bā’* as a *ḥarf jarr* (preposition) and *ism* as a *majrūr* (a noun governed by a preposition), resulting from the effect of *bā’*. The analysis then proceeds to determine the grammatical position of *bi-smi* as a phrase linked to an ellipsis (*al-maḥzūf*). The text then provides the resolution, stating *taqdīruhu abtadi’ u bi-smi...* (its *taqdīr*, “implied phrase,” is: I commence in the name [of]...). This analysis explains the way authors and translators render the *basmala* whenever composing or copying a text, by expressions such as *Kumulai membaca kitab ini...* (I begin to read this book...) or *Kumulai risalah ini...* (I begin this treatise...). This case illustrates an expansion of meaning proposed by translators, transmitting an Arabic linguistic examination of the sentence into Malay.

The manuscript collection of Surau Simaung demonstrates that this mode of intellectual inquiry remained deeply embedded within surau communities. The study of Arabic undertaken in these settings was not merely a theoretical endeavour grounded in standard textbooks—such as the *Ājurrūmiyya*, *Qaṭr al-nadā’*, *Alfiyya Ibn Mālik*, *al-Kāfiyya*, and *al-‘Awāmil*, together with their accompanying *sharḥ* (commentaries)—but was also complemented by practical engagement with the *tarkīb* and *i’rāb* traditions. This analytical approach was not limited to linguistic texts; works from other disciplines were likewise

subjected to grammatical scrutiny. Although we currently lack evidence of texts in other fields—such as *kalām*, mysticism, and others³⁸—developing into distinct genres akin to *tarkīb* and *i‘rāb*, linguistic annotations, whether brief or elaborate, are nonetheless commonly found beneath the lines or in the margins of many texts. Not limited to interlinear translation, this grammatical attentiveness is also reflected in running-sequential translations. For instance, when ‘Abd al-Šamad explicates the core theological formula *lā ilāha illā-‘l-lāh* (there is no God but Allah), he begins by analysing the type of *lā* used in the phrase and outlining its semantic implications.

Translation in this context reflects a deeper concern on the part of Malay translators from the surau community than merely bridging two different languages. Snouck Hurgronje’s observation of the difficulties faced by Southeast Asian Muslim communities in learning and reading Arabic can be understood as their effort to overcome the language barrier—particularly given Arabic’s considerably more complex grammatical structure compared to Malay.³⁹ While the difference in language is undeniably a significant factor in any act of translation, the tradition of Arabic translation in the surau goes beyond this. Linguistic difference is part of the puzzle, but not its foundation. What lies at the core is textual examination.

For this reason, the conventional definition of translation—such as: “reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source-language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style”⁴⁰—fails to capture the nature of translation within the Malay/Minangkabau surau tradition. This textual corpus of Surau Simaung shows that for the surau communities, translation was not primarily a matter of seeking equivalents in Malay, but first and foremost an exercise in textual examination. The accuracy of translation lay not in finding a natural equivalent in Malay, but in the successful exploration of all the grammatical details of the Arabic text. Clarity lies not in seamless, idiomatic Malay expression, but rather in the strongest resonance with the original semantic connotation of the Arabic expression. Ricci suggests that interlinear translation “divulges the detailed mechanism of translating prepositions, markers of gender, case, and tense into a very different linguistic context.”⁴¹ Indeed, the actual practice of translation was the transfer of Arabic textual analysis into Malay. For the surau communities, translation was an act of textual analysis of Arabic in the vernacular; it thus became the vernacular practice of a post-classical linguistic examination of texts.

38 A comparable genre of text is found in *tajwīd*, in which the author examines the *tajwīd* rules for every individual word of the Qur’an (DS 0043 0008, p. 70r).

39 C. Snouck Hurgronje, *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslems of the East-Indian Archipelago* (Brill, 2007), 284. On this question see Ricci’s article in the present issue.

40 Eugene A. Nida and Charles R. Taber, *The Theory and Practice of Translation* (Brill, 1982), 12.

41 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 78.

Conclusion

The surau functioned as a vibrant ecosystem for the transmission of Islamic texts in the Minangkabau world, where scholars and students engaged in the continuous practice of teaching, reading, and translating texts. The Surau Simaung collection stands as a remarkable testament to this tradition, comprising 88 manuscripts and 209 texts. The collection spans works from the early Malay scholars at the turn of the seventeenth century to texts produced well into the twentieth century, offering a broad and rich corpus for understanding the surau textual tradition.

This study has shown that translation practices in the surau were diverse, encompassing holistic, running-sequential, and interlinear paradigms. Among these, occasional interlinear translation predominates, revealing a distinctive form of grammatical literalism rooted in the Arabic linguistic structure. This grammatical literalism, noted as early as Van Ronkel's observations, reflects a deliberate and nuanced engagement with Arabic grammar, lexicon, and syntax—a reflection of post-classical scholarly practices.

What emerges from the Surau Simaung corpus is not simply a record of Malay translations of Arabic texts, but a vernacularized mode of textual analysis. Translation functioned as an instrument of grammatical inquiry, enabling students to penetrate the structure and meaning of Arabic discourse through the medium of Malay. This approach departs from conventional models of translation as equivalence, and instead foregrounds translation as a pedagogical and analytical act.

At its core, translation in the surau tradition was a vernacular expression of the post-classical Islamic intellectual project. Translation, in this context, was not primarily about finding lexical equivalents in Malay, but fundamentally an exercise in textual analysis. Its accuracy was measured not by how naturally it read in Malay, but by how thoroughly it engaged with the grammatical structure of the Arabic source. Clarity was achieved not through idiomatic fluency, but through the closest possible alignment with the semantic nuance of the original Arabic expression. The surau thus emerges not only as a site of transmission, but as a site of transformation: where Arabic knowledge traditions were not merely received but reconstituted through local, oral, and linguistically exacting modes of engagement.

References

- ANWAR, Khaidir. "Minangkabau, Background of the Main Pioneers of Modern Standard Malay in Indonesia." *Archipel* 12, no. 1 (1976): 77–93. <https://doi.org/10.3406/arch.1976.1296>.
- AZRA, Azyumardi. *Surau: Pendidikan Islam Tradisi dalam Transisi dan Modernisasi*. PT. Logos Wacana Ilmu, 2003.
- BRUCKMAYR, Philipp. "The Šarḥ/Hāšiya Phenomenon in Southeast Asia: From al-Sanūsī's Umm al-Barāhīn to Malay Sifat Dua Puluh Literature." *MIDÉO. Mélanges de l'Institut Dominicain d'études Orientales*, no. 32 (May 15, 2017): 27–52.
- DOBBIN, Christine. *Kebangkitan Islam dalam Ekonomi Petani yang Sedang Berubah, Sumatra Tengah, 1784–1847*, translated by Lillian D. Tedjasudana. INIS, 1992.

- DRAKARD, Jane. "A Kingdom of Words: Minangkabau Sovereignty in Sumatran History." PhD. Dissertation, The Australian National University, 1993.
- EL SHAMSY, Ahmed. *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition*. Princeton University Press, 2020.
- FATHURAHMAN, Oman. "Naskah dan Rekonstruksi Sejarah Lokal Islam; Contoh Kasus dari Minangkabau." *Wacana* 7, no. 2 (2005).
- HADLER, Jeffrey. *Muslims and Matriarchs: Cultural Resilience in Indonesia through Jihad and Colonialism*. Cornell University Press, 2008. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.7591/j.ctt7zc7n>.
- KOORIA, Mahmood. *Islamic Law in Circulation: Shāfiʿī Texts across the Indian Ocean and the Mediterranean*. Cambridge Studies in Islamic Civilization. Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- MAFTUHIN, Arif. "Translating the Untranslatable: The Jalālayn Learning as a Translation Practice." *Indonesia and the Malay World*, January 4, 2024, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2264672>.
- NIDA, Eugene A., and Charles R. Taber. *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Brill, 1982.
- PRAMONO. *Khazanah Naskah Minangkabau*. Penerbit Erka, 2018.
- RICCI, Ronit. "Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation." *Journal of World Literature* 1, no. 1 (2016): 68–80. <https://doi.org/10.1163/24056480-00101008>.
- . "Story, Sentence, Single Word: Translation Paradigms in Javanese and Malay Islamic Literature." In *A Companion to Translation Studies*, by Sandra Bermann and Catherine Porter, 543–56. Blackwell Companions to Literature and Culture 86. West Sussex: Wiley Blackwell, 2014.
- RIDDELL, Peter G. "Literal Translation, Sacred Scripture and Kitab Malay." *Studia Islamika* 9, no. 2 (2002): 1–28. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15408/sdi.v9i1.672>.
- SNOUCK HURGRONJE, C. *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslems of the East-Indian Archipelago*. Brill, 2007.
- RONKEL, Ph. S. van. *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalam Arab Terhadap Tatakalam Melayu*, translated by A. Ikram. Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as "Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische," *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528
- VOORHOEVE, P. *Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Sumatra*. Bibliographical Series 1. Netherlands: 1955.
- YUSUF, M, ed. *Katalogus Manuskrip dan Skriptorium Minangkabau*. C-DATS-TUFS, 2006.

Ingenuity Between the Lines: *Interlinear Translation from Arabic to Malay to Vernacular in Mindanao*

MIDORI KAWASHIMA (Professor Emeritus, Sophia University, Tokyo)¹

Abstract

This article discusses the development, characteristics, and significance of interlinear translations in Mindanao, in the southern Philippines. This is a topic that has received little attention thus far. Focusing on the Lanao region, the article analyzes interlinear translations from Arabic to Malay and Maranao, the region's vernacular language, that are found in four books of hadiths.

The analysis revealed that interlinear translation did not simply replace Arabic words with their equivalents in the target language. Rather, it was an intellectual endeavor in which scholars exercised their ingenuity. The study also sheds light on the region's linguistic practices and demonstrates the influence of the Maranao language on the development of a local variation of Malay. The most significant contribution of the Maranao Muslims to interlinear translation was creating interlinear translations in their own language. This marked a departure from their previous reliance on Malay as an auxiliary language for studying Arabic and Islam. Reformist Maranao Muslim scholars emphasized correctly understanding the meaning of Qur'anic verses and hadiths, so they created interlinear translations in their own language to replace Malay.

Interlinear translation in the vernacular played a significant role in developing Islamic literature in the region. By creating these translations, Muslim scholars developed the ability to carefully read and interpret Arabic texts and convey their meanings accurately and clearly in Maranao. These translations nurtured authorship and readership, paving the way for the later flourishing of vernacular Islamic literary culture.

Keywords: Maranao, interlinear translation, Arabic, Malay, The Philippines, Mindanao, hadith literature

Introduction

Islamic manuscripts containing Malay interlinear translations of the Arabic originals were widely used by Malay-speaking Muslims in Southeast Asia. Muslims on the island of

¹ I would like to thank Dr Ronit Ricci and Dr Fadhli Lukman for their comments on an earlier version of this article. I am also indebted to Dr Moctar Matuan for his advice on the Maranao language. However, I take full responsibility for any errors. Fig. 4, 8, 10a, 10d, and 19–20 were photographed by Midori Kawashima in 2024. Fig. 2–5, 6–7, 9, 10b and 10c, 11–16, 18, and 21 were photographed by Midori Kawashima and her team in 2012. Field trips to the Philippines were supported by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science Research Grant (JSPS-KAKENHI 17K03144 and 20K02007).

Mindanao in the southern Philippines are no exception. To what extent was this practice transmitted to, and adopted by Muslims in Mindanao? What are the characteristics of their interlinear translation? Did they add their own innovations? What role did interlinear translation play in the development of Islam in Mindanao? This article aims to answer these questions and shed light on the intellectual activities of Muslims in Mindanao. The article will focus on four works dealing with hadiths—three manuscripts and a lithographed book—created and used by Muslims in the Lanao region of Mindanao from the late 18th to the mid-20th century. The article will analyze the interlinear translations found in these works, identify general trends and characteristics, and discuss the significance of interlinear translation.

First, I will provide an overview of the Lanao region, its language and script, and a brief history of the interlinear translation in the region. Next, I will describe the four books of hadith, referred to as Books A through D. The following three sections will examine interlinear translations from Arabic to Malay, from Arabic to Maranao (the region’s vernacular language), and from Arabic to both Malay and Maranao.² Lastly, I will discuss the characteristics and significance of interlinear translations in the Lanao region.

Background

Region, Language, and Script

The term “the Lanao region” is used to refer to the geographical area under the jurisdiction of the provinces of Lanao del Sur and Lanao del Norte, located in the central part of the island of Mindanao. The Islamization of Mindanao and Sulu progressed in conjunction with that of other parts of maritime Southeast Asia through visits by Muslim traders and missionaries. The Sulu and Magindanao³ sultanates were established in the mid-15th and early 16th centuries, respectively. In 1570, the Spaniards arrived in Manila. Subsequently, they established colonial rule over most parts of Luzon and Visayas and conducted military expeditions to Mindanao and Sulu to spread Catholicism and occupy certain areas. Muslim rulers resisted the Spanish advances, resulting in intermittent warfare. Consequently, Islam became confined to the Mindanao and Sulu islands.⁴ As a result, from the Spanish period until now, Muslims in the Philippines have primarily lived on the Mindanao and Sulu islands and their adjacent islands to the south. The vast majority of the Muslims in the Philippines are Sunni, like other Southeast Asian Muslims.

Muslims in the Philippines consist of several ethnic groups and each group has its own language, social structure, tradition of governance, and cultural practices. The Maranaos, a Muslim ethnic group who speak the language of the same name, predominantly inhabit the Lanao region (see Map 1). The Maranao language belongs to the Greater Central Philippine Language subgroup and is closely related to the Magindanao and Iranun languages of the Philippines and the Iranun language of Sabah in Malaysia. The Maranao language used to be

2 The term “Maranao” is also written as “Maranaw,” “Meranao,” “Meranaw,” or “Muranau.”

3 Also written as Maguindanao, Magindanaw, or Magindanawon.

4 Cesar Adib Majul, *Muslims in the Philippines* (Saint Mary’s Publishing, 1978).

written in the Arabic script with some modifications, which is similar to Malay *Jawi*, although the former usually has vowel marks while the latter does not. The Maranao people called their literature such as epics and poems written in Arabic script *kirim*, while some use the term *batang Arab* (Arabic letters) for other documents and manuscripts, including Islamic manuscripts. In this article, I use the term *Jawi* to refer to the Arabic script used in Malay and other Austronesian languages, including Maranao. On the other hand, Frank C. Laubach, an American Protestant missionary who arrived in the Lanao region in 1929, developed a Latin script-based writing system for the Maranao language and led a literacy campaign using it during the 1930s.⁵ This system gradually gained popularity with the spread of public education in the region. By the late 20th century, the majority of the Maranao people had adopted the Latin script to write their language.

Map 1 Major Ethnic Groups Comprising Muslim Population in the Philippines⁶

The writing tradition and manuscript culture in Mindanao and Sulu developed under the strong influence of the Malay writing tradition and manuscript culture. Malay was the lingua franca in maritime Southeast Asia, including Mindanao, and it was the main language for

5 For Laubach’s literacy campaign in the Lanao region see Midori Kawashima, “Islamic Reformism and an American Protestant Missionary: Contest over the Publication of the Qur’anic Verses in Mindanao under the US Colonial Rule,” *Sophia Journal of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies*, no. 34 (2016). 191-195; Frank C. Laubach, *The Philippines Literacy Method* (Boston, 1936); Frank C. Laubach, *Forty Years with the Silent Billion* (Fleming H. Revell Company, 1970).

6 Adapted from the map in Peter Gowing, ed., *Muslim Filipinos – Heritage and Horizon* (New Day Publishers, 1979), reverse of the front cover.

trade and the transmission of Islamic knowledge. Until the mid-20th century, Islamic scholars and students in Mindanao relied on Malay manuscripts and books, as well as on Arabic ones, as primary sources of religious knowledge. Popular religious figures skilled in traditional medicine, divination, and other such arts also used Malay works as a source of their knowledge.

Interlinear Translation in the Lanao Region: A Brief History

It is difficult to determine when the practice of interlinear translation first reached the Lanao region because few of the old manuscripts have survived. Besides, many of the surviving manuscripts lack a date. Even when a date is provided, it is often unclear whether it refers to the writing of the original or its copying. Of the manuscripts I have examined thus far, the oldest with an interlinear translation and reliable date indications is a compilation of hadiths referred to as *Book A* in this article. This work is part of the manuscript collection inherited by the family of the late Muhammad Amer Guro sa Masiu (d. ca. 2012) in the town of Taraka, Lanao del Sur (Ms 8).⁷ This collection will be referred to as the Guro sa Masiu Collection, or GM for short, hereafter. Dated AH 1212 (AD 1797–1798), this manuscript contains interlinear Malay translations of nearly the entire Arabic text. Since it was written by Maranao scholars from the Lanao region, the method of interlinear translation must have been introduced beforehand, likely by traveling scholars. This book will be examined in detail in the following sections (see also Fig. 5 below).

Another early work with interlinear translations is a manuscript compiled by Tuan Muhammad Said. He was an Islamic scholar from the town of Binidayan in the Lanao region and was also known as *Sayyidna* and *Haji sa Binidayan* (Haji of Binidayan). His descendants inherited this manuscript, which is known by the title *Ahl al-sunnah wa-al-jamā'ah* (Usman Imam Shiek al-Aman Collection, Ms 1).⁸ Tuan Muhammad Said made a pilgrimage to Mecca in the early 19th century. While traveling home, he stopped in Perlis, a port town on the west coast of the Malay Peninsula, where he wrote the manuscript. It is a compilation of brief Sufi texts, mostly in Malay and some in Arabic. Some of the Arabic texts are accompanied by their Malay interlinear translations, including a treatise entitled *Sakarāt al-mawt* (Advent of Death) (see Fig. 1). Later, his descendants transcribed it in a different format, writing the entire Arabic text first, followed by the Malay translation.⁹ Thus, the interlinear translation evolved into an independent translation.

7 *Guro sa Masiu* (Teacher of Masiu) is the title conferred on the religious leader in the *Pengampong* (principality) of Masiu, which is one of the *pat a pengampong* (four principalities) in the traditional ruling system of Lanao. For *Guro sa Masiu*, see Labi Sarip Riwarung, “The Qur’an and Prayer Scroll of Guro sa Masiu, Taraka,” in *The Qur’an and Islamic Manuscripts of Mindanao*, Monograph Series no. 10, ed. Midori Kawashima (Institute of Asian Cultures, Sophia University, 2012), 29.

8 For this manuscript and Tuan Muhammad Said, see Midori Kawashima, “Connecting Mindanao to Hijaz: The Journey of “Sayyidna” Tuan Muhammad Said,” in *The Library of an Islamic Scholar of Mindanao: The Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library, Marawi City, Philippines: An Annotated Catalogue with Essays*, Occasional Papers 27, eds. Oman Fathurahman, Midori Kawashima, and Labi Riwarung (Institute of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies, Sophia University, 2019), 73–128.

9 The two copies of *Sakarāt al-mawt* in the different format are found in the Collection of Sheik Muhammad

Fig. 1 *Sakar al-mawt*. Usman Imam Sheik Al-Aman Collection, Ms. I, f. 43r.

Some Arabic works with Malay interlinear translations appear to be relatively old, probably dating from the 19th or early 20th century. One example is *Baḥr lāhūrī*, which is generally known as *Baḥr al-lāhūt* (The Sea of Divinity), a treatise explaining Allah’s creation of all beings from a Sufi perspective (see Fig. 2).¹⁰ This work is found in the manuscript collection of a Maranao scholar from the town of Bayang, namely, Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang (b. c.1902, d. 1974) at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library in Marawi City (B4-

Said bin Imam sa Bayang in Marawi City (B1-Ms1 and B1-Ms3).

10 This work was identified by Oman Fathurahman.

Ms3). This collection will be referred to as Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, or SMS for short, hereafter.¹¹ An identical copy of this work, including the interlinear translation, exists in another manuscript in the same collection (B2-Ms7). This suggests that one of Sheik Muhammad Said’s descendants transcribed it verbatim, interlinear translation and all. Thus, the tradition of interlinear translation was inherited and reproduced.

Fig. 2 *Baḥr lāhūrī* [al-lāhūt], Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B4-Ms3, f.62r.

Another relatively old example of an interlinear translation can be found in an Arabic work titled *Kitāb al-sulṭān* (Book of the sultan), which translates to Malay as *Kitab pada*

11 This collection’s manuscripts are described in its annotated catalogue. See Fathurahman, Kawashima, and Riwarung, eds., *The Library*.

menyatakan sultan (Book explaining about the sultan). It is an excerpt from a treatise on Islamic jurisprudence titled *al-Mustahal* (The simple [work]), composed of several “books,” each dealing with a specific issue (SMS, B10-Ms1).¹² *Kitāb al-sulṭān* is one of these “books.” It quotes hadiths, including hadith *qudsi*, and describes the qualities and conditions required of sultans or rulers, as well as their duties. The space between the lines of the original text was too narrow to add an interlinear translation. Therefore, the translator copied the Arabic text onto separate sheets of paper with ample space between the lines and wrote the Malay interlinear translation. Then, the translator re-bound the manuscript with the newly written sheets into a new volume (See Fig. 3). Evidently, the interlinear translation was created by someone from the Lanao region because part of the text was written on the back of two 19th-century letters from the Magindanao sultans addressed to Maranao leaders in the Lanao region. Of the many issues covered in *al-Mustahal*, the translator must have been particularly interested in this book dealing with rulers. It is surmised that the scholar created the interlinear translation to thoroughly understand the text’s contents and to use the bilingual text for educational or advisory purposes.

Other relatively old Arabic manuscripts with Malay interlinear translations include a compilation of hadiths entitled *Ḥadīth arbaʿīn* (Forty hadiths), referred to as *Book B* in this article and discussed below (SMS, B7-Ms3), as well as an illuminated manuscript of *Mawlid sharaf al-anām* (The birth of the best of mankind), an account of the life of the Prophet Muhammad.¹³ Additionally, there is a list of frequently used Arabic words and their Malay translations that was presumably used for reading and translating Arabic texts into Malay (SMS, B7-Ms2). This vocabulary list will also be discussed below (see Fig. 11). Thus, Malay interlinear translation, a form that is part of the literary tradition of Islamic manuscripts in Southeast Asia, was accepted, developed, and became established in the Lanao region through its use, copying and creation.

The Maranao scholars also applied the same method to their own language, creating Maranao interlinear translations. This emerged as part of the movement to produce Islamic texts in Maranao. It is not clear when the first Islamic manuscript in Maranao was produced. Thus far, the oldest Islamic manuscripts from the Lanao region that can be reliably dated are from the 18th and early 19th centuries. They are almost exclusively in Arabic and Malay, with Maranao limited to brief notes, incantations, and spells.¹⁴ Later Maranao manuscripts, estimated to date from the late 19th to early 20th century, include books on Allah’s creation

12 The type of paper used in the manuscript and the Javanese marginal notes suggest that it originated in Java. For more information on this manuscript, see Fathurahman, Kawashima, and Riwarung, eds., *The Library*, 351–358.

13 Ahmad Bashir Collection, Ms 3. For images from this manuscript see Fig. 18–21 of Kawashima, ed., *The Qur’an and Islamic Manuscripts*. For additional information on the manuscript, see also Annabel Teh Gallop, “Islamic Manuscript Art of the Philippines,” in *The Qur’an and Islamic Manuscripts*, 79–80.

14 Older Maranao manuscripts likely exist in genres such as genealogy, agreements, and classic literature, including epics and poems.

Fig. 3 *Kitāb al-sultān*. Sheik Muhammad Said Collection. B10-Ms1. Right-hand page: Copy of *Kitāb al-sultān* with a Malay interlinear translation. Left-hand page: The Arabic text in the original manuscript. ff.180v.-181r.

Fig. 3a Beginning of *Kitāb al-sultān* in the original manuscript (enlarged). f.181r.

Fig. 3b Copy of the beginning of *Kitāb al-sulṭān* with the Malay interlinear translation. f. 179r.

based on Sufi cosmology (SMS, B2-Ms5) and Islamic jurisprudence (GM, Ms3). The latter contains a partial interlinear Maranao translation of an Arabic hadith text. There is also an Arabic book of hadiths with interlinear translations in both Malay and Maranao (SMS, B7-Ms8). This manuscript will be referred to as Book C and discussed below.

Interlinear translation was also adopted in lithographed Islamic books. Lithography was introduced to Southeast Asia in the early 19th century, initially in Batavia. From there, it spread to Palembang, Singapore and several other cities in Southeast Asia as well as Bombay. Lithography could reproduce familiar forms of handwritten manuscripts, including interlinear translations—diagonally written text in smaller letters between the lines of the main text. Some of the lithographed books produced in the late 19th and early 20th centuries contained interlinear translations in Malay, Javanese, Sundanese, and Buginese.¹⁵ Some of these books were brought to Mindanao by travelling scholars and returning hajjis. Fig. 4 illustrates this with a lithographed copy of *Daqā'iq al-akhbār fī dhikr al-jannah wa-al-nār* (Detailed reports on the account of Paradise and Hell), which deals with cosmological and eschatological issues, and contains a Javanese interlinear translation. This copy was found in the Guro sa Masiu Collection in the Lanao region. Therefore, Muslims in Mindanao were introduced to interlinear translation through these lithographic books as well as through manuscripts.

15 Cf. Ian Proudfoot, *Early Malay Printed Books: A Provisional Account of Materials Published in the Singapore-Malaysia Area up to 1920, Noting Holdings in Major Public Collections* (Academy of Malay Studies and the Library, University of Malaya, 1993), 29, 45–46, 76 (fn.181). See also Martin van Bruinessen “Kitab Kuning: Books in Arabic Script Used in the Pesantren Milieu: Comments on a New Collection in KITLV Library,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde van het Nederlandsch-Indie* 146, no. 2–3 (1990): 235; and Ronit Ricci, “Interlinear Translation in Print (Part 1),” *Interlinear Translation of the Month (blog)*, *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*, September 2024, <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/interlinear-translation-month-25>

Fig. 4 A Lithographed copy of *Daqa'iq al-akhbar* with Javanese interlinear translation found in the Guro sa Masiu Collection

Since the late 19th century, lithography was gradually replaced by typography.¹⁶ However, it was nearly impossible to use typography to reproduce interlinear translations in the above-

16 Proudfoot, *Early Malay Printed Books*, 45

mentioned familiar graphic forms because the process is complicated and difficult to implement. For this reason, works requiring interlinear translations in the traditional forms continued to be printed using lithography.

Another obstacle in the transition from lithography to typography was the vowel marks. While vowel marks are not normally used in the Malay Jawi script, they are fully used in Javanese, Sundanese, and Madurese texts written in Arabic script. The same is true for southern Philippine languages, such as Maranao, Magindanao, and Tausug. Although it is technically possible to print Arabic texts with vowel marks using typography, this method requires a unique typeface for each letter-vowel combination. This makes printing complicated and costly, often rendering it economically unfeasible. For example, when Spanish Jesuit missionary Jacinto Juanmartí had his book containing Magindanao text in Arabic script printed by an Arabic typography printing press in Singapore in 1888, he had to forgo vowel marks due to “insurmountable difficulties in rendering the Arabic characters with vowel marks.”¹⁷ Frank Laubach was also informed of these technical problems by the chief printer of *The Moro Outlook*, an English-Tausug semi-monthly bilingual newspaper launched by an agricultural school in Jolo in the 1920s. The newspaper was printed in Tausug Jawi script, which is fully vocalized, using typography.¹⁸ Due to these problems with typography, lithography continued to be used for printing texts in these languages in Arabic scripts. Consequently, lithographic books with interlinear translations in these languages survived well into the 20th century. This was the case with the Maranao language, which also typically uses vowel marks.

When Muslims in the Lanao region first printed Islamic books in the 1930s, they adopted lithography, a technology that could reproduce familiar forms of manuscripts, including vowel marks.¹⁹ This enabled them to continue the tradition of interlinear translation in printed books. The publication of Islamic books in Maranao was part of an Islamic reform movement led by Maranao scholars. In the late 1920s, a group of hajis from the region started an Islamic educational reform movement. In 1936, they organized the Kamilol Islam Society, an Islamic organization that aimed to establish Islam in the Lanao region in its presumed original, “complete” form.²⁰ A few years later, the society founded the region’s first modern Islamic school, or madrasa. During that same period, Laubach had been conducting a literacy campaign in Maranao using the Latin script, as mentioned above. Inspired by these activities, some Maranao scholars wrote Islamic books in Maranao in Jawi and had them printed in

17 Jacinto Juanmartí, *Compendio de historia universal desde la creación del mundo hasta la venida de Jesucristo y un breve vocabulario en Castellano y en Moro-Maguindanao por un padre Misionero dela Compañia de Jesús* (Imprenta de Koh Yew Hean, 1888), v–vi.

18 Frank C. Laubach, *Towards a Literate World* (Columbia University Press, 1938), 26–27.

19 For the beginning of the Maranao printing, see Midori Kawashima, “Early Maranao Printing in Mindanao: Maranao Books in Latin and Arabic scripts from the 1930s to 1950s,” in *Between Empires: Print Culture in the Philippines (1850-1930)*, edited by Benito Rial Costas and Marlon J. Sales (Brill, forthcoming).

20 The name of the society derived from the Arabic phrase *kāmil al-Islām*, which means “complete Islam.” For the Kamilol Islam Society, see Midori Kawashima, “The Islamic Reform Movement at Lanao in the Philippines during the 1930s: The Founding of the Kamilol Islam Society,” *The Journal of Sophia Asian Studies*, no. 27 (2009): 135–159.

lithographic presses in Singapore. One of these books included an interlinear Maranao translation (Book D below).²¹

Later, from the 1950s to the 1990s, several Maranao Islamic books containing Maranao interlinear translations were printed using mimeograph machines.²² Especially in the late 1960s, a group of Islamic school teachers in the Lanao area started a movement to publish Islamic books in Maranao Jawi to provide young people and the general public with reading material that was in line with Islamic values. They mimeographed Islamic books and sold them at affordable prices. One of them, *Parokonan*, is a prayer guide in which the Arabic text of the supplications was accompanied by a Maranao interlinear translation.²³ It seems to have been very popular because it was reprinted two years later. Another similar book which also included a Maranao interlinear translation was published in 1999.²⁴ Thus, the practice of Maranao interlinear translation survived well into the late 20th century.

However, by the late 20th century, the number of people using the Maranao Jawi script had declined, while more people were using the Latin script. This resulted in fewer Maranao Jawi Islamic books and a corresponding decline in interlinear translation. Most of the Maranao Islamic books currently sold in Lanao del Sur and in Muslim communities in Manila are written in the Latin script. Additionally, since the 2000s, computerized printing has replaced mimeograph printing, making interlinear translations difficult to reproduce. For this reason, new works with interlinear translations are almost unheard of today.

Description of the Four Books of Interlinear Hadiths

The four books of hadiths that will be discussed below are as follows.

Book A

Handwritten manuscript. Guro sa Masiu Collection, Ms8.

Title: *Kutub al-aḥādīth* (Books of the hadiths).

The colophon mentions the names of Datu Ulama and Datu Imam sa Masiu as the compilers or scribes.

21 Amir Husin Guro sa Masiu, *Hadīth al-Nabī ṣm* (Maṭba‘at Jāwī Farrisī, 1939). A copy of this book is held in the Guro sa Masiu Collection.

22 For the Maranao Jawi publications during this period, see Midori Kawashima, “‘Jawi’ (Batang Arab) Publication in Lanao, Philippines, from the 1950s to 1970s,” *The Journal of Sophia Asian Studies*, no. 27 (2009); and Labi Riwarung, Primo Salivio and Midori Kawashima, *A Catalogue of the Maisie Van Vactor Collection of Maranao Materials in the Arabic Script at the Gowing Memorial Research Center*, ed. Midori Kawashima (Institute of Asian Cultures, Sophia University, 2011).

23 Guro wa Alim Bayang ibn Ismail, *Parokonan* (Lanao del Sur, 1971–1972). From Maisie Van Vactor Collection, 039.

24 ‘Abd al-Ḥalīm Ambuloto, *Rāshid al-Islām* (Maṭba‘at al-Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ḥalīm Ambuloto, 1999). From Southeast Asian Kitab Collection of Sophia University, Tokyo.

Date: 1797–1798.

Language: Arabic with Malay interlinear translation.

59 folios.

Notes: This is a collection of hadiths consisting of forty chapters. The manuscript also contains several brief texts written in different handwritings. It does not include *isnād*, or the chain of narrators of a hadith. Each hadith begins with the phrase “*Qāla al-nabīy šm*”²⁵ (The Prophet šm said) which is rubricated. Interlinear translation is provided for most of the Arabic text, except for the aforementioned beginning phrase.

Fig. 5 Book A. ff.4v.–5r.

25 “šm” is an abbreviation of the honorific phrase *šallāllāhu ‘alayhi wa-sallam* (May Allah’s blessings and peace be upon him) in reference to the Prophet Muhammad.

Book B

Handwritten Manuscript. Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3.

Title: *Hadīth arba ‘īn* (Forty hadiths).

Author, compiler, or scribe: Anonymous.

Undated.

Language: Arabic with Malay interlinear translation.

44 folios.

Notes: This work is written from f.1r to f.23r. It is different from the famous Forty Hadiths compiled by Abū Zakarīyā Yaḥyā ibn Sharaf al-Nawawī al-Dimashqī (d. 1278).²⁶ This work includes *isnād* for all the hadiths. Interlinear translation is provided for all the Arabic text, except the phrase “*Qāla rasūlullāhi ṣallāllāhu ‘alayhi wa-sallam.*”

Fig. 6 Book B. ff.2v.–3r.

26 Al-Nawawī’s *Forty Hadiths* has been translated and commented on in various languages and is widely used by Muslims in Southeast Asia.

Book C

Handwritten Manuscript. Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms8.

Title: *Kitāb al-hadīth* (Book of hadith).

Author, compiler, or scribe: Anonymous.

Undated.

Language: Arabic with Malay interlinear translation. Part of the text is further accompanied by Maranao interlinear translation, which was likely written by Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang between 1930 to 1974.

26 folios.

Notes: This work does not include *isnād*. Each hadith begins with the phrase “*Qāla al-nabī ṣallāllāhu ‘alayhi wa-sallam*” which is rubricated. Interlinear translation in Malay is provided for all the Arabic text except for the aforementioned beginning phrase.

Fig. 7 Book C. ff.23v.–24r.

Book D

Lithographed book. Guro sa Masiu Collection.

Title in Arabic: *Hadīth al-Nabī ṣm* (Hadith of the Prophet ṣm)

Title in Maranao: *Tothol o Nabi* (Story from the Prophet).

Written by Amir Husin Guro sa Masiu ibn ‘Abd Allāh ibn Shaykh Shahīd Allāh.

Printer: Maṭba‘at Jāwī Farrisī, Singapore.

Date of publication: 1939.

Language: Arabic with Maranao interlinear translation.

60 pages.

Notes: The copy is incomplete. This work is written on pages 3–14. It does not include *isnād*. Each hadith begins with the phrase “*Qāla al-nabī ṣallāllāhu ‘alayhi wa-sallam.*” Interlinear translation is provided for the entire text except for the aforementioned phrase.

Fig. 8 Book D. pp.12–13.

Arabic to Malay Interlinear Translation

Previous studies have noted the consistency with which Arabic words and phrases are translated into Malay in interlinear translations.²⁷ For instance, certain Arabic words and expressions, including prepositions and conjunctions, are typically translated into specific Malay words. This standardizes the interlinear translation method from Arabic to Malay. However, despite this general tendency toward uniformity, interlinear translations may reveal unintentional or intentional changes in nuance or meaning, creating variations, as discussed by Ronit Ricci.²⁸ This section examines the two inherent natures of Malay interlinear translation: uniformity and variation. First, we will focus on the tendency toward standardization by examining a hadith from Book A, followed by an Arabic-Malay vocabulary that presumably played a crucial role in standardizing the interlinear translation. Next, we will examine the tendency toward variation in Books A through C.²⁹

Standard Pattern of Interlinear Translation

An Example from Book A

As mentioned above, the basic principle of an interlinear translation from Arabic to Malay is to replace each Arabic word with an equivalent Malay word while maintaining the original word order. To illustrate this principle, let us examine the following hadith cited in this manuscript.³⁰

Whoever recites the two sermons incorrectly, even by one letter, or by the rule of *idghām*,³¹ or by anything else, his prayer will be invalid for it is as if he had killed seventy prophets sent by God.³²

27 For example, see Ronit Ricci, “Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation,” *Journal of World Literature*, no. 1 (2016): 68–80; Ronit Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* across the Indonesian-Malay World,” *Indonesian and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143–164; Aglaia Iankovskaia, “Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje,” *Archipel*, no. 106 (2023): 89–124. Also see Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalam Arab Terhadap Tatakalam Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528. The main argument of Ph. S. van Ronkel is summarized in Ricci, “Reading between the Lines,” 70.

28 Ricci, “Reading between the Lines”; Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid.”

29 The issues of authenticity, source, and various interpretations of these hadiths are outside the scope of this article and will not be addressed.

30 This hadith is written in a different handwriting on the page before the main text begins.

31 In *tajwīd*, the art of reciting the Qur’an, *idghām* refers to merging one letter into another, causing the initial letter to lose its distinct sound.

32 GM, Ms 8, f.4r.

Fig. 9 shows an image of the text. The Arabic text and the Malay interlinear translation, along with their English translations, are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 9 A Hadith from Book A (underlined by this author).

As Table 1 shows (see below), the Malay interlinear translation maintains the original word order and translates the Arabic text mostly word for word. For example, the Arabic preposition *bi* and the conjunctions *aw*, *wa*, and *fa* are replaced by the Malay preposition *dengan* and the conjunctions *atau*, *dan*, and *maka*, respectively. The Arabic third-person male singular pronoun, *hu/hi*,³³ is translated into the non-gender-specific Malay third-person singular pronoun *nya*.

Another issue is number. Malay words do not have distinct singular and plural forms. Plurality is expressed through context or by using a number. To emphasize plurality, the singular noun may be repeated. In the above text, the Malay translation expresses the numbers indicated by the Arabic nouns by adding a numerical adjective to the equivalent Malay word. For instance, the word *khuṭbataini* is the dual form of *khuṭbah*, which means sermon. It is translated as *dua khutbah* (two sermons). The word *ḥarf*, the singular form of “letter,” is translated as *satu huruf*, meaning “[even] one letter.” Books A through C also offer many more examples of interlinear translation from Arabic to Malay that follow the standardized method described above. This will be demonstrated later.

33 The pronoun *hu* becomes *hi* when it follows the vowel “i” or the diphthong “ay.”

Arabic								
Man	qara'a	al-khuṭbataini	bi-khilāfi	ḥarfan ³⁴	aw	idghāmin	wa-	ghairihi
Whoever	recites	the two sermons	incorrectly	[even] by one letter	or	[by the rule of] <i>idghām</i> ,	or by others,	
Malay								
s-m-n ³⁵	akan membaca	dua khutbah	dengan menyalah	satu huruf ³⁶	atau	idgham	dan	lainnya
Whoever	recites	the two sermons	incorrectly	[even] by one letter,	or	[by the rule of] <i>idghām</i> ,	or by others,	
Arabic								
	batalat	ṣalātuḥu	fa-	qad qatala	sab'īna	nabiyyan	mursalan.	
	his prayer will be invalid		for	he has already killed	seventy	prophets	sent [by God].	
Malay								
nescaya	batal	sembahyangnya	maka	adakalanya seperti	membunuh	tuju[h]pulu[h]	nabi	yang disuruh.
surely,	his prayer will be invalid		for	it is as if	he had killed	seventy	prophets	sent [by God].

Table 1 Arabic and Malay Texts Cited from Book A (Guro sa Masiu Collection, Ms 8, f.4r.). Words and letters in [...] are additions by this author.

However, not every Malay word in the interlinear translation is an equivalent of an Arabic word in the original text. There are some exceptions. First, the Malay interlinear translation adds an adverb that is not present in the original text. Adding the adverb *nescaya*, which means “surely,” emphasizes that the prayer will be invalid. Including the adverb also makes the Malay sentence sound more natural. The Malay translation also adds the phrase *adakalanya seperti*, meaning “it is like” or “it is as if.” The Arabic text uses a metaphor that equates “reciting the two sermons incorrectly” with “killing seventy prophets,” implying a similarity between the two actions without using the words “like” or “as if.” Conversely, the Malay translation uses a simile, explicitly stating what is implied in the original.

It is also noteworthy that the text illustrates one of the regional variations in Malay spelling as written in Jawi script: the omission of the letter *ha* at the end of a word. The words *membunuh* (m-m-b-w-n-h: to kill), *tujuh* (t-w-j-h: seven), and *puluh* (p-w-l-h: ten) are written as *membunu* (m-m-b-w-n), *tuju* (t-w-j) and *pulu* (p-w-l), respectively, as seen in Fig. 9 above (underlined). The

³⁴ Written as *kharfan*.

³⁵ This word is unclear.

³⁶ Written as *khuruf*.

Maranao words *bono* (to kill) and *polo* (ten) are pronounced with a glottal stop at the end and are written without the final *ha*.³⁷ This may have influenced how the Maranao people pronounced these Malay words and wrote them in Jawi script. There are several other examples that demonstrate the influence of Maranao on Malay. The final *ha* in the word *sudah* (already) is also omitted in Book A. The final *ha* in *tujuh* and *puluh* is consistently omitted in Book B and occasionally in Book C (see Fig. 10a-10c). This phenomenon is not limited to interlinear translations; it occasionally appears in Malay texts in manuscripts from Mindanao. For example, in a Malay text written in an insertion of Book C, the final *ha* in *tujuh puluh* is also omitted.

Another variation in spelling is found in the Malay word *dengan* (with, by), which is pronounced /da'ŋan/. The vowel in the first syllable is schwa in standard Malay. However, Book A provides a few instances in which the word is written as d-a-n-g-n, with the letter *alif* inserted between the first two consonants (see Fig. 10d).³⁸ Thus, the spelling in the interlinear translation reflects the local pronunciation of the language, making it an important resource for identifying regional variations in Malay.

d. GM, Ms8, f.8v. *dangan*

Fig. 10 Variations of the Malay Jawi spelling found in manuscripts from Mindanao (Underlined by this author)

37 The word for “seven” in Maranao is *pito*, which is the same as in Tagalog and Cebuano, as well as other Philippine languages.

38 Ervan Nurtawab documents the vocalization of the first syllable in the words *dengan* and *seperti* as *dangan* and *saparti*, respectively, in a Malay note written in a Qur’an manuscript from Bayang, Mindanao. See Ervan Nurtawab, “Description of the Notes Found in the Qur’an of Bayang,” in *The Qur’an and Islamic Manuscripts*, 19–20.

Arabic-Malay Vocabulary

In order to create an interlinear translation from Arabic to Malay, it is necessary to understand the meanings of Arabic words and their Malay equivalents. But how did people learn these meanings in an era before printed dictionaries existed? They presumably learned through oral instruction and written texts, including those with interlinear translations. To learn Malay translations of Arabic words, some people compiled lists of Arabic words commonly used in Islamic texts and their Malay translations.³⁹

Similar Arabic-Malay vocabulary can be found in a manuscript from the Sheik Muhammad Said Collection (B7-Ms2, f.1). This undated manuscript, consisting of 22 folios, deals with *taṣrīf*, or the conjugation of Arabic verbs. It was written in Arabic by an anonymous scribe. Of interest here is a list of thirty Arabic words and their Malay translations written in different handwriting on the last three lines (lines 5–7) of the cover. We will refer to this list as *The Vocabulary*. The Malay words are written under the corresponding Arabic words, mostly horizontally, though some diagonally, making it another example of an interlinear translation. Fig. 11 shows the first two lines (lines 5-6) of *The Vocabulary*, and Table 2 (next page) presents the Arabic and Malay words from Fig. 11.⁴⁰

Fig. 11 Arabic-Malay Vocabulary in Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms2, f.1r.

Most of the Arabic words listed fall into one of the following four categories: prepositions (codes 2, 3, 16, and 20–24); negatives (codes 6, 9–12); conjunctions (codes 13–15, 17, and 18); relative pronouns (codes 4, 5, 7, and 8). These parts of speech appear frequently in Arabic texts and play an important role. To comprehend Arabic sentences, it is crucial to understand their meanings. Therefore, this vocabulary list was likely created to facilitate reading and translating Arabic texts into Malay, including creating interlinear translation.

39 For a manuscript of Malay-Arabic Vocabulary from the 19th century West-Sumatra, see Aglaia Iankovskaia's article in the present issue.

40 The third line of *The Vocabulary* contains six Arabic words: *bāb* (door, chapter); four grammatical terms, including *udghimat* (merged into another letter), along with their Malay translations; and one illegible word.

Line 5 (right to left)			
Code	Arabic	Malay	Meaning in English
1	<i>raṭḥun</i>	<i>basah</i>	wet
2	<i>min</i>	<i>daripada</i>	from
3	<i>ilā</i>	<i>kepada</i>	to
4	<i>mā</i>	<i>yang</i>	what; {who, which}
5	<i>mā</i>	<i>barang</i>	whatever
6	<i>mā</i>	<i>tiada</i>	not
7	<i>man</i>	<i>jika</i>	whoever; {if}
8	<i>man</i>	<i>barang siapa</i>	whoever
9	<i>lā</i>	<i>tiada</i>	not
10	<i>lam</i>	<i>tiada</i>	not
11	<i>lan</i>	<i>tia[da]</i>	not
12	<i>lammā</i>	<i>tiada</i>	not, not yet
13	<i>inna</i>	<i>bahawasanya</i>	indeed, that (introducing a clause)
Line 6 (right to left)			
Code	Arabic	Malay	Meaning in English
14	<i>anna</i>	<i>bahawasanya</i>	that (introducing a clause)
15	<i>bal</i>	<i>tetapi</i>	however, but
16	<i>illā</i>	<i>melainkan</i>	except
17	<i>lākinna</i>	<i>tetapi</i>	however, but
18	<i>ka'anna</i>	<i>seolah2</i>	as if
19	<i>laita</i>	<i>kiranya</i>	if only, I wish
20	<i>'alā</i>	<i>atas</i>	upon
21	<i>fī</i>	<i>pada</i>	at, in
22	<i>fī</i>	<i>dalam</i>	inside
23	<i>ilā</i>	<i>kepada</i>	to
24	<i>'an</i>	<i>daripada</i>	from

Table 2 Arabic and Malay Words in *The Vocabulary* (SMS, B7-Ms2, f.1r., lines 5–6). Words in [...] are from this author. If the Arabic and Malay words have different meanings, the English translation of the Malay word is written in {...}.

Were these Malay translations actually used for interlinear translations in this region? Let's examine the text in Book A. Table 3 (next page) lists 28 Arabic words selected from Book A and shows their translations in both Book A and in *The Vocabulary*. Most of these words are prepositions, conjunctions, negative particles, and relative pronouns that

Arabic words	Meaning	Malay translations	
		Book A	<i>The Vocabulary</i>
bi	in, at, on, with	dengan, dangan, sebab	
fī	in, at, on, by	dalam, pada, kepada	dalam, pada
‘alā	on, upon, above	atas	atas
‘an	from, about	daripada	daripada
min	from, of, some of	daripada, seorang daripada	daripada
li	for, because of, by	bagi, akan	
ilā	to, toward	kepada	kepada
illā	unless, except	melainkan	melainkan
baina	between	antara	
ma‘a	with	serta	
ḥattā	until	hingga	
ka	as, like	seperti, serasi	
aw	or	atau	
wa	and	dan	
fa	then, thus, for, therefore	maka	
thumma	then, after that	kemudian	
idhā	when, if, whenever	apabila	
inna	that, verily	bahawasanya	bahawasanya
anna	that	bahawasanya	bahawasanya
an	that	bahawasanya	
lā	not	tiada	tiada
lam	not	tiada	tiada
mā	not	tiada	tiada
mā	whatever, what	barang yang, yang	barang, yang
man	whoever	s-m-n, barang siapa	barang siapa, jika
ka’anna	as if, as though	seperti	seolah2
ammā ba‘du	thereafter	bermula kemudian	
kull	each	tiap2	

Table 3 Arabic Words and Their Malay Translations in Two Manuscripts. Book A is Guro sa Masiu Collection, Ms 8, and *The Vocabulary* is Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms2, f.1r.

frequently appear in Arabic texts. Fourteen of the words are included in *The Vocabulary*. The Malay translations are consistent in both sources except for the translations of *ka'anna* (as if) and *man* (whoever).⁴¹

Since these two manuscripts are from different scholars' collections in different towns, it is unlikely that the author of Book A referenced this vocabulary directly. However, similar vocabularies may have circulated among scholars in the region. In any case, the consistency of these translations indicates that standard Malay translations of Arabic words had reached the Lanao region by the end of the 18th century, when Book A was written. These vocabulary lists likely played an important role in establishing and maintaining accepted Arabic-to-Malay translations, including interlinear ones. Thus, they were responsible for standardizing these translations.

Additions and Changes

An interlinear translation typically replaces each Arabic word with its corresponding Malay word. However, closer examination of the texts reveals many instances in which words and phrases not appearing in the original text are used in the interlinear translation. We have already examined instances of an adverb being added in the Malay translation. These cases demonstrate the translators' ingenuity and are important evidence of their intellectual efforts. What are these changes, and why were they made? We will explore these questions by examining Malay interlinear translation in Books A, B, and C.

Adding Customary Honorifics

Ronit Ricci highlights the prevalent use of titles and honorifics in the Javanese translation of the Arabic religious poem *Maulid syaraf al-anām* (The birth of the best of mankind). Ricci notes the Javanese tradition of "almost never referring to a person by their name alone" and suggests that titles and honorifics are "a way to situate individuals within a social context."⁴² These characteristics are also evident in Arabic to Malay interlinear translations in the Lanao region.

In Arabic texts, the word *Allāh* is usually followed by the honorific *ta'ālā* (the Exalted), forming the phrase *Allāh ta'ālā*. However, the word *Allāh* occasionally appears in Arabic texts on its own, without the honorific. In such cases, translators always add the honorific *ta'āla*. The following is an example from Book B:

Man a'āna tāliba al-'ilmi a'āhu Allāhu kitābahu bi-al-yumnā (Whoever helps a seeker of knowledge, Allah will give him his account in the right hand.)

41 In Book A, *man* (whoever) is usually translated as s-m-n or s-m-n *orang* (s-m-n person) and only rarely as *barang siapa*. The word s-m-n has yet to be identified. Book B translates *man* as either s-m-n or *barang siapa* almost equally often, while Book C consistently translates the word as *barang siapa*. Examples of these translations can be found in the cited texts from these books below.

42 Ronit Ricci, "Added in Translation: Keywords for the Study of Javanese Islamic Texts," *Philological Encounters*, no. 9 (2024): 44.

Barang siapa menolong menuntut ilmu nescaya dianugerahkan Allahu taala suratannya dengan kanan (Whoever helps a seeker of knowledge, he will surely be awarded by Allah the Exalted with his account by the right [hand]).⁴³

In Arabic texts, the names of prophets often appear without the honorific *nabī* (prophet). In such cases, the Malay translation consistently adds the honorific *nabi*. When referring to the Prophet Muhammad, the honorific *nabi kita* (our prophet) is usually added, as shown in the following example from Book C:

Al-ṣalāt wa-al-salām ‘alā Muḥammadin ... (May blessings and peace be upon Muhammad) ...

Bermula rahmat Allah dan salamnya atas nabi kita Muhammad ... (May Allah’s blessings and peace be upon our prophet Muhammad) ...⁴⁴

When other prophets, such as Ādam, Ibrāhīm, and Mūsā, are referred to without honorific titles in the Arabic text, the Malay translation always adds the word *nabi* before their names.⁴⁵ Using the honorific titles is so deeply ingrained in their literary traditions, it was natural for the translators to add these honorifics for Allah and the names of the prophets.

Clarifying the Pronouns’ Referents

The Malay translation occasionally clarifies Arabic pronouns by adding the personal or common nouns that specify to whom or to what they refer.⁴⁶ The following is an example from Book B.

Fig. 12 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3, f.3r.

43 SMS, B7-Ms3, f.16r. The words under discussion are underlined. Words in [...] are additions by this author. The same applies below.
 44 SMS, B7-Ms8, f.3r.-v.
 45 Examples can be found in SMS, B7-Ms8, ff.5r-6r.
 46 For clarification of pronoun reference in the Javanese interlinear translation, see Ronit Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid,” 157.

In the Arabic text above, the words of the Prophet Muhammad are written as direct speech, using the genitive case of the first-person singular pronoun *ya* to refer to the Prophet.⁵² However, the corresponding Malay text is written in indirect speech in the third person, using the word *nabi* instead of the first-person singular possessive pronoun *ku*, resulting in the phrase “Whoever prays for the Prophet ...” This change was likely intended to emphasize to the reader that the speaker is the Prophet Muhammad himself.

Clarifying Words and Phrases Other than Pronouns

In addition to clarifying pronouns, translators sometimes added words or altered the wording to ensure accurate understanding of the text. Let us examine four instances of this from Book B. The first example is a hadith that lists the rewards that Allah will give to those who seek knowledge. The Arabic and Malay texts and their English translations are presented below alongside an image (Fig. 14a-b).

Fig. 14a Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3, f.2r.

⁵² *ya* is a variant of the genitive case of the first-person singular pronoun *ī* used when it follows the diphthong *ay*.

Fig. 14b Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3, f.2v.

Man *ta'allama* mas'alatan min al-'ilmi qalladahu Allāhu ta'alā yawma al-qiyamati alfa qilādatin min nūrin wa-ghafara lahu alfa⁵³ dhanbin wa-banā⁵⁴ lahu madīnatan fi al-jannati min dhahabin wa-kataba lahu bi-kulli sha'ratin 'alā jasdihi hijjatan⁵⁵ wa-'umratan (Whoever learns a matter of knowledge, Allah the Exalted will adorn him on the Day of Judgment with a thousand necklaces of light, forgive him a thousand sins, build for him a golden city in Paradise, and foreordain for him for every hair on his body [a reward equal to that of] a hajj and an umrah.)

s-m-n mengajar ilmu akan satu masalah daripada ilmu nescaya beri Allah taala pakaian akan hari kiamat seribu pakaian daripada cahaya dan diampun baginya seribu dusanya dan perbuatkan baginya akan satu negeri dalam syurga daripada emas dan *disurat* baginya dengan tiap2 bulu atas tubuhnya *pahala* haji dan haji umrah⁵⁶ (Whoever teaches knowledge [even] about a single issue of knowledge, Allah the Exalted will surely give [him] a thousand garments of light on the Day of Resurrection, forgive him a thousand sins, build for him a golden city in Paradise, and

53 Vocalized as *alfu* in the text.

54 Written as *bannā* in the text.

55 Written as *hujatan* in the text.

56 The term *haji umrah* likely implies *haji kecil* (small hajj), which refers to 'umrah.

it will be written for him that for every hair on his body [he will receive] a reward [equal to that of] hajj and umrah).⁵⁷

Although the Malay text largely agrees with the Arabic text, there are some discrepancies. First, the Arabic word *ta'allama* (study, learn) is replaced with the Malay word *mengajar* (teach). This change in meaning was likely caused by misreading *ta'allama* as *'allama* (teach). Second, the Arabic word *qiladah* (necklace) is replaced with the Malay word *pakaian* (garment). This change was likely due to an error. Third, the adverb *nescaya* (surely) is added to the Malay sentence to make it more natural, as discussed above. However, our focus here is on the meaning of the Arabic word *kataba* in an Islamic context, and how this meaning is reflected in the Malay translation.

The word *kataba* primarily means “write,” but in an Islamic context, especially when referring to Allah’s actions, it means “prescribe,” or “foreordain or predestine” someone for a particular fate.⁵⁸ Thus, the Arabic text means, “Allah will foreordain for him for every hair on his body [a reward equal to that of] a hajj and an umrah,” as mentioned above. In this context, the word *kataba* already implies the meaning of “giving rewards.” Let’s look at the Malay translation again.

disurat baginya dengan tiap2 bulu atas tubuhnya pahala hajj dan haji umra (it will be written for him that for every hair on his body [he will receive] a reward [equal to that of] hajj and umrah)⁵⁹

The word *kataba* is replaced with the Malay word *disurat*, the passive form of the verb *menyurat* (write). If the readers of Book B were familiar with the Islamic meaning of the word *kataba* and understood that *disurat* had that meaning, a word-for-word translation of the rest of the text would suffice. However, the author of Book B added the word *pahala* (reward) to the Malay translation. He did so because he was unsure whether his intended readers would understand the Islamic meaning of the Arabic word *kataba*, or if they would interpret the Malay word *disurat* as having that connotation. Therefore, he added the word *pahala* to ensure the Arabic text’s true meaning would be conveyed to readers.

The second example is the term *kitāb Allāh* (Book of Allah), which the interlinear translation specifies as the Qur’an in a straightforward manner.

*āyah*⁶⁰ min *kitābi Allāhi* (a verse from the Book of Allah)

satu ayat daripada kitab ertinya *Qur’an* (a verse from the Book, which means the Qur’an)⁶¹

57 SMS, B7-Ms3, ff.2r.-v.

58 See, for example, *kataba* in the Arabic-English dictionary by Hans Wehr. Cf. Hans Wehr, *A Dictionary of Modern Written Arabic (Arabic-English)*, ed. J. Milton Cowan (Spoken Language Services, 1994): 951. I would like to thank Fadhli Lukman for his advice regarding the Islamic meaning of *kataba*, although I take full responsibility for any errors.

59 SMS, B7-Ms3, f.2v.

60 Written as *ayah* in the text.

61 SMS, B7-Ms3, f.20r.

The term *kitāb Allāh* (Book of Allah) refers to the Qur'an, but some people may not be familiar with the term. Therefore, the translator replaced the word Allah with an explanatory phrase *ertinya Qur'an* (its meaning is the Qur'an) to ensure clarity.

The third example is the opening phrase of the *shahādah* or Profession of Faith, that is, *ashhadu* (I testify) (see Fig. 15). This single Arabic word was not simply translated into a Malay word. Instead, it is explained using three verbs:

Fig. 15 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3, f.1r.

*dan ku ikrarkan serta ku ketahui dan ku nyatakan*⁶² (and I pledge and I also know and declare)⁶³

This passage demonstrates the translator's enthusiasm for conveying the full meaning of the word.

The fourth example clarifies the meaning of the Arabic word *amīn* by explaining it in the Malay interlinear translation. At the end of the introduction, the author offers a supplication to Allah for blessings and concludes it with the word *amīn*. The Malay interlinear translation of this word is as follows (see also Fig. 16).

Fig. 16 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms3, f.3r.

Terima olehmu pinta hambamu (Please accept the request of your servant).

⁶² The last two *ku* are written as *k* in the original text.

⁶³ SMS, B7-Ms3, f.1r.

Muslims use the word *amīn* or *āmīn* at the end of a prayer to mean “O Allah, please grant our supplication.”⁶⁴ The widely circulated worship guide *Perukunan Melayu Besar* (hereafter, *Perukunan*)⁶⁵ also provides an interlinear translation that explains the meaning of the word in a similar way.

Fig. 17 Malay translation of *Āmīn* in *Perukunan Melayu Besar*⁶⁶

*Perkenankanlah olehmu akan permohonan kami*⁶⁷ (Please approve our request).

Although the translation in Book B uses simpler language than that in *Perukunan*, both convey the same meaning. This suggests that it was common practice to include the semantic connotation of the word *amīn* in the interlinear Malay translation, even though doing so makes the translation too long to fit under the word *amīn*.

Book C also provides examples of adding words to translations for clarification. One of them contains the words of the Prophet Muhammad concerning the causes that could lead to the destruction of the Muslim community. The Arabic and Malay texts and their English translations are shown below.

-
- 64 J. Pedersen, “Amīn,” in *Encyclopaedia of Islam New Edition Online (EI-2 English)*, ed. P. Bearman (Brill, 2012) doi: https://doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_SIM_0597; Admin PMWP, “Irsyad al-Fatwa Series 6: The Meaning of ‘Amin’ after the Recitation of Al-Fatihah,” *Mufti of Federal Territory’s Office*, 24 November 2014, <https://muftiwp.gov.my/en/artikel/irsyad-fatwa/irsyad-fatwa-umum-cat/2045-irsyad-fatwa-series-6-the-meaning-of-amin-after-the-recitation-of-al-fatihah>. I am grateful to Fadhli Lukman for bringing the meaning of the word *amīn* to my attention. However, I am solely responsible for any errors.
- 65 *Perukunan Melayu Besar* is a collection of the teachings of Muḥammad Arshad al-Banjārī, an 18th-century scholar from South Kalimantan, compiled by his descendants. See Azyumardi Azra, *The Origins of Islamic Reformism in Southeast Asia: Networks of Malay-Indonesian and Middle-Eastern ‘Ulamā’ in the 17th and 18th Centuries* (University of Hawa’i Press, 2004): 129.
- 66 Muḥammad Arshad Banjar, *Perukunan Melayu Besar* (al-Aydarus, n.d.), 9.
- 67 *Kamus Dewan*, a modern Malay dictionary, also defines the word *amin* similarly, as “*perkenankanlah ya Allah doa kami*” (Please approve, O Allah, our supplication). See Noresah bt. Baharom, et. al., eds., *Kamus Dewan Edisi Ketiga* (Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka, 2002): 37.

Fig. 18 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms8, f.26v.

*Halāku*⁶⁸ *ummatī fī ithnayni fī tarki al-‘ilmi wa-jam’ⁱ⁶⁹ al-māli* (The destruction of my nation is because of two things; abandoning knowledge and accumulating wealth).

Membinasakan umatku dalam dua perkara suatu meninggalkan mencari al-ilmu dan kedua menghimpunkan arta (The destruction of my nation is because of two things; First, abandoning seeking the knowledge, and second, accumulating wealth).⁷⁰

The translator has added the words “first” and “second” to indicate the two causes, making it easier for the reader to understand.

Another example is found in the interlinear translation of the phrase “in the way of Allah” used in a hadith in Book C.

fī sabīli Allāhi (in the way of Allah)

pada jalan sabil Allah taala (in the way of Sabil Allah the Exalted).⁷¹

The Malay preposition *pada* is equivalent to the Arabic preposition *fī* (in), and the Arabic phrase *sabīl Allāh* (the way of Allah) is used as is. This shows that the Arabic phrase was incorporated into the Malay language. However, the translator added the Malay word *jalan* (way) to the phrase even though *sabīl*, the Arabic word for “way,” is already included. This resulted in the duplication of the word meaning “way.” The translator probably added *jalan* because he thought the reader might not know the meaning of *sabīl* and wanted to ensure that the phrase’s meaning was clearly conveyed.

Thus, rather than strictly sticking to a word-for-word translation, the creator of the interlinear text occasionally added words or changed the wording. While most of these changes are minor and barely noticeable, they demonstrate the translator’s commitment to conveying the original meaning accurately and clearly. Such changes are most frequent in

68 Vocalized as *hilāku* in the text.

69 Written as *jam’i* in the text.

70 SMS, B7-Ms8, f.26v.

71 SMS, B7-Ms8, f.7v. The full text of the hadith reads: “Whoever spends a dirham on a seeker of knowledge, it is as if he has spent a mountain of red gold in the way of Allah.”

Book B, followed by Book C, and least frequent in Book A, and these differences may stem from the books' purposes, creation times, and the authors' backgrounds. Book B is the only one of the three books that includes *isnād*, or chain of narrators, for each of the hadiths. This indicates that whoever compiled Book B was well-versed in hadith literature. This may explain the frequent additions and changes to clarify the hadith text in the interlinear Malay translation.

Are these features also found in the Maranao interlinear translation? Are there any characteristics unique to the Maranao interlinear translation? The next section will address these questions.

Arabic to Maranao Interlinear Translation: Book D

We will examine Book D, which is a lithographed copy of the Book of Hadiths with a complete Maranao interlinear translation. Book C, which contains a partial Maranao interlinear translation as well as a complete Malay interlinear translation, will be discussed separately in the following section.

Standard Patterns of Interlinear Translation

Examples from Book D

At the beginning of Book D, the following hadith is quoted: "He who seeks this world loses, and he who seeks the Hereafter gains."⁷² The Arabic and Maranao texts and their English translations are presented in Fig. 19 and Table 4.

Fig. 19 Amir Husin, *Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ*, p.3.

⁷² Husin, *Hadīth*, 3.

Arabic							
Tālibu	al-dunyā		khasāratu ⁷³	wa-	tālibu	al-akhirati	ribḥun
He who seeks	this world		will lose	and	he who seeks	the Hereafter	will gain
Maranao							
Aya so tontot niyan	so doniya	na disomala	a lugi	go	so tontot niyan	so akhirat	na laba ⁷⁴
He who seeks	this world	will surely	lose	and	he who seeks	the Hereafter	will gain

Table 4 Amir Husin, *Hadith of the Prophet ṣm*, p.3.

The Arabic word *tālib*, meaning “seeker,” is translated into the Maranao phrase *tontot niyan*, meaning “he who seeks.” The other words—*dunyā* (world), *khasārah* (loss), *wa* (and), *āakhirah* (Hereafter), and *ribḥ* (gain, profit)—are also translated into their Maranao equivalents and written diagonally beneath the Arabic counterparts. The Arabic words are essentially translated word for word while maintaining the original order. These features are consistent with the Malay interlinear translations discussed above.

However, the Maranao language has a unique feature not found in Arabic or Malay. It has many particles, such as ligatures that link words (e.g., *a*, *na*), and case markers that indicate the relationship between words (e.g., *so*, *ko*, *sa*, *o*).⁷⁵ In the above Maranao text, the first word, *aya*, marks the beginning of a sentence or phrase dealing with a new topic. The particle *so* is a nominative marker for the noun that follows, and *na* is a ligature that links the subject and predicate. Due to the abundance of particles, the Maranao translation of an Arabic word or phrase tends to be longer than the original. For example, the four-letter word *tālib* (t-a-l-b) is translated into the twelve-letter Maranao phrase *aya so tontot niyan* (a-y s-w t-n-t-w-t n-y-n). However, the scribe of Book D managed to fit the Maranao words under the Arabic word by writing neatly in small letters.

Arabic nouns are also distinguished by number in the Maranao text. Like in Malay, the Maranao words do not have singular and plural forms. Plurality is expressed by adding the pluralizing particle *manga* or the adjective *langowa*, which means “all,” or by using a number. The following is an example of this:

rokonun min arkāni al-Islāmi (a pillar of the pillars of Islam)

isa rokon phoon ko langowa na rokon a Islam (one pillar of all the pillars of Islam).⁷⁶

In another passage, the author clarifies the meaning of the Arabic third-person dual pronoun *humā*, which means “both of them,” in the Maranao text. He provides a numerical

⁷³ Written as *khasratu*.

⁷⁴ Written as *labah*.

⁷⁵ Howard P. McKaughan and Batua Al-Macaraya, *A Maranao Dictionary* (De La Salle University Press, 1996), 3–4.

⁷⁶ Husin, *Hadith*, 3.

reference and clarifies the pronoun's referent, translating it as *dowa o wakto*, which means "two of the five prescribed prayers to be performed at specified times each day."⁷⁷

The author of Book D also attempts to convey the emphasis expressed in the Arabic text in the Maranao interlinear translation. This emphasis is found in a hadith about the Day of Resurrection. To clarify the context, the English translation of the entire hadith is provided below, based on the Arabic text.⁷⁸ The emphatic expression is underlined.

He [Prophet Muhammad] said, "Jibrīl frightened me with the horrors of the Day of Resurrection until he made me cry. So I said to him, 'O Jibrīl, has my Lord not forgiven me for whatever sins in the past and those yet to come?' He said, 'O Muhammad! You will certainly witness horrors of that Day that will make you forget the forgiveness."⁷⁹

The Arabic and Maranao texts of the last sentence and their English translations are as follows:

Latushāhidanna min ahwāli dhālika al-yawmi mā yunsika al-maghfirata (You will certainly witness horrors of that day that will make you forget the forgiveness.)

*Disomala na mailay ngka*⁸⁰ *phoon so langowano riwareng ko manaa maototo a alongan na di ka den indara inon o Tohan ka ko kapakadaa niyan ko dosa* (You will certainly witness all the disturbances of that very day. Your Lord will not forsake you in granting forgiveness to nullify sins.).

The first underlined expression, *latushāhidanna*, is a verb with two intensifying elements: *la*, meaning "certainly," and the suffix *-anna*, which forms an emphatic verb. Therefore, the verb means "you will certainly witness." The Maranao text conveys this emphasis by adding the phrase *disomala na* (certainly) at the beginning of the sentence.

The second underlined expression emphasizes the Day (of Resurrection) by adding the demonstrative pronoun *dhālika*, meaning "that," to the noun *al-yawmi* (the day). The Maranao text reflects this emphasis by adding the adjective phrase *manaa maototo a* (that very ...) to the noun *alongan* (day).

Additionally, this passage provides an interesting example of how a misunderstanding of Arabic words can lead to a new interpretation of the hadith. The Maranao text's meaning in the latter half of the passage, *na di ka den indara inon...*, differs from the Arabic text's meaning in the corresponding section, *mā yunsika al-maghfirata*. This discrepancy likely

77 Husin, *Ḥadīth*, 8.

78 A similar hadith is included in the *tafsīr* of a 13th-century Andalusian scholar, al-Qurṭubī, for Q5:109. See Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad al-Qurṭubī, *al-Jāmi' al-aḥkām al-Qur'ān*, vol. 8 (al-Resāla, 2006), 280. When translating the above-cited hadith into English, I referred to Aisha Bewley's translation of the commentary. See Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad al-Qurṭubī, *Tafsīr al-Qurṭubī: The General Judgements of the Qur'ān and Clarification of What It Contains of the Sunnah and Āyahs of Discrimination*, trans. Aisha Bewley, vol. 6 (Diwan Press, 2021): 314.

79 Husin, *Ḥadīth*, 8.

80 Written as *nka* in the text.

occurred because the Maranao author interpreted the Arabic relative pronoun *mā* (what) as the negative particle *mā* (not) and misread the phrase *yunsīka* (make you forget) as *yansāka* (forget you).

Standard Maranao Translation of Specific Arabic and Malay Words

We have seen that frequently used Arabic words are translated into specific Malay words in the interlinear translation. Let us examine whether the same is true for the Maranao interlinear translation. Table 5 lists 25 basic Arabic words used in Book A and D, along with their Malay translations from Book A and *The Vocabulary*, and also the Maranao translations from Book D.

As with Malay, these Arabic words are consistently translated into specific Maranao words or phrases. However, the Arabic conjunction *fa* (then, so, thus, etc.) is often omitted in the Maranao translation. Some Maranao words used to translate Arabic words are similar to Malay words that also translate the same Arabic words. For example, *serta* and *sarta* are used in Malay and Maranao texts, respectively, to translate the Arabic preposition *maʿa* (with). Similarly, *bagi* and *bagian* translate the Arabic preposition *li* (for) in Malay and Maranao, respectively. The Malay word *apabila* appears once in the Maranao text as a translation of the Arabic conjunction *idhā* (when or if). These examples illustrate the influence of Malay on the Maranao language, as well as the role translation played in introducing Malay vocabulary into it.

Additions and Changes

Adding Customary Honorifics

As previously mentioned, the Malay interlinear translation adds the word *taala* after Allah and the word *nabi* before the names of the prophets, even though these honorifics are absent from the Arabic text. This holds true with the Maranao interlinear translation in Book D. Following are some examples.

*Amā*⁸¹ *takhshā Allāha* (Do you not fear Allah?)

*Ino ba ngka*⁸² *di khaleken so Allah taala* (Do you not fear Allah the Exalted)⁸³

Similarly, in the Maranao interlinear translation, the name of the Prophet Muhammad, as well as the names of other prophets such as Ibrāhīm, Yūnus, Mūsā, and ʿĪsā are consistently preceded by the word *nabi*.⁸⁴ This is likely because the author followed the Malay convention for similar Arabic texts. The importance of honorifics in the Maranao society may also explain why this convention was adopted.

81 Written as *ammā* in the text.

82 Written as *nka* in the text.

83 Husin, *Ḥadīth*, 4.

84 Husin, *Ḥadīth*, 10–11

Arabic	Meaning	Malay translation	Maranao translation
bi	in, at, on, with	dengan, dangan, sebab	sabap sa, sabap o
fi	in, at, on, by	dalam, pada, kepada	ko dalem o, madadalem ko
‘alā	on, upon, above	atas	sanko
‘an	from, about	daripada	phoon ko
min	from, of, some of	daripada, seorang daripada	phoon ko
li	for, because of, by	bagi, akan	bagian, atag
ilā	to, toward	kepada	san
illā	unless, except	melainkan	inonta o
ma‘a	with	serta	sarta a
ḥattā	untill	hingga	taman sa
ka	as, like	seperti, serasi	izan o
wa	and	dan	go
fa	then, thus, for, therefore	maka	go, na (often omitted without translation)
thumma	then, after that	kemudian	oriyan na
idhā	when, if, whenever	apabila	apabila, kotika a
law	if		o manaya o
inna	that, verily	bahawasanya	sakatotooan
anna	that	bahawasanya	sakatotooan
lā	not	tiada	di
lam	not	tiada	di
mā	not	tiada	di
mā	whatever, what	barang, yang	nganin
man	whoever	s-m-n, barang siapa, jika	si taw a
ka’anna	as if, as though	seperti, seolah2	izan o
kull	each	tiap2	toktokel ko, makatoketokel ko

Table 5 Arabic Words and Their Malay and Maranao Translations in Manuscripts from the Lanao Region of Mindanao⁸⁵

⁸⁵ The Malay translation is from Guro sa Masiu (Ms 8) and Sheik Muhammad Said Collections (B7-Ms2, f.1r), and the Maranao is from Husin, *Hadīth*.

Additions and Changes for Clarification

The Maranao interlinear translation in Book D contains many examples of added words and altered wording that clarify the original Arabic. To illustrate this point, let us examine an excerpt from a hadith that includes several such instances. This hadith was narrated by Anas ibn Mālik who recounted his conversation with the Prophet Muhammad. According to Anas, the Prophet told him that Allah commanded him to say, “I seek refuge in the Lord of *Falaq*.”⁸⁶ Anas then asked the Prophet, “What is *Falaq*?,” to which the Prophet answered that it is a well in Hell. The Arabic and Maranao texts and their English translations are provided below, alongside the image (Fig. 20). Words under discussion are underlined and assigned a symbol from (a) to (g). Words added to the original text in the Maranao translation are in bold letters.

Fig. 20 Amir Husin, Hadith of the Prophet ﷺ, p.8.

Bi-qawlihi ta‘ālā,^(a) “*Qul a‘ūdhu bi-Rabbi al-Falaqi.*”^(b) “*Mā al-falaqu, Yā Rasūl Allāh.*” *Fa-qāla,*^(d) “*Hiya bi‘irun*^(e) *fī jahannama.*”^(f) *Law ṭāra ṭā‘irun alfa sannatin, lā yaşīlu ilayhā.*”^(g)⁸⁷

(In the words of He who is Exalted,^(a) “Say: I seek refuge with the Lord of *Falaq*.”^(b) “What is *Falaq*?, O Messenger of Allah.” He said,^(d) “It is a well^(e) in Hell.^(f) Even if a bird flew for a thousand years, it would never reach it.”^(g))

86 Sūrat al-Falaq (Q113:1).

87 We will discuss later what the final personal pronoun *hā* (translated as “it” here) refers to.

Sabap sa pitharo o Allah taala^(a) a “Tharoangka,⁸⁸ Ya Muhammad, a lumindong ako sabap ko Tohan ko Falaq.”^(b) Pitharo o Anas,^(c) “Antona a angkoto⁸⁹ a Falaq?, Ya Rasul Allah.” Pitharo o Rasul Allah,^(d) “Aya oto na landeng^(e) a madadalem ko naraka jahanam^(f) o manaya o layog o papanok a sagembetan⁹⁰ na disomala a sanggibo ragon na di misampay⁹¹ ko sabala a kilid iyan.”^(g)

(In the words of Allah the Exalted,^(a) “Say, O Muhammad, I take refuge in the Lord of Falaq.”^(b) Said Anas,^(c) “What is that Falaq?, O Messenger of Allah.” Messenger of Allah said,^(d) “It is a gorge^(e) inside Hell.^(f) It is as if even a swift bird flying for a thousand years would not reach the other side of it.”^(g))

We will examine how the author of Book D added or altered words in the Maranao interlinear translation. Specifically, we will focus on the Arabic and Maranao expressions marked (a) through (g) and consider why the author selected these Maranao words.

Expression (a): The Arabic phrase *bi-qawlihi ta‘ālā* literally means “in the words of He who is Exalted.” Although this phrase refers to Allah, it does not mention His name directly. In the Maranao version, the personal pronoun *hi* (his) is replaced with its referent, Allah, forming the direct expression, “in the words of Allah the Exalted.” This was likely done to emphasize that these are the words of Allah Himself.

Expression (b): The words, “Say: I seek refuge with the Lord of Falaq,” are quoted from Sūrat al-Falaq (Q113:1) of the Qur’an. In translating the Qur’anic verse, the author of Book D likely referred to existing Maranao *tafsīr*, rather than translating from scratch. Were there any Maranao *tafsīr* in the Lanao region at that time? Indeed, a Maranao scholar, namely, ‘Abd al-Ḥaḡīr Makalawan ibn Nuskhah ‘Ālim from the town of Ramain, wrote a *tafsīr* of Juz’ ‘*Amma* or the last thirtieth division of the Qur’an in Maranao and published it in 1933, six years before Book D was published (hereafter, Makalawan’s *tafsīr*). Makalawan’s *tafsīr* is the earliest known Maranao *tafsīr* in print. It likely circulated among contemporary Maranao scholars, as evidenced by the fact that a copy is found in the collection of Sheik Muhammad Said who lived in Bayang, a town on the opposite side of Lake Lanao.⁹² In his *tafsīr*, Makalawan explains the same verse from the Qur’an as follows:⁹³

88 Written as *Tharoangka*.

89 Written as *ankoto*.

90 Written as *sagebetan* in the text.

91 Written as *misanpay* in the text.

92 SMS, B17-Ms1. For Makalawan’s *tafsīr*, see Midori Kawashima, “Islamic Reformism and an American Protestant Missionary: Contest over the Publication of the Qur’anic Verses in Mindanao under the US Colonial Rule,” *Sophia Journal of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies*, no. 34 (2016): 173–210.

93 First, several verses (*āyah*) from the Qur’an are presented in Arabic, followed by their Maranao translations and explanations. Then, the Arabic text of the next several verses is presented, followed by their Maranao translations and explanations. This pattern repeats.

Qul a'ūdhu bi-Rabbi al-Falaqi (Say, I take refuge with the Lord of *Falaq*)

Tharoangka, Ya Muhammad sm, melindong ako sabap ko ngaran a dhat o Tohan ko paridi a Falaq (Say, O Muhammad sm: I take refuge with the name of the essence of the Lord of the well of *Falaq*).⁹⁴

The following is the Maranao interlinear translation of the same verse in Book D:

Tharoangka, Ya Muhammad, a lumindong ako sabap ko Tohan ko Falaq (Say, O Muhammad, I take refuge in the Lord of *Falaq*.)

The underlined words in Makalawan's *tafsīr* and Book D are identical. The double-underlined words *melindong* and *lumindong* both come from the same root, *lindong* (shelter), and both mean "to take refuge." The close resemblance of the two texts suggests that the author of Book D likely referenced Makalawan's *tafsīr* when creating the Maranao interlinear translation.

Page | 162

However, there are also a few discrepancies between the two texts. For example, Makalawan uses the phrase *sabap ko ngaran a dhat o Tohan* (with the name of the essence of the Lord), which is not found in the Arabic text or used in Book D.⁹⁵ Furthermore, Makalawan explains that the word *al-Falaq* refers to a well (*paridi*), whereas Book D interprets it as a gorge. This difference will be discussed below.

The above discussion indicates that the interlinear translation was not just created through a simple word-for-word translation. Rather, it was influenced by other related literature, such as *tafsīr*. This is particularly evident in quotations from the Qur'an.

Expression (c) (in the Maranao text): The Arabic text does not state who asked the question, "What is *Falaq*?" and the reader is expected to infer that it was Anas ibn Mālik, upon whose authority the hadith was narrated. The Maranao text clarifies this by inserting the phrase, "Said Anas."

Expression (d): This is another example that clarifies the speaker's identity. The Arabic phrase "he said" does not specify who is speaking, except to say that the speaker is male, singular, and in the third person. However, the context suggests that these are the words of the Prophet Muhammad. The Maranao interlinear translation clarifies this by explicitly stating, "The Messenger of Allah said." These examples demonstrate that, like the Malay interlinear translation, the Maranao interlinear translation clarifies who is speaking.

Expression (e): The word *falaq* in Sūrat al-Falaq has several interpretations. The most widely accepted interpretation is that it refers to "daybreak" (*ṣubḥ*). However, some scholars have offered alternative interpretations, including "one of the names of Hell," "a well or pit (*jubb*), valley or gorge (*wādīn*), tree, mountain, rock, or prison in Hell," and "all creation."⁹⁶ In the Arabic text of Book D, the Prophet Muhammad explains that *Falaq* is

94 'Abd al-Ḥaqīr Makalawan ibn Nuskhah 'Ālim, *Tafsīr Juz' 'Amma bi-lughat Lanao* (Matba'at Ḥājj 'Abd al-Rahmān ibn 'Abd al-'Azīz, 1933), 53.

95 According to Fadhli Lukman, this is a translation of the Arabic phrase *bi-ism dhāt rabb*, which is a theological expression typically used in reference to God. Its use could imply the author's orientation toward Ash'arism (Personal communication with Lukman, June 20, 2025).

96 Aḥmad ibn Muḥammad al-Tha'labī, *al-Kashf wa-al-bayān fī tafsīr al-Tha'labī*, vol.6 (Dār al-kutub al-

the name of a well (*bi'r*) in Hell. However, the Maranao text in Book D translates *Falaq* as a gorge (*landeng*). Meanwhile, the Makalawan's *tafsīr* interprets *Falaq* as a well (*paridi*) in Hell. This shows that the author of Book D did not simply replace the Arabic word *bi'r* with its Maranao equivalent. Nor did he unquestioningly follow the Makalawan's *tafsīr*. Rather, it appears that he selected a word that aligned with his own interpretation based on other sources.

Expression (f): The Arabic word *jahannam* refers to Hell. The Maranao interlinear translation retains this word and adds the Maranao (and Malay) word for Hell, *naraka*,⁹⁷ creating the Malay-Arabic phrase *naraka jahanam*. This results in the duplication of the word Hell.

Expression (g): The Arabic text states, "Even if a bird flew for a thousand years, it would never reach it." This hypothetical expression illustrates the enormous distance that one must travel to reach "it." But what does "it" mean? The Arabic text does not explicitly specify what "it" refers to, allowing for multiple interpretations. One interpretation is to consider the distance from our location (in this world) to the well in Hell. In this interpretation, the singular feminine demonstrative pronoun *hā* (it or her) refers to the well (*bi'r*), which is a feminine singular noun. Another interpretation considers this expression to signify the depth of the well. In this case, the distance is vertical, from the ground level to the bottom of the well.⁹⁸

The Maranao interlinear translation offers yet another interpretation. In the first place, it interprets the word *Falaq* as "gorge" in Hell. Then, it clarifies that the pronoun "it" refers to "the other side" of the gorge. According to this interpretation, the distance seems to refer to the horizontal distance between the two sides of the gorge. Furthermore, the Maranao text adds the adjective "swift" to "bird" to further emphasize the enormous distance.

Thus, even such a short passage demonstrates the author's ingenuity and commitment to conveying the meaning of the Arabic text clearly and effectively. In addition to these examples, the Maranao interlinear translation of Book D offers several other interesting cases of words added or changed by the author. For example, the Maranao interlinear translation clarifies what is implied by a figurative speech.

'ilmiyya, 2004): 452. See also David Penchansky, "Interpreting the Qur'an Using Some Methods from Biblical Scholarship: An Analysis of the "Taking Refuge" Suras," *Draft 5*, July 2010, https://www.academia.edu/808172/Surah_Al_Falaq_113_and_Surah_An_Nas_114_A_Literary_Reading#/loswp-work-container

97 *Naraka* or *neraka* is a Malay word of Sanskrit origin that was presumably adopted into the Maranao vocabulary.

98 I am grateful to Fadhli Lukman for bringing this second interpretation to my attention. I have also found a similar text that aligns with this interpretation in a manuscript from Timbuktu, Mali, West Africa. The Timbuktu manuscript explicitly states the distance to the bottom of the well, as follows: He [Prophet] said, "A well in Hell. If a bird flew in it for a thousand years, it would not reach its bottom." See Floréal Sanagustin, *Le conte de Tawwaddud al-jariya, Version de Tombouctou, Edition critique* (École normale supérieure de Lyon, 2012): 26. The almost identical language used in the two manuscripts indicates that they are both based on the same original source.

allaḍīna yaknizūna al-dhahaba wa-al-fiḍḍata (Those who hoard gold and silver)

Aya siran oto a pethago a tamok o bolawan go pirak (Those who keep safe the wealth of gold and silver)⁹⁹

In the Arabic text, the phrase “gold and silver” implies wealth. The Maranao text explicitly says this by adding the word “wealth.”

Another is the addition of a Maranao word to a Malay-Arabic loan phrase as found in the following case.

Innahu qāla khawwafanī Jibrīl min hauli yawmi al-qiyāmati haṭṭā abkānī (Verily, he [the Prophet Muhammad] said, “Jibrīl frightened me with the horrors of the Day of Resurrection until he made me cry.”)

a sa katotooan iyan na pitharo o iyan a inipangangalek raken o Jabarail phoon so riwareng sa alongan a hari kiamat taman sa miyakasegada (Verily, he said, “Jibrīl frightened me with the disturbances of the Day of Resurrection until he made my eyes teary.”)¹⁰⁰

Page | 164

The phrase *yawm al-qiyāmat* translates to *hari kiamat* in Malay. However, to make this term more understandable for the Maranao people, the author of Book D added the Maranao word *alongan*, meaning “day,” resulting in the duplication of the word for “day.”

The above analysis has revealed the following points: the Maranao interlinear translation in Book D generally follows a basic pattern similar to the Malay interlinear translation, using words corresponding to Arabic. Additionally, words not found in the original Arabic text have been added and expressions have been modified. These changes are intended to clarify the text’s meaning. These features are also generally observed, albeit to varying degrees, in the Malay interlinear translation of the three aforementioned manuscripts (Books A, B, and C). However, the Maranao interlinear translation tends to be longer than the Malay translation due to the abundance of particles. Overall, the Maranao interlinear translation is more than just a simple replacement of Arabic words with their Maranao equivalents. Rather, it clarifies difficult or opaque parts of the original Arabic text by modestly adding or changing words. Therefore, it can be considered an inconspicuous annotation.

The Maranao interlinear translation of Book D has more added and changed words than the Malay interlinear translations in Books A–C. This difference can be explained by the fact that Book D is a printed book, while Books A–C are handwritten manuscripts. Book D, published in 1939, is also more recent than Books A–C. Unlike manuscripts intended for oneself, family, or a small circle of scholars and students, Book D was intended for a wider literate audience among the Maranao people. For this reason, the author likely strove to make the Maranao text clear, accurate, and concise enough to fit within the limited space between the lines.

99 Husin, *Hadīth*, 7

100 Husin, *Hadīth*, 7

Arabic to Malay and Maranao: Book C¹⁰¹

Book C is one of the few manuscripts with interlinear translations in both Malay and Maranao. While the Arabic text is fully accompanied by a Malay interlinear translation, a Maranao interlinear translation is provided only for six lines on f. 23r.–v. (see Fig. 7 above). Through a comparison of the Maranao text with the Arabic original and the Malay translation, we will explore the method employed in creating the Maranao translation and consider its purpose.

Fig. 21 Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam Collection, B7-Ms8 (Enlarged), f.23r. and f.23v., respectively.

Fig. 21 is an enlarged image of the beginning of the section accompanied by both Malay and Maranao interlinear translations. The Maranao text is written in a different handwriting style and type of ink. Due to the distinct handwriting and ink, it is surmised that the Maranao

101 This section is an expanded version of my blogpost on the Textual Microcosms website. See Midori Kawashima, “Arabic to Malay and Maranao: Interlinear Translation in a Collection of Hadiths from Mindanao,” *Interlinear Translation of the Month (blog)*, *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*, April 2025, <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/interlinear-translation-month-32>.

text was written by Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang. As Said inherited Islamic manuscripts from his grandfather, the Imam of Bayang, around 1930, he likely wrote the Maranao interlinear translation sometime between then and his death in 1974.¹⁰² The section begins with the following words, which are attributed to the Prophet Muhammad.

Whoever speaks worldly words in five places, Allah the Exalted will resurrect him on the Day of Resurrection in the form of a pig.

Then, it lists the five places:

First, the mosque. Second, the graves. Third, where the corpse is. Fourth, at the council of scholars. Fifth, where the Qur'an is recited.

Table 6 shows the original Arabic text of the first sentence, the Malay and Maranao translations, and their English translations.

Arabic							
Man	takallama	bi-	kalāmi	al-dunyā	fi	khamsati	makānin,
Whoever	speaks	wordly words			in	five	places,
Malay							
Barang siapa	berkata2	dengan	kata	dunia	pada	lima	tempat,
Whoever	speaks	wordly words			in	five	places,
Maranao							
Si taw a	di i tharo	sa	katharo	sa doniya	dalem o	lima	tampat,
Whoever	speaks	wordly words			in	five	places,

Arabic							
	ba'atha	Allāhu	ta'āla	yawma	al-qiyāmati	kaşūrati	al-khinzīri.
	Allah the Exalted will raise him			on the Day	of Resurrection	in the form	of a pig.
Malay							
nescaya	dibangkitkan	Allah	taala	pada	hari	kiamat	seperti rupanya
certainly	Allah the Exalted will raise him			on	the Day	of Resurrection	in the form
							of a pig.
Maranao							
	oyagen	o Allah	taala	ko	alongan	a kiyamat	sa giyoto paras
	Allah the Exalted will raise him			on	the Day	of Resurrection	in the form
							of a pig.

Table 6 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms8, f. 23r.-v.

102 For the profile of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang, see Midori Kawashima, "History of the Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang in Marawi City, Lanao del Sur, Philippines," in Fathurahman, Kawashima and Riwarung eds., *The Library*, 57-64.

The Arabic text has been translated word for word into Malay and Maranao, maintaining the original word order. The Malay words are written diagonally below the corresponding Arabic words and divided according to the Arabic spacing. The Maranao text is written below the Malay text, also diagonally. However, unlike the Malay text, the spacing is not always clear. Instead of clearly separating each word and placing it directly below the corresponding word, the Maranao text tends to be written continuously without spaces, as in the first line of this hadith. Consequently, the words *dalem o*, meaning “in,” are written in the next line or in the first line of the next page, rather than below the corresponding Arabic and Malay words *fi* and *pada*. The characters in the Malay text are much smaller than those in the Arabic text; however, the Maranao text is written in larger characters than the Malay text.

In the text above, the Arabic expression “*man* + verb,” meaning “whoever does this and that,” is replaced by the Malay expression “*barang siapa* (whoever) + verb” and the Maranao expression “*si/so taw* (the person) + verb.” These Malay and Maranao words are standard translations of *man* (whoever) as seen in Table 5.

This raises the question: was the Maranao text translated from the original Arabic text or from the Malay translation? A closer examination of the texts suggests that the translator carefully read the Arabic text and selected Maranao words that accurately conveyed its meaning. For instance, the plural form of a noun used in the Maranao text aligns with the Arabic text, not the Malay text. The following illustrates this point:

Wa-thānīhā man fī al-qubūri (And the second is whoever [speaks worldly words] at the graves)

Malay: *Dan yang kedua barang siapa di dalam kubur* (And the second is whoever [speaks worldly words] in the grave/graves)

Maranao: *Ikadowa so taw a di i tharo ko manga tampat* (The second is whoever speaks [worldly words] at the graves)¹⁰³

The Arabic text uses the word *qubūr* (graves), which is the plural form of *qabr* (grave). The Malay text above uses the word *kubur*, which is derived from the Arabic word *qubūr*. Since Malay words do not have distinct singular and plural forms, *kubur* can mean either “grave” or “graves.” Conversely, the Maranao text uses the pluralizing particle *manga* to express plurality of *tampat* (grave). Because plurality is explicit in the Arabic text, and not in the Malay text, it is reasonable to assume that the translator referred to the Arabic text.

The addition of a Maranao word to the text on another page is further evidence that the translator referred to the original Arabic text (see Fig. 22, next page).

103 SMS, B7-Ms8, f.23v.

Fig. 22 Sheik Muhammad Said Collection, B7-Ms8, f.24r. Underlined by this author.

This passage has only a Malay interlinear translation, not a Maranao one. The Arabic text and the Malay translation are as follows.

*Man fasada qalbu*¹⁰⁴ *ghariqa*¹⁰⁵ *fi āfāti*¹⁰⁶ *al-dunyā* (Whoever has a corrupt heart will drown in the scourges of this world)

Barang siapa maka binasalah hatinya karamlah ia di dalam pekerjaan dunia (Whoever has a ruined heart will drown in the affairs of this world)¹⁰⁷

The Arabic word *āfāt* is a plural form of *āfah* (harm, scourge), which is translated into Malay as *pekerjaan* (work, affair). The Maranao translator was not satisfied with this translation and corrected it by writing the Maranao word *pakabinasa*, which means “can bring destruction,” as the meaning of *āfāt*. This correction demonstrates that the translator did not simply accept the Malay interlinear translation, but critically examined and corrected it based on the Arabic language.

This is consistent with the social circumstances of Islamic scholars in the Lanao region in the mid-20th century. As previously mentioned, the 1930s saw the establishment of the Kamilol Islam Society, the region’s first reformist Islamic organization, and its madrasa. The madrasa emphasized the importance of Arabic in Islamic studies, incorporating Arabic grammar into its curriculum. Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang, the scholar who wrote the Maranao interlinear translation, later sent his son to the madrasa, demonstrating his

104 The word *qalbu* is vocalized as *qalba* in the text.

105 The word *ghariqa* is vocalized as *ghuraqa* in the text.

106 The word *āfāti* is vocalized as *afāti* in the text.

107 SMS, B7-Ms8, f.24r.

openness to the reformist ideas.¹⁰⁸ Thus, scholars in the region became increasingly aware of the importance of Arabic texts in Islamic learning. However, it was difficult for the vast majority of Muslims, including scholars, to learn directly from Arabic texts. Therefore, they needed an accurate Maranao translation of these texts with which to study Arabic and Islam. Given these circumstances, it is likely that Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang based the Maranao translation primarily on the Arabic text, though he also referenced the Malay translation. This budding Islamic reformism also explains why Book D, which contains the Maranao interlinear translation, was published in the 1930s.

Conclusion

This study analyzed interlinear translations from Arabic to Malay and Maranao found in four books of hadith from the Lanao region of Mindanao. The analysis revealed several characteristics. First, interlinear translations into Malay and Maranao in the region generally follow the pattern commonly found in Arabic-to-Malay interlinear translations in Southeast Asia. An Arabic word is replaced with an equivalent word in the target language that is written diagonally in smaller letters beneath the Arabic text. Thus, despite its inland location, the Lanao region shared an Islamic literary tradition of interlinear translation with other places in maritime Southeast Asia.

Furthermore, a closer reading of the text reveals that interlinear translations have occasionally added to or altered words in the original text. For example, honorifics have been added to the names of Allah and the prophets, as in the Arabic-to-Javanese interlinear translation. Other examples include adding adverbs for emphasis and to make the text sound more natural. Additionally, the interlinear translation often clarifies pronoun referents and opaque expressions in the Arabic text. Occasionally, the interlinear translation provides an explanation for an Arabic term, even if it extends beyond the space directly below the original words. The translator likely referred to other sources when creating the interlinear translation. These sources included a vocabulary list of frequently used Arabic words and their translations, as well as a *tafsīr* in the target language. When creating a Maranao interlinear translation, in addition to the existing Malay interlinear translation, the Maranao translator read both Arabic and Malay texts, critically reviewed the Malay text, and corrected it based on the Arabic text.

Therefore, interlinear translation was not merely a mechanical replacement of Arabic words with their equivalents in the target language. Rather, it was an intellectual endeavor. Muslim scholars strove to convey the meaning of the Arabic text accurately and clearly by adding words and rephrasing to varying degrees, depending on their intended purpose. The space between the lines provided an arena in which scholars could exercise their ingenuity.

The study also sheds light on the region's linguistic practices. One example is the frequent omission of the final *ha* in Malay words in interlinear translations from Mindanao. Additionally, the ambiguous schwa vowel in standard Malay is replaced with a broad /a/, which is represented by the letter *alif* in writing. These regional variations in Malay spelling

108 Kawashima, "History," 64.

help us identify Mindanao manuscripts that have been brought to elsewhere in the world, confirming their origin. Words in the Maranao text that are the same as or similar to Malay words with the same meaning suggest Malay influence on the language used in Islamic literature. Studies of these issues from broader perspectives, such as those of the southern Philippines (including Magindanao and Sulu regions) and Southeast Asia, are expected to provide further insights into the subject.

The most significant contribution of the Maranao Muslims to interlinear translation is the creation of interlinear translation in their own language. This marked a departure from their previous reliance on Malay. They produced manuscripts and lithographed books containing Maranao interlinear translations. Lithography was later replaced by mimeograph printing. As a result, interlinear translations continued to be produced until the late 20th century.

The emergence of the Maranao interlinear translations was most significantly influenced by the Islamic reform movement led by local scholars. The scholars aimed to educate the general public about Islamic teachings based on the Qur'an and hadith. As part of this effort, they made sure that Qur'anic verses, hadiths, and prayers were understood correctly as written in the original Arabic. To accomplish this, they translated them into Maranao, the language spoken by the general populace, rather than Malay, the language used by experts and semi-experts. Interlinear translations also helped students learn Arabic. Consequently, Maranao replaced Malay as the auxiliary language used to study Arabic and Islam. Nevertheless, the supremacy of Arabic as the language for Islamic learning remained unchanged and was even further emphasized.

Most works with Maranao interlinear translations focus on hadith collections and prayer guides. This reflects the Islamic reform movement leaders' emphasis on reading and understanding the original Arabic text. They found interlinear translation to be an appropriate means to this end. Additionally, interlinear translations created a unique beauty and atmosphere favored by readers familiar with traditional Islamic manuscripts.

As previously mentioned, interlinear translation is rarely used in current Maranao Islamic texts, primarily due to the widespread use of the Latin script for writing the Maranao language and the decline of mimeograph printing. Nevertheless, interlinear translations played a significant role in developing Islamic literature in the Lanao region of Mindanao. In creating interlinear translations from Arabic to Maranao, Maranao Muslim scholars acquired the necessary skills and experience to read and interpret Arabic texts carefully, convey their meanings accurately and clearly, and to annotate them in Maranao. By nurturing authorship and readership, they gave rise to the Maranao Islamic publishing movement that began in the 1950s and which culminated in the Maranao *tafsīr* by Saromantang.¹⁰⁹ This *tafsīr* covers all the surahs of the Qur'an and is written in the Latin script. These Islamic books written in the vernacular played an important role in making religious knowledge accessible to the general population and spreading the Islamic reform movement at the grassroots level. Thus, interlinear translations paved the way for the flourishing of Islamic literary culture in later years, making a significant contribution to its development.

109 Abdulaziz Guroalim Saromantang, *So Qur'an al Karim ago so Kiya pema ana iron Ko basa a Iranan sa pilimpinas* (King Fahd Complex for the Printing of the Holy Qur'an, 2002).

References

Collections

- Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library, Marawi City, Philippines. (SMS).
- Guro sa Masiu Collection, Taraka, Lanao del Sur, Philippines. (GM).
- Maisie Van Vactor Collection of Maranao Materials in the Arabic Script at the Gowing Memorial Research Center, Marawi City, Philippines.
- Southeast Asian Kitab Collection, Institute of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies, Sophia University, Tokyo, Japan.
- Usman Imam Shiek Al-Aman Collection, Metro Manila, Philippines.

Published Materials

- ADMIN PMWP. “Irsyad al-Fatwa Series 6: The Meaning of ‘Amin’ after the Recitation of Al-Fatihah.” *Mufti of Federal Territory’s Office*. 24 November 2014. <https://muftiwp.gov.my/en/artikel/irsyad-fatwa/irsyad-fatwa-umum-cat/2045-irsyad-fatwa-series-6-the-meaning-of-amin-after-the-recitation-of-al-fatihah>.
- AMBULOTO, ‘Abd al-Halīm. *Rāshid al-Islām*. Maṭba‘at al-Shaykh ‘Abd al-Halīm Ambuloto, 1999.
- AZRA, Azyumardi. *The Origins of Islamic Reformism in Southeast Asia: Networks of Malay-Indonesian and Middle-Eastern ‘Ulamā’ in the 17th and 18th Centuries*. University of Hawa’i Press, 2004.
- BAHAROM, Noresah bt. et. al., eds. *Kamus Dewan Edisi Ketiga*. Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka, 2002.
- BANJAR, Muḥammad Arshad. *Perukunan Melayu Besar*. al-Aydarus, n.d.
- BRUINESSEN, Martin van. “Kitab Kuning: Books in Arabic Script Used in the Pesantren Milieu: Comments on a New Collection in KITLV Library.” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde van het Nederlandsch-Indie* 146, no. 2–3 (1990).
- FATHURAHMAN, Oman, Midori Kawashima, and Labi Riwarung, eds. *The Library of an Islamic Scholar of Mindanao: The Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library, Marawi City, Philippines: An Annotated Catalogue with Essays*. Occasional Papers 27. Institute of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies, Sophia University, 2019.
- GALLOP, Annabel Teh. “Islamic Manuscript Art of the Philippines.” In *The Qur’an and Islamic Manuscripts of Mindanao*. Monograph Series No. 10, edited by Midori Kawashima. Institute of Asian Cultures, Sophia University, 2012.
- GOWING, Peter, ed. *Muslim Filipinos – Heritage and Horizon*. New Day Publishers, 1979.
- HUSIN, Amir, Guro sa Masiu. *Hadīth al-Nabī ṣm*. Maṭba‘at Jāwī Farrisī, 1939.
- IANKOVSKAIA, Aglaia. “Between Translation and Commentary: An Interlinear Text from the Collection of Snouck Hurgronje.” *Archipel*, no. 106 (2023).
- IBN ISMAIL, Guro wa Alim Bayang. *Parokonan*. Lanao del Sur, 1971–1972.
- IBN NUSKHAH ‘ĀLIM, ‘Abd al-Ḥaḳīr Makalawan. *Tafsīr Juz’ ‘Amma bi-lughat Lanao*. Maṭba‘at Ḥājj ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn ‘Abd al-‘Azīz, 1933.
- JUANMARTÍ, Jacinto. *Compendio de historia universal desde la creación del mundo hasta la venida de Jesucristo y un breve vocabulario en Castellano y en Moro-Maguindanao por un padre Misionero*

de la Compañía de Jesús. Imprenta de Koh Yew Hean, 1888.

- KAWASHIMA, Midori. "Arabic to Malay and Maranao: Interlinear Translation in a Collection of Hadiths from Mindanao," *Interlinear Translation of the Month (blog)*. *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*. April 2025. <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/interlinear-translation-month-32>.
- . "Connecting Mindanao to Hijaz: The Journey of "Sayyidna" Tuan Muhammad Said." In *The Library of an Islamic Scholar of Mindanao: The Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library, Marawi City, Philippines: An Annotated Catalogue with Essays*. Occasional Papers 27, edited by Oman Fathurahman, Midori Kawashima, and Labi Riwarung. Institute of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies, Sophia University, 2019.
- . "Early Maranao Printing in Mindanao: Maranao Books in Latin and Arabic Scripts from the 1930s to 1950s." In *Between Empires: Print Culture in the Philippines (1850-1930)*, edited by Benito Rial Costas and Marlon J. Sales (Brill, forthcoming).
- . "History of the Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang in Marawi City, Lanao del Sur, Philippines," In *The Library of an Islamic Scholar of Mindanao: The Collection of Sheik Muhammad Said bin Imam sa Bayang at the Al-Imam As-Sadiq (A.S.) Library, Marawi City, Philippines: An Annotated Catalogue with Essays*. Occasional Papers 27, edited by Oman Fathurahman, Midori Kawashima, and Labi Riwarung. Institute of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies, Sophia University, 2019.
- . "The Islamic Reform Movement at Lanao in the Philippines during the 1930s: The Founding of the Kamilol Islam Society." *The Journal of Sophia Asian Studies*, no. 27 (2009).
- . "Islamic Reformism and an American Protestant Missionary: Contest over the Publication of the Qur'anic Verses in Mindanao under the US Colonial Rule." *Sophia Journal of Asian, African, and Middle Eastern Studies*, no. 34 (2016).
- . "'Jawi' (Batang Arab) Publication in Lanao, Philipines, from the 1950s to 1970s." *The Journal of Sophia Asian Studies*, no. 27 (2009).
- , ed. *The Qur'an and Islamic Manuscripts of Mindanao*. Monograph Series no. 10. Institute of Asian Culture Sophia University, 2012.
- LAUBACH, Frank C. *Forty Years with the Silent Billion*. Fleming H. Revell Company Old Tappan, 1970.
- . *The Philippines Literacy Method*. Boston, 1936.
- . *Towards a Literate World*. Colombia University Press, 1938.
- MAJUL, Cesar Adib. *Muslims in the Philippines*. Saint Mary's Publishing, 1978.
- MCKAUGHAN, Howard P. and Batua Al-Macaraya. *A Maranao Dictionary*. De La Salle University Press, 1996.
- NURTAWAB, Ervan. "Description of the Notes Found in the Qur'an of Bayang." In *The Qur'an and Islamic Manuscripts of Minadao*. Monograph Series no. 10, edited by Midori Kawashima. Institute of Asian Cultures Sophia University, 2012.
- PENCHANSKY, David. "Interpreting the Qur'an Using Some Methods from Biblical Scholarship: An Analysis of the "Taking Refuge" Suras." *Draft 5*. July 2010. https://www.academia.edu/808172/_Surah_Al_Falaq_113_and_Surah_An_Nas_114_A_Literary_Reading#loswp-work-container.
- PEDERSEN, J. "Amīn." In *Encyclopaedia of Islam New Edition Online (EI-2 English)*, edited by P. Bearman. Brill, 2012. doi: https://doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_SIM_0597
- PROUDFOOT, Ian. *Early Malay Printed Books: A Provisional Account of Materials Published in the Singapore-Malaysia Area up to 1920, Noting Holdings in Major Public Collections*. Academy of Malay Studies and the Library, University of Malaya, 1993.
- al-QURṬUBI, Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad. *Al-Jāmi' li-ahkām al-Qur'ān*, vol. 8. Al-Resāla, 2006.

- . *Tafsīr al-Qurtubī: The General Judgements of the Qurʾān and Clarification of What It Contains of the Sunnah and Āyahs of Discrimination*, translated by Aisha Bewley. Diwan Press, 2012.
- RICCI, Ronit. “Added in Translation: Keywords for the Study of Javanese Islamic Texts.” *Philological Encounters*, no. 9 (2024): 36–59.
- . “Interlinear Translation in Print (Part 1).” *Interlinear Translation of the Month (blog)*. *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*. September 2024. <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/interlinear-translation-month-25>.
- . “Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* across the Indonesian-Malay World.” *Indonesian and the Malay World* 51, no. 150 (2023): 143–164.
- . “Reading between the Lines: A World of Interlinear Translation.” *Journal of World Literature*, no. 1 (2016): 68–80.
- RIWARUNG, Labi Sarip. “The Qurʾan and Prayer Scroll of Guro sa Masiu, Taraka.” In *The Qurʾan and Islamic Manuscripts of Minadao*. Monograph Series no. 10, edited by Midori Kawashima. Institute of Asian Cultures Sophia University, 2012.
- , Primo Salivio, and Midori Kawashima. *A Catalogue of the Maisie Van Vactor Collection of Maranao Materials in the Arabic Script at the Gowing Memorial Research Center*, edited by Midori Kawashima. Institute of Asian Cultures, Sophia University, 2011.
- RONKEL, Ph. S. van. *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalam Arab Terhadap Tatakalam Melayu*, translated by A. Ikram. Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda. Bhratara, 1977. First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41 (1899): 498–528.
- SANAGUSTIN, Floréal. *Le conte de Tawwaddud al-jariya. Version de Tombouctou. Edition critique*. École normale supérieure de Lyon, 2012.
- SAROMANTANG, Abdulaziz Guroalim. *So Qurʾan al Karim ago so Kiya pema ana iron Ko basa a Ironan sa pilimpinas*. King Fahd Complex for the Printing of the Holy Qurʾan, 2002.
- al-THAʿLABI, Aḥmad ibn Muḥammad. *al-Kashf wa-l-bayān fī tafsīr al-Thaʿlabī*, vol. 6. Dār al-kutub al-ʿilmiyya, 2004.
- WEHR, Hans. *A Dictionary of Modern Written Arabic (Arabic-English)*, edited by J. Milton COWAN. Spoken Language Services, 1994.

© Midori Kawashima, Professor Emeritus, Sophia University, Tokyo
 ◀ midori-k@sophia.ac.jp ▶

Not the Utawi You Think You Know: Some Preliminary Notes on Early Javanese Interlinear Translations

MUHAMMAD DLUHA LUTHFILLAH (Hebrew University of Jerusalem)¹

Abstract

This article explores the historical trajectory of the Javanese word *utawi* within the tradition of interlinear translation of Arabic Islamic texts from the 16th to the 19th century. While in contemporary usage—particularly within *pesantren* communities where this translation practice has largely survived—*utawi* serves as a marker of the *mubtada*' (subject) in nominal sentences, earlier evidence reveals a more layered history. Based on close philological analysis of manuscripts, the study demonstrates that in the 16th and 17th centuries *utawi* was primarily employed to render the *wāw al-isti'nāf*, an Arabic particle that signals the beginning of a new sentence or clause. Only gradually, especially during the 18th century, did *utawi* become stabilized as a marker of the *mubtada*', a pattern that continued into the 19th century and even today. This diachronic shift highlights not only the changing role of a single lexical item but also broader pedagogical and linguistic transformations in the Javanese Islamic tradition. By tracing these developments, the article contributes to a more precise understanding of the internal mechanics of interlinear translation and proposes that patterns of *utawi* usage can serve as valuable indicators for the dating of otherwise anonymous manuscripts. Ultimately, this study situates *utawi* as both a linguistic key and a historical witness to the intellectual practices that shaped Islamic learning in Java.

Keywords: *utawi*, Arabic-Javanese interlinear translation, *pesantren*, Islamic manuscript culture, *mubtada*', *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

1 This research was made possible through the generous support of *Textual Microcosms: A New Approach in Translation Studies*, a project funded by the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement no. 101001731). I am profoundly grateful to Professor Ronit Ricci, the project's principal investigator and my academic supervisor, for her consistently incisive and constructive insights, and for her patient and compassionate mentorship in shaping me into a more rigorous scholar. I also extend my sincere thanks to Bang Fadhli Lukman who generously made time for our late-night discussions. I am deeply indebted to both for their invaluable intellectual contributions. Any remaining errors or inaccuracies are solely my own responsibility.

Introduction

One of the most striking features of early Islamic literature in Java is its systematic use of interlinear translation, a pedagogical and commentarial method that allowed readers to access Arabic religious texts through the local language, Javanese. Within this system, certain words functioned as grammatical and discursive markers, guiding readers through the syntactic and semantic structure of the source text. Among these, the word *utawi*, the focus of this article, stands out for its consistent presence and evolving role across manuscripts from the 16th century until today. While *utawi* is most commonly known today as an indicator of the subject of a nominal Arabic sentence (*mubtada'*), its historical usage suggests a more complex trajectory that deserves closer examination.

Despite the abundance of scholarship on Javanese literature and Islamic manuscript traditions, few studies have addressed the grammatical mechanics of interlinear translation, and even fewer have examined the diachronic development of specific translation devices like *utawi*. Existing works tend to focus either on the content of these manuscripts or on broader questions of Islamization and textual transmission.² While pioneering scholars have provided invaluable insights into the literary and historical contexts of Javanese Islamic texts,³ they did not delve into the microstructure of translation practices. The internal linguistic system these texts employ remains largely underexplored, leaving open the question of how specific grammatical markers emerged, stabilized, or shifted in meaning and function over time.

Before proceeding further, a brief introduction of the system of interlinear translation practiced in Java merits attention here. Among the communities that employ it—most notably the *pesantren* (Islamic boarding school) milieu—this system is often referred to as the “*utawi-iki-iku* translation system.” The use of *utawi-iki-iku* as a shorthand for *pesantren* interlinear translation system likely stems from the frequent appearance of these three words, particularly in the translation of chapter titles in classical texts. The classical books studied in *pesantren* are typically divided into chapters, each introduced by a simple phrase such as *bāb al-ṭahāra* (chapter on purification) or *bāb al-bay'* (chapter on trade). To translate these chapter titles, *pesantren* scholars developed a complex grammatical analysis and rendered that analysis into Javanese.

2 Merle C. Ricklefs, *Mystic Synthesis in Java: A History of Islamization from the Fourteenth to the Early Nineteenth Centuries* (East Bridge, 2006); G.W.J. Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari: A 16th Century Javanese Muslim Text Attributed to the Saint of Bonan Re-Edited and Translated with an Introduction* (Springer Netherlands, 1969); Azyumardi Azra, *Jaringan Ulama: Timur Tengah dan Kepulauan Nusantara Abad XVII Dan XVIII: Melacak Akar-Akar Pembaruan Pemikiran Islam di Indonesia* (Mizan, 1994).

3 See, for example, G.W.J. Drewes, *Een Javaanse Primbon: Uit De Zestiende Eeuw Opnieuw Uitgegeven En Vertaald* (Brill, 1954); G.W.J. Drewes and L.F. Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri* (Foris Publication, 1986); Nancy K. Florida, *Writing the Past, Inscribing the Future* (Duke University Press, 1995); Merle C. Ricklefs, *The Seen and Unseen Worlds in Java, 1726–1749: History, Literature and Islam in the Court of Pakubuwana II* (University of Hawai'i Press, 1998); Ronit Ricci, *Islam Translated: Literature, Conversion, and the Arabic Cosmopolis of South and Southeast Asia* (University of Chicago Press, 2011).

Written Arabic original	<i>bāb al-ṣalā</i>
Grammatically analyzed	<i>[hādhā] bāb [fī bayān] al-ṣalā</i>
Utawi-iki-iku translation	<i>[utawi iki iku] bab [ingdalem nerangaken] ṣalāt</i>
English translation	[utawi this is] a chapter [on explaining] prayer

Table 1 Translation of an Arabic chapter title with *utawi-iki-iku* system

Upon grammatical analysis, *bāb al-ṣalā* is understood as a shortened form of *hādhā bāb fī bayān al-ṣalā* (this is a chapter explaining purification), where *hādhā* functions as the *mubtada'* (subject) and *bāb* as the *khbar* (predicate). In modern pesantren interlinear translation, *mubtada'* and *khbar* are typically rendered with *utawi* and *iku*, respectively, resulting in a full translation of *bāb al-ṣalā* as *utawi iki iku bab ingdalem nerangaken ṣalāt* (*utawi* this is a chapter on explaining prayer).⁴ This analytical approach is applied not only to chapter titles but also to any phrase requiring similar treatment, making *utawi-iki-iku* so common that it has come to represent the distinctive translation system of pesantren.

Fig. 1 An interlinear translation of an Arabic phrase into Javanese using the *utawi-iki-iku* system

Studies such as those by Sidney Jones and Aly Basalamah have tried to provide a sort of introduction to the system.⁵ They indicate that by the 20th century, Javanese Muslims had developed a distinct system to interlinearly translate Arabic textbooks. One key feature of this system, as Basalamah describes it, is a form of “*bahasa simbolik*” (symbolic language)

4 *Utawi* is left untranslated here and kept at the beginning of the sentence to reflect its position in the original Javanese text, while the rest of the sentence has English equivalents, including “is” for *iku*.
 5 Sidney Jones, “Arabic Instruction and Literacy in Javanese Muslim Schools,” *International Journal of Society and Language* 42 (1983): 83–94; Aly Abubakar Basalamah, “Memahami Kitab Kuning Melalui Terjemahan Tradisional: Suatu Pendekatan Tradisional Terjemahan Pondok Pesantren,” *Al-Jami’ah* 55 (1994): 61–69.

that encodes grammatical positions, morphemic changes, and other linguistic elements, including words like *utawi*. Beyond *utawi*, the system developed symbols to indicate a wide range of grammatical (*naḥw*) statuses—such as *ing* for *mafʿūl bih* (object) and *apane* for *tamyīz* (a specifier)—as well as several other aspects, including morphology (*ṣarf*), particularly in marking past (*māḍī*) and future (*mustaqbal*) tenses when they need to be explicitly shown.⁶ Interlinear translation practices in pesantren served a dual purpose: they facilitated both the study of the textbook’s content and the learning of Arabic itself. As neither Jones nor Basalamah focuses on any particular pesantren as a case study, their research implies that this interlinear translation system had become a widely recognized convention across Javanese-speaking regions. Building on the research of Jones and Basalamah and connecting it with what I have observed in the interlinear translation practices in pesantren, I believe that Javanese Muslims, particularly those in pesantren communities, have taken for granted that this system has been a long-established convention, not only in the present but even in centuries past.

This study aims to fill part of that gap, namely the lack of detailed analysis of the internal linguistic mechanics of Javanese interlinear translation and their historical development, and to challenge that taken-for-granted approach to the Javanese interlinear translation system. In doing so the study traces the historical trajectory of *utawi* as it appears mainly in a corpus of interlinear Javanese translations of Arabic texts dated between the 16th and 19th centuries. It draws on close philological analysis of selected manuscripts from pesantren collections and public archives, examining not only the appearance of *utawi* but also its syntactic environments and co-occurrence with other translation markers. The investigation is guided by a diachronic framework, allowing for the identification of gradual shifts, ruptures, and moments of stabilization in translation practice.

Throughout this article I argue that the function of *utawi* shifted over time—initially serving to render the Arabic conjunction *wāw al-isti’nāf* (a type of *wāw*, “and”, that starts a new, independent sentence or clause) and later becoming stabilized as a marker of the *muḥtadā*.⁷ This analysis relies on both dated and undated manuscripts, with the aim of establishing not only patterns of linguistic change but also potential implications for dating anonymous texts. By doing so, I aim to provide new insights into the evolution of the Javanese interlinear tradition, demonstrating how the changing role of *utawi* reflects broader pedagogical and linguistic transformations in Islamic Java. Ultimately, this micro-level focus contributes to a more nuanced understanding of textual transmission, local hermeneutics, and the historical development of Islamic education in the region.

6 Saiful Umam, “Localizing Islamic Orthodoxy in Northern Coastal Java in the Late 19th and Early 20th Centuries: A Study of Pegon Islamic Texts” (PhD Dissertation, University of Hawai’i, 2011). Following on Umam’s footsteps, Muhammad Jaeni and Sahal Mahfudh provide a more detailed and comprehensive discussion of this system. See Muhammad Jaeni, “Pola-Pola Pengapsahan Kitab Pesantren Kiai Pesisir Utara Jawa Tengah Abad XIX-XX: Kajian Histori-Sosiolinguistik” (UIN Walisongo, 2019); Sahal Mahfudh, “Al-Kitāba al-‘Arabiyya Li-Lughat al-Jāwiyyah (Pegon): Dirāsa Lughawiyya Ijtimā’iyya ‘alā -Stibqā’ihā Fī Muḥtama’ al-Besantren al-Taqlīdī Bi-Jāwā” (UIN Sunan Kalijaga, 2023).

7 It is important to note that a *muḥtadā* refers only to the subject of a nominal sentence. The subject of a verbal sentence is called a *fā’il* (literally “the doer,” or “the one who performs an action”).

Utawi (اتاوي or اتاو)

Gericke and Roorda explain that *utawi* is a refined form of *atawa* or *utawa*.⁸ In Javanese, this word functions as a “conjunction that links what follows to what precedes it, [presenting it as an alternative or] as something else” and serves as a counterpart to Dutch words such as *of* (or), *en/of anders* (and/or otherwise), *als ook* (as well), and *ook* (also).⁹ Elsewhere, Gericke and Roorda also note that Javanese speakers do not always use *utawi* in this sense.¹⁰ In other words, Javanese speakers express such conjunctive meanings with alternative forms and use *atawa-utawa-utawi* more flexibly to express additional meanings.

The word *utawi* is used very frequently in two manuscripts known to date as the earliest witnesses of Arabic-Javanese interlinear translation practices. Purchased by Jan Theunisz (d. 1638) in the Netherlands around 1610 and now kept in the library of the University of Amsterdam, I F 31 and I H 1 recorded the appearance of *utawi* more than a hundred times.¹¹ In all these instances, I found that *utawi* is used in translations of words that are preceded by the Arabic particle *wāw*, known in Arabic grammar as *wāw al-isti'nāf*.¹² As an introduction to a new sentence, what follows it might be a nominal sentence (*jumla ismiyya*) or a verbal one (*jumla fi'liyya*). In the case of a nominal sentence, the first word following the *wāw* is the *mubtada'* and can only be a noun (*ism*) or a word that acts as a noun (similar to the English infinitive). With this in mind, and considering the modern understanding of *utawi* in the *utawi-iku* system as rendering the *mubtada'* status, the clearest examples supporting my

8 It is interesting to note that *utawi* is one of very few words, if not the only one from the *krama* (refined) register used as grammatical indicators in the *utawi-iki-iku* translation system.

9 Johann F.C. Gericke and Taco Roorda, *Javaansch-Nederlandsch Handwoordenboek* (Brill, 1901), 1:86.

10 Johann F.C. Gericke and Taco Roorda, *Javaansch-Nederduitsch Woordenboek* (Johannes Müller, 1847), 33.

11 Although often attested as the earliest Javanese interlinear manuscripts, the two manuscripts have enjoyed very little attention from scholars. To the best of my knowledge, only Nur Ahmad has revisited these two manuscripts in a few short essays of his. His writings on these manuscripts were initially published around 2017 as popular essays on the Islamic website www.alif.id. In 2020, they were compiled into a book titled *Wajah Islam Nusantara: Jejak Tradisi Santri, Aksara Pegon, dan Keberislaman dalam Manuskrip Kuno* (Tangerang: Pustaka Compass, 2020). However, his analysis remains limited to the translation of two Arabic words, which he argues are uniquely adapted to the local linguistic context, without delving further into the manuscripts themselves. The two words in question are *siwāk*, which is translated as *susur* (betel chewing?), and *safar*, which is translated as *pelayaran* (sailing). Ahmad then connects both terms to the socio-cultural context of Javanese society, which was familiar with both betel chewing and seafaring. For further discussion, see <https://jangkah.id/2024/01/11/islam-akses-literasi-dan-pribumisasi-pelajaran-dari-dua-manuskrip-kitab-fikih-dengan-terjemah-pegon-jawa-tahun-1610-m/>, accessed in March 2025. It is worth noting that Ahmad draws these examples only from the translation practices found in the *Kitab al-Īdāh* (cataloged as I H 1). For more about I F 31 and I H 1, see also Hendrik Frederik Wijnman, “De Hebraicus Jan Theunisz Barbarossius Alias Johannes Antonides Als Lector in Het Arabisch Aan de Leidse Universiteit (1612/1613). Een Hoofdstuk Amsterdamsche Geleerdengeschiedenis,” *Studia Rosenthaliana* 2, no. 2 (1968): 22–23.

12 I follow Dror’s translation of Bābitī’s definition of *wāw al-isti'nāf*. She writes that “*wāw l-isti'nāf* is used as a particle with which a speech begins, [or] the sentence that followed it is completely independent in meaning from the sentence that precedes it.” Yehudit Dror, “Is Each Particle in the Qur’ān Translatable? The Case of Wāw al-Isti’nāf Preceding the Fawāsil,” *Babel* 61, no. 1 (2015): 24.

argument are cases where *utawi* is followed by a word that is not a noun or noun-like, i.e., *fi'l* (verb) or *ḥarf*.¹³

Such examples are not uncommon in both of these texts. In I F 31, we encounter *wa-yajūzu* (and it is allowed), which is translated as *utawi wenang* (*utawi* is allowed) (Fig. 1). Since *yajūzu* is a verb, it cannot directly serve as a *mubtada'* unless it is either nominalized (e.g., *jawāz*) or introduced by a particle such as *an*, forming *an yajūza*. In this case, *yajūzu* appears directly after the *wāw* (*wa-yajūzu*), which means the word—*yajūzu*—cannot function as a *mubtada'*. Yet it is translated as *utawi wenang*. This raises a problem: since *wenang* corresponds to *yajūzu*, it is unlikely that *utawi* is translating the *mubtada'*. Instead, it seems that *utawi* is being used to render the particle *wa*.

Fig. 2 *Al-Ghāya wa-l-Taqrīb*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I F 1, fol. 34. A *wāw*-rendering *utawi* is followed by the verb *yajūzu* (*wenang*, “is allowed”).

The *isti'nāf* function of the *wāw* is especially important in Arabic, which doesn't use punctuation marks like periods, commas, or others to indicate the position of words, phrases, or sentences within a text. To clarify the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*, I will provide a more complete context of the sentence from this example.

Wa-ṣalātu l-jamā'ati sunnatun mu'akkad. [sic.] Wa-yajibu 'alā l-ma'mūmi an yanwiya l-jamā'ata dūna l-imāmi. Wa-yajūzu an ya'tamma al-hurru bi-l-'abdi.

Congregational prayer is a *sunna mu'akkad* (highly emphasized practice/tradition). A *ma'mūm* (congregant) is required to have an intention (*niyya*) to join the congregation, but the *imām* (prayer leader) is not. A free person is allowed to become a *ma'mūm* (congregant) of a slave.¹⁴

In this “paragraph” the *wāw* does not function as a conjunction but rather marks the beginning of a new sentence. This role is similar to that of, in English, a capital letter after a period, which signals the end of the previous sentence. When encountering a period, a reader

13 Finding an exact English equivalent for *ḥarf* is quite challenging—if one exists at all. In Arabic grammar, *ḥarf* is part of the tripartite division of parts of speech, alongside *ism* and *fi'l*. While *ism* is commonly equated with “noun” and *fi'l* with “verb,” *ḥarf* is almost always defined in negative terms. Sibawayh, one of the foundational figures in Arabic grammatical theory, describes *ḥarf* as “that which conveys a meaning but is neither a noun nor a verb” (*jā'a li-ma'nan laysa bi-sm wa-lā fi'l*) Sibawayh, *Al-Kitāb* (Maktaba al-Khānjī, 1988), 1:12. As such, *ḥarf* encompasses a wide range of categories that, in English grammar, would be distributed across distinct parts of speech—namely, prepositions, conjunctions, and particles.

14 I F 31, fols. 33–34

immediately knows that the sentence they are reading has ended, and what follows is the start of a new sentence. Similarly, when encountering wāw al-isti'nāf, a reader immediately knows that they are facing a new sentence, and the previous one has concluded.

In I H 1, we encounter another case, when *wa-idhā* (and when/if) is translated as *utawi tatkala* (*utawi* when/if) (Fig. 2). This is an even stronger example because *idhā* is a conditional particle (*adāt al-shart*), so there is no way the particle can serve as a *mubtada'* in a sentence. However, the interlinear translation uses *utawi tatkala*. Using the same logic as before, we can identify *tatkala* as rendering *idhā*, and once again, *utawi* is translating the particle *wa*. The function of *isti'nāf* in this example is also easier to recognize because it is the first sentence in a new *kitāb* (literally “book,” but used here in the sense of “chapter”).

Fig. 3 *Al-Īdāh*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, fol. 13. A *wāw*-rendering *utawi* is followed by the conditional particle *idhā* (*tatkala* [when/if]).

The only instance of *utawi* that clearly represents the position of the *mubtada'*—as it does in modern usage—is in the phrase *kullu mā'in* (all kinds of water) on fol. 2 of I H 1 (Fig. 3). This word begins the first sentence of a new *kitāb*, does not have *wāw al-isti'nāf*, but is translated with *utawi*. Apart from this example, *utawi* is always used to translate the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*.

Fig. 4 *Al-Īdāh*, Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, fol. 2. The only *utawi* to function as indicating the *mubtada'* status.

The use of *utawi* to render a *mubtada'* that is not preceded by *wāw al-isti'nāf* appears more frequently in Sloane 2645 from the British Library collection, a copy of *al-Muqaddima al-*

Ḥaḍrāmiyya (The Ḥaḍrami Introduction or Prolegomenon).¹⁵ However, this usage consistently occurs at the beginning of a new *faṣl* (section), specifically in the translation of its first word. Within the main body of a *faṣl*, *mubtada*'s that lack *wāw al-isti'nāf* are almost never translated with *utawi*. Notably, there is also a *faṣl* whose first sentence begins with a verb (*fi'l*) and lacks *wāw al-isti'nāf*, but is still translated with *utawi* (Fig. 4). While this might be seen as an error, it is also possible that the translator of Sloane 2645 was so accustomed to encountering the formula *wāw al-isti'nāf* + *fi'l* at the beginning of a *faṣl*, and thus inserted *utawi* out of habit. In any case, I would argue that Sloane 2645 reflects a broader pattern in which *utawi* is predominantly used to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

Fig. 5 *Al-Muqaddima al-Ḥaḍrāmiyya*, British Museum Library, Sloane 2645, fol. 75v. The use of *utawi* in translating *fi'l* without *wāw al-isti'nāf*.

Alongside the general patterns outlined above, the three earliest manuscripts (I F 31 and I H 1 from University of Amsterdam and Sloane 2645 from British Library) also present exceptions in the use of *utawi* and in the translation of words that either contain *wāw al-isti'nāf* or function grammatically as *mubtada*'. The pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she), when occupying the syntactic position of the *mubtada*', are consistently rendered formulaically as *iya iku* (it is). When preceded by *wāw*—whether as *isti'nāf* or simple conjunction—the phrase is not introduced by *utawi*, but by *lan* (and), resulting in *lan iya iku* (and it is). Conversely, *utawi* is consistently absent when the *mubtada*' is preceded not by *wāw al-isti'nāf* but by *fā' al-isti'nāf*.¹⁶ In such cases, it is either replaced by *maka* (then) or omitted altogether. A similar pattern can be observed in the translation of *wa-ammā* (and, as for) and *fa-ammā* (then, as

15 Sloane 2645 is a copy and translation of a legal treatise authored by 'Abdullāh b. 'Abd al-Raḥmān Bā Faḍl (d. 1512) of Ḥaḍramawt, Yemen—hence its title, *al-Muqaddima al-Ḥaḍrāmiyya*. It was copied (and possibly also translated) by a scribe named 'Abd al-Qadīm. The colophon records the date as 1545 in the Javanese calendar—an Islamized adaptation of the lunar Indic Saka calendar—corresponding to 1623/4 AD. While there is no clear record of how the manuscript came into the hands of the British scholar and collector Sir Hans Sloane (d. 1753), it was most likely acquired through trade. For further information on the Sloane collection, see Annabel Teh Gallop, “Southeast Asian Manuscripts from the Collection of Sir Hans Sloane in the British Library,” *Wacana* 20, no. 1 (2019): 15–31. For details on the Javanese calendar, see Ian Proudfoot, *Old Muslim Calendars of Southeast Asia* (Brill, 2006).

16 Besides *wāw*, *fā'* can also function as *isti'nāf*, that is “when *fa-* is taken as beginning a new utterance, unconnected to the preceding one.” For more, see Arik Sadan, *The Subjunctive Mood in Arabic Grammatical Thought* (Brill, 2012), 152.

for): the former is regularly rendered as *utawi anapun*, while the latter appears as either *maka anapun* or simply *anapun*.

This usage of *utawi* to render the *wāw* in its function as an *isti'nāf* particle can also be observed in other early Islamic manuscripts, including *Pegon* manuscripts not composed in interlinear format as well as texts written in Javanese script. By contrast, the alternative function of *utawi*—namely, its role in marking the *mubtada'*—along with the exceptional uses outlined above, appears to be limited to a narrower corpus of interlinear works.¹⁷ One such example is the manuscript from the Leiden University Library, cataloged as Or. 5716. This manuscript contains several texts, one of which is a translation of *al-Muntahī*, a Sufi poetic work by Hamzah Fansuri.¹⁸ This manuscript comes from Banten in the 17th century and is written in prose, in *Pegon* script.¹⁹ The manuscript includes Arabic quotations that are then translated into Javanese, including the hadith “*al-insānu sirrī wa-anā sirruhu*”²⁰ (Man is My secret and I am its secret) and the wise words of a Sufi “*al-Ḥaqqu ‘aynu l-khalqi in kunta dhā ‘ayni wa-l-khalqu ghayru l-Ḥaqqi in kunta dhā ‘aqli*” (God the Truth is the very essence of the creature if you are one with sight [a person who sees], the servant is not God the Truth if you are someone of reason).²¹ In both of these examples, there are several words that function as *mubtada'*: *al-insānu* (Man), *wa-anā* (and I), *al-Ḥaqqu* (God the Truth), and *wa-l-khalqu* (and the creature). However, of these four, only the *mubtada'* that follows *wāw* is translated with *utawi* (see the table below). Thus, *utawi* does not indicate the *mubtada'* but rather translates the *isti'nāf* function of *wāw*.

17 I classify the broader corpus into two script traditions: Javanese and *Pegon* scripts. The *Pegon* manuscripts can be further divided into those with and without interlinear translation. In the following two to three pages, I offer a brief and tentative observation on manuscripts outside my main corpus—namely, non-interlinear *Pegon* manuscripts and texts written in Javanese script.

18 Jan Just Witkam, *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden* (Ter Lugt Press, 2007), 6:194.

19 There is some disagreement about the dating of this manuscript, but I concur with Drewes, who follows Voorhoeve in assigning it to the 17th century Paul Voorhoeve, *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands* (Leiden University Press, 1980), 86. Drewes provides several reasons to support this dating, including the paper's watermark, the type of damage the paper has sustained, and the history of the reception of *al-Muntahī* in Banten, the manuscript's region of origin Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 251–52.

20 Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 269.

21 Drewes and Brakel, *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*, 257. English translations are mine. The English translations are deliberately kept as faithful as possible, in part to reproduce for the reader the riddle-like quality experienced by Javanese readers of the sentences.

<i>al-insānu</i>	<i>sirrī</i>	<i>wa-anā</i>	<i>sirruhu</i>
<i>manusia</i>	<i>iku rahsaningsun,</i>	<i>utawi ingsun</i>	<i>pun rahsane</i>
Man	is my secret	<i>utawi</i> I	am its secret
<i>al-ʿaqqu</i>	<i>?aynu l-khalqī</i>	<i>in kunta</i>	<i>dhā ʿayni</i>
<i>Kang Pangeran</i>	<i>iku kahananing kawula,</i>	<i>lamun sira</i>	<i>wong kang aningali</i>
God	is the state of the servant	if you are	a person who sees
<i>wa-l-khalqu</i>	<i>ghayru l-ʿaqqī</i>	<i>in kunta</i>	<i>dhā ʿaqli</i>
<i>Utawi kawula</i>	<i>iku liyan saking kahananing Pangeran</i>	<i>lamun ana sira</i>	<i>wong barbudi</i>
<i>Utawi</i> the servant	is other than [or is not] the state of God	if you are	a person of wisdom

Table 2 Line-by-line Javanese translation of Arabic quotations in Leiden UB Or. 5716.*

Further attestation can be found in another collection at the Leiden University Library. The manuscript with the code Or. 1928 is also known by the title used by Drewes in his translation of this manuscript, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*.²² Originating from the northern coast of Java in the 16th century, this manuscript is a treatise on Islamic theology and Sufism, featuring Seh ul-Bari as a religious figure presenting the key teachings of Islam that form the content of the book.²³ In one of the discussions, there is a phrase “*utawi ana woñ sasar sawiji, Arabiyah arane, ak(e)cap*” (Or. 1928 fol. 27). This marks the beginning of a story about someone who, according to the author of this manuscript, does not practice Islam properly, thus becoming *sasar* (Jv. lost, gone astray). In telling this story, Or. 1928 is not translating from Arabic, making it an important example. While in the previous example we saw line-by-line translation (not word-for-word as in I F 31 and I H 1), here we encounter a stand-alone Javanese sentence whose construction follows a logic similar to that of interlinear translation.

The story of the person who went astray has been discussed by several scholars, resulting in various English translations of this expression. In his pioneering research, Drewes translated the sentence quite loosely as, “Another false doctrine is that of ‘Arabiyya (Ibn al-‘Arabi) who teaches as follows.”²⁴ However, I tend to agree with Yumi Sugahara’s more faithful translation, “There is another person who has lost his way. His name is ‘Arabiyya. He teaches as follows”, which allows us to better recognize the function of *utawi* in this sentence.²⁵ However, I must point out that even in Sugahara’s faithful translation, *utawi* is

22 Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*.

23 Theodore G. Th. Pigeaud, *Literature of Java* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1968), 2:52.

24 Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 59.

25 Yumi Sugahara, “Sunan Bonang’s Teaching: Ethical Sufism in Sixteenth-Century Java,” in *Storied Island: New Explorations in Javanese Literature*, ed. Ronit Ricci (Brill, 2023), 137.

not translated: “there is” translates *ana*, “another” likely translates *sawiji*, “person” translates *woñ*, “lost” translates *sasar*, and “who has” is an addition to make the English translation more readable, much like how *sawiji* (another) is moved to the beginning of the sentence this translation. I believe my argument about *utawi* as a rendering of *wāw al-isti’nāf* also applies here. Whether intentionally or not, by not translating *utawi* and capitalizing the letter T in “There,” Sugahara has preserved every word of the source text.²⁶

The final attestation comes from a manuscript in the collection of Thomas Erpenius, now housed in the Cambridge University Library. This manuscript bears a symbol indicating that before becoming part of Erpenius’ collection, it was owned by Josephus Scaliger, who passed away in 1609. In other words, this manuscript may have been written in the early 17th century or even the 16th century.²⁷ The manuscript with the code Gg.5.22 is a collection of several texts on Islamic theology and law (*fiqh*). In one section, there is an explanation of several theological and legal principles in Islam presented in the form of a catechisms with the formula *utawi lamun (utawi if)*. This section spans several pages from fol. 114, and I will only highlight two examples.

On fol. 114, there is a catechism point: “*Utawi lamun sira tinakonan apa tegesing iman, sauranira, aneguhaken i barang kang den ucap, dene wo sawiji*” (*utawi if you are asked what īmān means, reply “fulfilling what has been spoken, even if it’s just one thing”*). On fol. 116: “*Utawi lamun sira tinakonan apa agama kang fardlu i syarang, sauranira agama ing Allah*” (*utawi if you are asked which religion mandates the sharī’a, reply “the religion of Allah”*). In both of these examples, *utawi* is followed by *lamun*, which functions as a conditional particle, similar to *idhā* in the previous example. In this textual context, the appearance of *utawi* coincides with the beginning of a new catechism point—here, it resembles the appearance of *wāw* when it functions as *isti’nāf*.

The various examples of *utawi* usage discussed above suggest that, by the 17th century, there already existed an established interlinear translation system, to which the interlinear texts bear witness—a system that employed *utawi* to render *wāw al-isti’nāf*. In this system, *utawi* was also occasionally used to mark the *mubtada’* position but to a much lesser degree compared to its use for *isti’nāf*. This system seems to have been widely adopted and well-established, as evidenced by its use in Islamic manuscripts written in other formats, such as prose, during this period and probably the preceding century. However, several questions remain: When was this system first implemented? How did it become so influential and pervasive? In what circumstances and within what kinds of communities was it used? And how long did it remain in use? Unfortunately, the material evidence currently available to us does not allow for definitive answers to all of these questions—except, perhaps, the last one.

26 Another example of *utawi* as indicating a *mubtada’* can be found in this manuscript. In fol. 37, there is the phrase: “*Heh mitraninsun, kalawan ta sira aja ña(m)bil dedeniñ woñ, utawi aja sira murtad in samitranira kañ asih in sira, kufur ukume,*” which Drewes translates as “My friends! Do not pay attention merely to people’s mistakes. Do not renounce your friends who are well-disposed towards you. That is unbelief.” Drewes, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 67. Here, *utawi* also marks the beginning of a new discourse/point/sentence.

27 Majid Daneshgar, *Reconstructing Erpenius’ Library: The First Collection of Oriental Manuscripts at Cambridge University Library* (Brill, 2025), 61.

Utawi in Transition

Before continuing the discussion, I must clarify that all the manuscripts in the previous section are from the 17th century, or are presumed to be from that period. This section, however, focuses on manuscripts from the period leading into and throughout the 18th century, with occasional references to 19th-century materials. I should also note that I did not address the regional provenance of the manuscripts discussed earlier as the regional provenance of most of these manuscripts is unknown. For the sake of the argument I am proposing, I will take the same approach in this section, momentarily setting aside regional considerations. Therefore, anyone examining the regional aspect of these manuscripts and finding regional variations may and should revise and adjust this argument accordingly.

In this section, I explore the shifting use of utawi as documented in several 18th-century manuscripts. By “shifting,” I refer to the changing proportion between the use of utawi to render wāw al-isti’nāf and its use to mark the mubtada’. While the former was clearly dominant in the 17th century, the pattern begins to reverse in the 18th. The manuscripts reveal a gradual shift: from the dominance of utawi-for-isti’nāf, to a more balanced usage, and eventually to the predominance of utawi as indicating the mubtada’. They also show a growing complexity in how wāw al-isti’nāf and mubtada’ are translated, especially when appearing with ḥarf or certain formulaic expressions. The following examples will help clarify these points.

The manuscript catalogued as A 45 in the collection of the National Library of the Republic of Indonesia (Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, henceforth PNRI) is a composite manuscript. It comprises copies and interlinear translations of *Tuḥfat al-ṭālib al-mubtadī wa-minḥat al-sālik al-muhtadī* (fols. 1–142) and *Zubdat al-asrār* (fols. 153–385), along with various marginal and interstitial notes. Both works are attributed to Yūsuf Tāj al-Khalwatī al-Maqāṣirī (d. 1111/1699), although his name appears only in the copy of *Zubda*. This second work also includes a colophon—which the first text lacks—dating it to 1087 AH (1676 AD). However, as the colophon belongs to the source text, it cannot serve as direct evidence for dating the interlinear translation. At most, it provides a *terminus post quem* for its composition. I will return to this issue of dating in the following section; here, I focus on the use of utawi in this manuscript.

In this manuscript and the following examples, I will examine the use and absence of utawi across three categories: (1) mubtada’ preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, (2) mubtada’ not preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, and (3) wāw al-isti’nāf followed by *fi’l* or ḥarf. In this particular manuscript, utawi is most frequently used to translate cases in the first category and appears much less often in the second and third. While there are always some instances where the translation occurs without utawi in all the categories, it is most notably absent in the translation of the second. Interestingly, some verbs (*fi’l*) are translated with utawi even when they are not preceded by wāw al-isti’nāf, as shown in the case of *i’lam* (imperative, “know!” or “be aware!”) in Fig. 5. A likely explanation for this is that *i’lam* often appears elsewhere in the text preceded by and is regularly translated with utawi. Thus, it can be inferred that the utawi-for-isti’nāf pattern remains dominant in this manuscript.

Fig. 6 *Tuhfat al-ṭālib al-mubtadī*, The National Library of Indonesia, A 45, fol. 157. The formulaic translation of the pronoun *hiya* and the use of *utawi* for neither *wāw al-isti'nāf* nor *mubtada'*.

There are several intriguing points worth noting. The exceptions observed in the three earlier interlinear manuscripts regarding the translation of pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she), as well as instances where *fa-* (then) interrupts the structure of *wāw al-isti'nāf* and *mubtada'*, also appear in this manuscript, albeit with even greater consistency. In cases where *huwa* and *hiya* occupy the grammatical position of *mubtada'*, with or without *wāw* (whether functioning as *isti'nāf* or as a conjunction), they are invariably translated in a formulaic manner as *lan iya iku* (and it is) (as shown in Fig. 5). A new exception I identified in this manuscript pertains to the translation of ordinal numbers (e.g., *awwal/ūlā* for “first,” *thānī* for “second,” *thālith* for “third,” etc.). In this manuscript these terms are never translated with *utawi*, or, if *utawi* is used, it only appears for *awwal/ūlā* and is not used for subsequent ordinals. All of this, in my view, reinforces the previous conclusion that the *utawi-for-isti'nāf* pattern remains dominant in manuscripts from the third quarter of the 17th century.

As the century drew to a close, the pattern of *utawi* usage appears to have undergone a shift. This transition is evident in the composite manuscript A 97 from the collection of the National Library of Indonesia. Written in or after 1100/1688, this manuscript employs *utawi* to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf* (including instances where it is followed by *ḥarf*), but it predominantly uses *utawi* to render the *mubtada'*.²⁸ Notably, the phrase *wa-lam*, which is frequently translated with *utawi* even when *wāw al-isti'nāf* is absent (as seen in A 45), is never rendered as *utawi* in this manuscript; it only has *lan* (and). Likewise, *wa-ammā*, a

28 On the first page of the manuscript, there is an ownership statement that mentions the year of its composition, although it is unfortunately incomplete. The statement reads: “*Sharah Tuhfa Mawāhib al-Mursala kalaning sinerat sasi Jumadil Akhir tanggal ping roliku(r) tahun zā(y) ... nabi ṣal'am [sic.] ... sewu satu(s) ... lemampah*” (Supercommentary on *Tuhfa*, the *Mawāhib al-Mursala*, written in the month of *Jumādā al-Ākhir*, the twenty-second, year *zāy* ... the Prophet *ṣal'am* ... one thousand and one hundred ... has passed). The letters in brackets indicate they are missing. I have left gaps in some places to account for the words that should have appeared but are cut off. This note indicates that the manuscript was written in or after the year 1100 AH, corresponding to approximately 1688 AD.

commonly occurring phrase, is no longer translated with *utawi* as it typically is. This suggests a discernible shift, with the use of *utawi* to translate the *mubtada'* becoming increasingly dominant.

The dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'* appears to have remained relatively stable until the first quarter of the 18th century, as evidenced in the manuscript Or. 5675 from the Leiden University Library. This manuscript, dated 1142 AH (1729–30 AD), consistently translates the *mubtada'* with or without *wāw al-isti'nāf* using *utawi*. Although there are a few instances where the *mubtada'* is translated without *utawi*, these occurrences are sufficiently rare and can be regarded as human errors. The translations of *huwa/hiya*, *wa-ammā*, *fa-ammā*, and *wa-lam* remain consistently without *utawi*, reflecting the same pattern observed in the PNRI A 97 manuscript. Of particular note in Or. 5675 is the complete absence of instances where *wāw al-isti'nāf*, followed by *fi'l* or *ḥarf*, are translated with *utawi*. This suggests the dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'*. Nevertheless, this manuscript does not signify the end of the use of *utawi-for-isti'nāf*. Another Leiden collection, Or. 1842, which includes colophons dating from 1168/1754-5 and 1186/1772-3, offers important evidence for that. In this manuscript we observe the same general pattern of *utawi* usage with a continued dominance of *utawi-for-mubtada'*. Yet, *utawi* continues to appear in the translation of *wāw al-isti'nāf* followed by *fi'l* and *ḥarf*, albeit with considerably lower frequency.²⁹

Fig. 7 An untitled tract from al-Rifā'i order, Leiden University Library, Or. 1842, fol. 346r. The use of *utawi* to translate *wāw al-isti'nāf* followed by a *fi'l*.

29 Another example is found in fol. 336v, where *wa-yajibu* (and it is mandatory) is translated as *utawi wajib* (*utawi* mandatory). Additionally, an interesting case of translation variation appears on fol. 106r, where two instances of *wa-mā*—where *mā* functions as a *ḥarf nafī* (negative particle)—are translated differently, offering an intriguing example of *ḥarf* usage. In this instance, the first *wa-mā* appears in *wa-mā mashā aḥad* (and no one is walking) and translates to *utawi oratah lumaku wong sawiji* (*utawi* someone is not walking). The second *wa-mā* appears in *wa-mā awā aḥad* (and no one is going down) and translates to *lan ora tumurun wong sawiji* (and someone is not going down). The use of *utawi* and *lan* may indicate the translator's different understandings of the two instances of *wa-mā*: the first as *isti'nāf*, thus rendered with *utawi*, and the second as *'ataf* (conjunction), rendered with *lan*.

The manuscripts reveal a gradual shift in the dominant usage of utawi from translating wāw al-isti'nāf to translating mubtada'. This transition is marked by several observable symptoms, two of the most notable being the increasing frequency with which utawi is used to translate mubtada' without a preceding wāw al-isti'nāf and the absence of utawi in rendering wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a fi'l or ḥarf. This shift is clearly evident in manuscript PNRI A 97, dating from the last quarter of the 17th century, and becomes more pronounced in Leiden Or. 5675 from the first quarter of the 18th century.

The increasing dominance is further observed in Leiden Or. 1842, from the second and third quarters of the 18th century, where the dominance of utawi-for-mubtada' is firmly established. However, even within this pattern, utawi-for-isti'nāf has not been entirely supplanted. While instances of utawi-for-isti'nāf become increasingly subtle, a careful reader can still discern their presence. The dominance of utawi-for-mubtada' and the subtle appearance of utawi-for-isti'nāf continued well into the 19th century (Fig. 8a and 8b). The older form *utawi anapun* for *wa-ammā* appears to have persisted, likely because it did not entirely conflict with the utawi-for-mubtada' structure, given that the word following *wa-ammā* in many instances is a noun functioning as a muhtada'.

Fig. 8a An untitled work on Islamic theology, Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, fol. 75v. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf plus ḥarf in a 19th-century manuscript.

Fig. 8b An untitled work on Islamic theology, Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, fol. 75v. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf plus fi'l in a 19th-century manuscript.

These compelling findings lead to several critical questions that require extensive evidence and further contextual understanding to be addressed thoroughly. How should we interpret this shift in usage? Does it represent a change in emphasis, and if so, what were the underlying reasons? What specific factors in the 18th century contributed to this transition? Is this shift the only significant one within this period, or are there other notable transitions to be considered? If other shifts did occur in subsequent periods, what factors might have driven them? Are the factors influencing the shift in utawi usage the same as those influencing other changes? Do these transitions provide insights into a broader historical, intellectual, or cultural transformation, such as the evolving orientation of Javanese Islamic identity?

Utawi as a Dating Device?

Although these questions remain a mystery and will likely require considerable time before we can provide solid answers, the shift in the use of utawi offers valuable insights for philologists and historians in various ways, one among them being the consideration of manuscripts' dating. Insights emerging from scholarly exchanges I have had with experts in Islamic manuscript traditions in Java suggest that the better we understand the nature and system of Javanese interlinear translation, the more we are able to approximate the regional provenance and dating of an anonymous and undated manuscript. The evidence presented above suggests a clearer understanding of the function of utawi and in this section, I offer several case studies that demonstrate how utawi can be used as a tool for dating interlinear manuscripts.

The manuscript in the Leiden collection, coded Or. 7165, presents an intriguing case given the rarity of its interlinear translation. It is a composite manuscript, believed by Voorhoeve to have been written in the 17th century. Characterized by relatively wide spacing and only rare occasional, sporadic interlinear translation, this manuscript poses particular challenges for dating attempts that rely on utawi as an analytical device. Can we hope to date a manuscript that features so few interlinear translations? Let us give it a try. In the instances where interlinear translations do appear, utawi is used multiple times, and interestingly, quite a few instances of utawi translate a wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a verb or particle. The manuscript never uses utawi to indicate the position of the mubtada', which serves as an important clue. When placed within the pattern observed in the previous sections, this provides further support for the hypothesis that this manuscript was written in the 17th century. Furthermore, the word translated as utawi is the famous phrase *wa-'lam* (know!), which, in 17th-century manuscripts like PNRI A 45, receives utawi without the need for the wāw al-isti'nāf.

Fig. 9 *Al-Miṣbāḥ fī al-Naḥw*, Leiden University Library, Or. 7165, a composite text, fol. 11r. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by the verb *i'lam*.

In the previous section, I discussed the dating issue of PNRI A 45. The year 1087 AH (1676 AD), mentioned in the manuscript's colophon, is part of the source text and, therefore, cannot be directly used to establish the date of the interlinear translation. This date should be regarded only as a *terminus post quem* for the translation's composition. Nevertheless, within this manuscript, utawi remains predominantly employed to translate wāw al-isti'nāf. Words functioning as mubtada' that are not preceded by wāw al-isti'nāf are frequently translated without utawi. Furthermore, the manuscript presents a notable instance where the verb *i'lam* is translated with utawi, despite the absence of wāw al-isti'nāf preceding it. In essence, the use of utawi for wāw al-isti'nāf holds a dominant position in this text. All of this indicates the characteristic usage of utawi in the 17th century and earlier. Had this manuscript been written in the 18th century or later, one would anticipate a greater prevalence of utawi used to translate the mubtada'. Thus, while the date 1087/1676 cannot serve as the definitive year for the interlinear translation's composition, the usage of utawi helps to narrow the translation's period of creation to a window spanning from 1087/1676 to the early 18th century.

Another example is PNRI A 54 and the manuscript from the Great Banten Mosque (Masjid Agung Banten, henceforth MAB 1). Both are Javanese Quran translations from Banten—A 54 was originally housed in the royal palace before being transferred to the Bataviaasch Genootschap (the precursor to the PNRI), while MAB 1, as the name suggests, belongs to the collection of Masjid Agung Banten. They are believed to be complete translations of the Quran, although today we no longer have access to the entire translated text. PNRI A 54 is missing the 15th and 16th *juz*'s (parts), while MAB 1 retains only the translation of the last 10 *juz*' (21-30). Both are undated; however, scholars speculate that PNRI A 54 dates from the 18th century, while local oral tradition holds that MAB 1 was written a century earlier. Does the use of utawi support or challenge these chronological assumptions?

Fig. 10 Quran with Javanese interlinear translation, The National Library of Indonesia, A 54 a, fol. 5. The use of utawi to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by the ḥarf *min*.

In PNRI A 54, utawi is used to translate words in the position of the *mubtada'*. However, when this *mubtada'* is preceded by *fa*, utawi is replaced by *maka* or is omitted altogether.³⁰ The same applies to *fa-ammā*, whereas *wa-ammā* is always translated as *lan anapun* instead of *utawi anapun*. The pronouns *huwa* (he) and *hiya* (she) are translated as *iya iku* and take the addition of *lan* (and) when preceded by wāw al-isti'nāf. However, most notably, utawi is still used to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a ḥarf (Fig. 11).³¹ This pattern is also found in MAB 1, with the exception of the latter. In MAB 1, I did not find utawi used to translate wāw al-isti'nāf followed by either ḥarf or *fi'l*. In other words, the use of utawi in both manuscripts strengthens the assumption that PNRI A 54 dates from the 18th century, but does not support (and may even weaken) the assumption that MAB 1 originates from the 17th century. The latter may be an exception to the rule or rather date from the late 18th century or later.

Certainly, looking at the usage of utawi alone cannot serve as a decisive method for dating a manuscript. However, the key point I wish to make is that a deeper understanding of the

30 For example, the translation of *fa-Allāhu khayrun ḥifẓan* in Q. 12:64 as *maka Allah iku lewih becik pangreksane* (then Allah is the one whose surveillance is better) (PNRI A 54c, fol. 5).

31 In the course of my investigation, I have not encountered any instance in this manuscript where utawi is used to translate a wāw al-isti'nāf followed by a *fi'l*.

characteristics of interlinear translation can offer valuable clues or reinforce hypotheses regarding the dating of a manuscript. If one delves deeper into the various code words used in Javanese interlinear translations, beyond just *utawi*, much more can be uncovered, far beyond dating. *Utawi* is a gateway to a rich and beautiful tropical rainforest of knowledge.

Conclusion

Throughout this article, I have explored the use of the word *utawi* in early Islamic literature in Java, mostly within interlinear translation texts. In modern usage, *utawi* is primarily employed to denote a word in the position of the nominal sentence's subject, the *mubtada'*. However, when examined diachronically, starting from the earliest available manuscripts—dating back to the 16th century—it becomes apparent that *utawi*'s role underwent notable change. In the 16th and 17th centuries, *utawi* primarily served as a translation for the *isti'nāf* function of the Arabic particle *wāw*. Only in a limited number of cases did it signify the *mubtada'* of a translated phrase. This usage pattern does, however, include exceptions for certain words, such as the pronouns *huwa–hiya* (he–she) and ordinal numbers like *awwal–thānī–thālith* (first–second–third). Moreover, the translation of *utawi* was subject to variation when faced with *fa* (then). Nonetheless, in this early period, *utawi* was predominantly employed to translate the *isti'nāf* function, rather than serving to indicate the *mubtada'*.

As time went on, the use of *utawi* to mark the *mubtada'* became increasingly prominent, while its earlier function as a rendering of *wāw al-isti'nāf* gradually receded. This shift is clearly observable in 18th-century manuscripts, where *utawi-for-mubtada'* gains stability toward century's end, and instances of *utawi-for-isti'nāf* become markedly infrequent. Exceptions to this pattern—such as its use with certain pronouns or after specific particles—also show signs of consolidation, further reinforcing *utawi-for-mubtada'* as the prevailing norm. Yet, traces of its former function as a marker of *isti'nāf* persisted well into the 19th century, and as of writing this study, I have yet to identify the precise point at which that function disappeared altogether. Although much remains to be explored about the historical trajectory of *utawi*, the patterns that have emerged thus far offer a useful framework for various lines of inquiry, chief among them the dating of manuscripts. As demonstrated in the final section, patterns in *utawi* usage often align with other manuscript features that can help suggest a likely date of origin.

By outlining these findings, I hope to invite readers to reassess and deepen their understanding of the Javanese interlinear translation system, particularly as it appears in manuscripts from the formative period of Javanese Islam (the 16th-18th centuries). Just as *utawi*—whose partial “life history” I have attempted to trace here—underwent a historical evolution, other elements of the *utawi-iku* translation system must have followed their own developmental paths. Some may have assumed stable functions from the outset, while others likely experienced gradual yet meaningful transitions, as *utawi* did.

References

Manuscripts

Interlinear manuscripts

1. Library of the University of Amsterdam, I F 1, *al-Ghāya wa-l-Taqrīb*, regional provenance unknown, *terminus ante quem* 1610.
2. Library of the University of Amsterdam, I H 1, *al-Īdāh*, regional provenance unknown, *terminus ante quem* 1610.
3. The British Museum Library, Sloane 2645, *al-Muqaddima al-Ḥadrāmiyya*, regional provenance unknown, colophon bringing the year 1545 AJ (Anno Javanese) = 1623 AD.
4. Leiden University Library, Or. 7165, *al-Miṣbāh fī al-Nahw*, regional provenance unknown, supposedly from the 17th century.
5. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 45, *Tuḥfat al-Ṭālib al-Mubtadī*, copied in Banten 1087/1676.
6. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 97, *al-Mawāhib al-Mursala*, copied in Banten in 1116/1705.
7. Leiden University Library, Or. 2016, composite manuscript on theology and sufism, copied in 18th-century Banten.
8. Leiden University Library, Or. 5675, *Mashra‘ al-Khuṣūṣ ilā Ma‘ānī al-Nuṣūṣ*, copied in Banten in 1142/1729-30.
9. Perpustakaan Nasional Republik Indonesia, A 34, *al-Fayḍ al-‘Ahd fī al-‘Ilm bi-‘Uluww al-Sanad*, copied in Banten in 1174/1760-1.
10. Leiden University Library, Or. 1842, composite manuscript containing varying works on sufism, supposedly copied in Banten in the second half of the 18th century.
11. Endangered Archives Programme British Library, EAP061/2/34, untitled work on Islamic theology, copied in Lamongan, East Java, supposedly in the 19th century.

Non-interlinear manuscripts in *Pegon*

1. Leiden University Library, Or. 5716, *al-Muntaḥī*, probably from 17th-century Banten.
2. Leiden University Library, Or. 3050, untitled work on Islamic theology and sufism, regional provenance unknown, hypothetically Kudus, Central Java, 17th century.

Non-interlinear manuscripts in Javanese script

1. Leiden University Library, Or. 1928, *The Admonitions of Seh Bari*, 16th century, probably from Tuban, East Java.
2. Cambridge University Library, Erpenius Collection, Gg.5.22, untitled work on Islamic law, regional provenance unknown, 16th century.

Studies

- AZRA, Azyumardi. Jaringan Ulama: Timur Tengah dan Kepulauan Nusantara Abad XVII Dan XVIII: Melacak Akar-Akar Pembaruan Pemikiran Islam Di Indonesia. Mizan, 1994.
- BASALAMAH, Aly Abubakar. “Memahami Kitab Kuning Melalui Terjemahan Tradisional: Suatu Pendekatan Tradisional Terjemahan Pondok Pesantren.” *Al-Jami’ah*, no. 55 (1994): 61–69.
- DANESHGAR, Majid. *Reconstructing Erpenius’ Library: The First Collection of Oriental Manuscripts at Cambridge University Library*. Brill, 2025.
- DREWES, G.W.J. *Een Javaanse Primbon: Uit De Zestiende Eeuw Opnieuw Uitgegeven En Vertaald*. Brill, 1954.

- . *The Admonitions of Seh Bari: A 16th Century Javanese Muslim Text Attributed to the Saint of Bonan Re-Edited and Translated with an Introduction*. Springer Netherlands, 1969.
- , and L.F. Brakel. *The Poems of Hamzah Fansuri*. Foris Publication, 1986.
- DROR, Yehudit. “Is Each Particle in the Qur’ān Translatable? The Case of Wāw al-Isti’nāf Preceding the Fawāsil.” *Babel* 61, no. 1 (2015): 22–42.
- FLORIDA, Nancy K. *Writing the Past, Inscribing the Future*. Duke University Press, 1995.
- GALLOP, Annabel Teh. “Southeast Asian Manuscripts from the Collection of Sir Hans Sloane in the British Library.” *Wacana* 20, no. 1 (2019): 15–31.
- GERICKE, Johann F.C., and Taco Roorda. *Javaansch-Nederduitsch Woordenboek*. Johannes Müller, 1847.
- , and Taco Roorda. *Javaansch-Nederlandsch Handwoordenboek*. Vol. 1. Brill, 1901.
- JAENI, Muhammad. “Pola-Pola Pengapsahan Kitab Pesantren Kiai Pesisir Utara Jawa Tengah Abad XIX-XX: Kajian Histori-Sosiolinguistik.” Ph.D Dissertation, UIN Walisongo, 2019.
- JONES, Sidney. “Arabic Instruction and Literacy in Javanese Muslim Schools.” *International Journal of Society and Language* 42 (1983): 83–94.
- MAHFUDH, Sahal. “Al-Kitāba al-‘Arabiyya Li-Lughat al-Jāwiyyah (Pegon): Dirāsa Lughawiyya Ijtimā’iyya ‘alā -Stibqā’ihā Fī Mujtama‘ al-Besantren al-Taqlīdī Bi-Jāwā.” Ph.D Dissertation, UIN Sunan Kalijaga, 2023.
- PIGEAUD, Theodore G. Th. *Literature of Java*. Vol. 2. Martinus Nijhoff, 1968.
- PROUDFOOT, Ian. *Old Muslim Calendars of Southeast Asia*. Brill, 2006.
- RICCI, Ronit. *Islam Translated: Literature, Conversion, and the Arabic Cosmopolis of South and Southeast Asia*. University of Chicago Press, 2011.
- RICKLEFS, Merle C. *Mystic Synthesis in Java: A History of Islamization from the Fourteenth to the Early Nineteenth Centuries*. East Bridge, 2006.
- . *The Seen and Unseen Worlds in Java, 1726-1749: History, Literature and Islam in the Court of Pakubuwana II*. University of Hawai’i Press, 1998.
- SADAN, Arik. *The Subjunctive Mood in Arabic Grammatical Thought*. Brill, 2012.
- SIBAWAYH. *Al-Kitāb*. Vol. 1. Maktaba al-Khānjī, 1988.
- SUGAHARA, Yumi. “Sunan Bonang’s Teaching: Ethical Sufism in Sixteenth-Century Java.” In *Storied Island: New Explorations in Javanese Literature*, edited by Ronit Ricci. Brill, 2023.
- UMAM, Saiful. “Localizing Islamic Orthodoxy in Northern Coastal Java in the Late 19th and Early 20th Centuries; A Study of Pegon Islamic Texts.” Ph.D Dissertation, University of Hawai’i, 2011.
- VOORHOEVE, Paul. *Handlist of Arabic Manuscripts in the Library of the University of Leiden and Other Collections in the Netherlands*. Leiden University Press, 1980.
- WIJNMAN, Hendrik Frederik. “De Hebraicus Jan Theunisz Barbarossius Alias Johannes Antonides Als Lector in Het Arabisch Aan de Leidse Universiteit (1612/1613). Een Hoofdstuk Amsterdamsche Geleerdengeschiedenis.” *Studia Rosenthaliana* 2, no. 2 (1968): 1–29.
- WITKAM, Jan Just. *Inventory of the Oriental Manuscripts of the Library of the University of Leiden*. Vol. 6. Ter Lugt Press, 2007.

Interlinear Texts from Indonesia: *Preliminary Thoughts on Their Study*

RONIT RICCI (Hebrew University of Jerusalem and Australian National University)¹

Abstract

Interlinear translations have been known in Indonesia's Islamic communities since at least the late 16th century with extant evidence in the form of manuscripts pointing to their ongoing popularity in the following centuries. Such translations encompass important works composed in Arabic and rendered in the languages of the archipelago, and they touch upon key fields of knowledge, among them Islamic law, theology and grammar. But has this textual abundance been matched by the range of scholarly writings produced about this phenomenon? This paper asks if and how interlinear texts from Indonesia were studied by scholars in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. It does not attempt to offer an exhaustive survey but rather raises questions about how interlinear translations were perceived and points to possible trends that have helped shape the scholarly context for the Textual Microcosms project, currently exploring interlinear translation across the Indonesian-Malay world.

Keywords: Indonesia, Java, Interlinear translation, colonial scholarship, pesantren

Introduction

Indonesia is a vast, multilingual and multicultural archipelago and has been a crossroads of religious ideas and practices for many centuries. The history of Islam in the region goes back to at least the 13th century and likely earlier and Islam is now the religion of approximately 90% of Indonesia's citizens. Arabic texts, above all the Qur'an but also legal, ritual, historical and hagiographical texts of diverse origins in their original, adapted and translated forms played a central role in the process of Islamization which unfolded gradually across the region. In the long process of Islamization translation and education played major roles. Interlinear translation—the addition of a translation in between the lines of a text—reflected

¹ I thank the Israel Science Foundation (grant no. 2009/19) and the European Research Council Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant agreement No. CoG 101001731) for generously funding the research on which this study is based. My thanks go also to all participants in the "Interlinear Translation Across the Muslim World" workshop, to my co-editor Dr Fadhli Lukman and to Tony Day, for their insightful and constructive comments.

a linking of the two as it was used to teach both the Arabic language and the doctrines and rituals of the faith.

This article emerged from on-going research on interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world, understood as a translation method, a historical and living practice, and a site of a range of encounters. A site where two languages meet one another, where ideas, beliefs and textual histories of one culture approach another's, teacher and disciple interact, and colors, ink types, scripts and frames structure visual encounters on a page. How was this phenomenon studied by others, especially early on, and what assumptions about it might we have inherited, I wondered.

Interlinear translations have been known in Indonesia's Islamic communities for several centuries with extant evidence in the form of manuscripts pointing to their ongoing popularity from the late sixteenth century. Such translations encompass important works composed in Arabic and rendered in the languages of the archipelago, and they touch upon key fields of knowledge, among them Islamic law, theology, sufism and grammar.²

In thinking about interlinear translation from Arabic to local languages two initial questions that emerge are which languages were used to produce the translations and how significant were Islamic interlinear translations in the Indonesian archipelago.³ Within the vast, diverse and multi-lingual archipelago the two languages that stand out are Malay and Javanese, used more often than other languages to provide an interlinear translation of Arabic texts, although translations into Sundanese, Bugis, Makassarese, Madurese and additional languages were produced as well.⁴ Regarding the significance of interlinear translations from this region two types of evidence stand out in particular: chronological and quantitative. I begin with chronology.

One of the earliest known Arabic-Malay interlinear exemplars is found in a manuscript of Islamic Creed ('*Aqā'id*) by al-Nasafī dated 1590, while the Arabic to Malay *al-Burda* was inscribed in 1600 at the latest.⁵ Indonesian manuscripts from the sixteenth century are rare, making both of these manuscripts among the oldest Malay (and more generally Indonesian) manuscripts of any genre extant. Other early examples include early 17th century fragments from the Arabic poem *Bad'i al-āmāli*, a beginner's treatise on theology with interlinear Malay translation, and an early 18th century treatise on marriage, *Aḥkām al-nikāḥ*, also with

-
- 2 Azyumardi Azra, "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia." In *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, ed. Henri Chambert-Loir (Gramedia, 2009, 435–443).
 - 3 Using "Indonesia," and also "the Indonesian archipelago" are of course anachronisms as the state was founded in 1945, but I will use them here for the sake of brevity and convenience. There are additional, non-Islamic traditions of interlinear translation in the archipelago, however in this article my focus is for the most part on Islamic texts.
 - 4 Malay was the most important language to the spread of Islam in the region, a lingua franca of trade, travel, diplomacy and religious teaching. Javanese was the language of the largest ethnic group and one that possessed a literary and religious writing tradition going back to at least the 9th century.
 - 5 On the former see S. M. N. Al-Attas, *The Oldest Known Malay Manuscript: a 16th century Malay Translation of the 'Aqā'id of Al-Nasafī* (University of Malaya, 1988). On the latter see G.W. J. Drewes, *Een 16de Eeuwse Maleische Vertaling van de Burda van al-Busiri (Arabisch Lofdicht op Mohammad)* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1955).

interlinear Malay translation.⁶

In the case of Arabic to Javanese, the earliest known exemplar of interlinear translation from Arabic is said to be the *Masā'il al-ta'lim*, dated 1623 at the latest and housed at the British Library (see Fig. 1).⁷ Another, possibly even earlier example is a copy of *al-Īdāh* from the collection of Jan Theunisz (d. 1638) currently at the Library of the University of Amsterdam.⁸ Both are works on jurisprudence (*fiqh*). The fact that some of the earliest surviving manuscripts still extant from the archipelago are in the form of interlinear translations is telling and suggests this form of writing may have been among the first to circulate as Islam was taking hold in the region. At the very least these dated manuscripts

Fig. 1 *Masā'il al-ta'lim*, Arabic with Javanese translation and notes, 1623. British Library, [Sloane 2645, ff. 6v–7r](#)

- 6 Both are discussed by Ph. S. van Ronkel, on which see more below. Ph. S. van Ronkel, “Account of Six Malay Manuscripts of the Cambridge University Library,” *Bijdragen tot de taal-, land- en volkenkunde* 46, no. 1 (1896): 1–53, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90000076>. There are also examples from the archipelago of early interlinear translations from Persian into Malay, but these lie outside the purview of this article. On such examples see Majid Daneshgar, “Persianate Aspects of the Indonesian-Malay World: Some Rare Manuscripts in the Leiden University Library,” *Dabir*, no. 8 (2021): 51–78.
- 7 Bernard Arps and Annabel Teh Gallop, *Golden Letters: Writing Traditions of Indonesia/Surat Emas: Budaya Tulis di Indonesia* (The British Library; Yayasan Lontar, 1991), 100; I. Yahya, M.A.K. Hassan, dan Farkhan, *Penerjemahan Manuskrip Masā'il al-ta'lim ke dalam Aksara Pegon pada Abad ke-17 M* (IAIN Surakarta Press, 2018).
- 8 This is manuscript I H 1. Muhammad Dluha Lutfillah, Personal communication, January 2025.

offer concrete evidence for interlinear translations having been created and read during this early period.

In addition to the chronologically important evidence of very early surviving manuscripts there is quantitative evidence of the prevalence of interlinear translation from libraries at Islamic boarding schools (*pesantren* in Java, *surau* in Sumatra) whose collections have been digitized by the Endangered Archives Programme and DREAMSEA initiatives, as well as from an in-progress database that draws on Indonesian manuscript collections in the British Library, Leiden University, the National Library of Indonesia, and more (for an example see Fig. 2).⁹

Fig. 2 Nazm poem. Arabic with Malay translation, 1870s, Palembang, Sumatra. [DS 0005 0002](#)

9 For the Endangered Archives Programme see <https://eap.bl.uk/>. For pesantren collections see, for example, <https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP061-1> (from Langitan) and <https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP061-2> (Kranji). For DREAMSEA see <https://dreamsea.co/>.

Hence we know that interlinear translations circulated early on and that, in certain educational contexts, they were numerous. We also know that most extant manuscripts in Indonesia generally (and in collections of Indonesian manuscripts outside Indonesia, e.g., in Leiden, Kuala Lumpur, London), and also specifically those from pesantren, date from the 19th century. This is important because the height of colonial scholarly production about Indonesian religions, languages and cultures was in the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth centuries, suggesting that there was no dearth of interlinear translations to be examined and studied during this period. Did this phenomenon inspire interest and curiosity among scholars? What evidence is available on inquiries into the practice and its implications?

To consider these questions this article explores how interlinear translation was addressed in scholarship on Indonesia, with a focus on the 19th and early 20th centuries: what was written about it, and by whom? How was the practice described and understood? What significance was attached to it, if any? It offers a preliminary survey and tentative thoughts about how interlinear translations were perceived during this period and points to possible trends that have helped shape the scholarly context for the Textual Microcosms project, currently exploring interlinear translation across the Indonesian-Malay world.¹⁰

Where are the Interlinear Translations?

Working within the framework of Textual Microcosms and considering various approaches to the study of interlinear translation raised the question of how earlier researchers viewed these texts. The search for interlinear texts and for their explication and analysis in scholarship turned out to be more challenging than I had expected, as outlined in the following pages.

In what may be one of the early mentions of interlinear translation in a scholarly publication the famed Dutch linguist H. N. van der Tuuk, writing in the Leiden-based journal *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde (BKI)* in 1866, mentioned an Arabic to Malay interlinear translation of al-Samarkandi's *Bayān 'aqīdah al-uṣūl* (commonly known in Indonesia by its author's name) in a brief report he published on various Malay manuscripts.¹¹ There was no detailed description or discussion, but the author was clearly familiar with this popular text and noted that interlinear translations of al-Samarkandi into Javanese in west Java were "numerous" and that there was also, in Batavia, a commentary on the text which had an interlinear translation in Javanese. Finally, he mentioned that he was in the possession of two such commentaries in Sundanese.¹² Based on this fleeting note we can conclude that

¹⁰ For more on Textual Microcosms, a European Research Council Horizon 2020 project (CoG 101001731) see <https://textualmicrocosms.huji.ac.il/>.

¹¹ H. N. van der Tuuk, "Aanteekeningen," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 13, no.1 (1866): 466–467. This was in fact a set of "Notes." Mention of the interlinear translation text occurred within a survey of various manuscripts, including a section on manuscripts from the Indian Office in London that were previously held at the East India House.

¹² Sundanese is spoken in the western part of Java. It is not clear from Van der Tuuk description whether

Van der Tuuk was familiar with the phenomenon, with interlinear translations from Arabic into two or three languages (Malay, Javanese, possibly Sundanese), and with their popularity. There is nothing in his brief paragraph that expresses any surprise or special interest or insight.

Fifteen years later, writing in the same journal, the philologist A. W. T. Juynboll discussed an Arabic to Javanese interlinear translation of the same text, which he had translated into Dutch. His article, which contained only two pages written by him and ten pages of the interlinear text, was titled “A Muslim catechism in Arabic with a Javanese interlinear translation in *Pegon* script.”¹³ All we learn about the manuscript on which his translation was based is that it was brought by one of his students from Java to Holland, and that large parts of it were eaten up by ants.¹⁴ Although Juynboll highlighted the interlinear translation in his article’s title, he seemed interested in authorship, content and textual versions but said nothing of the translation method, its uses or implications. The Dutch translation he produced referred only to the Arabic text, ignoring the potential meanings and nuances of the Javanese interlinear translation and its use as a pedagogical and cultural phenomenon. Although this remains unacknowledged, the Dutch in fact replaced the Javanese as the translation language.

In the same *BKI* volume Juynboll published three more brief articles on the *Samarkandi*, titled “The Samarkandi Catechism Reviewed” parts I, II and III.¹⁵ In the first he explained that he recently came across a manuscript with the Arabic Samarkandi text and a commentary on it that helped him better understand it and therefore he was able to improve his earlier Dutch translation and he decided to publish this Arabic text. In part II he republished his Dutch translation, and in part III are found his notes, which address several points appearing in the Arabic text and also discussed in the commentary (e.g., the angels, God’s throne, God’s oneness). No further mention is made of the interlinear translation and one can contrast the ongoing interest of Juynboll in the Arabic text and his attempts to read and re-read it, along with the helpful commentary (which could have been compared to the Javanese translation, asking, for example, if there were any echoes of the commentary within the translation) with

the Sundanese text contains an interlinear translation or just commentaries. Van der Tuuk, “Aanteekeningen,” 467.

13 A.W.T. Juynboll, “Een Moslimsche catechismus in her Arabisch met eene Javaansche interlineare vertaling in pegonschrift,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 215–227. Juynboll wrote that “Since the Arabic text is not entirely complete, and there are also gaps in the Javanese interlinear translation, I have tried to consult more manuscripts of this work, but so far without result,” a comment that shows that he likely relied at least somewhat on the translation to understand the Arabic. “Nevertheless,” he continued, “I believe that this edition should not be postponed, but on the contrary can be useful, since for many people there may be a good opportunity to compare other copies with the text given here, so that this provisional edition can soon be replaced by a better one. That is why I only give here the Arabic and Javanese text with a simple translation, without further explanation, which will certainly not be lacking in a later edition.” *Ibid.*, 215.

14 The translation into Dutch appears in the same volume: A.W.T. Juynboll, “Een Moslimsche catechismus in het Arabisch met eene Javaansche interlineare vertaling in pegonschrift uitgegeven en in het Nederlansch vertaald,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 229–231.

15 A.W.T. Juynboll, “Samarkandi’s Catechismus opnieuw besproken,” I, II, III, *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 267–274, 275–278, 279–284, respectively.

his silence on the Javanese rendering of this important work to which, at least in these writings, he did not seem to attach significance.

It is worthy of note that in both the initial article (see note 13) and in his “Review part I” Juynboll expressed some hesitation about publishing on *al-Samarkandi* without reviewing and comparing additional exemplars for detail and depth but decided nonetheless to go forward with the rationale that even partial scholarship on these texts is important and would assist others with access to similar sources, yet none of his considerations touch on the existence of the interlinear translation.

During approximately the same period the work of Ph. S. van Ronkel stands out for his interest in the practice and his attentiveness to the detail that is among the hallmarks of interlinear translation. In an 1896 article describing six manuscripts housed at the Cambridge University library he discussed two that included interlinear texts and commented in detail on several of their dimensions.¹⁶ Possibly following that work, as well as an examination of additional manuscripts he encountered, Van Ronkel several years later (1899) published what constituted a pioneering attempt to survey the interlinear practice and map its far-reaching effects.¹⁷

Van Ronkel’s main claim, based on a range of interlinear translation examples, was that there was a striking uniformity in the way Malay scholars and scribes translated Arabic words, idioms, and grammatical particles, such as prepositions, into Malay. He showed how they also tended to standardize the way in which markers of gender, number, and tense—omnipresent in Arabic but not in Malay—were rendered in a manner that could be understood and internalized by the texts’ audiences. Further, he claimed that interlinear translation not only impacted content and the way vocabulary was appropriated or adapted in a new language and culture, but also that such translations were a powerful influence on recasting the more subtle realm of Malay syntax. For example, he found that the Arabic preposition *bi* was consistently translated as *dengan*, and so the phrase *bismillāh* (in the name of God) was translated into Malay as *dengan nama Allah*, rather than the conventional *atas nama Allah*. Moreover, Van Ronkel showed also how various irregular constructions in Malay can be understood if retranslated (i.e., “translated backwards”) into Arabic. Such patterns were then gradually assimilated into texts that were not interlinear translations, generalized and incorporated into the Malay language, and gaining a life of their own that was no longer dependent on a detailed translation strategy. Using Arabic syntax to write Malay thus gradually became more habitual, so much so that it is clearly visible in examples taken from the Malay *hikayat* genre, often recounting tales of love, adventure, and travel that have little to do explicitly with religion.¹⁸

16 Van Ronkel, “Account of Six Malay Manuscripts,” 1–53.

17 Ph. S. van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat Arab Terhadap Tatakalimat Melayu*, trans. A. Ikram, Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as “Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41 (1899): 498–528.

18 A similar process was most likely taking shape in Javanese, through interlinear translations from Arabic. For a discussion of an example that points to how “interlinear translation Javanese” was employed in Javanese-only literature, see Ronit Ricci, “Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* Across the Indonesian-Malay World,” *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no.150 (2023):

Van Ronkel was very much aware that by considering interlinear translation from Arabic into Malay in a systematic way—unlike earlier studies of specific texts—he was entering uncharted waters, delving into a topic that had not yet been articulated, much less so explored.¹⁹ He understood interlinear translation as a profoundly important practice that shaped the Malay language anew. In his view it reshaped the language as it appeared in the interlinear translations but, beyond this prevalent but specific usage, it also transformed Malay much more broadly, in the writing of other texts and eventually, in all likelihood, in speech. His remains a seminal study, with its importance lying both in the many details and examples provided and in the kinds of questions raised, the phenomena noticed and the depth of engagement.²⁰

Snouck Hurgronje, a key scholar-administrator of the late 19th century Dutch East Indies,²¹ also addressed the practice and pedagogy of interlinear translation. During his stay in Mecca (1884–1885) he spent much of his time with the Jawah community, documenting their lives there. He distinguished between two pedagogical methods for teaching pilgrims from the archipelago Arabic and Islamic texts: in Java, he wrote, people studied from books written in Javanese or Malay or they began without any preparation to read small introductory works in Arabic to which they added a translation between the lines based on their teacher’s words. In Mecca, on the other hand, Javanese and Malay were used consistently as a means to introduce students to Arabic, particularly to its grammar, so that gradually they gained enough knowledge, through constant translation and interpretation into their own language, to be able to read books of law and doctrine in Arabic. Snouck very clearly prioritized the Meccan method based on the study of Arabic grammar and syntax via interlinear translation as opposed to learning bits of Arabic by rote. He called the Javanese method “pitiful” and stated that in some areas, notably west Java, Arabia-trained teachers were gaining the upper hand for the Arab method which “should gradually drive out the older systems of teaching.”²² His depiction offers important insights on the use of interlinear translation and raises questions about it, perhaps above all about whether it could be a practice that developed in Arabia—in Mecca—and not in Indonesia.

His writing also touched upon a suggested hierarchy of Indonesian languages vis-a-vis Arabic, claiming that only Malay and Javanese fully attained the status of a “speech of Moslim civilization,” while Madurese, Buginese and Makassarese attained it to some degree

143–164. DOI: 10.1080/13639811.2023.2221927

19 Van Ronkel, *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalimat*, 12.

20 Although Van Ronkel passed away many years later, in 1954, I was unable to find evidence of another major work of his on this topic. For a list of his publications see P. Voorhoeve, “Bibliografie der Geschriften van Prof. Dr. Ph. S. van Ronkel,” in *Bingkisan Budi, een bundel opstellen aan Dr. Philippus Samuel Van Ronkel door vrienden en leerlingen aangeboden op zijn tachtigste verjaardag* (A. W. Sijthoff’s Uitgeversmaatschappij N.V., 1950), 346–354.

21 On Snouck Hurgronje see, for example, Léon Buskens, Jan Just Witkam and Annemarie van Sandwijk, eds., *Scholarship in Action: Essays on the Life and Work of Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje (1857–1936)* (Brill, 2022). <https://library.open.org/handle/20.500.12657/87102>

22 Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje, *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslims of the East-Indian-Archipelago. 1888–1889* (E. J. Brill, 1931), 283–286.

and Sundanese, Acehnese and others not at all. This claim he based on his observation that there was a large number of translations of Arabic works into Malay and Javanese as well as a variety of compilations, commentaries and a rich popular literature in these languages which was independent of the Arabic, while the other languages “have shown themselves as suitable garb for Islam in much less degree.” Those speaking Madurese, Buginese or Makassarese had to learn Javanese or Malay in order to enter the fields of Islamic knowledge, if Arabic proved too difficult. Most coming from Lampung, Aceh, Sumbawa and elsewhere studied via Malay while the Sundanese of west Java typically did so through Javanese, even while still in Indonesia, and in Mecca had a choice between the two languages and “at most the beginners gain help in understanding only from a few short notes or fragmentary interlinear translations in their mother-tongue, dictated by some teacher from their own district.”²³ It is important to consider possible implications of Snouck Hurgronje’s comments on the link between the level of Arabic and Islamic piety among different linguistic groups (whether real or perceived) on the history of scholarship. His observations about Javanese and Malay are relevant to any discussion of the volume and range of interlinear translations into these languages as compared with others, at least within the extant archive.

Snouck Hurgronje’s two-volume *The Acehnese*, was written after his book on Mecca and with the perspective he had gained there, observing and interpreting what he saw in Aceh, at least in part, through that earlier lens.²⁴ In *The Acehnese* volume 2 he offered a comparison between the method practiced “since ancient times” by Javanese and Sundanese Muslim wishing to study the Arabic books of law and doctrine and the method practiced in Aceh by those who wished to be considered as *ulama*. He began by describing how the Javanese pupil read a sentence which was then translated literally into Javanese (and the translation language differed greatly from that of daily life), with Arabic technical terms left untranslated. The word-for-word translation (*ma’na* or *logat*) was followed by an explanatory paraphrase (*murad*). He concluded that the Javanese remained patient with this method because they took pleasure in reading the authoritative Arabic text in the original, with the subsequent word-for-word literal translation removing all doubt—so he believed—regarding the meaning of the Arabic words. The Sundanese, he added, followed the same method but in their case only the *murad* was given in their language.²⁵

Snouck Hurgronje then moved on to the other method, the one he had also seen in Mecca, which over the previous thirty to forty years “gained supremacy in Java under Mekkan and Hadramite influence” which is “more logical but requires much greater patience and perseverance.” This involved studying Arabic grammar for several years and only then beginning to read simple works. This method “which in Java can still be called new-fashioned, appears to have been in vogue in Aceh for a long time past... The student in Aceh begins by struggling through a mountain of grammatical matter.”²⁶ He mentioned that the grammar books were translated from Arabic to Malay (likely employing the interlinear

23 Hurgronje, *Mekka*, 283–284.

24 Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, vol. 2, trans. A.W.S. O’Sullivan (E.J. Brill, 1906), 5–7.

25 Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, 6–7.

26 Hurgronje, *The Acehnese*, 7.

method but this is not stated) and he noted the difficulty for local Muslims for whom Acehese, not Malay, was the mother tongue, and that most therefore did not complete their elementary studies. As in his earlier scholarship Snouck here prioritized the value of the Meccan method of studying Arabic but he did not provide historical evidence for the claim that it “appears to have been” practiced in Aceh “for a long time,” just as he neglected to prove that the other method was used “since ancient times” by Javanese and Sundanese Muslims. The former claim may have been true, in which case the method may have indeed been brought to Aceh earlier than to Java, and Aceh’s ties with the Middle East, due to its location and particular history may have proved stronger that the influence of traditions practiced on neighboring islands, however no details are offered on how and when the method arrived or developed in Aceh.

Also towards the end of the 19th century, in 1886, Van den Berg published his by now famous study of Islamic education on the islands of Java and Madura in which he listed many of the religious books studied at the time in the pesantren.²⁷ He only mentioned interlinear translation once, when discussing how certain sections of Islamic jurisprudence texts were typically not taught (for example the sections on criminal law and slavery), and therefore the interlinear translations for these sections were often lacking.²⁸ From this extremely brief mention one has the impression that Van den Berg was aware of the translation practice (and he must have seen many such translations while touring the pesantren) as the implication was that other sections of such texts, which were taught, did have interlinear translations and notes, but he treated them matter-of-factly, so much so that they were not worthy of mention. Van den Berg also described lessons he witnessed as consisting of the reading of an Arabic book, sentence by sentence, with an explanation in the vernacular offered by the teacher. The explanation usually took the form of translation but at times additional clarification was given based on other works.²⁹ This may have been a depiction of the use of interlinear translation but it is not discussed.

Another example that gives insight on interlinear translation as a pedagogical method, but was written from a different perspective (yet in Dutch), is Achmad Djajadiningrat’s early 20th century account of life in a pesantren.³⁰ It depicted an episode in the life of Wardi, the young son of the district chief (*wedana*) of Banten in west Java who was sent to live as a student in a pesantren (*santri*) away from home.³¹ The *kyai*—the religious scholar heading the pesantren—asked what Wardi knew and when he replied that he could only recite the Qur’an the *kyai* said he will need to start with *Sittien*, referring to the popular Shāfi’ī jurisprudence

27 L. W. C. van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs op Java en Madoera en de daarbij Gebruikte Arabische Boeken,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 31 (1886): 518–555.

28 Van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs,” 533.

29 Van den Berg, “Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs,” 524.

30 Achmad Djajadiningrat, “Het Leven in een Pasantren,” *Tijdschrift voor het Binnenlandsch Betuur*, no. 34 (1908): 1–22.

31 Djajadiningrat, who was the the regent (*bupati*) of Serang from 1901–1917, was apparently writing his own memories of his brief childhood stay at a pesantren, see Zamakhsyari Dhofier, *Tradisi Pesantren. Studi Pandangan Hidup Kyai dan Visinya Mengenai Masa Depan Indonesia* (LP3ES, 2011), 39.

work *al-Sittin Mas'ala*. The kyai then summoned his advanced student to meet Wardi and asked the student to “write a *Sittien* for him, but without *logat*; he needs to get used to difficulties at once.” Djajadiningrat added a footnote for *logat*: *interlineaire vertaling* (interlinear translation).³²

This seems to imply that Wardi would need to fill in the translation as he made progress. In the classes, that took place in the mosque, beginners sat in front and moved gradually to the back as they progressed. The santris repeated the Javanese translation of the Arabic one by one, in a Javanese that was described as a very different and difficult form of the language than what was habitually used (a point also made by Snouck Hurgronje, see above). The kyai translated the Arabic into Javanese, explained and gave examples, yet the author noted that many students were forced to quit after studying *Sittien* as diligence was insufficient for success and very few reached the level of studying Arabic texts on doctrine and law. It is a brief description, in which studying interlinear translations of Islamic texts was portrayed as a completely routine part of everyday pesantren life and the practice of translation was not addressed in any specific way. Perhaps it can be understood implicitly that this pedagogical system did not suffice for most beyond a very basic level, as Snouck Hurgronje too suggested in his writings. It is also possible that, constituting such a routine pedagogy, no need was felt to describe it, and it was thus transparent also for a Javanese author who wrote about Islamic education, similar to the European scholars' approach.

In addition to Dutch and Indonesian writings on the topic French scholarship about it was also produced. In a 1904 article titled “A Malay interlinear translation of al-Sanūsī's *‘Aqīda*” Antoine Cabaton discussed a 1893 Arabic to Malay interlinear translation of al-Sanūsī's *al-‘Aqīda* belonging to al-Hajj Ismā‘īl, a Malay imam of Cochinchina, and produced a French translation of this work.³³ As background Cabaton mentioned that the Malays in Cham, as opposed to local Muslims, were more orthodox in their practice and possessed manuscripts of the Qur'an, hadith, tafsir and various works on Islam's precepts. Of the manuscript he wrote that it contained the Arabic text, quite correct at the beginning but full of spelling mistakes towards the end, and an interlinear Malay version of the *‘Aqīda*, a work on scholastic theology that, he noted, was held in very high esteem by Muslims.³⁴

Cabaton went on to explain that he found it unnecessary to reproduce the Arabic text, although it differed in several ways from the one published by Wolff in 1848, because it was identical to that which was printed in Cairo in 1901. Additionally, he noted, there were also copies of the work in France's national library.³⁵ This section, in which he laid out his reasons for not reproducing the Arabic source, is the only one in the article referring to it. So, although “interlinear translation” appears in the article's title it is quite marginal to this study. Cabaton did mention that “Our manuscript... which slavishly reproduces the Arabic original, is a curious specimen of the numerous interlinear translations of Arabic works made by the

32 Djajadiningrat, “Het Leven in een Pasantren,” 5.

33 Antoine Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise de La ‘Aqīda d’Al-Senūsī,” *Journal Asiatique* (1904): 115–145.

34 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 116.

35 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 117.

Malays,” but did not elaborate on why he made this claim. He also commented on how literal the translation method was in its attempt to replicate the Arabic, so that “if the syntax is therefore a little tormented, it does not result in any obscurity.” Finally, he noticed that Arabic technical terms were conserved, but care was almost always taken to render them by Malay equivalents preceded by the word *artinya* (“the meaning is”, “this means”).³⁶

In a further, very brief article, Cabaton again discussed the Muslims of CochinChina and the importance of the *Aqīda* amongst them, and mentioned the interlinear translation of the text he had encountered. This article examined a “table” that Cabaton believed was a summary of a “more developed dogmatic work” and formed part of Islamic education for the Chams.³⁷ He suspected it was based on al-Samarqandi, and very much abbreviated because its audience required the most basic doctrine. The text was copied by the same Malay of CochinChina mentioned above, the imam al-Hajj Ismā‘īl. Here too there was no engagement with interlinear translation, which is not mentioned, even though in the article’s last two pages there are several examples of the genre.³⁸ Cabaton seemed more interested in the content and in a discrepancy he perceived between the teachings and the actions of local Muslims.

In a third instance of work on an interlinear translation Cabaton published an article on a Malay telling of the story of Raden Paku, otherwise known as Sunan Giri, one of the nine *walis* said to have converted Java to Islam.³⁹ That telling was in fact the Malay translation which had appeared in between the lines of a Javanese text but Cabaton was studying and translating (into French) the Malay only. He argued that from the point of view of language and style the legend of Sunan Giri “has the defects of all interlinear translations of its kind: obscurity and inclusion of Javanese words.” He was also critical of the Malay version for containing “numerous lacunae” and he viewed it as a clumsy adaptation of a more developed narrative.⁴⁰ More generally, Cabaton here was not interested in the interlinear aspect of the text but only in the biography of Sunan Giri, one viewed as central to the historiography of Java’s Islamization. The three articles by Cabaton, taken together, point to his awareness of the interlinear translation practice in both CochinChina and Java and to his acquaintance with at least several such manuscripts, but not to an interest in the practice per se. Rather, his focus lay in the history and content of the texts.

Returning to Dutch scholarship, Pigeaud, in his book on Javanese folk performance mentioned a compilation of *mauluds*, printed in Bombay, in Arabic with Javanese interlinear glosses.⁴¹ The language, he wrote, was “the peculiar Javanese written in unvocalized Arabic

36 Cabaton, “Traduction interlinéaire malaise,” 120.

37 Antoine Cabaton, “Un abrégé malais du Catéchisme musulman,” *T’oung Pao* 5, no. 2 (1904): 157–164.

38 Antoine Cabaton, “Un abrégé malais,” 163–164.

39 Antoine Cabaton, “Raden Paku, Sunan de Giri (légende musulmane javanaise): Texte malais, traduction française et notes,” *Revue de l’histoire des religions*, no. 54 (1906): 374–400.

40 Cabaton, “Raden Paku,” 377.

41 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen. Bijdrage tot de Beschrijving van Land en Volk* (Batavia: Volkslectuur, 1938). *Mauluds* are panegyrics on the Prophet Muhammad, recited on the anniversary of his birth and other occasions. On the issue of terminology (i.e., “translation” vs. “gloss”), see below.

script from the old-fashioned religious schools (pesantrens).⁴² Pigeaud went on to explain that for those unfamiliar with it, this Javanese was almost impossible to understand, especially because “it wishes to represent all Arabic phrases, including plurals and articles,” referring to the literalness of this translation method and to its striving to replicate the Arabic as closely as possible. When, however, one has become somewhat accustomed to this form of Javanese, he believed it was a fairly easy and reliable means of acquainting oneself with the contents of the Arabic texts and their highly elaborate vocabulary. Pigeaud noted that there were additional Arabic textbooks printed with Javanese interlinear glosses and that such works exercised an influence on the development of the Javanese language and the definition of commonly-used words. He offered an example from the *Sarpoel Anam (Maulud Sharaf al-Anām)* noting not only the word-for-word Javanese translation but also the use of certain inserted Javanese “code words” that indicated the grammatical position of a word within the sentence or a function like number (e.g., an indication of the plural form).⁴³

Pigeaud touched in this brief passage upon several key issues related to interlinear translation including its emerging availability in print, its literalness and detail, its effectiveness in conveying the Arabic source text, the existence of an internal system of “code words” that assisted in understanding Arabic syntax, and the translations’ impact on Javanese. Although he did not delve on these matters in this instance it is clear that he was deeply familiar with the interlinear translation paradigm and, indeed, in his later work and especially in his catalogue of Javanese literature published thirty years later, he would discuss many such texts in relative detail.

I have offered several examples of writings on interlinear translation from the second half of the 19th century and the first decades of the 20th. Among writings from this period there are also “non-examples” to note, by which I refer to scholars who wrote surveys or studies of particular regions in the archipelago with descriptions of everything from geography to cooking to religion, or more specifically studies about Islam, but did not mention interlinear translation as a pedagogical, cultural or religious practice.⁴⁴

An important example of scholarship that may be positioned in between studies that discussed interlinear translation and those that did not is Brumund’s 1857 book on public education among the Javanese.⁴⁵ It was the earliest study of Islamic education (and other educational systems) in colonial Indonesia, written with the stated goal of better understanding ideas and practices of education in Java.⁴⁶ The book purported to offer a

42 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen*, 290. The unvocalized Arabic script used to write Javanese is known as *gundhul* (bald, hairless).

43 Th. Pigeaud, *Javaanse Volksvertoningen*, 290–292.

44 Antoine Cabaton, *Java, Sumatra and the Other Islands of the Dutch East Indies*, trans. Bernard Miall (T.F. Unwin, 1911); William Marsden, *The History of Sumatra, Containing an Account of the Government, Laws, Customs, and Manners of the Native Inhabitants, with A Description of the Natural Productions, and A Relation of the Ancient Political State* (London: Printed for the Author, 1783); Guillaume F. Pijper, *Fragmenta Islamica. Studiën over her Islamisme in Nederlandsch Indië* (E.J. Brill, 1934); Thomas Stamford Raffles, *The History of Java in Two Volumes* (London: Black, Farbury and Allen, 1817).

45 J.F.G. Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen* (Batavia: Van Haren Noman & Kolff, 1857).

46 There were earlier reports and studies on a smaller scale, e.g., the 1831 government report on native

detailed overview of pesantren education yet it did not engage with the widespread practice of interlinear translation and, more generally, the author was unable to learn much of substance of the Javano-Islamic pedagogical system. For example, in a section describing the *langgars* (small houses of worship and study where youngsters often begun their educational journey), Brumund wrote that “it is said that there are thirteen Korans, at least parts of the Koran translated into Javanese and written with Arabic characters. I have never come across them. In Samarang, I am told that someone saw an Arabic Koran with an interlinear partial Javanese translation. Another was recently discovered elsewhere.”⁴⁷ Discussing the students at a pesantren in Langkong he claimed that they were taught to read and write Arabic “more or less mechanically” and that they “usually do not understand anything of what they read; now and then the haji gives the meaning and through this they then get some understanding, but very imperfect, incomplete and inaccurate.”⁴⁸ The author repeatedly mentioned his surprise and dismay that the kyais he met did not seem to know anything or be able to explain to him what he wanted to hear, about their institutions, text books and pedagogy, but he also mentioned he had only basic Malay (and this while studying a Javanese system) and it did not seem to occur to him that the kyais may not have wanted to engage with him on religious matters. His approach to what he found was summed up well in the following statement: “Whichever pesantren you visit, they can only show you the Koran, which they do not understand, as well as the kitabs, which contain a number of prescriptions of dry and burdensome religious ceremonies.”⁴⁹ Brumund’s study points to some of the limits of colonial research during this period: barriers of language, the difficulty of attaining certain types of information and an ideological bias that prevented him from seeing anything useful or productive in this particular system. As far as interlinear translations go, he was aware of their existence and possibly also of their use in some cases, and he made many assumptions about the pedagogical institutions in which these translations played a major role, but he was unable to gain access to them, both physically and in terms of the translations’ significance.

Where are the Interlinear Translations? Part II: Manuscript Catalogues

In addition to articles and books, a separate yet related body of works to examine when considering scholarship on interlinear translation are catalogues of Indonesian manuscripts. Such catalogues, assembled since around the mid-19th century, were sometimes written by colonial scholar-administrators, often the same figures who also wrote articles and books about their findings (e.g., Van der Tuuk). Catalogues, by definition, categorize the manuscripts according to certain criteria (be it language, region, collector, topic, genre, etc.)

educational institutions in Java, cited in Dhofier, *Tradisi Pesantren*, 64. On this history of native education see also J.A. van der Chijs, “Bijdragen tot de Geschiedenis van het Inlandsch Onderwijs in Nederlandsch-Indië. Aan officiële bronnen ontleend,” *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde*, no. 16 (1864): 212–323.

⁴⁷ Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 13.

⁴⁸ Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 19.

⁴⁹ Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 25.

and tend to offer only brief information. In both early and more recent catalogues interlinear translation does not form a category of analysis or of listing. At times the existence of such a translation is not even mentioned in item descriptions or is mentioned as such with little detail or none at all.

For example, in a recent catalogue of manuscripts from West Kalimantan, a compilation of Arabic grammatical texts is described as written in the Arabic language and Arabic script without noting that it contains an interlinear translation into Javanese. The number of lines per page is noted as between five to nine, thus discounting the lines of translation. Interestingly, when the opening lines of the manuscript are quoted as part of the entry, the Arabic appears followed by the Javanese translation in parentheses, including the Javanese “code word” *utawi* that in such translations signals the subject of the Arabic nominal sentence.⁵⁰ A reader familiar with the interlinear model might well recognize these brief lines as indicating the existence of an interlinear translation of the grammatical work but for others it is only the photo of the manuscript page that clarifies this fact (see Fig. 3). Since most catalogue entries do not include a photo, the likelihood of missing relevant items is not negligible.⁵¹ However, it is important to note that in some cases an interlinear translation (*terjemahan antarbaris*) is explicitly noted while in others there is mention of two languages, e.g., Arabic and Malay, but the conjunction “and” remains ambiguous as there are various ways in which a text can be composed of two languages and interlinear translation is but one of them.

Whether or not the addition of an interlinear translation to a text or several texts within a bound manuscript was noted by the catalogue compiler or not would certainly have an effect on the availability of such texts for study and even of the awareness of their existence by future generations of scholars. And even if scholars wished to study the phenomenon it was often difficult to locate and assess the relevant texts based on the catalogues. An in-depth discussion of this aspect is beyond my scope but I will offer one example in order to make the point.⁵²

In the descriptive, four-volume catalogue of Balinese, Javanese and Sasak manuscripts in Van der Tuuk’s collection published by Brandes beginning in 1901 there are 1658 items in total and only four mentions of interlinear translations (three in volume 1, one in volume 2, none in volumes 3 and 4).⁵³ How to explain this? The issue of noticing and/or mentioning

50 On the historical development of the use of *utawi* see Muhammad Dluha Lutfillah’s article in the present issue.

51 Titik Pudjiastuti, ed. *Naskah-naskah Koleksi Masyarakat Indonesia Tengah Pontianak-Kalimantan Barat* (Perpusnas Press, 2020), 33–34. For additional examples see p. 60, 80.

52 There are several notable exceptions, all relatively recent, among them the catalogues compiled by Pigeaud, Florida, and Ricklefs, Voorhoeve and Gallop, all of whom paid attention to the interlinear phenomenon and noted it, often with precision and nuance. As noted above other catalogues, including the one for West Kalimantan, also documented interlinear translation, but at times inconsistently.

53 J. Brandes, *Beschrijving der Javaansche, Balineesche en Sasaksche Handschriften aangetroffen in de natenschap van Dr. H. N. van der Tuuk, en door hem vermaakt aan de Leidsche Universiteitsbibliotheek*, 4 delen (Batavia en Weltevreden: Landsdrukkerij, 1901–1926).

Fig. 3 Kompilasi Tata Bahasa Arab (Arabic Grammar Compilation), Abdurrahman Husein al-Falugha Collection, Pontianak, West Kalimantan BAH/17/AHF/I/PON. In Pudiastuti 2020: 34.

interlinear translation is in part an issue of the terminology employed in scholarship and all the more so in catalogues that dedicate little space to each manuscript, and so the question of whether “interlinear” or a related term appears at all in a concise entry signals the difference between knowing, as a reader, that a text was interlinear (or followed a similar model) or not being aware of the fact. There has been a great deal of variability in terminology related to the interlinear practice, i.e., translation, glosses, interpretation, commentary and notes, which makes even searchable catalogues and databases difficult to assess and use for the purpose of identifying interlinear translations. The variety of terms reflects, in addition to idiosyncratic choices by compilers, perceptions of translation that have shifted over time and the ways different languages depict the practice: the complexity of what might seem like “translation” but upon a closer look branches off into glosses, notes, interpretation, *maarti* or *kitab gandhul*.⁵⁴ In order to better assess the actual number of interlinear texts in Brandes’

⁵⁴ The latter two terms are examples of indigenous terminology that in no way engages with the idea of lines. *Maarti* (Balinese, to give meaning) refers to typically Old Javanese to Balinese translations of Indic texts that are inscribed on palm leaves (*lontar*), with small dots connecting between original and translation; *kitab gandhul* refers to Javanese translation between the lines of an Arabic text in which the

catalogue one would need to search for these different terms, and likely additional ones, closely examine the possibly-relevant entries, and reach tentative conclusions as a truly clear picture would be unlikely to emerge based on the available information.⁵⁵

Preliminary Thoughts: Interlinear Translation and Scholarship on Indonesia

This article emerged out of interest in how interlinear translation in the Indonesian-Malay world had been studied, especially early on, and what assumptions about it might have been inherited by those studying this phenomenon in the present. My initial search for secondary sources did not produce much, and so the question remained: where are the interlinear texts, and writings about them, hiding within scholarship on Indonesia?

The examples discussed, on the whole, do not point to much interest in interlinear translation, even among scholars writing about Islamic manuscripts and educational contexts. Mine was by necessity a partial and rather tentative sample. Still, I believe it needs to be viewed within the general, broad scholarship produced about Indonesian religious and literary writings during the particular time period and also beyond it: interlinear translations, despite their abundance, the wealth of linguistic, historical and cultural information they can offer, and their importance as a method of teaching, learning and transmitting religious-textual traditions, including from early on in the process of Islamization in the Indonesian-Malay world, have been little studied. This is especially striking when considered within the broader framework of (primarily Dutch) colonial and postcolonial philology which produced numerous, and often systematic textual and linguistic studies of Indonesian writings.⁵⁶ Even studies that focused on translations from Arabic into Malay, or the influence of Arabic on the Malay language, tended to ignore or marginalize the interlinear model.⁵⁷ The compilers of

Javanese words “hang” or “dangle” (*gandhul*) from the Arabic ones.

- 55 In the more recent past, with many collections undergoing digitization, the availability of images makes things clearer, however even then searches are hampered by the use of multiple terms and, in some repositories, the neglect to employ “interlinear” as a descriptive category. Filtering collections by the number of languages appearing in a manuscript, sometimes the only hint that interlinearity may be present, is insufficient and produces many “false positives” that are not interlinear.
- 56 Examples include J. Gonda, *Sanskrit in Indonesia* (International Academy of Indian Culture, 1952); C. Hooykaas, *The Old-Javanese Ramayana Kakawin with Special Reference to the Problem of Interpolation in Kakawins* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1955); William Marsden, *A Grammar of the Malayan Language, with an introduction and praxis* (London: Cox and Baylis, 1812); Th. Pigeaud, *Literature of Java*, 4 volumes (Martinus Nijhoff, 1967–1980); A. Teeuw, *Modern Indonesian Literature*, 2 volumes (Martinus Nijhoff, 1967, 1979); H. N. van der Tuuk, “Kort verslag van de Maleische handschriften in het East India House te Londen,” *Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch-Indie*, no. 1 (1849): 385–405; E.M. Uhlenbeck, “Beknopte Javaansche grammatica (Concise Javanese Grammar)” (Volkslectuur, 1941); E.M. Uhlenbeck, “A Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Java and Madura” (Martinus Nijhoff, 1964); P. J. Zoetmulder, *Kalangwan: A Survey of Old Javanese Literature* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1974).
- 57 G. W. J. Drewes, “The History of the Malay Language: A Preliminary Survey,” *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 115, no. 2 (1959): 138–156; Cyril Skinner, “The Influence of Arabic on Modern Malay (with particular reference to spoken Malay),” In *Cyril Skinner (1924–1986). Orientalist, Linguist,*

dictionaries produced for multiple Indonesian languages also seem to have disregarded the interlinear texts as an important source even though the interlinear text can itself be viewed as a dictionary, offering a source and method to trace the history of words and their meanings.⁵⁸ One exception (although not in the sphere of Islamic texts) was Van der Tuuk, who included many examples from Balinese *maarti* texts in his trilingual Old Javanese-Balinese-Dutch dictionary (1897–1912).⁵⁹ Catalogues, as noted above, were also for the most part not fruitful sources for locating and studying interlinear translations. In part this was due to the variability of terminology which makes even searchable catalogues and databases difficult to assess and use for this purpose and, more generally, it seems that interlinear translation was often not considered as a vital dimension of manuscripts, worthy of elaboration or even mention. I suggest that the fact they were difficult to locate in catalogues, used as an important resource by scholars, contributed to cementing their relative “invisibility.”

The gaps and silences in what can be termed “the interlinear archive,” presented in a preliminary manner in this article, make writing about it challenging as it is more difficult to write about and explain gaps in, and fragments of, scholarship, than to engage with more fully available sources, and perhaps many others are out there awaiting discovery and analysis. In addition, regarding what I called “non-examples,” that is surveys of Indonesia (focusing on regions or themes) that make no mention of interlinear translation, it is always possible and probable that their authors’ interest lay elsewhere, or that language barriers hampered their efforts.⁶⁰ However, if we assume that the examples presented do add up to something, I make several suggestions below as to why interlinear translations have not been studied or documented more extensively.

Can we detect here, as has been more generally proposed regarding colonial Dutch scholarship, a bias towards the Hindu-Buddhist and away from the Islamic? The approach or lack thereof towards interlinear texts may have been part of the trend, i.e., an enduring interest

Historian, Scholar. A Collection of Essays and Reviews, ed. Corfield, J. (Monash Asia Institute, 1996): 3–20.

- 58 William Marsden, *A Dictionary of the Malayan Language, in two parts, Malayan and English and English and Malayan* (London: Cox and Baylis, 1812); B. F. Matthes, *Boegineesch-Hollandsch woordenboek met Hollandsch-Boegineesch woordenlijst* (Den Haag: Martinus Nijhoff, 1874); J. Pijnappel, *Maleisch-Hollandsch Woordenboek*, 3rd edition (Amsterdam: Frederik Muller, 1884); J. Rigg, *A Dictionary of the Sunda Language of Java* (Batavia: Lange and Co., 1862); R.J. Wilkinson, *A Malay-English Dictionary*, 2 vols. (Kelly and Walsh, 1901; Macmillan & Co., 1959).
- 59 H.N. van der Tuuk, *Kawi-Balinesch-Nederlands Woordenboek* (Batavia: Landsdrukkerij, 1897–1912). According to Teeuw van der Tuuk “paid much attention” throughout his research to Balinese “interlinear translations, explanations and comments” within Old Javanese texts. In an 1871 letter van der Tuuk referred to such manuscripts he had encountered as “innumerable.” A. Teeuw, “Van der Tuuk as lexicographer,” *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996) 126. Whereas this article focuses for the most part on scholarship related to Islamic interlinear translations, a comparison with non-Islamic such translations from Indonesia is warranted.
- 60 As for language competence, the need to know both Arabic and an Indonesian language in order to read interlinear texts, many of the Dutch colonial scholars studied Arabic in addition to at least one Indonesian language as part of their training. Some scholar-administrators, e.g., Sir Stamford Thomas Raffles who wrote extensively about literature, relied on local informants.

in the ruins of temples, ancient sculpture, the role of Sanskrit in Old Javanese poetry, Islam as a “thin veneer” covering prior traditions as well as a deep-seated anxiety about Islam.⁶¹ Although interlinear translation was widespread in particular places, above all in the Islamic educational sphere, it seems to have often remained unseen.⁶² This approach was evident, for example, in Brumund’s book where, discussing the study of Arabic texts, he posed the questions: “is all of this something more than mechanical teaching? What is taught for the cultivation of the intellect, for the ennoblement of the heart, and the sanctification of life; what to inculcate in them pure concepts of God and religion, and to make them feel for them?” More generally, he viewed the pesantren as “institutions, established to complete the work of destruction of mind and heart...”⁶³ These quotes point to an approach which saw Islam as a debilitating religion, the method of Islamic teachings as technical and superficial and Arabic as almost unattainable, whereas the author praised traditional (i.e., non-Islamic) Javanese literature for its beauty and its being filled with educational and religious prescriptions that, according to Brumund, were deliberately not included in the pesantren curriculum because the kyais preferred their disciples to be ignorant so they could remain in power.⁶⁴

On the point of a certain invisibility of interlinear translations I would add that further to the question of scholarship’s approaches to Islam, it is interesting that texts that have a prominent visual aspect—text and translation often written in different-sized or colored script, multi-directional writing on the page, note-filled margins—are invisible or barely visible in the scholarship. That their visibility has not called much attention to them reveals a blind spot of traditional philology that has privileged textual analysis to the point of ignoring other major dimensions of the manuscripts.⁶⁵

It also seems, based on the evidence so far, that interlinear translation was taken at face value, or taken for granted as a convenient way to translate, to transfer meaning efficiently from one language to another. If it was but a technical device without much depth and with

61 For a literary work in which Islam is portrayed as a hidden danger, lurking in the shadows of Dutch colonial life and threatening to overcome it, see Louis Couperus, *De Stille Kracht* (Amsterdam: L.J. Veen, 1900), translated into English by Alexander Teixeira de Mattos under the title *The Hidden Force*.

62 This argument would be strengthened by showing that, on the contrary, traditions of non-Islamic and especially Hindu-Buddhist interlinear translation were studied more extensively during this period. Such a comparative study has yet to be undertaken but, for now, to support the claim I suggest that (1) interlinear translation was used most widely in Islamic circles and so that is where most sources could be found and (2) a towering figure like Van der Tuuk, who was interested in Christian, Hindu-Buddhist and other non-Islamic cultures, and who was also familiar with Islamic interlinear texts (see above), did not disregard but rather was fascinated by Balinese interlinear translations and incorporated many of them into his dictionary.

63 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 24.

64 Brumund, *Het Volksonderwijs onder de Javanen*, 26. In the same section Javanese literature is also described as “a product of licentious imagination and excessive sensuality” yet nevertheless containing the above praiseworthy traits.

65 For an analysis that attempts to challenge this blind spot see Ronit Ricci, “Implicit Comparisons: Visuality and the Interlinear Manuscript Page,” *History and Theory*, published online 16 September 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1111/hith.70002>.

no significant implications what more was there to say about it?⁶⁶ This approach is evident today if students and teachers in Islamic boarding schools are asked if there is reason to study the practice, and it may have been also prevalent in the past and conveyed to European scholars who showed an interest or who came across interlinear texts. Such an approach was apparent, for example, in Juynboll's articles discussed above in which he only translated and analyzed an Arabic text, disregarding the translation. Interlinear texts may have also looked familiar to European scholars from their own world—the languages and the religion were different but the practice, especially for translating Latin into vernaculars, was well known in Europe for centuries. Could this explain why Dutch and British scholars, generally so interested in the details of Indonesia's cultures, and studying them so extensively, were not more curious?

Perhaps there were other reasons for interlinear translation not having been taken too seriously, besides its view as a technical device, that had to do with understandings of "translation." As has been pointed out, terminologies for the practice as documented in articles and catalogues varied widely, suggesting that there was no agreement on whether the words between the lines constituted a translation (whatever the definition of this unruly term), or a commentary, gloss, interpretation, or explanatory notes, each of which could be understood differently on an epistemological level and valued or judged differently by scholars. The stark literalness of many Islamic interlinear translations, the effort to replicate the Arabic to the highest degree which produced clusters of words and sentences that were entirely unidiomatic, likely seemed like a pointless form of translation to some. It may also be, again within the broader sphere of colonial scholarship on Indonesian manuscripts and texts in which works were often evaluated based on their similarity (imagined or real) to earlier sources or Ur-texts, that the interlinear text could have been viewed as a form of interpolation: an unwanted, unwelcome addition that somehow contaminated the original, authentic text, in this case an Arabic one.⁶⁷

Scholars who were exceptions to the rule in their interest and in the studies they produced, above all Van Ronkel and Snouck Hurgronje, showed how those who did examine the practice of Islamic interlinear translation more closely discovered its complexity and its implications which were apparent in the linguistic, religious and social spheres. Van Ronkel, as a central example of producing in-depth scholarship, clearly engaged with many interlinear texts in order to reach the level of detail and nuance presented in his studies. He detected dimensions of the genre that others disregarded, missed or ridiculed, including the extreme literalness of the method that, having its own logic, prioritized single words over sentence comprehensibility; the type of vocabulary translated in interlinear texts; both common and

66 Returning to the translations' general invisibility, I note that convenience, efficiency and precision, usually associated during the colonial period with the Dutch, and much less so with Indonesians, was disregarded, or rendered invisible when it was accomplished, and on a large scale, by native translators.

67 Much of the scholarship that claims "interpolation" on the part of Indonesian writers is focused on Indian civilization-derived texts, see, for example, R. Ng. Poerbatjaraka, "Arjunawiwāha: Tekst en vertaling," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 82 (1926): 181–305; C. Hooykaas, *The Old Javanese Rāmāyaṇa Kakawin with Special Reference to the Problem of Interpolation in Kakawins* (Martinus Nijhoff, 1950).

unusual forms of rendering Arabic into Malay; and the source of much of the Arabic vocabulary adapted into Malay about which he dropped some hints but did not explicitly discuss. Snouck Hurgronje noted and described the differences between two methods of studying Arabic texts by Indonesians from various regions of the archipelago at home and in Mecca, offering a glimpse into the ethnic, linguistic, and social aspects of adhering to these practices. The work of these scholars (and other, more recent ones whose studies lie beyond the scope of this article) points to the richness of interlinear translations as a research topic and to the many yet unanswered questions about them that await investigation.

References

- AL-ATTAS, S. M. N. *The Oldest Known Malay Manuscript: a 16th Century Malay Translation of the 'Aqa'id of Al-Nasafi*. University of Malaya, 1988.
- ARPS, B., and A.T. GALLOP. *Golden Letters: Writing Traditions of Indonesia/Surat Emas: Budaya Tulis di Indonesia*. The British Library; Yayasan Lontar, 1991.
- AZRA, Azyumardi. "Naskah Terjemahan Antarbaris: Kontribusi Kreatif Dunia Islam Melayu-Indonesia." In *Sadur: Sejarah Terjemahan di Indonesia dan Malaysia*, edited by Henri Chambert-Loir. Gramedia, 2009.
- BERG, L. W. C. van den. "Het Mohammedaansche Godsdienstonderwijs op Java en Madoera en de daarbij Gebruikte Arabische Boeken." *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 31 (1886): 518–555.
- BRANDES, J. *Beschrijving der Javaansche, Balineesche en Sasaksche Handschriften aangetroffen in de nalatenschap van Dr. H. N. van der Tuuk, en door hem vermaakt aan de Leidsche Universiteitsbibliotheek*. 4 delen. Landsdrukkerij, 1901–1926.
- BUSKENS, Léon, Jan Just Witkam and Annemarie van Sandwijk, eds., *Scholarship in Action: Essays on the Life and Work of Christiaan Snouck Hurgronje (1857–1936)*. Brill, 2022. <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/87102>.
- CABATON, Antoine. "Traduction interlinéaire malaise de La 'Aqida d'al-Senūsī." *Journal Asiatique* (1904): 115–145.
- CABATON, Antoine. "Un abrégé malais du Catéchisme musulman." *T'oung Pao* 5, no. 2 (1904): 157–162.
- . "Raden Paku, Sunan de Giri (légende musulmane javanaise). Texte malais, traduction française et notes." *Revue de l'histoire des religions*, no. 54 (1906): 374–400.
- . *Java, Sumatra and the Other Islands of the Dutch East Indies*, translated by Bernard Miall. T.F. Unwin, 1911.
- CHIJS, J.A. van der. "Bijdragen tot de Geschiedenis van het Inlandsch Onderwijs in Nederlandsch-Indië. Ann officiële bronnen ontleend." *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal-, Land en Volkenkunde*, no. 16 (1864): 212–323.
- DANESHGAR, Majid. "Persianate Aspects of the Indonesian-Malay World: Some Rare Manuscripts in the Leiden University Library." *Dabir*, no. 8 (2021): 51–78.
- DHOFIER, Zamakhsyari. *Tradisi Pesantren. Studi Pandangan Hidup Kyai dan Visinya Mengenai Masa Depan Indonesia*. LP3ES, 2011.

- DJAJADININGRAT, Achmad. "Het Leven in een Pesantren." *Tijdschrift voor het Binnenlandsch Betuur*, no. 34 (1908): 1–22.
- DREWES, G.W. J. *Een 16de Eeuwse Maleische Vertaling van de Burda van al-Busiri (Arabisch Lofdicht op Mohammad)*. Martinus Nijhoff, 1955.
- . "The History of the Malay Language: A Preliminary Survey." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 115, no. 2 (1959): 138–156.
- FLORIDA, Nancy K. *Javanese Literature in Surakarta Manuscripts: Manuscripts of the Mangkunagaran Palace*. Vol. 2. Cornell University Press, 2000.
- . *Javanese Literature in Surakarta Manuscripts: Manuscripts of the Radya Pustaka Museum and the Hardjonagaran Library*. Vol. 3. Cornell University Press, 2012.
- GONDA, J. *Sanskrit in Indonesia*. International Academy of Indian Culture, 1952.
- HOOYKAAS, C. *The Old-Javanese Ramayana Kakawin with Special Reference to the Problem of Interpolation in Kakawins*. Martinus Nijhoff, 1955.
- HURGRONJE, Snouck C. *The Achehnese*, translated by A.W.S. O'Sullivan. 2 volumes. E.J. Brill, 1906.
- . *Mekka in the Latter Part of the 19th Century: Daily Life, Customs and Learning, the Moslims of the East-Indian-Archipelago. 1888–1889*. E. J. Brill, 1931.
- JUYNBOLL, A. W. T. "Een Moslimsche Catechismus in het Arabisch met eene Javaansche Interlineaire Vertaling in Pegonschrift," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 29, no. 2 (1881): 215–227.
- . "Een Moslimsche Catechismus in het Arabisch met eene Javaansche Interlineaire Vertaling in Pegonschrift Uitgegeven en in het Nederlandsche Vertaald," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 29, no. 2 (1881): 229–231.
- . "Samarkandi's Catechismus opnieuw besproken, I." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 267–274.
- . "Samarkandi's Catechismus opnieuw besproken, II." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 275–278.
- . "Samarkandi's Catechismus opnieuw besproken, III." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 29 (1881): 279–284.
- MARSDEN, William. *The History of Sumatra, Containing an Account of the Government, Laws, Customs, and Manners of the Native Inhabitants, with A Description of the Natural Productions, and A Relation of the Ancient Political State*. London: Printed for the Author, 1783.
- . *A Dictionary of the Malayan Language, in two parts, Malayan and English and English and Malayan*. London: Cox and Baylis, 1812.
- . *A Grammar of the Malayan Language, with an Introduction and Praxis*. London: Cox and Baylis, 1812.
- MATTHES, B. F. *Boegineesch-Hollandsch woordenboek met Hollandsch-Boegineesch woordenlijst*. Den Haag: Martinus Nijhoff, 1874.
- PIGEAUD, Th. "Javaanse Volksvertoningen." *Bijdrage tot de Beschrijving van Land en Volk*. Volkslectuur, 1938.
- . *Literature of Java*. 4 volumes. Martinus Nijhoff, 1967–1980.

- PIJNAPPEL, J. *Maleisch-Hollandsch Woordenboek*. 3rd edition. Amsterdam: Frederik Muller, 1884.
- PIJPER, Guillaume F. *Fragmenta Islamica. Studiën over her Islamisme in Nederlandsch Indië*. E.J. Brill, 1934.
- PUDJIASTUTI, Titik. ed. *Naskah-naskah Kolesksi Masyarakat Indonesia Tengah Pontianak-Kalimantan Barat*. Perpusnas Press, 2020.
- RAFFLES, Thomas Stamford. *The History of Java in Two Volumes*. London: Black, Farbury and Allen, 1817.
- RICCI, Ronit. "Mediating the Maulid: Interlinear Translations of the *Maulid Syaraf al-Anām* Across the Indonesian-Malay World." *Indonesia and the Malay World* 51, no.1 50 (2023):143–164. DOI: [10.1080/13639811.2023.2221927](https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2023.2221927).
- . "Implicit Comparisons: Visuality and the Interlinear Manuscript Page." *History and Theory*, , published online 16 September 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1111/hith.70002>.
- RICKLEFS, Merle C., P. Voorhoeve and Annabel Teh Gallop. *Indonesian Manuscripts in Great Britain. A Catalogue of Manuscripts in Indonesian Languages in British Public Collections*. New Edition with Addenda and Corrigenda. EFEO, PNRI and Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia, 2014.
- RIGG, J. *A Dictionary of the Sunda Language of Java*. Batavia: Lange and Co., 1862.
- RONKEL, Ph. S. van. "Account of Six Malay Manuscripts of the Cambridge University Library." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 46, no. 1 (1896): 1–53, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90000076>.
- . *Mengenai Pengaruh Tatakalamit Arab Terhadap Tatakalamit Melayu*, translated by A. Ikram. Seri Terjemahan Karangan-karangan Belanda (Bhratara, 1977). First published as "Over de Invloed der Arabische Syntaxis op de Maleische," *Tijdschrift voor Indische Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde*, no. 41(1899): 498–528
- . "Catalogus der Maleische Handschriften van het Koninklijk Instituut voor de Taal- Land- en Volkenkunde van Nederlands-Indië," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 60, no. 1 (1908): 181–240, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90001922>
- . "Beschrijving der Maleische Handschriften van de Bibliotheque Royale te Brussel," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 60, no. 1 (1908): 501–519, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90001934>
- SKINNER, Cyril. "The Influence of Arabic on Modern Malay (with particular reference to spoken Malay)." In *Cyril Skinner (1924–1986). Orientalist, Linguist, Historian, Scholar. A Collection of Essays and Reviews*, edited by Corfield, J. Monash Asia Institute, 1996.
- TEEUW, A. *Modern Indonesian Literature*. 2 vols. Martinus Nijhoff, 1967, 1979.
- . "Van der Tuuk as lexicographer." *Archipel*, no. 51 (1996): 113–133. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3406/arch.1996.1097>
- TUUK, H. N. van der "Kort verslag van de Maleische handschriften in het East India House te Londen." *Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch-Indie*, no. 1 (1849): 385–405.
- . *Tobasche spraakkunst, eerste stuk*. Amsterdam: Muller, 1864.
- . "Aanteekeningen." *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* 13, no.1 (1866): 462–470.
- TUUK, H.N. van der. *Kawi-Balinesesch-Nederlands Woordenboek*. Batavia: Landsdrukkerij, 1897–1912.

- UHLÉNBECK, E. M. “Beknopte Javaansche grammatica (Concise Javanese Grammar).” Volkslectuur, 1941.
- UHLÉNBECK, E. M. “A Critical Survey of Studies on the Languages of Java and Madura.” Nijhof, 1964.
- VOORHOEVE, P. “Bibliografie der Geschriften van Prof. Dr. Ph. S. van Ronkel.” in *Bingkisan Budi, een bundel opstellen aan Dr. Philippus Samuel Van Ronkel door vrienden en leerlingen aangeboden op zijn tachtigste verjaardag*. A. W. Sijthoff’s Uitgeversmaatschappij N.V., 1950.
- WILKINSON, R. J. *A Malay-English Dictionary*. 2 vols. Kelly and Walsh, 1901; Macmillan & Co., 1959.
- YAHYA, I., Hassan, M. A. K. dan Farkhan. *Penerjemahan Manuskrip Masā’il at-Ta’līm ke dalam Aksara Pegon pada Abad ke-17 M*. IAIN Surakarta Press, 2018.

© Ronit Ricci, Hebrew University of Jerusalem and Australian National University

◀ Ronit.Ricci@mail.huji.ac.il ▶

Notes on Contributors

Aglaia IANKOVSKAIA – is a postdoctoral researcher at SOAS University of London, project “Mapping Sumatra’s Manuscript Cultures”, and a former postdoctoral fellow with “Textual Microcosms.” Her PhD is from 2016 from the Russian Academy of Sciences, and her interests lie in the field of cultural engagements between the Middle East and the Indonesian-Malay world.

A.C.S PEACOCK – is Bishop Wardlaw Professor of Islamic History at the University of St Andrews, UK, and a Fellow of the British Academy. His research focuses on the history, intellectual culture and manuscripts of the premodern eastern Islamic world. Recent publications include *Arabic Literary Culture in Southeast Asia in the Seventeenth and Eighteenth centuries* (Brill, 2024) and *Islam, Literature and Society in Mongol Anatolia* (Cambridge 2019).

Fadhli LUKMAN – is a faculty member at the Department of Qur’anic Studies of Universitas Islam Negeri Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta, Indonesia and currently a post-doctoral fellow at the Textual Microcosms project funded by ERC. His work mainly deals with Qur’anic studies and social, intellectual, and textual history of Islam in Indonesia, with his most recent publication includes “*Conflicting Interests in the Creation of a State-Authorised Translation: Comparing the Saudi and Indonesian Editions of Al-Qur’an dan Terjemahnya*,” *Journal of Qur’anic Studies* Vol. 26, no. 1, 2024 and *The Official Indonesian Qur’an Translation: The History and Politics of Al-Qur’an dan Terjemahnya*, The Global Qur’an Series (Cambridge, OpenBook Publisher, 2022).

Midori KAWASHIMA – is a Professor Emeritus at Sophia University in Tokyo, where she was a member of the Faculty of Global Studies until her retirement in 2019. She specialises in the history of religious, political, and social movements and thought among Muslims in the Philippines. Her current research focuses on the intellectual activities of Mindanao Muslims from the 19th to the mid-20th century, the networks linking the southern Philippines with other areas of Southeast Asia and the Middle East, and Islamic manuscripts and printed materials in the Philippines. For more details, please visit her website, where most of her publications are available: <https://kawashimamidori.jp>.

Notes on Contributors

Muhammad Dluha LUTHFILLAH – is a PhD student at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, and a member of an ERC-funded project Textual Microcosms. He got his BA in tafsir studies and MA in gender studies, both from Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. He is now working on 18th-century interlinear Quran translations into Javanese with special attention to gender aspects.

Raphael MICHAELI – is enrolled in his Ph.D. as part of the MprinT project at Bergen University, Norway. His dissertation focuses on mawlid manuscripts, early prints, and oral performances in Lamu (Kenya), describing the textual and intellectual changes that occurred during the transition from manuscript usage to print I in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Ronit RICCI – is professor of Asian Studies and Comparative Religion at the Hebrew University and PI for the Textual Microcosms project. She teaches and writes about Javanese and Malay manuscript cultures, translation studies, and Islamic literary cultures in the Indonesian-Malay world, south India and Sri Lanka.